

Different Digits Equivalent Fractions - I₁

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Abstract

This work brings equivalent fractions from 3 to 9 digits without repetition of digits. For repetition of digits the number of equivalent fractions increases too much. The 10-digits equivalent fractions are in the second part [15].

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¹This work is a reorganized version of author's previous three works <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a148.pdf> [6], <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a149.pdf> [7] and <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a150.pdf> [8] done in 2016

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1 Introduction

The author [9, 10, 11, 12, 13] gave **selfie fractions**, recently summarized in [14]. By **selfie fractions** we understand that there are two fractions having same digits on both sides, where one of the side is with same digits in numerators and denominators, separated by certain operations. There are many ways of writing **selfie fractions**. See below some examples:

• Addable Fractions

$$\frac{96}{352} = \frac{9+6}{3+52}, \frac{182}{6734} = \frac{18+2}{6+734}, \text{ etc.}$$

• Subtractable Fractions

$$\frac{204}{357} = \frac{20-4}{35-7}, \frac{726}{1089} = \frac{72-6}{108-9}, \text{ etc.}$$

- **Dottable Fraction**

$$\frac{13}{624} = \frac{1 \times 3}{6 \times 24}, \frac{416}{728} = \frac{4 \times 16}{7 \times 2 \times 8}, \text{ etc.}$$

- **Dottable with Potentiation Fractions**

$$\frac{95}{342} = \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 2}, \frac{728}{1456} = \frac{7^2 \times 8}{14 \times 56}, \text{ etc.}$$

- **Mixed Fractions: All Operations**

$$\frac{4980}{5312} = \frac{4 - 9 + 80}{5 \times (3 + 1)^2}, \frac{3249}{5168} = \frac{(3 + 2^4) \times 9}{(5 - 1) \times 68}, \text{ etc.}$$

1.1 Equivalent Selfie Fractions

Still there are *selfie fractions* those can be written as equivalent forms, see below some examples,

- **Addable**

$$\frac{1453}{2906} = \frac{1 + 453}{2 + 906} = \frac{145 + 3}{290 + 6} = \frac{1 + 45 + 3}{2 + 90 + 6}.$$

- **Subtractable**

$$\frac{932}{1864} = \frac{9 - 32}{18 - 64} = \frac{93 - 2}{186 - 4}.$$

- **Dottable and Addable**

$$\frac{1680}{59472} = \frac{1 \times 6 \times 80}{59 \times 4 \times 72} = \frac{1 + 6 + 8 + 0}{59 + 472}.$$

- **Dottable, Addable and Subtractable**

$$\frac{302}{8154} = \frac{30 \times 2}{81 \times 5 \times 4} = \frac{3 + 02}{81 + 54} = \frac{3 - 02}{81 - 54}.$$

- **Symmetric Addable and Subtractable**

$$\frac{645}{1290} = \frac{6 - 45}{12 - 90} = \frac{6 + 45}{12 + 90}.$$

• Dottable and Addable together

$$\frac{284}{639} = \frac{2 \times 8 + 4}{6 + 39} = \frac{28 + 4}{6 \times (3 + 9)}.$$

• Mixed - All Operations

$$\frac{73842}{90516} = \frac{7 - 3 \times (8 - 4^2)}{9 \times 05 - 1 - 6} = \frac{7 \times (3 + 8) + 4^2}{90 + (5 - 1) \times 6} = \frac{738 + 4 + 2}{905 + 1 + 6}.$$

For more details on *equivalent* and *symmetric equivalent fractions* refer author's work, [14]. Above examples are with different digits. The work on repetition of digits shall be dealt elsewhere.

In this paper our aim is little different, i.e., we want to bring **equivalent fractions** without use of any operations, just with different digits. Below are some examples to understand the idea of *equivalent fractions* for different digits:

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{24} = \frac{4}{32}, \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{4}{356} = \frac{6}{534}, \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{27}{3456} = \frac{42}{5376},$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{315}{4620} = \frac{342}{5016}, \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{123}{58764} = \frac{164}{78352},$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{26418} = \frac{618}{45732} = \frac{714}{52836} = \frac{732}{54168} = \frac{738}{54612}, \text{ etc.}$$

Some studies in this direction can be seen in [3, 4, 5]. Work of these authors is concentrated on equivalent fractions for the digits 1 to 9, calling **pandigital fractions**. While, we worked for all digits, i.e., for 3 to 10 digits. In this paper, we worked only for the digits 3 to 9. For the 10 digits refer author's work [15]. This work is reorganized version of author's previous three works [6, 7, 8] done in 2016.

For more work on numbers in different situations refer summary of author work [16, 17]. From historical point of view refer to classical books [1], [2].

2 3 to 5 Digits

This section deals with equivalent fractions for different order of digits. The work is for fractions having 3 to each 8 digits.

2.1 3 and 4-Digits

This subsection give equivalent fractions using 3 and 4 different digits. In this case we have only one example for each case.

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{24} = \frac{4}{32}, \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{4}{356} = \frac{6}{534}.$$

2.2 5-Digits

This subsection deals with equivalent fractions having 5 different digits. In this case we have only 3 possibilities, one with digits 2 to 6 and two with digits 4 to 8.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \blacktriangleright \frac{46}{253} = \frac{64}{352}, & \blacktriangleright \frac{47}{658} = \frac{56}{784} & \blacktriangleright \frac{48}{576} = \frac{57}{684}. \end{array}$$

3 6-Digits

This subsection deals with equivalent fractions having 5 different digits. In this case we have only 55 possibilities, separated by different digits, such as 0 to 5, 1 to 6, 2 to 7, 3 to 8 and 4 to 9.

3.1 6-Digits: 0 to 5

There are only 3 possibilities of equivalent fractions with the digits 0 to 5.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \blacktriangleright \frac{14}{3052} = \frac{23}{5014} & \blacktriangleright \frac{152}{304} = \frac{215}{430} & \blacktriangleright \frac{153}{204} = \frac{315}{420}. \end{array}$$

3.2 6-Digits: 1 to 6

There are only 5 possibilities of equivalent fractions with digits 1 to 6.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1536} = \frac{51}{3264}, & \blacktriangleright \frac{35}{1246} = \frac{65}{2314}, & \blacktriangleright \frac{52}{4316} = \frac{64}{5312}, \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{24}{3516} = \frac{42}{6153}, & \blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1452} = \frac{63}{2541}, & \end{array}$$

3.3 6-Digits: 2 to 7

There are total 37 possibilities of equivalent fractions with the digits 2 to 7.

$$\begin{array}{cccc} \blacktriangleright \frac{243}{567} := \frac{324}{756} & \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{543} := \frac{356}{724} & \blacktriangleright \frac{24}{3567} := \frac{32}{4756} & \blacktriangleright \frac{27}{3564} := \frac{36}{4752} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{264}{357} := \frac{352}{476} & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{564} := \frac{364}{752} & \blacktriangleright \frac{24}{3756} := \frac{42}{6573} & \blacktriangleright \frac{27}{5643} := \frac{36}{7524} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{264}{573} := \frac{352}{764} & \blacktriangleright \frac{276}{345} := \frac{372}{465} & \blacktriangleright \frac{24}{5673} := \frac{32}{7564} & \blacktriangleright \frac{32}{4576} := \frac{52}{7436} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{354} := \frac{356}{472} & \blacktriangleright \frac{324}{567} := \frac{432}{756} & \blacktriangleright \frac{24}{5736} := \frac{27}{6453} & \blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2567} := \frac{72}{5436} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{534} := \frac{273}{546} = \frac{327}{654} & \blacktriangleright \frac{327}{564} := \frac{436}{752} & \blacktriangleright \frac{27}{3456} := \frac{42}{5376} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36}{5472} := \frac{37}{5624} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{cccc} \triangleright \frac{43}{5762} := \frac{54}{7236} & \triangleright \frac{56}{3472} := \frac{73}{4526} & \triangleright \frac{3}{26457} := \frac{4}{35276} & \triangleright \frac{3}{56724} := \frac{4}{75632} \\ \triangleright \frac{45}{3276} := \frac{65}{4732} & \triangleright \frac{56}{4732} := \frac{74}{6253} & \triangleright \frac{3}{26754} := \frac{4}{35672} & \triangleright \frac{3}{57264} := \frac{4}{76352} \\ \triangleright \frac{54}{2376} := \frac{74}{3256} & \triangleright \frac{57}{2643} := \frac{76}{3524} & \triangleright \frac{3}{27564} := \frac{4}{36752} & \\ \triangleright \frac{54}{2673} := \frac{72}{3564} & \triangleright \frac{57}{3264} := \frac{76}{4352} & \triangleright \frac{3}{54267} := \frac{4}{72356} & \\ \triangleright \frac{54}{3267} := \frac{72}{4356} & \triangleright \frac{3}{24567} := \frac{4}{32756} & \triangleright \frac{3}{56427} := \frac{4}{75236} & \end{array}$$

3.4 6-Digits: 3 to 8

There are only 4 possibilities of equivalent fractions with the digits 3 to 8.

$$\begin{array}{cc} \triangleright \frac{384}{576} = \frac{438}{657} & \triangleright \frac{57}{3648} = \frac{84}{5376} \\ \triangleright \frac{48}{3756} = \frac{84}{6573} & \\ \triangleright \frac{48}{5376} = \frac{57}{6384} & \end{array}$$

3.5 6-Digits: 5 to 9

There are only 6 possibilities of equivalent fractions with the digits 5 to 9.

$$\begin{array}{cc} \triangleright \frac{456}{798} = \frac{564}{987} & \triangleright \frac{74}{5698} = \frac{98}{7546} \\ \triangleright \frac{497}{568} = \frac{749}{856} = \frac{854}{976} & \triangleright \frac{76}{4598} = \frac{94}{5687} \\ \triangleright \frac{57}{6498} = \frac{84}{9576} & \\ \triangleright \frac{67}{4958} = \frac{79}{5846} & \end{array}$$

4 7-Digits

This subsection deals with equivalent fractions having 7 different digits. In this case we have total 66 possibilities, separated by different digits, such as 0 to 6, 1 to 7, 2 to 8 and 3 to 9.

4.1 7-Digits: 0 to 6

There are total 37 possibilities of equivalent fractions with the digits 0 to 6.

▶ $\frac{130}{2456} = \frac{325}{6140}$	▶ $\frac{520}{4316} = \frac{640}{5312}$	▶ $\frac{32}{41056} = \frac{41}{52603}$
▶ $\frac{130}{2564} = \frac{325}{6410}$	▶ $\frac{523}{1046} = \frac{532}{1064} = \frac{652}{1304}$	▶ $\frac{35}{12460} = \frac{65}{23140}$
▶ $\frac{136}{2450} = \frac{340}{6125}$	▶ $\frac{531}{4602} = \frac{612}{5304}$	▶ $\frac{36}{14520} = \frac{63}{25410}$
▶ $\frac{164}{2530} = \frac{410}{6325}$	▶ $\frac{10}{24536} = \frac{25}{61340}$	▶ $\frac{43}{26015} = \frac{52}{31460}$
▶ $\frac{240}{1536} = \frac{510}{3264}$	▶ $\frac{10}{25364} = \frac{25}{63410}$	▶ $\frac{52}{43160} = \frac{64}{53120}$
▶ $\frac{240}{3516} = \frac{420}{6153}$	▶ $\frac{16}{24530} = \frac{40}{61325}$	▶ $\frac{2}{104536} = \frac{5}{261340}$
▶ $\frac{250}{1364} = \frac{625}{3410}$	▶ $\frac{23}{10465} = \frac{32}{14560}$	▶ $\frac{2}{105364} = \frac{5}{263410}$
▶ $\frac{260}{3145} = \frac{416}{5032}$	▶ $\frac{23}{14605} = \frac{41}{26035}$	▶ $\frac{2}{130456} = \frac{5}{326140}$
▶ $\frac{315}{4620} = \frac{342}{5016}$	▶ $\frac{24}{13650} = \frac{60}{34125}$	▶ $\frac{2}{130564} = \frac{5}{326410}$
▶ $\frac{350}{1246} = \frac{650}{2314}$	▶ $\frac{24}{15360} = \frac{51}{32640}$	▶ $\frac{2}{136504} = \frac{5}{341260}$
▶ $\frac{354}{1062} = \frac{534}{1602}$	▶ $\frac{24}{16530} = \frac{60}{41325}$	▶ $\frac{2}{165304} = \frac{5}{413260}$
▶ $\frac{360}{1452} = \frac{630}{2541}$	▶ $\frac{24}{35160} = \frac{42}{61530}$	
▶ $\frac{413}{2065} = \frac{461}{2305} = \frac{641}{3205}$	▶ $\frac{25}{13460} = \frac{40}{21536}$	

4.2 7-Digits: 1 to 7

There are total 10 possibilities of equivalent fractions with the digits 1 to 7.

▶ $\frac{143}{2756} = \frac{341}{6572}$	▶ $\frac{13}{27456} = \frac{31}{65472}$	▶ $\frac{26}{15743} = \frac{62}{37541}$
▶ $\frac{156}{2743} = \frac{372}{6541}$	▶ $\frac{24}{15376} = \frac{51}{32674}$	▶ $\frac{37}{12654} = \frac{46}{15732}$
▶ $\frac{273}{1456} = \frac{651}{3472}$	▶ $\frac{24}{17536} = \frac{51}{37264}$	
▶ $\frac{572}{3146} = \frac{752}{4136}$	▶ $\frac{26}{14573} = \frac{62}{34751}$	

4.3 7-Digits: 2 to 8

There are total 13 possibilities of equivalent fractions with the digits 2 to 8.

$$\triangleright \frac{253}{4876} = \frac{352}{6784}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{483}{2576} = \frac{537}{2864} = \frac{672}{3584}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{46}{27853} = \frac{64}{38752}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{276}{4853} = \frac{384}{6752}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{638}{5742} = \frac{647}{5823} = \frac{836}{7524}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{46}{53728} = \frac{73}{85264}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{328}{4756} = \frac{364}{5278}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{23}{48576} = \frac{32}{67584}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{63742} = \frac{76}{83524}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{374}{2856} = \frac{572}{4368}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{38}{25764} = \frac{83}{56274}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{374}{6528} = \frac{473}{8256}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{46}{25783} = \frac{64}{35872}$$

4.4 7-Digits: 3 to 9

There are total 6 possibilities of equivalent fractions with the digits 3 to 9.

$$\triangleright \frac{48}{37596} = \frac{84}{65793}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{584}{3796} = \frac{596}{3874} = \frac{698}{4537}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{48}{39756} = \frac{84}{69573}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{697}{3485} = \frac{769}{3845} = \frac{937}{4685} = \frac{967}{4835} = \frac{973}{4865}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{57}{63498} = \frac{84}{93576}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{476}{3598} = \frac{578}{4369} = \frac{986}{7453}$$

5 8-Digits

This subsection deals with equivalent fractions having 8 different digits. In this case we have total 3859 possibilities, separated by different digits, such as 0 to 7, 1 to 8 and 2 to 9.

5.1 8-Digits: 0 to 7

There are total 42 possibilities of equivalent fractions with the digits 0 to 7.

$$\triangleright \frac{1365}{2704} = \frac{2310}{4576}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1560}{2743} = \frac{3720}{6541}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3146}{5720} = \frac{4136}{7520}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1430}{2756} = \frac{3410}{6572}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1572}{3406} = \frac{3462}{7501}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3172}{5460} = \frac{3721}{6405}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1456}{2730} = \frac{3472}{6510}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2163}{5047} = \frac{3054}{7126} = \frac{3216}{7504}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3256}{4107} = \frac{5632}{7104}$$

▶ $\frac{3426}{5710} = \frac{4263}{7105}$	▶ $\frac{260}{14573} = \frac{620}{34751}$	▶ $\frac{17}{346052} = \frac{35}{712460}$
▶ $\frac{103}{25647} = \frac{247}{61503}$	▶ $\frac{260}{15743} = \frac{620}{37541}$	▶ $\frac{23}{104765} = \frac{32}{145760}$
▶ $\frac{130}{27456} = \frac{310}{65472}$	▶ $\frac{273}{14560} = \frac{651}{34720}$	▶ $\frac{24}{153760} = \frac{51}{326740}$
▶ $\frac{140}{23576} = \frac{275}{46310}$	▶ $\frac{370}{12654} = \frac{460}{15732}$	▶ $\frac{24}{175360} = \frac{51}{372640}$
▶ $\frac{143}{27560} = \frac{341}{65720}$	▶ $\frac{370}{21645} = \frac{406}{23751}$	▶ $\frac{26}{145730} = \frac{62}{347510}$
▶ $\frac{147}{30625} = \frac{174}{36250}$	▶ $\frac{415}{67230} = \frac{451}{73062}$	▶ $\frac{26}{157430} = \frac{62}{375410}$
▶ $\frac{154}{32670} = \frac{217}{46035}$	▶ $\frac{427}{30561} = \frac{742}{53106}$	▶ $\frac{31}{245706} = \frac{67}{531042}$
▶ $\frac{156}{27430} = \frac{372}{65410}$	▶ $\frac{435}{26071} = \frac{570}{34162}$	▶ $\frac{37}{126540} = \frac{46}{157320}$
▶ $\frac{206}{15347} = \frac{674}{50213}$	▶ $\frac{457}{30162} = \frac{547}{36102}$	▶ $\frac{52}{317460} = \frac{61}{372405}$
▶ $\frac{214}{53607} = \frac{304}{76152}$	▶ $\frac{473}{26015} = \frac{572}{31460} = \frac{752}{41360}$	
▶ $\frac{240}{15376} = \frac{510}{32674}$	▶ $\frac{13}{274560} = \frac{31}{654720}$	
▶ $\frac{240}{17536} = \frac{510}{37264}$	▶ $\frac{14}{350672} = \frac{23}{576104}$	

5.2 8-Digits: 1 to 8

• Two Equivalent Fractions

There are total 3770 possibilities, where 3583 are with only one equivalent fraction, while 187 are more than one equivalent fractions. First we have written only with one possibility:

▶ $\frac{1235}{7486} = \frac{1365}{8274}$	▶ $\frac{1253}{6874} = \frac{1432}{7856}$	▶ $\frac{1258}{6734} = \frac{1564}{8372}$	▶ $\frac{1274}{3568} = \frac{2548}{7136}$
▶ $\frac{1243}{5786} = \frac{1582}{7364}$	▶ $\frac{1257}{3684} = \frac{2514}{7368}$	▶ $\frac{1267}{3584} = \frac{2534}{7168}$	▶ $\frac{1274}{3658} = \frac{2548}{7316}$
▶ $\frac{1243}{5876} = \frac{1562}{7384}$	▶ $\frac{1257}{4368} = \frac{2514}{8736}$	▶ $\frac{1267}{4358} = \frac{2534}{8716}$	▶ $\frac{1274}{6853} = \frac{1456}{7832}$
▶ $\frac{1248}{3576} = \frac{1872}{5364}$	▶ $\frac{1258}{3674} = \frac{2516}{7348}$	▶ $\frac{1268}{3574} = \frac{2536}{7148}$	▶ $\frac{1275}{3468} = \frac{1425}{3876}$
▶ $\frac{1248}{6357} = \frac{1536}{7824}$	▶ $\frac{1258}{4367} = \frac{2516}{8734}$	▶ $\frac{1268}{4357} = \frac{2536}{8714}$	▶ $\frac{1275}{6834} = \frac{1425}{7638}$

$\triangleright \frac{1284}{3567} = \frac{2568}{7134}$	$\triangleright \frac{1375}{6248} = \frac{1625}{7384}$	$\triangleright \frac{1456}{2378} = \frac{2184}{3567}$	$\triangleright \frac{1564}{3782} = \frac{3128}{7564}$
$\triangleright \frac{1284}{3657} = \frac{2568}{7314}$	$\triangleright \frac{1384}{2567} = \frac{2768}{5134}$	$\triangleright \frac{1456}{2873} = \frac{3472}{6851}$	$\triangleright \frac{1564}{3827} = \frac{3128}{7654}$
$\triangleright \frac{1287}{4356} = \frac{2457}{8316}$	$\triangleright \frac{1384}{2657} = \frac{2768}{5314}$	$\triangleright \frac{1456}{3782} = \frac{2184}{5673}$	$\triangleright \frac{1572}{3648} = \frac{2751}{6384}$
$\triangleright \frac{1287}{6435} = \frac{1647}{8235}$	$\triangleright \frac{1387}{4526} = \frac{2318}{7564}$	$\triangleright \frac{1458}{2673} = \frac{4158}{7623}$	$\triangleright \frac{1572}{4836} = \frac{2751}{8463}$
$\triangleright \frac{1325}{4876} = \frac{1725}{6348}$	$\triangleright \frac{1426}{3875} = \frac{3174}{8625}$	$\triangleright \frac{1458}{3762} = \frac{2187}{5643}$	$\triangleright \frac{1573}{2864} = \frac{3146}{5728}$
$\triangleright \frac{1328}{4576} = \frac{2158}{7436}$	$\triangleright \frac{1427}{3568} = \frac{2854}{7136}$	$\triangleright \frac{1476}{3528} = \frac{2583}{6174}$	$\triangleright \frac{1573}{4286} = \frac{3146}{8572}$
$\triangleright \frac{1356}{2478} = \frac{3164}{5782}$	$\triangleright \frac{1427}{3658} = \frac{2854}{7316}$	$\triangleright \frac{1476}{3852} = \frac{2583}{6741}$	$\triangleright \frac{1574}{2638} = \frac{3148}{5276}$
$\triangleright \frac{1357}{2684} = \frac{2714}{5368}$	$\triangleright \frac{1428}{3567} = \frac{2856}{7134}$	$\triangleright \frac{1478}{2356} = \frac{5173}{8246}$	$\triangleright \frac{1574}{2836} = \frac{3148}{5672}$
$\triangleright \frac{1357}{4268} = \frac{2714}{8536}$	$\triangleright \frac{1428}{3657} = \frac{2856}{7314}$	$\triangleright \frac{1547}{3682} = \frac{2431}{5786}$	$\triangleright \frac{1574}{2863} = \frac{3148}{5726}$
$\triangleright \frac{1358}{2674} = \frac{2716}{5348}$	$\triangleright \frac{1428}{3675} = \frac{1836}{4725}$	$\triangleright \frac{1562}{3784} = \frac{3124}{7568}$	$\triangleright \frac{1574}{3286} = \frac{3148}{6572}$
$\triangleright \frac{1358}{4267} = \frac{2716}{8534}$	$\triangleright \frac{1436}{2578} = \frac{2154}{3867}$	$\triangleright \frac{1562}{4378} = \frac{3124}{8756}$	$\triangleright \frac{1574}{3628} = \frac{3148}{7256}$
$\triangleright \frac{1367}{2584} = \frac{2734}{5168}$	$\triangleright \frac{1436}{5782} = \frac{2154}{8673}$	$\triangleright \frac{1563}{2874} = \frac{3126}{5748}$	$\triangleright \frac{1574}{3826} = \frac{3148}{7652}$
$\triangleright \frac{1367}{4258} = \frac{2734}{8516}$	$\triangleright \frac{1437}{2568} = \frac{2874}{5136}$	$\triangleright \frac{1563}{4287} = \frac{3126}{8574}$	$\triangleright \frac{1576}{2438} = \frac{3152}{4876}$
$\triangleright \frac{1368}{2574} = \frac{2736}{5148}$	$\triangleright \frac{1437}{2658} = \frac{2874}{5316}$	$\triangleright \frac{1564}{2378} = \frac{3128}{4756}$	$\triangleright \frac{1576}{3248} = \frac{4137}{8526}$
$\triangleright \frac{1368}{4257} = \frac{2736}{8514}$	$\triangleright \frac{1438}{2567} = \frac{2876}{5134}$	$\triangleright \frac{1564}{2738} = \frac{3128}{5476}$	$\triangleright \frac{1576}{3824} = \frac{3152}{7648}$
$\triangleright \frac{1368}{5472} = \frac{1863}{7452}$	$\triangleright \frac{1438}{2576} = \frac{2157}{3864}$	$\triangleright \frac{1564}{2837} = \frac{3128}{5674}$	$\triangleright \frac{1576}{3842} = \frac{3152}{7684}$
$\triangleright \frac{1372}{5684} = \frac{1386}{5742}$	$\triangleright \frac{1438}{2657} = \frac{2876}{5314}$	$\triangleright \frac{1564}{2873} = \frac{3128}{5746}$	$\triangleright \frac{1576}{4238} = \frac{3152}{8476}$
$\triangleright \frac{1374}{2568} = \frac{2748}{5136}$	$\triangleright \frac{1438}{5762} = \frac{2157}{8643}$	$\triangleright \frac{1564}{3287} = \frac{3128}{6574}$	$\triangleright \frac{1576}{4382} = \frac{3152}{8764}$
$\triangleright \frac{1374}{2658} = \frac{2748}{5316}$	$\triangleright \frac{1452}{3876} = \frac{2541}{6783}$	$\triangleright \frac{1564}{3728} = \frac{3128}{7456}$	$\triangleright \frac{1578}{2364} = \frac{3156}{4728}$

▶ $\frac{1578}{2436} = \frac{3156}{4872}$	▶ $\frac{1586}{4327} = \frac{3172}{8654}$	▶ $\frac{1637}{4258} = \frac{3274}{8516}$	▶ $\frac{1736}{4258} = \frac{3472}{8516}$
▶ $\frac{1578}{3624} = \frac{3156}{7248}$	▶ $\frac{1587}{2634} = \frac{3174}{5268}$	▶ $\frac{1638}{4257} = \frac{3276}{8514}$	▶ $\frac{1738}{2456} = \frac{5214}{7368}$
▶ $\frac{1578}{3642} = \frac{3156}{7284}$	▶ $\frac{1587}{2643} = \frac{3174}{5286}$	▶ $\frac{1638}{5742} = \frac{2457}{8613}$	▶ $\frac{1738}{2546} = \frac{5214}{7638}$
▶ $\frac{1578}{4236} = \frac{3156}{8472}$	▶ $\frac{1587}{3264} = \frac{3174}{6528}$	▶ $\frac{1642}{3578} = \frac{3284}{7156}$	▶ $\frac{1738}{2564} = \frac{3476}{5128}$
▶ $\frac{1578}{4362} = \frac{3156}{8724}$	▶ $\frac{1587}{3426} = \frac{3174}{6852}$	▶ $\frac{1642}{3758} = \frac{3284}{7516}$	▶ $\frac{1738}{4256} = \frac{3476}{8512}$
▶ $\frac{1582}{3647} = \frac{2486}{5731}$	▶ $\frac{1587}{4263} = \frac{3174}{8526}$	▶ $\frac{1643}{2587} = \frac{3286}{5174}$	▶ $\frac{1742}{3658} = \frac{2613}{5487}$
▶ $\frac{1582}{3764} = \frac{3164}{7528}$	▶ $\frac{1587}{4326} = \frac{3174}{8652}$	▶ $\frac{1643}{2857} = \frac{3286}{5714}$	▶ $\frac{1742}{3856} = \frac{2613}{5784}$
▶ $\frac{1582}{4376} = \frac{3164}{8752}$	▶ $\frac{1587}{4623} = \frac{1863}{5427}$	▶ $\frac{1653}{2748} = \frac{3857}{6412}$	▶ $\frac{1742}{5638} = \frac{2613}{8457}$
▶ $\frac{1584}{2637} = \frac{3168}{5274}$	▶ $\frac{1624}{3578} = \frac{3248}{7156}$	▶ $\frac{1653}{4872} = \frac{1824}{5376}$	▶ $\frac{1742}{5836} = \frac{2613}{8754}$
▶ $\frac{1584}{2736} = \frac{3168}{5472}$	▶ $\frac{1624}{3758} = \frac{3248}{7516}$	▶ $\frac{1654}{2378} = \frac{2481}{3567}$	▶ $\frac{1743}{2586} = \frac{3486}{5172}$
▶ $\frac{1584}{3276} = \frac{1672}{3458}$	▶ $\frac{1627}{3584} = \frac{3254}{7168}$	▶ $\frac{1654}{3782} = \frac{2481}{5673}$	▶ $\frac{1743}{2856} = \frac{3486}{5712}$
▶ $\frac{1584}{3627} = \frac{3168}{7254}$	▶ $\frac{1627}{4358} = \frac{3254}{8716}$	▶ $\frac{1658}{2374} = \frac{2487}{3561}$	▶ $\frac{1746}{2538} = \frac{5238}{7614}$
▶ $\frac{1584}{3726} = \frac{3168}{7452}$	▶ $\frac{1628}{3574} = \frac{3256}{7148}$	▶ $\frac{1658}{3742} = \frac{2487}{5613}$	▶ $\frac{1746}{5382} = \frac{2134}{6578}$
▶ $\frac{1584}{7326} = \frac{1632}{7548}$	▶ $\frac{1628}{4357} = \frac{3256}{8714}$	▶ $\frac{1683}{5247} = \frac{1836}{5724}$	▶ $\frac{1756}{2384} = \frac{3512}{4768}$
▶ $\frac{1584}{7623} = \frac{1632}{7854}$	▶ $\frac{1634}{2578} = \frac{2451}{3867}$	▶ $\frac{1726}{3584} = \frac{3452}{7168}$	▶ $\frac{1756}{3824} = \frac{3512}{7648}$
▶ $\frac{1586}{2734} = \frac{3172}{5468}$	▶ $\frac{1634}{2587} = \frac{3268}{5174}$	▶ $\frac{1726}{4358} = \frac{3452}{8716}$	▶ $\frac{1756}{3842} = \frac{3512}{7684}$
▶ $\frac{1586}{3274} = \frac{3172}{6548}$	▶ $\frac{1634}{2857} = \frac{3268}{5714}$	▶ $\frac{1728}{4356} = \frac{3456}{8712}$	▶ $\frac{1756}{4238} = \frac{3512}{8476}$
▶ $\frac{1586}{3427} = \frac{3172}{6854}$	▶ $\frac{1634}{5782} = \frac{2451}{8673}$	▶ $\frac{1734}{2586} = \frac{3468}{5172}$	▶ $\frac{1756}{4382} = \frac{3512}{8764}$
▶ $\frac{1586}{4273} = \frac{3172}{8546}$	▶ $\frac{1637}{2584} = \frac{3274}{5168}$	▶ $\frac{1736}{2584} = \frac{3472}{5168}$	▶ $\frac{1758}{2436} = \frac{3516}{4872}$

$\triangleright \frac{1758}{3624} = \frac{3516}{7248}$	$\triangleright \frac{1784}{3562} = \frac{3568}{7124}$	$\triangleright \frac{1854}{3762} = \frac{2781}{5643}$	$\triangleright \frac{1862}{7543} = \frac{2156}{8734}$
$\triangleright \frac{1758}{3642} = \frac{3516}{7284}$	$\triangleright \frac{1824}{3576} = \frac{3648}{7152}$	$\triangleright \frac{1854}{6732} = \frac{2163}{7854}$	$\triangleright \frac{1863}{2574} = \frac{3726}{5148}$
$\triangleright \frac{1758}{4236} = \frac{3516}{8472}$	$\triangleright \frac{1824}{3756} = \frac{3648}{7512}$	$\triangleright \frac{1854}{7326} = \frac{2163}{8547}$	$\triangleright \frac{1863}{4257} = \frac{3726}{8514}$
$\triangleright \frac{1758}{4362} = \frac{3516}{8724}$	$\triangleright \frac{1826}{3574} = \frac{3652}{7148}$	$\triangleright \frac{1856}{2374} = \frac{2784}{3561}$	$\triangleright \frac{1864}{2573} = \frac{3728}{5146}$
$\triangleright \frac{1762}{3458} = \frac{2643}{5187}$	$\triangleright \frac{1826}{4357} = \frac{3652}{8714}$	$\triangleright \frac{1856}{2734} = \frac{3712}{5468}$	$\triangleright \frac{1864}{3257} = \frac{3728}{6514}$
$\triangleright \frac{1762}{3584} = \frac{3524}{7168}$	$\triangleright \frac{1827}{3564} = \frac{3654}{7128}$	$\triangleright \frac{1856}{2743} = \frac{3712}{5486}$	$\triangleright \frac{1873}{2564} = \frac{3746}{5128}$
$\triangleright \frac{1762}{3854} = \frac{2643}{5781}$	$\triangleright \frac{1827}{4356} = \frac{3654}{8712}$	$\triangleright \frac{1856}{3274} = \frac{3712}{6548}$	$\triangleright \frac{1873}{4256} = \frac{3746}{8512}$
$\triangleright \frac{1762}{4358} = \frac{3524}{8716}$	$\triangleright \frac{1834}{2576} = \frac{2751}{3864}$	$\triangleright \frac{1856}{3427} = \frac{3712}{6854}$	$\triangleright \frac{1874}{2563} = \frac{3748}{5126}$
$\triangleright \frac{1762}{5438} = \frac{2643}{8157}$	$\triangleright \frac{1834}{5762} = \frac{2751}{8643}$	$\triangleright \frac{1856}{3724} = \frac{3248}{6517}$	$\triangleright \frac{1874}{3256} = \frac{3748}{6512}$
$\triangleright \frac{1762}{5834} = \frac{2643}{8751}$	$\triangleright \frac{1836}{4257} = \frac{3672}{8514}$	$\triangleright \frac{1856}{3742} = \frac{2784}{5613}$	$\triangleright \frac{2145}{7683} = \frac{2365}{8471}$
$\triangleright \frac{1764}{2583} = \frac{5712}{8364}$	$\triangleright \frac{1836}{5742} = \frac{2754}{8613}$	$\triangleright \frac{1856}{4273} = \frac{3712}{8546}$	$\triangleright \frac{2156}{3784} = \frac{4312}{7568}$
$\triangleright \frac{1764}{2853} = \frac{2156}{3487}$	$\triangleright \frac{1837}{2564} = \frac{3674}{5128}$	$\triangleright \frac{1856}{4327} = \frac{3712}{8654}$	$\triangleright \frac{2158}{3764} = \frac{4316}{7528}$
$\triangleright \frac{1764}{5283} = \frac{2548}{7631}$	$\triangleright \frac{1837}{4256} = \frac{3674}{8512}$	$\triangleright \frac{1856}{4372} = \frac{3248}{7651}$	$\triangleright \frac{2158}{4376} = \frac{4316}{8752}$
$\triangleright \frac{1768}{4352} = \frac{2184}{5376}$	$\triangleright \frac{1842}{3576} = \frac{3684}{7152}$	$\triangleright \frac{1857}{2634} = \frac{3714}{5268}$	$\triangleright \frac{2164}{3578} = \frac{4328}{7156}$
$\triangleright \frac{1782}{3456} = \frac{2673}{5184}$	$\triangleright \frac{1842}{3756} = \frac{3684}{7512}$	$\triangleright \frac{1857}{2643} = \frac{3714}{5286}$	$\triangleright \frac{2164}{3758} = \frac{4328}{7516}$
$\triangleright \frac{1782}{3654} = \frac{2673}{5481}$	$\triangleright \frac{1843}{7562} = \frac{2134}{8756}$	$\triangleright \frac{1857}{3264} = \frac{3714}{6528}$	$\triangleright \frac{2174}{3658} = \frac{3261}{5487}$
$\triangleright \frac{1782}{5436} = \frac{2673}{8154}$	$\triangleright \frac{1852}{3764} = \frac{3241}{6587}$	$\triangleright \frac{1857}{3426} = \frac{3714}{6852}$	$\triangleright \frac{2174}{3856} = \frac{3261}{5784}$
$\triangleright \frac{1782}{5634} = \frac{2673}{8451}$	$\triangleright \frac{1852}{4376} = \frac{3241}{7658}$	$\triangleright \frac{1857}{4263} = \frac{3714}{8526}$	$\triangleright \frac{2174}{5638} = \frac{3261}{8457}$
$\triangleright \frac{1784}{2356} = \frac{3568}{4712}$	$\triangleright \frac{1854}{2376} = \frac{2781}{3564}$	$\triangleright \frac{1857}{4326} = \frac{3714}{8652}$	$\triangleright \frac{2174}{5836} = \frac{3261}{8754}$

▶ $\frac{2176}{3458} = \frac{3264}{5187}$	▶ $\frac{2378}{4156} = \frac{4756}{8312}$	▶ $\frac{2568}{4371} = \frac{5136}{8742}$	▶ $\frac{2586}{4173} = \frac{5172}{8346}$
▶ $\frac{2176}{3854} = \frac{3264}{5781}$	▶ $\frac{2378}{5416} = \frac{3567}{8124}$	▶ $\frac{2571}{3684} = \frac{5142}{7368}$	▶ $\frac{2586}{4317} = \frac{5172}{8634}$
▶ $\frac{2176}{4358} = \frac{4352}{8716}$	▶ $\frac{2378}{5614} = \frac{3567}{8421}$	▶ $\frac{2571}{4368} = \frac{5142}{8736}$	▶ $\frac{2587}{3164} = \frac{5174}{6328}$
▶ $\frac{2176}{5438} = \frac{3264}{8157}$	▶ $\frac{2416}{3578} = \frac{4832}{7156}$	▶ $\frac{2573}{4186} = \frac{5146}{8372}$	▶ $\frac{2587}{3416} = \frac{5174}{6832}$
▶ $\frac{2176}{5834} = \frac{3264}{8751}$	▶ $\frac{2416}{3758} = \frac{4832}{7516}$	▶ $\frac{2573}{4681} = \frac{4316}{7852}$	▶ $\frac{2587}{4163} = \frac{5174}{8326}$
▶ $\frac{2178}{3456} = \frac{3267}{5184}$	▶ $\frac{2418}{3576} = \frac{4836}{7152}$	▶ $\frac{2574}{3168} = \frac{3861}{4752}$	▶ $\frac{2587}{4316} = \frac{5174}{8632}$
▶ $\frac{2178}{5346} = \frac{2574}{6318}$	▶ $\frac{2418}{3756} = \frac{4836}{7512}$	▶ $\frac{2574}{3186} = \frac{5148}{6372}$	▶ $\frac{2617}{3584} = \frac{5234}{7168}$
▶ $\frac{2178}{5634} = \frac{3267}{8451}$	▶ $\frac{2563}{4187} = \frac{5126}{8374}$	▶ $\frac{2574}{3681} = \frac{5148}{7362}$	▶ $\frac{2617}{4358} = \frac{5234}{8716}$
▶ $\frac{2184}{3576} = \frac{4368}{7152}$	▶ $\frac{2564}{3187} = \frac{5128}{6374}$	▶ $\frac{2576}{3418} = \frac{3864}{5127}$	▶ $\frac{2618}{3574} = \frac{5236}{7148}$
▶ $\frac{2184}{3756} = \frac{4368}{7512}$	▶ $\frac{2564}{3718} = \frac{5128}{7436}$	▶ $\frac{2576}{3814} = \frac{3864}{5721}$	▶ $\frac{2618}{4357} = \frac{5236}{8714}$
▶ $\frac{2187}{3645} = \frac{2781}{4635}$	▶ $\frac{2564}{3817} = \frac{5128}{7634}$	▶ $\frac{2578}{3416} = \frac{3867}{5124}$	▶ $\frac{2637}{4158} = \frac{5274}{8316}$
▶ $\frac{2314}{5768} = \frac{3471}{8652}$	▶ $\frac{2567}{3814} = \frac{5134}{7628}$	▶ $\frac{2578}{3614} = \frac{3867}{5421}$	▶ $\frac{2638}{4157} = \frac{5276}{8314}$
▶ $\frac{2356}{4178} = \frac{4712}{8356}$	▶ $\frac{2567}{3841} = \frac{5134}{7682}$	▶ $\frac{2581}{3674} = \frac{5162}{7348}$	▶ $\frac{2641}{3857} = \frac{3614}{5278}$
▶ $\frac{2358}{4176} = \frac{4716}{8352}$	▶ $\frac{2567}{4138} = \frac{5134}{8276}$	▶ $\frac{2581}{4367} = \frac{5162}{8734}$	▶ $\frac{2641}{5738} = \frac{3614}{7852}$
▶ $\frac{2374}{5618} = \frac{3561}{8427}$	▶ $\frac{2567}{4381} = \frac{5134}{8762}$	▶ $\frac{2584}{3617} = \frac{5168}{7234}$	▶ $\frac{2657}{3814} = \frac{5314}{7628}$
▶ $\frac{2374}{5816} = \frac{3561}{8724}$	▶ $\frac{2568}{3174} = \frac{3852}{4761}$	▶ $\frac{2584}{3671} = \frac{5168}{7342}$	▶ $\frac{2657}{3841} = \frac{5314}{7682}$
▶ $\frac{2376}{4185} = \frac{4136}{7285}$	▶ $\frac{2568}{3714} = \frac{5136}{7428}$	▶ $\frac{2584}{3716} = \frac{5168}{7432}$	▶ $\frac{2657}{4138} = \frac{5314}{8276}$
▶ $\frac{2376}{5418} = \frac{3564}{8127}$	▶ $\frac{2568}{3741} = \frac{5136}{7482}$	▶ $\frac{2586}{3174} = \frac{5172}{6348}$	▶ $\frac{2657}{4381} = \frac{5314}{8762}$
▶ $\frac{2376}{5814} = \frac{3564}{8721}$	▶ $\frac{2568}{4137} = \frac{5136}{8274}$	▶ $\frac{2586}{3417} = \frac{5172}{6834}$	▶ $\frac{2658}{3714} = \frac{5316}{7428}$

▶ $\frac{2658}{3741} = \frac{5316}{7482}$	▶ $\frac{2741}{3568} = \frac{5482}{7136}$	▶ $\frac{2856}{4173} = \frac{5712}{8346}$	▶ $\frac{3256}{4187} = \frac{6512}{8374}$
▶ $\frac{2658}{4137} = \frac{5316}{8274}$	▶ $\frac{2741}{3658} = \frac{5482}{7316}$	▶ $\frac{2856}{4317} = \frac{5712}{8634}$	▶ $\frac{3257}{4186} = \frac{6514}{8372}$
▶ $\frac{2658}{4371} = \frac{5316}{8742}$	▶ $\frac{2748}{3165} = \frac{6412}{7385}$	▶ $\frac{2857}{3164} = \frac{5714}{6328}$	▶ $\frac{3276}{4851} = \frac{5148}{7623}$
▶ $\frac{2671}{3584} = \frac{5342}{7168}$	▶ $\frac{2784}{3516} = \frac{4872}{6153}$	▶ $\frac{2857}{3416} = \frac{5714}{6832}$	▶ $\frac{3286}{4157} = \frac{6572}{8314}$
▶ $\frac{2671}{4358} = \frac{5342}{8716}$	▶ $\frac{2814}{3567} = \frac{5628}{7134}$	▶ $\frac{2857}{4163} = \frac{5714}{8326}$	▶ $\frac{3287}{4156} = \frac{6574}{8312}$
▶ $\frac{2674}{3581} = \frac{5348}{7162}$	▶ $\frac{2814}{3657} = \frac{5628}{7314}$	▶ $\frac{2857}{4316} = \frac{5714}{8632}$	▶ $\frac{3416}{5782} = \frac{5124}{8673}$
▶ $\frac{2681}{3574} = \frac{5362}{7148}$	▶ $\frac{2814}{3675} = \frac{3618}{4725}$	▶ $\frac{2863}{4157} = \frac{5726}{8314}$	▶ $\frac{3418}{5762} = \frac{5127}{8643}$
▶ $\frac{2681}{4357} = \frac{5362}{8714}$	▶ $\frac{2814}{5376} = \frac{3417}{6528}$	▶ $\frac{2864}{3157} = \frac{5728}{6314}$	▶ $\frac{3562}{4178} = \frac{7124}{8356}$
▶ $\frac{2681}{4375} = \frac{4213}{6875}$	▶ $\frac{2816}{3574} = \frac{5632}{7148}$	▶ $\frac{2871}{5643} = \frac{3654}{7182}$	▶ $\frac{3567}{4128} = \frac{7134}{8256}$
▶ $\frac{2684}{3571} = \frac{5368}{7142}$	▶ $\frac{2816}{4357} = \frac{5632}{8714}$	▶ $\frac{2873}{4156} = \frac{5746}{8312}$	▶ $\frac{3567}{4281} = \frac{7134}{8562}$
▶ $\frac{2684}{3751} = \frac{5612}{7843}$	▶ $\frac{2817}{3564} = \frac{5634}{7128}$	▶ $\frac{2874}{3156} = \frac{5748}{6312}$	▶ $\frac{3568}{4127} = \frac{7136}{8254}$
▶ $\frac{2684}{7315} = \frac{3172}{8645}$	▶ $\frac{2817}{4356} = \frac{5634}{8712}$	▶ $\frac{3142}{5768} = \frac{4713}{8652}$	▶ $\frac{3568}{4271} = \frac{7136}{8542}$
▶ $\frac{2714}{3568} = \frac{5428}{7136}$	▶ $\frac{2831}{6745} = \frac{3427}{8165}$	▶ $\frac{3156}{4287} = \frac{6312}{8574}$	▶ $\frac{3571}{4268} = \frac{7142}{8536}$
▶ $\frac{2716}{3584} = \frac{5432}{7168}$	▶ $\frac{2836}{4157} = \frac{5672}{8314}$	▶ $\frac{3157}{4286} = \frac{6314}{8572}$	▶ $\frac{3576}{4182} = \frac{7152}{8364}$
▶ $\frac{2716}{4358} = \frac{5432}{8716}$	▶ $\frac{2837}{4156} = \frac{5674}{8312}$	▶ $\frac{3174}{5682} = \frac{4761}{8523}$	▶ $\frac{3576}{4218} = \frac{7152}{8436}$
▶ $\frac{2718}{3564} = \frac{5436}{7128}$	▶ $\frac{2841}{3567} = \frac{5682}{7134}$	▶ $\frac{3182}{5476} = \frac{3784}{6512}$	▶ $\frac{3576}{4812} = \frac{5364}{7218}$
▶ $\frac{2718}{4356} = \frac{5436}{8712}$	▶ $\frac{2841}{3657} = \frac{5682}{7314}$	▶ $\frac{3186}{4257} = \frac{6372}{8514}$	▶ $\frac{3578}{4162} = \frac{7156}{8324}$
▶ $\frac{2736}{4158} = \frac{5472}{8316}$	▶ $\frac{2856}{3174} = \frac{5712}{6348}$	▶ $\frac{3187}{4256} = \frac{6374}{8512}$	▶ $\frac{3578}{4216} = \frac{7156}{8432}$
▶ $\frac{2738}{4156} = \frac{5476}{8312}$	▶ $\frac{2856}{3417} = \frac{5712}{6834}$	▶ $\frac{3248}{5761} = \frac{3712}{6584}$	▶ $\frac{3581}{4267} = \frac{7162}{8534}$

$$\triangleright \frac{3582}{4176} = \frac{7164}{8352}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3614}{5782} = \frac{5421}{8673}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3617}{4258} = \frac{7234}{8516}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3618}{4257} = \frac{7236}{8514}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3618}{5742} = \frac{5427}{8613}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3627}{4158} = \frac{7254}{8316}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3628}{4157} = \frac{7256}{8314}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3657}{4128} = \frac{7314}{8256}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3657}{4281} = \frac{7314}{8562}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3658}{4127} = \frac{7316}{8254}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3658}{4271} = \frac{7316}{8542}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3671}{4258} = \frac{7342}{8516}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3672}{5814} = \frac{4536}{7182}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3681}{4257} = \frac{7362}{8514}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3716}{4258} = \frac{7432}{8516}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3718}{4256} = \frac{7436}{8512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3724}{5168} = \frac{4851}{6732}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3724}{5681} = \frac{4312}{6578}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3726}{4158} = \frac{7452}{8316}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3728}{4156} = \frac{7456}{8312}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3742}{5618} = \frac{5613}{8427}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3742}{5816} = \frac{5613}{8724}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3756}{4182} = \frac{7512}{8364}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3756}{4218} = \frac{7512}{8436}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3758}{4162} = \frac{7516}{8324}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3758}{4216} = \frac{7516}{8432}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3762}{4158} = \frac{7524}{8316}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3762}{5418} = \frac{5643}{8127}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3762}{5814} = \frac{5643}{8721}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3781}{5624} = \frac{4378}{6512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3782}{4156} = \frac{7564}{8312}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3782}{5146} = \frac{5246}{7138}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3782}{5416} = \frac{5673}{8124}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3782}{5614} = \frac{5673}{8421}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3814}{5762} = \frac{5721}{8643}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3816}{4257} = \frac{7632}{8514}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3816}{5742} = \frac{5724}{8613}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3817}{4256} = \frac{7634}{8512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3826}{4157} = \frac{7652}{8314}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3827}{4156} = \frac{7654}{8312}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{3852}{4716} = \frac{6741}{8253}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{4128}{5376} = \frac{4386}{5712}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{4237}{5168} = \frac{4683}{5712}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{4318}{5627} = \frac{5842}{7613}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{4326}{5871} = \frac{4578}{6213}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{4352}{6817} = \frac{5376}{8421}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{4368}{5712} = \frac{5148}{6732}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{4617}{5832} = \frac{5643}{7128}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{4752}{6183} = \frac{6512}{8473}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{4781}{5362} = \frac{7513}{8426}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{5246}{7381} = \frac{5418}{7623}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{5328}{6417} = \frac{6512}{7843}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{5328}{7146} = \frac{6512}{8734}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{5346}{7128} = \frac{6534}{8712}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{5418}{6732} = \frac{6321}{7854}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{5418}{7326} = \frac{6321}{8547}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{5432}{8176} = \frac{5723}{8614}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{5824}{7136} = \frac{6734}{8251}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{123}{56874} = \frac{164}{75832}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{123}{58764} = \frac{164}{78352}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{124}{35678} = \frac{248}{71356}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{124}{35768} = \frac{248}{71536}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{124}{36578} = \frac{248}{73156}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{124}{36758} = \frac{248}{73516}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{124}{37568} = \frac{248}{75136}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{124}{37658} = \frac{248}{75316}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{126}{37485} = \frac{246}{73185}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{126}{53874} = \frac{147}{62853}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{126}{54873} = \frac{132}{57486}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{126}{57834} = \frac{162}{74358}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{126}{58734} = \frac{147}{68523}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{126}{73584} = \frac{134}{78256}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{127}{35684} = \frac{254}{71368}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{127}{36584} = \frac{254}{73168}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{127}{43568} = \frac{254}{87136}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{127}{43658} = \frac{254}{87316}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{128}{34576} = \frac{216}{58347}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{128}{35674} = \frac{256}{71348}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{128}{36574} = \frac{256}{73148}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{128}{43567} = \frac{256}{87134}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{128}{43657} = \frac{256}{87314}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{128}{45376} = \frac{214}{75863}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{132}{48576} = \frac{146}{53728}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{134}{25687} = \frac{268}{51374}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{134}{25867} = \frac{268}{51734}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{134}{26587} = \frac{268}{53174}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{134}{26857} = \frac{268}{53714}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{134}{28567} = \frac{268}{57134}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{134}{28657} = \frac{268}{57314}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{136}{74528} = \frac{138}{75624}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{137}{25684} = \frac{274}{51368}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{137}{26584} = \frac{274}{53168}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{137}{42568} = \frac{274}{85136}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{137}{42658} = \frac{274}{85316}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{138}{24567} = \frac{184}{32756}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{138}{25674} = \frac{276}{51348}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{138}{26457} = \frac{184}{35276}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{138}{26574} = \frac{276}{53148}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{138}{26754} = \frac{184}{35672}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{138}{27564} = \frac{184}{36752}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{138}{42567} = \frac{276}{85134}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{138}{42657} = \frac{276}{85314}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{138}{54267} = \frac{184}{72356}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{138}{56427} = \frac{184}{75236}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{138}{56724} = \frac{184}{75632}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{138}{57264} = \frac{184}{76352}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{138}{76452} = \frac{153}{84762}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{142}{35678} = \frac{284}{71356}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{142}{35768} = \frac{284}{71536}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{142}{36758} = \frac{284}{73516}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{142}{37568} = \frac{284}{75136}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{142}{37856} = \frac{213}{56784}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{142}{38576} = \frac{213}{57864}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{142}{56378} = \frac{213}{84567}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{142}{57368} = \frac{157}{63428}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{142}{57638} = \frac{213}{86457}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{142}{57836} = \frac{213}{86754}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{142}{58376} = \frac{213}{87564}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{142}{63758} = \frac{168}{75432}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{143}{25687} = \frac{286}{51374}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{143}{25867} = \frac{286}{51734}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{143}{26587} = \frac{286}{53174}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{143}{26857} = \frac{286}{53714}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{143}{27586} = \frac{341}{65782}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{143}{28567} = \frac{286}{57134}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{143}{28657} = \frac{286}{57314}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{143}{28756} = \frac{341}{68572}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{145}{23876} = \frac{435}{71628}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{146}{23875} = \frac{438}{71625}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{147}{36582} = \frac{231}{57486}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{152}{34768} = \frac{361}{82574}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{152}{36784} = \frac{154}{37268}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{152}{38476} = \frac{342}{86571}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{153}{27846} = \frac{312}{56784}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{154}{23786} = \frac{462}{71358}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{154}{26378} = \frac{476}{81532}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{154}{28763} = \frac{286}{53417}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{154}{36827} = \frac{352}{84176}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{156}{24378} = \frac{312}{48756}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{156}{27384} = \frac{312}{54768}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{156}{27438} = \frac{312}{54876}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{156}{28374} = \frac{312}{56748}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{156}{28734} = \frac{312}{57468}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{156}{32874} = \frac{312}{65748}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{156}{34287} = \frac{312}{68574}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{156}{34872} = \frac{351}{78462}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{156}{37248} = \frac{273}{65184}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{156}{37284} = \frac{312}{74568}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{156}{37428} = \frac{312}{74856}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{156}{37824} = \frac{312}{75648}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{156}{37842} = \frac{312}{75684}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{156}{38274} = \frac{312}{76548}$$

$\triangleright \frac{156}{38427} = \frac{312}{76854}$	$\triangleright \frac{157}{36428} = \frac{314}{72856}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{37624} = \frac{316}{75248}$	$\triangleright \frac{162}{57438} = \frac{243}{86157}$
$\triangleright \frac{156}{42378} = \frac{312}{84756}$	$\triangleright \frac{157}{38264} = \frac{314}{76528}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{37642} = \frac{316}{75284}$	$\triangleright \frac{162}{57834} = \frac{243}{86751}$
$\triangleright \frac{156}{42738} = \frac{312}{85476}$	$\triangleright \frac{157}{38426} = \frac{314}{76852}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{42376} = \frac{316}{84752}$	$\triangleright \frac{162}{58374} = \frac{243}{87561}$
$\triangleright \frac{156}{42837} = \frac{312}{85674}$	$\triangleright \frac{157}{42638} = \frac{314}{85276}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{42637} = \frac{316}{85274}$	$\triangleright \frac{163}{25874} = \frac{326}{51748}$
$\triangleright \frac{156}{42873} = \frac{312}{85746}$	$\triangleright \frac{157}{42836} = \frac{314}{85672}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{42736} = \frac{316}{85472}$	$\triangleright \frac{163}{28574} = \frac{326}{57148}$
$\triangleright \frac{156}{43287} = \frac{312}{86574}$	$\triangleright \frac{157}{42863} = \frac{314}{85726}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{43627} = \frac{316}{87254}$	$\triangleright \frac{163}{42587} = \frac{326}{85174}$
$\triangleright \frac{156}{43728} = \frac{312}{87456}$	$\triangleright \frac{157}{43286} = \frac{314}{86572}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{43726} = \frac{316}{87452}$	$\triangleright \frac{163}{42857} = \frac{326}{85714}$
$\triangleright \frac{156}{43782} = \frac{312}{87564}$	$\triangleright \frac{157}{43628} = \frac{314}{87256}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{43762} = \frac{316}{87524}$	$\triangleright \frac{164}{23578} = \frac{328}{47156}$
$\triangleright \frac{156}{43827} = \frac{312}{87654}$	$\triangleright \frac{157}{43826} = \frac{314}{87652}$	$\triangleright \frac{162}{34578} = \frac{243}{51867}$	$\triangleright \frac{164}{23758} = \frac{328}{47516}$
$\triangleright \frac{156}{48372} = \frac{273}{84651}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{23764} = \frac{316}{47528}$	$\triangleright \frac{162}{35784} = \frac{324}{71568}$	$\triangleright \frac{164}{25738} = \frac{328}{51476}$
$\triangleright \frac{157}{26384} = \frac{314}{52768}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{24376} = \frac{316}{48752}$	$\triangleright \frac{162}{37458} = \frac{243}{56187}$	$\triangleright \frac{164}{25837} = \frac{328}{51674}$
$\triangleright \frac{157}{26438} = \frac{314}{52876}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{26374} = \frac{316}{52748}$	$\triangleright \frac{162}{37584} = \frac{324}{75168}$	$\triangleright \frac{164}{25873} = \frac{328}{51746}$
$\triangleright \frac{157}{28364} = \frac{314}{56728}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{26437} = \frac{316}{52874}$	$\triangleright \frac{162}{37854} = \frac{243}{56781}$	$\triangleright \frac{164}{27358} = \frac{328}{54716}$
$\triangleright \frac{157}{28436} = \frac{314}{56872}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{27364} = \frac{316}{54728}$	$\triangleright \frac{162}{38475} = \frac{346}{82175}$	$\triangleright \frac{164}{28357} = \frac{328}{56714}$
$\triangleright \frac{157}{28634} = \frac{314}{57268}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{27436} = \frac{316}{54872}$	$\triangleright \frac{162}{38574} = \frac{243}{57861}$	$\triangleright \frac{164}{28573} = \frac{328}{57146}$
$\triangleright \frac{157}{28643} = \frac{314}{57286}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{36274} = \frac{316}{72548}$	$\triangleright \frac{162}{43578} = \frac{324}{87156}$	$\triangleright \frac{164}{32587} = \frac{328}{65174}$
$\triangleright \frac{157}{32864} = \frac{314}{65728}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{36427} = \frac{316}{72854}$	$\triangleright \frac{162}{43758} = \frac{324}{87516}$	$\triangleright \frac{164}{32857} = \frac{328}{65714}$
$\triangleright \frac{157}{34286} = \frac{314}{68572}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{37264} = \frac{316}{74528}$	$\triangleright \frac{162}{53784} = \frac{176}{58432}$	$\triangleright \frac{164}{35728} = \frac{328}{71456}$
$\triangleright \frac{157}{36284} = \frac{314}{72568}$	$\triangleright \frac{158}{37426} = \frac{316}{74852}$	$\triangleright \frac{162}{54378} = \frac{243}{81567}$	$\triangleright \frac{164}{35782} = \frac{328}{71564}$

$\triangleright \frac{164}{35827} = \frac{328}{71654}$	$\triangleright \frac{174}{26358} = \frac{348}{52716}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{34582} = \frac{264}{51873}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{34562} = \frac{267}{51843}$
$\triangleright \frac{164}{37258} = \frac{328}{74516}$	$\triangleright \frac{174}{28356} = \frac{348}{56712}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{35824} = \frac{352}{71648}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{35624} = \frac{356}{71248}$
$\triangleright \frac{164}{37582} = \frac{328}{75164}$	$\triangleright \frac{174}{28563} = \frac{348}{57126}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{35842} = \frac{352}{71684}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{35642} = \frac{356}{71284}$
$\triangleright \frac{164}{38257} = \frac{328}{76514}$	$\triangleright \frac{174}{32586} = \frac{348}{65172}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{38254} = \frac{264}{57381}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{36254} = \frac{267}{54381}$
$\triangleright \frac{165}{27483} = \frac{385}{64127}$	$\triangleright \frac{174}{32856} = \frac{348}{65712}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{38542} = \frac{264}{57813}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{36542} = \frac{267}{54813}$
$\triangleright \frac{165}{32748} = \frac{385}{76412}$	$\triangleright \frac{174}{35628} = \frac{348}{71256}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{42358} = \frac{352}{84716}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{42356} = \frac{356}{84712}$
$\triangleright \frac{165}{34287} = \frac{415}{86237}$	$\triangleright \frac{174}{35826} = \frac{348}{71652}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{52384} = \frac{231}{68754}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{43562} = \frac{356}{87124}$
$\triangleright \frac{167}{52438} = \frac{183}{57462}$	$\triangleright \frac{174}{36582} = \frac{261}{54873}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{53482} = \frac{248}{75361}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{54236} = \frac{267}{81354}$
$\triangleright \frac{168}{25347} = \frac{432}{65178}$	$\triangleright \frac{174}{38562} = \frac{261}{57843}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{54238} = \frac{264}{81357}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{54362} = \frac{267}{81543}$
$\triangleright \frac{168}{35742} = \frac{412}{87653}$	$\triangleright \frac{174}{56238} = \frac{261}{84357}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{54382} = \frac{264}{81573}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{56234} = \frac{267}{84351}$
$\triangleright \frac{168}{54327} = \frac{264}{85371}$	$\triangleright \frac{174}{56382} = \frac{261}{84573}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{58234} = \frac{264}{87351}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{56342} = \frac{267}{84513}$
$\triangleright \frac{172}{34658} = \frac{368}{74152}$	$\triangleright \frac{174}{58236} = \frac{261}{87354}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{58342} = \frac{264}{87513}$	$\triangleright \frac{182}{34576} = \frac{273}{51864}$
$\triangleright \frac{173}{25864} = \frac{346}{51728}$	$\triangleright \frac{174}{58362} = \frac{261}{87543}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{23456} = \frac{267}{35184}$	$\triangleright \frac{182}{35764} = \frac{364}{71528}$
$\triangleright \frac{173}{28564} = \frac{346}{57128}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{23458} = \frac{264}{35187}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{23564} = \frac{356}{47128}$	$\triangleright \frac{182}{36547} = \frac{286}{57431}$
$\triangleright \frac{173}{42586} = \frac{346}{85172}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{23854} = \frac{264}{35781}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{23654} = \frac{267}{35481}$	$\triangleright \frac{182}{36574} = \frac{273}{54861}$
$\triangleright \frac{173}{42856} = \frac{346}{85712}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{24358} = \frac{352}{48716}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{24356} = \frac{356}{48712}$	$\triangleright \frac{182}{37456} = \frac{273}{56184}$
$\triangleright \frac{174}{23658} = \frac{261}{35487}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{24538} = \frac{528}{73614}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{25436} = \frac{267}{38154}$	$\triangleright \frac{182}{37564} = \frac{364}{75128}$
$\triangleright \frac{174}{23856} = \frac{261}{35784}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{25834} = \frac{264}{38751}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{25634} = \frac{267}{38451}$	$\triangleright \frac{182}{37654} = \frac{273}{56481}$
$\triangleright \frac{174}{25863} = \frac{348}{51726}$	$\triangleright \frac{176}{34258} = \frac{264}{51387}$	$\triangleright \frac{178}{34256} = \frac{267}{51384}$	$\triangleright \frac{182}{43756} = \frac{364}{87512}$

$$\triangleright \frac{182}{54376} = \frac{273}{81564}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{182}{56374} = \frac{273}{84561}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{182}{57436} = \frac{273}{86154}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{182}{57634} = \frac{273}{86451}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{184}{23576} = \frac{368}{47152}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{184}{23756} = \frac{368}{47512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{184}{25637} = \frac{368}{51274}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{184}{25736} = \frac{368}{51472}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{184}{26357} = \frac{368}{52714}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{184}{27356} = \frac{368}{54712}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{184}{35627} = \frac{368}{71254}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{184}{35726} = \frac{368}{71452}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{184}{35762} = \frac{368}{71524}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{184}{36257} = \frac{368}{72514}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{184}{37256} = \frac{368}{74512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{184}{37562} = \frac{368}{75124}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{186}{25734} = \frac{372}{51468}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{186}{25743} = \frac{372}{51486}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{186}{32574} = \frac{372}{65148}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{186}{34257} = \frac{372}{68514}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{186}{42573} = \frac{372}{85146}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{186}{43257} = \frac{372}{86514}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{186}{54732} = \frac{217}{63854}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{186}{73254} = \frac{217}{85463}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{187}{25634} = \frac{374}{51268}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{187}{25643} = \frac{374}{51286}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{187}{32564} = \frac{374}{65128}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{187}{34256} = \frac{374}{68512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{187}{42563} = \frac{374}{85126}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{187}{43256} = \frac{374}{86512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{187}{62543} = \frac{253}{84617}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{214}{35678} = \frac{428}{71356}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{214}{35768} = \frac{428}{71536}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{214}{36758} = \frac{428}{73516}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{214}{37568} = \frac{428}{75136}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{214}{37856} = \frac{321}{56784}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{214}{38576} = \frac{321}{57864}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{214}{56378} = \frac{321}{84567}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{214}{57638} = \frac{321}{86457}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{214}{57836} = \frac{321}{86754}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{214}{58376} = \frac{321}{87564}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{216}{34578} = \frac{324}{51867}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{216}{35784} = \frac{432}{71568}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{216}{37458} = \frac{324}{56187}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{216}{37584} = \frac{432}{75168}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{216}{38574} = \frac{324}{57861}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{216}{43578} = \frac{432}{87156}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{216}{43758} = \frac{432}{87516}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{216}{57438} = \frac{324}{86157}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{216}{57834} = \frac{324}{86751}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{216}{58374} = \frac{324}{87561}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{217}{43865} = \frac{427}{86315}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{218}{34576} = \frac{327}{51864}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{218}{35764} = \frac{436}{71528}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{218}{36574} = \frac{327}{54861}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{218}{37456} = \frac{327}{56184}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{218}{37564} = \frac{436}{75128}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{218}{37654} = \frac{327}{56481}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{218}{43576} = \frac{436}{87152}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{218}{43756} = \frac{436}{87512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{218}{54376} = \frac{327}{81564}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{218}{56374} = \frac{327}{84561}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{218}{57436} = \frac{327}{86154}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{218}{57634} = \frac{327}{86451}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{231}{47586} = \frac{263}{54178}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{234}{15678} = \frac{783}{52461}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{234}{15786} = \frac{468}{31572}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{234}{15876} = \frac{468}{31752}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{234}{16578} = \frac{351}{24867}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{234}{17658} = \frac{351}{26487}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{234}{18756} = \frac{468}{37512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{234}{56178} = \frac{351}{84267}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{234}{57618} = \frac{351}{86427}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{234}{57816} = \frac{351}{86724}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{234}{58176} = \frac{351}{87264}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{234}{58617} = \frac{342}{85671}$$

- | | | | |
|---|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{234}{67158} = \frac{263}{75481}$ | ▶ $\frac{238}{16574} = \frac{357}{24861}$ | ▶ $\frac{243}{17856} = \frac{486}{35712}$ | ▶ $\frac{254}{37618} = \frac{381}{56427}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{234}{76518} = \frac{261}{85347}$ | ▶ $\frac{238}{17546} = \frac{714}{52638}$ | ▶ $\frac{243}{18576} = \frac{486}{37152}$ | ▶ $\frac{254}{37816} = \frac{381}{56724}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{235}{68714} = \frac{245}{71638}$ | ▶ $\frac{238}{17564} = \frac{476}{35128}$ | ▶ $\frac{243}{18756} = \frac{486}{37512}$ | ▶ $\frac{254}{38176} = \frac{381}{57264}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{236}{14578} = \frac{354}{21867}$ | ▶ $\frac{238}{17654} = \frac{357}{26481}$ | ▶ $\frac{243}{58617} = \frac{324}{78156}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{13784} = \frac{768}{41352}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{236}{15478} = \frac{826}{54173}$ | ▶ $\frac{238}{41576} = \frac{476}{83152}$ | ▶ $\frac{245}{13867} = \frac{835}{47261}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{14378} = \frac{384}{21567}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{236}{15784} = \frac{472}{31568}$ | ▶ $\frac{238}{41756} = \frac{476}{83512}$ | ▶ $\frac{245}{13876} = \frac{735}{41628}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{17384} = \frac{512}{34768}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{236}{17458} = \frac{354}{26187}$ | ▶ $\frac{238}{54176} = \frac{357}{81264}$ | ▶ $\frac{245}{37681} = \frac{415}{63827}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{17834} = \frac{384}{26751}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{236}{17584} = \frac{472}{35168}$ | ▶ $\frac{238}{56174} = \frac{357}{84261}$ | ▶ $\frac{246}{13875} = \frac{738}{41625}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{18437} = \frac{512}{36874}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{236}{17854} = \frac{354}{26781}$ | ▶ $\frac{238}{57416} = \frac{357}{86124}$ | ▶ $\frac{246}{17538} = \frac{738}{52614}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{18734} = \frac{512}{37468}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{236}{18574} = \frac{354}{27861}$ | ▶ $\frac{238}{57614} = \frac{357}{86421}$ | ▶ $\frac{246}{35178} = \frac{367}{52481}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{18743} = \frac{512}{37486}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{236}{41578} = \frac{472}{83156}$ | ▶ $\frac{241}{35678} = \frac{482}{71356}$ | ▶ $\frac{246}{57318} = \frac{281}{65473}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{31874} = \frac{512}{63748}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{236}{41758} = \frac{472}{83516}$ | ▶ $\frac{241}{35768} = \frac{482}{71536}$ | ▶ $\frac{248}{57136} = \frac{341}{78562}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{34178} = \frac{384}{51267}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{236}{54178} = \frac{354}{81267}$ | ▶ $\frac{241}{36578} = \frac{482}{73156}$ | ▶ $\frac{254}{13786} = \frac{762}{41358}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{34187} = \frac{512}{68374}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{236}{57418} = \frac{354}{86127}$ | ▶ $\frac{241}{36758} = \frac{482}{73516}$ | ▶ $\frac{254}{16378} = \frac{381}{24567}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{37814} = \frac{384}{56721}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{236}{57814} = \frac{354}{86721}$ | ▶ $\frac{241}{37568} = \frac{482}{75136}$ | ▶ $\frac{254}{17638} = \frac{381}{26457}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{38417} = \frac{512}{76834}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{238}{14567} = \frac{612}{37458}$ | ▶ $\frac{241}{37658} = \frac{482}{75316}$ | ▶ $\frac{254}{17836} = \frac{381}{26754}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{41738} = \frac{512}{83476}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{238}{14576} = \frac{357}{21864}$ | ▶ $\frac{243}{15786} = \frac{486}{31572}$ | ▶ $\frac{254}{18376} = \frac{381}{27564}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{41837} = \frac{512}{83674}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{238}{15764} = \frac{476}{31528}$ | ▶ $\frac{243}{15876} = \frac{486}{31752}$ | ▶ $\frac{254}{31768} = \frac{381}{47652}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{41873} = \frac{512}{83746}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{238}{16457} = \frac{374}{25861}$ | ▶ $\frac{243}{17586} = \frac{486}{35172}$ | ▶ $\frac{254}{36178} = \frac{381}{54267}$ | ▶ $\frac{256}{43187} = \frac{512}{86374}$ |

$$\triangleright \frac{256}{43718} = \frac{512}{87436}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{256}{43817} = \frac{512}{87634}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{13684} = \frac{514}{27368}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{14368} = \frac{514}{28736}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{16384} = \frac{514}{32768}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{16438} = \frac{514}{32876}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{18364} = \frac{514}{36728}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{18436} = \frac{514}{36872}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{18634} = \frac{514}{37268}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{18643} = \frac{514}{37286}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{31864} = \frac{514}{63728}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{34186} = \frac{514}{68372}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{36184} = \frac{514}{72368}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{36418} = \frac{514}{72836}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{36814} = \frac{514}{73628}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{36841} = \frac{514}{73682}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{38164} = \frac{514}{76328}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{38416} = \frac{514}{76832}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{41368} = \frac{514}{82736}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{41638} = \frac{514}{83276}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{41836} = \frac{514}{83672}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{41863} = \frac{514}{83726}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{43186} = \frac{514}{86372}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{43618} = \frac{514}{87236}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{43681} = \frac{514}{87362}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{43816} = \frac{514}{87632}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{14367} = \frac{516}{28734}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{14376} = \frac{387}{21564}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{16437} = \frac{516}{32874}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{17364} = \frac{516}{34728}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{17634} = \frac{387}{26451}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{31476} = \frac{531}{64782}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{34176} = \frac{387}{51264}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{36417} = \frac{516}{72834}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{36714} = \frac{516}{73428}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{36741} = \frac{516}{73482}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{37164} = \frac{516}{74328}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{37614} = \frac{387}{56421}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{41367} = \frac{516}{82734}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{41637} = \frac{516}{83274}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{41736} = \frac{516}{83472}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{43617} = \frac{516}{87234}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{43671} = \frac{516}{87342}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{258}{43716} = \frac{516}{87432}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{263}{15874} = \frac{526}{31748}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{263}{18574} = \frac{526}{37148}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{263}{41587} = \frac{526}{83174}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{263}{41857} = \frac{526}{83714}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{264}{13857} = \frac{352}{18476}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{264}{15378} = \frac{816}{47532}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{264}{15738} = \frac{528}{31476}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{264}{15837} = \frac{528}{31674}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{264}{17358} = \frac{528}{34716}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{264}{18357} = \frac{528}{36714}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{264}{18573} = \frac{528}{37146}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{264}{31587} = \frac{528}{63174}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{264}{31857} = \frac{528}{63714}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{264}{35718} = \frac{528}{71436}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{264}{35817} = \frac{528}{71634}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{264}{35871} = \frac{384}{52176}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{264}{37158} = \frac{528}{74316}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{264}{57138} = \frac{352}{76184}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{265}{17384} = \frac{735}{48216}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{267}{13584} = \frac{534}{27168}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{267}{13854} = \frac{356}{18472}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{267}{14358} = \frac{534}{28716}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{267}{35814} = \frac{534}{71628}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{267}{35841} = \frac{534}{71682}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{267}{41358} = \frac{534}{82716}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{267}{43581} = \frac{534}{87162}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{267}{54138} = \frac{356}{72184}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{268}{13574} = \frac{536}{27148}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{268}{14357} = \frac{536}{28714}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{268}{35714} = \frac{536}{71428}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{268}{35741} = \frac{536}{71482}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{268}{41357} = \frac{536}{82714}$$

$\triangleright \frac{268}{43571} = \frac{536}{87142}$	$\triangleright \frac{274}{18356} = \frac{548}{36712}$	$\triangleright \frac{284}{15637} = \frac{568}{31274}$	$\triangleright \frac{286}{41573} = \frac{572}{83146}$
$\triangleright \frac{268}{43751} = \frac{516}{84237}$	$\triangleright \frac{274}{18563} = \frac{548}{37126}$	$\triangleright \frac{284}{15736} = \frac{568}{31472}$	$\triangleright \frac{286}{43157} = \frac{572}{86314}$
$\triangleright \frac{271}{35684} = \frac{542}{71368}$	$\triangleright \frac{274}{31586} = \frac{548}{63172}$	$\triangleright \frac{284}{16357} = \frac{568}{32714}$	$\triangleright \frac{287}{15634} = \frac{574}{31268}$
$\triangleright \frac{271}{36584} = \frac{542}{73168}$	$\triangleright \frac{274}{31856} = \frac{548}{63712}$	$\triangleright \frac{284}{17356} = \frac{568}{34712}$	$\triangleright \frac{287}{15643} = \frac{574}{31286}$
$\triangleright \frac{271}{43568} = \frac{542}{87136}$	$\triangleright \frac{274}{35618} = \frac{548}{71236}$	$\triangleright \frac{284}{35617} = \frac{568}{71234}$	$\triangleright \frac{287}{16534} = \frac{738}{42516}$
$\triangleright \frac{271}{43658} = \frac{542}{87316}$	$\triangleright \frac{274}{35681} = \frac{548}{71362}$	$\triangleright \frac{284}{35671} = \frac{568}{71342}$	$\triangleright \frac{287}{31564} = \frac{574}{63128}$
$\triangleright \frac{273}{14586} = \frac{651}{34782}$	$\triangleright \frac{274}{35816} = \frac{548}{71632}$	$\triangleright \frac{284}{35716} = \frac{568}{71432}$	$\triangleright \frac{287}{34156} = \frac{574}{68312}$
$\triangleright \frac{273}{15864} = \frac{546}{31728}$	$\triangleright \frac{274}{36158} = \frac{548}{72316}$	$\triangleright \frac{284}{36157} = \frac{568}{72314}$	$\triangleright \frac{287}{41563} = \frac{574}{83126}$
$\triangleright \frac{273}{16458} = \frac{567}{34182}$	$\triangleright \frac{274}{36581} = \frac{548}{73162}$	$\triangleright \frac{284}{36571} = \frac{568}{73142}$	$\triangleright \frac{287}{43156} = \frac{574}{86312}$
$\triangleright \frac{273}{41586} = \frac{546}{83172}$	$\triangleright \frac{274}{38156} = \frac{548}{76312}$	$\triangleright \frac{284}{37156} = \frac{568}{74312}$	$\triangleright \frac{312}{58764} = \frac{416}{78352}$
$\triangleright \frac{273}{41856} = \frac{546}{83712}$	$\triangleright \frac{275}{18634} = \frac{475}{32186}$	$\triangleright \frac{285}{16473} = \frac{645}{37281}$	$\triangleright \frac{314}{25687} = \frac{628}{51374}$
$\triangleright \frac{273}{48165} = \frac{413}{72865}$	$\triangleright \frac{276}{18354} = \frac{784}{52136}$	$\triangleright \frac{285}{67431} = \frac{345}{81627}$	$\triangleright \frac{314}{25768} = \frac{471}{38652}$
$\triangleright \frac{273}{58614} = \frac{364}{78152}$	$\triangleright \frac{276}{35184} = \frac{483}{61572}$	$\triangleright \frac{285}{74613} = \frac{315}{82467}$	$\triangleright \frac{314}{25867} = \frac{628}{51734}$
$\triangleright \frac{274}{13568} = \frac{548}{27136}$	$\triangleright \frac{281}{35674} = \frac{562}{71348}$	$\triangleright \frac{286}{13754} = \frac{517}{24863}$	$\triangleright \frac{314}{26587} = \frac{628}{53174}$
$\triangleright \frac{274}{13658} = \frac{548}{27316}$	$\triangleright \frac{281}{36574} = \frac{562}{73148}$	$\triangleright \frac{286}{14573} = \frac{682}{34751}$	$\triangleright \frac{314}{26857} = \frac{628}{53714}$
$\triangleright \frac{274}{15638} = \frac{548}{31276}$	$\triangleright \frac{281}{43567} = \frac{562}{87134}$	$\triangleright \frac{286}{15734} = \frac{572}{31468}$	$\triangleright \frac{314}{28567} = \frac{628}{57134}$
$\triangleright \frac{274}{15836} = \frac{548}{31672}$	$\triangleright \frac{281}{43657} = \frac{562}{87314}$	$\triangleright \frac{286}{31574} = \frac{572}{63148}$	$\triangleright \frac{314}{28657} = \frac{628}{57314}$
$\triangleright \frac{274}{15863} = \frac{548}{31726}$	$\triangleright \frac{284}{13567} = \frac{568}{27134}$	$\triangleright \frac{286}{34157} = \frac{572}{68314}$	$\triangleright \frac{314}{57682} = \frac{471}{86523}$
$\triangleright \frac{274}{16358} = \frac{548}{32716}$	$\triangleright \frac{284}{13657} = \frac{568}{27314}$	$\triangleright \frac{286}{37154} = \frac{627}{81453}$	$\triangleright \frac{315}{27468} = \frac{715}{62348}$

$\triangleright \frac{316}{25874} = \frac{632}{51748}$	$\triangleright \frac{326}{41857} = \frac{652}{83714}$	$\triangleright \frac{342}{56178} = \frac{513}{84267}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{27418} = \frac{712}{54836}$
$\triangleright \frac{316}{28574} = \frac{632}{57148}$	$\triangleright \frac{327}{15864} = \frac{654}{31728}$	$\triangleright \frac{342}{57618} = \frac{513}{86427}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{28174} = \frac{712}{56348}$
$\triangleright \frac{316}{42587} = \frac{632}{85174}$	$\triangleright \frac{327}{18564} = \frac{654}{37128}$	$\triangleright \frac{342}{57816} = \frac{513}{86724}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{28417} = \frac{712}{56834}$
$\triangleright \frac{316}{42857} = \frac{632}{85714}$	$\triangleright \frac{327}{41586} = \frac{654}{83172}$	$\triangleright \frac{342}{58176} = \frac{513}{87264}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{41728} = \frac{712}{83456}$
$\triangleright \frac{317}{25864} = \frac{634}{51728}$	$\triangleright \frac{327}{41856} = \frac{654}{83712}$	$\triangleright \frac{347}{15268} = \frac{724}{31856}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{41782} = \frac{712}{83564}$
$\triangleright \frac{317}{28564} = \frac{634}{57128}$	$\triangleright \frac{327}{58614} = \frac{436}{78152}$	$\triangleright \frac{351}{47268} = \frac{432}{58176}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{41827} = \frac{712}{83654}$
$\triangleright \frac{317}{42586} = \frac{634}{85172}$	$\triangleright \frac{341}{25687} = \frac{682}{51374}$	$\triangleright \frac{351}{48672} = \frac{378}{52416}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{42178} = \frac{712}{84356}$
$\triangleright \frac{317}{42856} = \frac{634}{85712}$	$\triangleright \frac{341}{25867} = \frac{682}{51734}$	$\triangleright \frac{352}{16478} = \frac{672}{31458}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{42718} = \frac{712}{85436}$
$\triangleright \frac{324}{15678} = \frac{486}{23517}$	$\triangleright \frac{341}{26587} = \frac{682}{53174}$	$\triangleright \frac{352}{17468} = \frac{648}{32157}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{42817} = \frac{712}{85634}$
$\triangleright \frac{324}{15786} = \frac{648}{31572}$	$\triangleright \frac{341}{26857} = \frac{682}{53714}$	$\triangleright \frac{354}{28617} = \frac{472}{38156}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{78142} = \frac{372}{81654}$
$\triangleright \frac{324}{16758} = \frac{486}{25137}$	$\triangleright \frac{341}{28567} = \frac{682}{57134}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{17284} = \frac{712}{34568}$	$\triangleright \frac{357}{12684} = \frac{714}{25368}$
$\triangleright \frac{324}{17586} = \frac{648}{35172}$	$\triangleright \frac{341}{28657} = \frac{682}{57314}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{17428} = \frac{712}{34856}$	$\triangleright \frac{357}{14268} = \frac{714}{28536}$
$\triangleright \frac{324}{18576} = \frac{648}{37152}$	$\triangleright \frac{342}{15786} = \frac{684}{31572}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{17824} = \frac{712}{35648}$	$\triangleright \frac{357}{16284} = \frac{714}{32568}$
$\triangleright \frac{324}{18756} = \frac{648}{37512}$	$\triangleright \frac{342}{15876} = \frac{684}{31752}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{17842} = \frac{712}{35684}$	$\triangleright \frac{357}{16428} = \frac{714}{32856}$
$\triangleright \frac{324}{58617} = \frac{432}{78156}$	$\triangleright \frac{342}{16578} = \frac{513}{24867}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{18274} = \frac{712}{36548}$	$\triangleright \frac{357}{18264} = \frac{714}{36528}$
$\triangleright \frac{326}{15874} = \frac{652}{31748}$	$\triangleright \frac{342}{16587} = \frac{486}{23571}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{18427} = \frac{712}{36854}$	$\triangleright \frac{357}{18426} = \frac{714}{36852}$
$\triangleright \frac{326}{18574} = \frac{652}{37148}$	$\triangleright \frac{342}{17586} = \frac{684}{35172}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{21784} = \frac{712}{43568}$	$\triangleright \frac{357}{26814} = \frac{714}{53628}$
$\triangleright \frac{326}{18745} = \frac{762}{43815}$	$\triangleright \frac{342}{17658} = \frac{513}{26487}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{24178} = \frac{712}{48356}$	$\triangleright \frac{357}{26841} = \frac{714}{53682}$
$\triangleright \frac{326}{41587} = \frac{652}{83174}$	$\triangleright \frac{342}{18756} = \frac{684}{37512}$	$\triangleright \frac{356}{27184} = \frac{712}{54368}$	$\triangleright \frac{357}{28164} = \frac{714}{56328}$

$\triangleright \frac{357}{28416} = \frac{714}{56832}$	$\triangleright \frac{358}{26417} = \frac{716}{52834}$	$\triangleright \frac{362}{41578} = \frac{724}{83156}$	$\triangleright \frac{367}{12584} = \frac{734}{25168}$
$\triangleright \frac{357}{28614} = \frac{476}{38152}$	$\triangleright \frac{358}{26714} = \frac{716}{53428}$	$\triangleright \frac{362}{41758} = \frac{724}{83516}$	$\triangleright \frac{367}{12845} = \frac{671}{23485}$
$\triangleright \frac{357}{41268} = \frac{714}{82536}$	$\triangleright \frac{358}{26741} = \frac{716}{53482}$	$\triangleright \frac{362}{54178} = \frac{543}{81267}$	$\triangleright \frac{367}{14258} = \frac{734}{28516}$
$\triangleright \frac{357}{41628} = \frac{714}{83256}$	$\triangleright \frac{358}{27164} = \frac{716}{54328}$	$\triangleright \frac{362}{57418} = \frac{543}{86127}$	$\triangleright \frac{367}{25814} = \frac{734}{51628}$
$\triangleright \frac{357}{41826} = \frac{714}{83652}$	$\triangleright \frac{358}{27416} = \frac{716}{54832}$	$\triangleright \frac{362}{57814} = \frac{543}{86721}$	$\triangleright \frac{367}{25841} = \frac{734}{51682}$
$\triangleright \frac{357}{42618} = \frac{714}{85236}$	$\triangleright \frac{358}{41267} = \frac{716}{82534}$	$\triangleright \frac{362}{58174} = \frac{543}{87261}$	$\triangleright \frac{367}{41258} = \frac{734}{82516}$
$\triangleright \frac{357}{42681} = \frac{714}{85362}$	$\triangleright \frac{358}{41627} = \frac{716}{83254}$	$\triangleright \frac{364}{15728} = \frac{728}{31456}$	$\triangleright \frac{367}{42581} = \frac{734}{85162}$
$\triangleright \frac{357}{42816} = \frac{714}{85632}$	$\triangleright \frac{358}{41726} = \frac{716}{83452}$	$\triangleright \frac{364}{15782} = \frac{728}{31564}$	$\triangleright \frac{368}{12574} = \frac{736}{25148}$
$\triangleright \frac{358}{12674} = \frac{716}{25348}$	$\triangleright \frac{358}{41762} = \frac{716}{83524}$	$\triangleright \frac{364}{15827} = \frac{728}{31654}$	$\triangleright \frac{368}{14257} = \frac{736}{28514}$
$\triangleright \frac{358}{14267} = \frac{716}{28534}$	$\triangleright \frac{358}{42176} = \frac{716}{84352}$	$\triangleright \frac{364}{17258} = \frac{728}{34516}$	$\triangleright \frac{368}{25714} = \frac{736}{51428}$
$\triangleright \frac{358}{16274} = \frac{716}{32548}$	$\triangleright \frac{358}{42617} = \frac{716}{85234}$	$\triangleright \frac{364}{17528} = \frac{741}{35682}$	$\triangleright \frac{368}{25741} = \frac{736}{51482}$
$\triangleright \frac{358}{16427} = \frac{716}{32854}$	$\triangleright \frac{358}{42671} = \frac{716}{85342}$	$\triangleright \frac{364}{17582} = \frac{728}{35164}$	$\triangleright \frac{368}{41257} = \frac{736}{82514}$
$\triangleright \frac{358}{17264} = \frac{716}{34528}$	$\triangleright \frac{358}{42716} = \frac{716}{85432}$	$\triangleright \frac{364}{18257} = \frac{728}{36514}$	$\triangleright \frac{368}{42571} = \frac{736}{85142}$
$\triangleright \frac{358}{17426} = \frac{716}{34852}$	$\triangleright \frac{362}{14578} = \frac{543}{21867}$	$\triangleright \frac{364}{21578} = \frac{728}{43156}$	$\triangleright \frac{371}{25684} = \frac{742}{51368}$
$\triangleright \frac{358}{17624} = \frac{716}{35248}$	$\triangleright \frac{362}{15784} = \frac{724}{31568}$	$\triangleright \frac{364}{21758} = \frac{728}{43516}$	$\triangleright \frac{371}{26584} = \frac{742}{53168}$
$\triangleright \frac{358}{17642} = \frac{716}{35284}$	$\triangleright \frac{362}{17458} = \frac{543}{26187}$	$\triangleright \frac{364}{25718} = \frac{728}{51436}$	$\triangleright \frac{371}{42568} = \frac{742}{85136}$
$\triangleright \frac{358}{21764} = \frac{716}{43528}$	$\triangleright \frac{362}{17584} = \frac{724}{35168}$	$\triangleright \frac{364}{25817} = \frac{728}{51634}$	$\triangleright \frac{371}{42658} = \frac{742}{85316}$
$\triangleright \frac{358}{24176} = \frac{716}{48352}$	$\triangleright \frac{362}{17854} = \frac{543}{26781}$	$\triangleright \frac{364}{27158} = \frac{728}{54316}$	$\triangleright \frac{371}{46852} = \frac{532}{67184}$
$\triangleright \frac{358}{26174} = \frac{716}{52348}$	$\triangleright \frac{362}{18574} = \frac{543}{27861}$	$\triangleright \frac{364}{28157} = \frac{728}{56314}$	$\triangleright \frac{372}{15648} = \frac{651}{27384}$

$\triangleright \frac{372}{18456} = \frac{837}{41526}$	$\triangleright \frac{374}{58162} = \frac{561}{87243}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{54182} = \frac{564}{81273}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{56214} = \frac{567}{84321}$
$\triangleright \frac{372}{18564} = \frac{651}{32487}$	$\triangleright \frac{374}{58216} = \frac{561}{87324}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{54218} = \frac{564}{81327}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{56241} = \frac{546}{81237}$
$\triangleright \frac{372}{41856} = \frac{651}{73248}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{14258} = \frac{564}{21387}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{58142} = \frac{564}{87213}$	$\triangleright \frac{381}{25674} = \frac{762}{51348}$
$\triangleright \frac{372}{48156} = \frac{651}{84273}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{14582} = \frac{564}{21873}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{58214} = \frac{564}{87321}$	$\triangleright \frac{381}{26574} = \frac{762}{53148}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{12568} = \frac{748}{25136}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{15824} = \frac{752}{31648}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{14256} = \frac{567}{21384}$	$\triangleright \frac{381}{42567} = \frac{762}{85134}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{12658} = \frac{748}{25316}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{15842} = \frac{752}{31684}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{14562} = \frac{567}{21843}$	$\triangleright \frac{381}{42657} = \frac{762}{85314}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{15628} = \frac{748}{31256}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{18254} = \frac{564}{27381}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{15642} = \frac{756}{31284}$	$\triangleright \frac{381}{47625} = \frac{673}{84125}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{15826} = \frac{748}{31652}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{18524} = \frac{658}{32417}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{16542} = \frac{567}{24813}$	$\triangleright \frac{382}{14576} = \frac{573}{21864}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{16582} = \frac{561}{24873}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{18542} = \frac{564}{27813}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{21456} = \frac{567}{32184}$	$\triangleright \frac{382}{15764} = \frac{764}{31528}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{18562} = \frac{561}{27843}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{21458} = \frac{564}{32187}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{21564} = \frac{756}{43128}$	$\triangleright \frac{382}{16574} = \frac{573}{24861}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{21658} = \frac{561}{32487}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{21584} = \frac{752}{43168}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{24156} = \frac{756}{48312}$	$\triangleright \frac{382}{17456} = \frac{573}{26184}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{21856} = \frac{561}{32784}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{21854} = \frac{564}{32781}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{25416} = \frac{567}{38124}$	$\triangleright \frac{382}{17564} = \frac{764}{35128}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{25681} = \frac{748}{51362}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{24158} = \frac{752}{48316}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{25614} = \frac{567}{38421}$	$\triangleright \frac{382}{17654} = \frac{573}{26481}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{26158} = \frac{748}{52316}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{25184} = \frac{517}{34628}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{41256} = \frac{483}{52716}$	$\triangleright \frac{382}{41576} = \frac{764}{83152}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{26581} = \frac{748}{53162}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{25418} = \frac{564}{38127}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{41562} = \frac{756}{83124}$	$\triangleright \frac{382}{41756} = \frac{764}{83512}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{26851} = \frac{782}{56143}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{25814} = \frac{564}{38721}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{42156} = \frac{756}{84312}$	$\triangleright \frac{382}{54176} = \frac{573}{81264}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{28156} = \frac{748}{56312}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{41582} = \frac{752}{83164}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{51624} = \frac{427}{58316}$	$\triangleright \frac{382}{56174} = \frac{573}{84261}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{56182} = \frac{561}{84273}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{41852} = \frac{658}{73241}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{54162} = \frac{567}{81243}$	$\triangleright \frac{382}{57416} = \frac{573}{86124}$
$\triangleright \frac{374}{56218} = \frac{561}{84327}$	$\triangleright \frac{376}{42158} = \frac{752}{84316}$	$\triangleright \frac{378}{56142} = \frac{567}{84213}$	$\triangleright \frac{382}{57614} = \frac{573}{86421}$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{12567} = \frac{768}{25134}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{12576} = \frac{468}{15327}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{12657} = \frac{768}{25314}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{15627} = \frac{768}{31254}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{15726} = \frac{768}{31452}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{15762} = \frac{768}{31524}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{16257} = \frac{768}{32514}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{17256} = \frac{768}{34512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{17562} = \frac{768}{35124}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{21576} = \frac{768}{43152}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{21756} = \frac{768}{43512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{25176} = \frac{528}{34617}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{25617} = \frac{768}{51234}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{25671} = \frac{768}{51342}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{25716} = \frac{768}{51432}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{26571} = \frac{768}{53142}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{27156} = \frac{768}{54312}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{27516} = \frac{672}{48153}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{76152} = \frac{432}{85671}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{387}{16254} = \frac{567}{23814}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{387}{24156} = \frac{731}{45628}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{412}{35678} = \frac{824}{71356}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{412}{35768} = \frac{824}{71536}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{412}{36578} = \frac{824}{73156}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{412}{36758} = \frac{824}{73516}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{412}{37568} = \frac{824}{75136}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{412}{37658} = \frac{824}{75316}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{413}{25687} = \frac{826}{51374}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{413}{25867} = \frac{826}{51734}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{413}{26587} = \frac{826}{53174}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{413}{26857} = \frac{826}{53714}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{413}{28567} = \frac{826}{57134}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{413}{28657} = \frac{826}{57314}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{23578} = \frac{832}{47156}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{23758} = \frac{832}{47516}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{25738} = \frac{832}{51476}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{25837} = \frac{832}{51674}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{25873} = \frac{832}{51746}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{27358} = \frac{832}{54716}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{28357} = \frac{832}{56714}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{28573} = \frac{832}{57146}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{32587} = \frac{832}{65174}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{32857} = \frac{832}{65714}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{35728} = \frac{832}{71456}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{35782} = \frac{832}{71564}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{35827} = \frac{832}{71654}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{37258} = \frac{832}{74516}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{37582} = \frac{832}{75164}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{416}{38257} = \frac{832}{76514}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{417}{25638} = \frac{834}{51276}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{417}{25836} = \frac{834}{51672}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{417}{25863} = \frac{834}{51726}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{417}{26358} = \frac{834}{52716}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{417}{28563} = \frac{834}{57126}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{417}{32586} = \frac{834}{65172}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{417}{32856} = \frac{834}{65712}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{417}{35628} = \frac{834}{71256}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{417}{35826} = \frac{834}{71652}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{417}{35862} = \frac{537}{46182}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{417}{36258} = \frac{834}{72516}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{417}{38256} = \frac{834}{76512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{23576} = \frac{836}{47152}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{23756} = \frac{836}{47512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{25637} = \frac{836}{51274}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{25736} = \frac{836}{51472}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{26357} = \frac{836}{52714}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{27356} = \frac{836}{54712}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{32756} = \frac{528}{41376}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{35627} = \frac{836}{71254}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{35726} = \frac{836}{71452}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{35762} = \frac{836}{71524}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{36257} = \frac{836}{72514}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{37256} = \frac{836}{74512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{37562} = \frac{836}{75124}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{52763} = \frac{462}{58317}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{418}{73625} = \frac{462}{81375}$$

$\triangleright \frac{421}{35678} = \frac{842}{71356}$	$\triangleright \frac{426}{31857} = \frac{852}{63714}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{36581} = \frac{854}{73162}$	$\triangleright \frac{431}{28657} = \frac{862}{57314}$
$\triangleright \frac{421}{35768} = \frac{842}{71536}$	$\triangleright \frac{426}{35718} = \frac{852}{71436}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{38156} = \frac{854}{76312}$	$\triangleright \frac{432}{15678} = \frac{648}{23517}$
$\triangleright \frac{421}{36578} = \frac{842}{73156}$	$\triangleright \frac{426}{35817} = \frac{852}{71634}$	$\triangleright \frac{428}{13567} = \frac{856}{27134}$	$\triangleright \frac{432}{15768} = \frac{654}{23871}$
$\triangleright \frac{421}{36758} = \frac{842}{73516}$	$\triangleright \frac{426}{37158} = \frac{852}{74316}$	$\triangleright \frac{428}{13657} = \frac{856}{27314}$	$\triangleright \frac{432}{15786} = \frac{864}{31572}$
$\triangleright \frac{421}{37568} = \frac{842}{75136}$	$\triangleright \frac{426}{38157} = \frac{852}{76314}$	$\triangleright \frac{428}{15637} = \frac{856}{31274}$	$\triangleright \frac{432}{16758} = \frac{648}{25137}$
$\triangleright \frac{421}{37658} = \frac{842}{75316}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{13568} = \frac{854}{27136}$	$\triangleright \frac{428}{15736} = \frac{856}{31472}$	$\triangleright \frac{432}{17586} = \frac{864}{35172}$
$\triangleright \frac{423}{15786} = \frac{846}{31572}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{13658} = \frac{854}{27316}$	$\triangleright \frac{428}{16357} = \frac{856}{32714}$	$\triangleright \frac{432}{18756} = \frac{864}{37512}$
$\triangleright \frac{423}{15876} = \frac{846}{31752}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{15638} = \frac{854}{31276}$	$\triangleright \frac{428}{17356} = \frac{856}{34712}$	$\triangleright \frac{432}{58617} = \frac{528}{71643}$
$\triangleright \frac{423}{17586} = \frac{846}{35172}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{15836} = \frac{854}{31672}$	$\triangleright \frac{428}{35617} = \frac{856}{71234}$	$\triangleright \frac{435}{12876} = \frac{835}{24716}$
$\triangleright \frac{423}{17856} = \frac{846}{35712}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{15863} = \frac{854}{31726}$	$\triangleright \frac{428}{35671} = \frac{856}{71342}$	$\triangleright \frac{435}{26187} = \frac{685}{41237}$
$\triangleright \frac{423}{18576} = \frac{846}{37152}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{16358} = \frac{854}{32716}$	$\triangleright \frac{428}{35716} = \frac{856}{71432}$	$\triangleright \frac{436}{15728} = \frac{872}{31456}$
$\triangleright \frac{423}{18756} = \frac{846}{37512}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{18356} = \frac{854}{36712}$	$\triangleright \frac{428}{36157} = \frac{856}{72314}$	$\triangleright \frac{436}{15782} = \frac{872}{31564}$
$\triangleright \frac{426}{15738} = \frac{852}{31476}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{18563} = \frac{854}{37126}$	$\triangleright \frac{428}{36571} = \frac{856}{73142}$	$\triangleright \frac{436}{15827} = \frac{872}{31654}$
$\triangleright \frac{426}{15837} = \frac{852}{31674}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{31586} = \frac{854}{63172}$	$\triangleright \frac{428}{37156} = \frac{856}{74312}$	$\triangleright \frac{436}{17258} = \frac{872}{34516}$
$\triangleright \frac{426}{15873} = \frac{852}{31746}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{31856} = \frac{854}{63712}$	$\triangleright \frac{431}{25687} = \frac{862}{51374}$	$\triangleright \frac{436}{17582} = \frac{872}{35164}$
$\triangleright \frac{426}{17358} = \frac{852}{34716}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{35618} = \frac{854}{71236}$	$\triangleright \frac{431}{25867} = \frac{862}{51734}$	$\triangleright \frac{436}{18257} = \frac{872}{36514}$
$\triangleright \frac{426}{18357} = \frac{852}{36714}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{35681} = \frac{854}{71362}$	$\triangleright \frac{431}{26587} = \frac{862}{53174}$	$\triangleright \frac{436}{21578} = \frac{872}{43156}$
$\triangleright \frac{426}{18573} = \frac{852}{37146}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{35816} = \frac{854}{71632}$	$\triangleright \frac{431}{26857} = \frac{862}{53714}$	$\triangleright \frac{436}{21758} = \frac{872}{43516}$
$\triangleright \frac{426}{31587} = \frac{852}{63174}$	$\triangleright \frac{427}{36158} = \frac{854}{72316}$	$\triangleright \frac{431}{28567} = \frac{862}{57134}$	$\triangleright \frac{436}{25718} = \frac{872}{51436}$

$\triangleright \frac{436}{25817} = \frac{872}{51634}$	$\triangleright \frac{438}{15762} = \frac{876}{31524}$	$\triangleright \frac{512}{36784} = \frac{576}{41382}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{17834} = \frac{843}{26751}$
$\triangleright \frac{436}{27158} = \frac{872}{54316}$	$\triangleright \frac{438}{16257} = \frac{876}{32514}$	$\triangleright \frac{513}{28647} = \frac{817}{45623}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{18374} = \frac{843}{27561}$
$\triangleright \frac{436}{28157} = \frac{872}{56314}$	$\triangleright \frac{438}{17256} = \frac{876}{34512}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{16378} = \frac{813}{24567}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{34178} = \frac{843}{51267}$
$\triangleright \frac{437}{12568} = \frac{874}{25136}$	$\triangleright \frac{438}{17562} = \frac{876}{35124}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{17638} = \frac{813}{26457}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{37418} = \frac{843}{56127}$
$\triangleright \frac{437}{12658} = \frac{874}{25316}$	$\triangleright \frac{438}{21576} = \frac{876}{43152}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{17836} = \frac{813}{26754}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{37814} = \frac{843}{56721}$
$\triangleright \frac{437}{15628} = \frac{874}{31256}$	$\triangleright \frac{438}{21756} = \frac{876}{43512}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{18376} = \frac{813}{27564}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{38174} = \frac{843}{57261}$
$\triangleright \frac{437}{15826} = \frac{874}{31652}$	$\triangleright \frac{438}{25617} = \frac{876}{51234}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{31768} = \frac{813}{47652}$	$\triangleright \frac{564}{13827} = \frac{752}{18436}$
$\triangleright \frac{437}{16258} = \frac{874}{32516}$	$\triangleright \frac{438}{25671} = \frac{876}{51342}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{36178} = \frac{813}{54267}$	$\triangleright \frac{564}{27138} = \frac{752}{36184}$
$\triangleright \frac{437}{18256} = \frac{874}{36512}$	$\triangleright \frac{438}{25716} = \frac{876}{51432}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{37618} = \frac{813}{56427}$	$\triangleright \frac{567}{13824} = \frac{756}{18432}$
$\triangleright \frac{437}{25618} = \frac{874}{51236}$	$\triangleright \frac{438}{26157} = \frac{876}{52314}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{37816} = \frac{813}{56724}$	$\triangleright \frac{567}{24138} = \frac{756}{32184}$
$\triangleright \frac{437}{25681} = \frac{874}{51362}$	$\triangleright \frac{438}{26571} = \frac{876}{53142}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{38176} = \frac{813}{57264}$	$\triangleright \frac{568}{23174} = \frac{852}{34761}$
$\triangleright \frac{437}{25816} = \frac{874}{51632}$	$\triangleright \frac{456}{32718} = \frac{576}{41328}$	$\triangleright \frac{543}{28617} = \frac{724}{38156}$	$\triangleright \frac{568}{31742} = \frac{852}{47613}$
$\triangleright \frac{437}{26158} = \frac{874}{52316}$	$\triangleright \frac{462}{53781} = \frac{726}{84513}$	$\triangleright \frac{546}{12873} = \frac{572}{13486}$	$\triangleright \frac{572}{14638} = \frac{682}{17453}$
$\triangleright \frac{437}{26581} = \frac{874}{53162}$	$\triangleright \frac{468}{13572} = \frac{867}{25143}$	$\triangleright \frac{546}{18732} = \frac{637}{21854}$	$\triangleright \frac{572}{48136} = \frac{741}{62358}$
$\triangleright \frac{437}{28156} = \frac{874}{56312}$	$\triangleright \frac{468}{32175} = \frac{628}{43175}$	$\triangleright \frac{546}{73218} = \frac{637}{85421}$	$\triangleright \frac{573}{28614} = \frac{764}{38152}$
$\triangleright \frac{438}{12567} = \frac{876}{25134}$	$\triangleright \frac{473}{21586} = \frac{781}{35642}$	$\triangleright \frac{561}{24378} = \frac{726}{31548}$	$\triangleright \frac{574}{16238} = \frac{861}{24357}$
$\triangleright \frac{438}{12657} = \frac{876}{25314}$	$\triangleright \frac{476}{32851} = \frac{748}{51623}$	$\triangleright \frac{561}{28743} = \frac{714}{36582}$	$\triangleright \frac{574}{16382} = \frac{861}{24573}$
$\triangleright \frac{438}{15627} = \frac{876}{31254}$	$\triangleright \frac{483}{16527} = \frac{736}{25184}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{14378} = \frac{843}{21567}$	$\triangleright \frac{574}{18236} = \frac{861}{27354}$
$\triangleright \frac{438}{15726} = \frac{876}{31452}$	$\triangleright \frac{486}{52731} = \frac{582}{63147}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{17438} = \frac{843}{26157}$	$\triangleright \frac{574}{18362} = \frac{861}{27543}$

$\triangleright \frac{574}{21638} = \frac{861}{32457}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{23814} = \frac{864}{35721}$	$\triangleright \frac{582}{14376} = \frac{873}{21564}$	$\triangleright \frac{654}{73218} = \frac{763}{85421}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{21836} = \frac{861}{32754}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{34182} = \frac{864}{51273}$	$\triangleright \frac{582}{16374} = \frac{873}{24561}$	$\triangleright \frac{658}{13724} = \frac{784}{16352}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{23168} = \frac{861}{34752}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{34218} = \frac{864}{51327}$	$\triangleright \frac{582}{17436} = \frac{873}{26154}$	$\triangleright \frac{672}{13584} = \frac{854}{17263}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{23618} = \frac{861}{35427}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{38142} = \frac{864}{57213}$	$\triangleright \frac{582}{17634} = \frac{873}{26451}$	$\triangleright \frac{672}{31584} = \frac{762}{35814}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{23816} = \frac{861}{35724}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{38214} = \frac{864}{57321}$	$\triangleright \frac{582}{34176} = \frac{873}{51264}$	$\triangleright \frac{731}{46852} = \frac{817}{52364}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{36182} = \frac{861}{54273}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{14236} = \frac{867}{21354}$	$\triangleright \frac{582}{36174} = \frac{873}{54261}$	$\triangleright \frac{732}{18546} = \frac{854}{21637}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{36218} = \frac{861}{54327}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{14362} = \frac{867}{21543}$	$\triangleright \frac{582}{37416} = \frac{873}{56124}$	$\triangleright \frac{732}{18654} = \frac{854}{21763}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{38162} = \frac{861}{57243}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{16234} = \frac{867}{24351}$	$\triangleright \frac{582}{37614} = \frac{873}{56421}$	$\triangleright \frac{732}{54186} = \frac{854}{63217}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{38216} = \frac{861}{57324}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{16342} = \frac{867}{24513}$	$\triangleright \frac{584}{12736} = \frac{657}{14328}$	$\triangleright \frac{732}{54618} = \frac{854}{63721}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{12384} = \frac{736}{15824}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{21436} = \frac{867}{32154}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{53874} = \frac{714}{62853}$	$\triangleright \frac{732}{61854} = \frac{854}{72163}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{13248} = \frac{684}{15732}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{21634} = \frac{867}{32451}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{57384} = \frac{731}{68542}$	$\triangleright \frac{732}{65418} = \frac{854}{76321}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{14238} = \frac{864}{21357}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{23416} = \frac{867}{35124}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{58734} = \frac{714}{68523}$	$\triangleright \frac{736}{14528} = \frac{782}{15436}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{14382} = \frac{864}{21573}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{23614} = \frac{867}{35421}$	$\triangleright \frac{618}{54732} = \frac{721}{63854}$	$\triangleright \frac{736}{21584} = \frac{874}{25631}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{18234} = \frac{864}{27351}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{24361} = \frac{748}{31526}$	$\triangleright \frac{618}{73254} = \frac{721}{85463}$	$\triangleright \frac{742}{13568} = \frac{756}{13824}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{18342} = \frac{864}{27513}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{32164} = \frac{782}{43516}$	$\triangleright \frac{624}{38571} = \frac{672}{41538}$	
$\triangleright \frac{576}{21438} = \frac{864}{32157}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{34162} = \frac{867}{51243}$	$\triangleright \frac{624}{53781} = \frac{752}{64813}$	$\triangleright \frac{12}{356784} = \frac{24}{713568}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{21834} = \frac{864}{32751}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{34216} = \frac{867}{51324}$	$\triangleright \frac{632}{17854} = \frac{764}{21583}$	$\triangleright \frac{12}{356874} = \frac{16}{475832}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{23184} = \frac{684}{27531}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{36142} = \frac{867}{54213}$	$\triangleright \frac{638}{54172} = \frac{748}{63512}$	$\triangleright \frac{12}{357468} = \frac{23}{685147}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{23418} = \frac{864}{35127}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{36214} = \frac{867}{54321}$	$\triangleright \frac{654}{18732} = \frac{763}{21854}$	$\triangleright \frac{12}{357648} = \frac{18}{536472}$

$\triangleright \frac{12}{357684} = \frac{24}{715368}$	$\triangleright \frac{12}{658734} = \frac{14}{768523}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{236758} = \frac{28}{473516}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{267358} = \frac{28}{534716}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{358764} = \frac{16}{478352}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{245687} = \frac{43}{812657}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{237568} = \frac{28}{475136}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{268357} = \frac{28}{536714}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{365784} = \frac{24}{731568}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{246857} = \frac{43}{816527}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{238576} = \frac{21}{357864}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{268573} = \frac{28}{537146}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{367584} = \frac{24}{735168}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{256874} = \frac{26}{513748}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{238756} = \frac{31}{528674}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{273568} = \frac{28}{547136}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{375684} = \frac{24}{751368}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{264875} = \frac{43}{876125}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{253786} = \frac{42}{761358}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{273658} = \frac{28}{547316}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{376584} = \frac{24}{753168}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{265874} = \frac{26}{531748}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{256378} = \frac{21}{384567}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{283567} = \frac{28}{567134}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{385476} = \frac{21}{674583}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{268574} = \frac{26}{537148}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{256738} = \frac{28}{513476}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{283657} = \frac{28}{567314}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{435678} = \frac{24}{871356}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{274586} = \frac{31}{654782}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{256837} = \frac{28}{513674}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{283675} = \frac{18}{364725}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{435768} = \frac{24}{871536}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{285674} = \frac{26}{571348}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{256873} = \frac{28}{513746}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{285673} = \frac{28}{571346}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{436578} = \frac{24}{873156}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{286574} = \frac{26}{573148}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{257368} = \frac{28}{514736}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{286573} = \frac{28}{573146}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{436758} = \frac{24}{873516}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{287456} = \frac{31}{685472}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{257638} = \frac{21}{386457}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{325687} = \frac{28}{651374}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{437568} = \frac{24}{875136}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{425687} = \frac{26}{851374}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{257836} = \frac{21}{386754}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{325867} = \frac{28}{651734}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{437658} = \frac{24}{875316}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{425867} = \frac{26}{851734}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{258367} = \frac{28}{516734}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{326587} = \frac{28}{653174}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{483576} = \frac{18}{725364}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{426587} = \frac{26}{853174}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{258376} = \frac{21}{387564}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{326857} = \frac{28}{653714}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{538746} = \frac{14}{628537}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{426857} = \frac{26}{853714}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{258673} = \frac{28}{517346}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{328567} = \frac{28}{657134}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{568743} = \frac{16}{758324}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{428567} = \frac{26}{857134}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{263578} = \frac{38}{715426}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{328657} = \frac{28}{657314}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{587346} = \frac{14}{685237}$	$\triangleright \frac{13}{428657} = \frac{26}{857314}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{265738} = \frac{28}{531476}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{356728} = \frac{28}{713456}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{587643} = \frac{16}{783524}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{235678} = \frac{28}{471356}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{265837} = \frac{28}{531674}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{356782} = \frac{28}{713564}$
$\triangleright \frac{12}{653874} = \frac{14}{762853}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{235768} = \frac{28}{471536}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{265873} = \frac{28}{531746}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{356827} = \frac{28}{713654}$

$\triangleright \frac{14}{357268} = \frac{28}{714536}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{385762} = \frac{21}{578643}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{237584} = \frac{32}{475168}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{325874} = \frac{32}{651748}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{357682} = \frac{28}{715364}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{537628} = \frac{17}{652834}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{238574} = \frac{24}{357861}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{328574} = \frac{32}{657148}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{358267} = \frac{28}{716534}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{562378} = \frac{21}{843567}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{238745} = \frac{48}{716235}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{342578} = \frac{24}{513867}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{362578} = \frac{21}{543867}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{563782} = \frac{21}{845673}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{243578} = \frac{32}{487156}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{342587} = \frac{32}{685174}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{365728} = \frac{28}{731456}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{576238} = \frac{21}{864357}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{243758} = \frac{32}{487516}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{342857} = \frac{32}{685714}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{365827} = \frac{28}{731654}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{576382} = \frac{21}{864573}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{243875} = \frac{48}{731625}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{345782} = \frac{24}{518673}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{367258} = \frac{28}{734516}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{578236} = \frac{21}{867354}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{253784} = \frac{48}{761352}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{357284} = \frac{32}{714568}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{367528} = \frac{18}{472536}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{578326} = \frac{18}{743562}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{254378} = \frac{24}{381567}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{357428} = \frac{32}{714856}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{367582} = \frac{28}{735164}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{578362} = \frac{21}{867543}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{257384} = \frac{32}{514768}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{357824} = \frac{32}{715648}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{368257} = \frac{28}{736514}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{582376} = \frac{21}{873564}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{257834} = \frac{24}{386751}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{357842} = \frac{32}{715684}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{372568} = \frac{28}{745136}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{583762} = \frac{21}{875643}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{258437} = \frac{32}{516874}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{358274} = \frac{32}{716548}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{372658} = \frac{28}{745316}$	$\triangleright \frac{14}{687253} = \frac{16}{785432}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{258734} = \frac{32}{517468}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{358427} = \frac{32}{716854}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{375682} = \frac{28}{751364}$	$\triangleright \frac{15}{238746} = \frac{45}{716238}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{258743} = \frac{32}{517486}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{372584} = \frac{32}{745168}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{376258} = \frac{21}{564387}$	$\triangleright \frac{15}{243876} = \frac{45}{731628}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{273584} = \frac{32}{547168}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{374528} = \frac{31}{725648}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{378256} = \frac{21}{567384}$	$\triangleright \frac{15}{263478} = \frac{35}{614782}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{274358} = \frac{32}{548716}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{374582} = \frac{24}{561873}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{378562} = \frac{21}{567843}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{234578} = \frac{24}{351867}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{283574} = \frac{32}{567148}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{375824} = \frac{32}{751648}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{382567} = \frac{28}{765134}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{235478} = \frac{56}{824173}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{284357} = \frac{32}{568714}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{375842} = \frac{32}{751684}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{382576} = \frac{21}{573864}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{235784} = \frac{32}{471568}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{285734} = \frac{32}{571468}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{378254} = \frac{24}{567381}$
$\triangleright \frac{14}{382657} = \frac{28}{765314}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{237458} = \frac{24}{356187}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{285743} = \frac{32}{571486}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{378542} = \frac{24}{567813}$

$\triangleright \frac{16}{384257} = \frac{32}{768514}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{457328} = \frac{26}{743158}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{285634} = \frac{34}{571268}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{428563} = \frac{34}{857126}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{385472} = \frac{31}{746852}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{542378} = \frac{24}{813567}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{285643} = \frac{34}{571286}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{432586} = \frac{34}{865172}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{385742} = \frac{24}{578613}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{543782} = \frac{24}{815673}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{325864} = \frac{34}{651728}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{432856} = \frac{34}{865712}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{423578} = \frac{32}{847156}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{574238} = \frac{24}{861357}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{328564} = \frac{34}{657128}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{435268} = \frac{21}{537684}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{423758} = \frac{32}{847516}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{574382} = \frac{24}{861573}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{342586} = \frac{34}{685172}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{435628} = \frac{34}{871256}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{425738} = \frac{32}{851476}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{578234} = \frac{24}{867351}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{342856} = \frac{34}{685712}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{435826} = \frac{34}{871652}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{425837} = \frac{32}{851674}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{578342} = \frac{24}{867513}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{356284} = \frac{34}{712568}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{436258} = \frac{34}{872516}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{425873} = \frac{32}{851746}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{582374} = \frac{24}{873561}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{356428} = \frac{34}{712856}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{438256} = \frac{34}{876512}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{427358} = \frac{32}{854716}$	$\triangleright \frac{16}{583742} = \frac{24}{875613}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{358264} = \frac{34}{716528}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{456382} = \frac{23}{617458}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{428357} = \frac{32}{856714}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{256384} = \frac{34}{512768}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{358426} = \frac{34}{716852}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{684352} = \frac{21}{845376}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{428573} = \frac{32}{857146}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{256438} = \frac{34}{512876}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{362584} = \frac{34}{725168}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{234576} = \frac{27}{351864}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{432587} = \frac{32}{865174}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{258364} = \frac{34}{516728}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{364258} = \frac{34}{728516}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{236574} = \frac{27}{354861}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{432857} = \frac{32}{865714}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{258436} = \frac{34}{516872}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{382564} = \frac{34}{765128}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{237546} = \frac{54}{712638}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{435728} = \frac{32}{871456}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{258634} = \frac{34}{517268}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{384256} = \frac{34}{768512}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{237564} = \frac{36}{475128}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{435782} = \frac{32}{871564}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{258643} = \frac{34}{517286}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{425638} = \frac{34}{851276}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{237654} = \frac{27}{356481}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{435827} = \frac{32}{871654}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{263584} = \frac{34}{527168}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{425836} = \frac{34}{851672}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{243576} = \frac{36}{487152}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{437258} = \frac{32}{874516}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{264358} = \frac{34}{528716}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{425863} = \frac{34}{851726}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{245376} = \frac{54}{736128}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{437582} = \frac{32}{875164}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{283564} = \frac{34}{567128}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{426358} = \frac{34}{852716}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{253746} = \frac{54}{761238}$
$\triangleright \frac{16}{438257} = \frac{32}{876514}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{284356} = \frac{34}{568712}$	$\triangleright \frac{17}{428356} = \frac{34}{856712}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{256437} = \frac{36}{512874}$

$\triangleright \frac{18}{257364} = \frac{36}{514728}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{375624} = \frac{36}{751248}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{547326} = \frac{21}{638547}$	$\triangleright \frac{21}{436578} = \frac{42}{873156}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{257634} = \frac{27}{386451}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{375642} = \frac{36}{751284}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{562374} = \frac{27}{843561}$	$\triangleright \frac{21}{436758} = \frac{42}{873516}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{263574} = \frac{36}{527148}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{376254} = \frac{27}{564381}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{563742} = \frac{27}{845613}$	$\triangleright \frac{21}{437568} = \frac{42}{875136}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{264357} = \frac{36}{528714}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{376542} = \frac{27}{564813}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{574236} = \frac{27}{861354}$	$\triangleright \frac{21}{437658} = \frac{42}{875316}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{273564} = \frac{36}{547128}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{423576} = \frac{36}{847152}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{574362} = \frac{27}{861543}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{157864} = \frac{46}{315728}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{274356} = \frac{36}{548712}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{423756} = \frac{36}{847512}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{576234} = \frac{27}{864351}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{158746} = \frac{27}{186354}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{342576} = \frac{27}{513864}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{425637} = \frac{36}{851274}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{576342} = \frac{27}{864513}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{158764} = \frac{46}{317528}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{345762} = \frac{27}{518643}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{425736} = \frac{36}{851472}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{654732} = \frac{21}{763854}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{175864} = \frac{46}{351728}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{356274} = \frac{36}{712548}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{426357} = \frac{36}{852714}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{673254} = \frac{21}{785463}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{178564} = \frac{46}{357128}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{356427} = \frac{36}{712854}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{427356} = \frac{36}{854712}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{732546} = \frac{21}{854637}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{185764} = \frac{46}{371528}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{357264} = \frac{36}{714528}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{435627} = \frac{36}{871254}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{732654} = \frac{21}{854763}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{187564} = \frac{46}{375128}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{357426} = \frac{36}{714852}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{435726} = \frac{36}{871452}$	$\triangleright \frac{21}{346857} = \frac{51}{842367}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{415786} = \frac{46}{831572}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{357624} = \frac{36}{715248}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{435762} = \frac{36}{871524}$	$\triangleright \frac{21}{357684} = \frac{42}{715368}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{415876} = \frac{46}{831752}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{357642} = \frac{36}{715284}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{436257} = \frac{36}{872514}$	$\triangleright \frac{21}{365784} = \frac{42}{731568}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{417586} = \frac{46}{835172}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{364257} = \frac{36}{728514}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{437256} = \frac{36}{874512}$	$\triangleright \frac{21}{367584} = \frac{42}{735168}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{417856} = \frac{46}{835712}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{365742} = \frac{27}{548613}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{437562} = \frac{36}{875124}$	$\triangleright \frac{21}{375684} = \frac{42}{751368}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{418576} = \frac{46}{837152}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{372564} = \frac{36}{745128}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{542376} = \frac{27}{813564}$	$\triangleright \frac{21}{376584} = \frac{42}{753168}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{418756} = \frac{46}{837512}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{374526} = \frac{23}{478561}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{543762} = \frac{27}{815643}$	$\triangleright \frac{21}{435678} = \frac{42}{871356}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{461587} = \frac{27}{541863}$
$\triangleright \frac{18}{374562} = \frac{27}{561843}$	$\triangleright \frac{18}{546732} = \frac{21}{637854}$	$\triangleright \frac{21}{435768} = \frac{42}{871536}$	$\triangleright \frac{23}{514786} = \frac{24}{537168}$

- ▶ $\frac{24}{135678} = \frac{48}{271356}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{135768} = \frac{48}{271536}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{136578} = \frac{48}{273156}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{136758} = \frac{48}{273516}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{137568} = \frac{48}{275136}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{137658} = \frac{48}{275316}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{137856} = \frac{72}{413568}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{138567} = \frac{32}{184756}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{153786} = \frac{72}{461358}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{156378} = \frac{48}{312756}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{157638} = \frac{48}{315276}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{157836} = \frac{48}{315672}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{157863} = \frac{48}{315726}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{158376} = \frac{48}{316752}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{158763} = \frac{48}{317526}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{163578} = \frac{48}{327156}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{163758} = \frac{48}{327516}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{175638} = \frac{48}{351276}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{175836} = \frac{48}{351672}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{175863} = \frac{48}{351726}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{178356} = \frac{48}{356712}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{178563} = \frac{48}{357126}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{183756} = \frac{48}{367512}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{185763} = \frac{48}{371526}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{187563} = \frac{48}{375126}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{315768} = \frac{62}{815734}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{315786} = \frac{48}{631572}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{315876} = \frac{48}{631752}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{317568} = \frac{51}{674832}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{317586} = \frac{48}{635172}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{317856} = \frac{48}{635712}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{318576} = \frac{48}{637152}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{318756} = \frac{48}{637512}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{356178} = \frac{48}{712356}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{357618} = \frac{48}{715236}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{357681} = \frac{48}{715362}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{357816} = \frac{48}{715632}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{358176} = \frac{48}{716352}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{358617} = \frac{32}{478156}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{361578} = \frac{48}{723156}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{361758} = \frac{48}{723516}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{365781} = \frac{48}{731562}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{367581} = \frac{48}{735162}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{375618} = \frac{48}{751236}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{375681} = \frac{48}{751362}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{375816} = \frac{48}{751632}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{376158} = \frac{48}{752316}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{376581} = \frac{48}{753162}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{378156} = \frac{48}{756312}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{381576} = \frac{48}{763152}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{381756} = \frac{48}{763512}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{567138} = \frac{32}{756184}$
- ▶ $\frac{24}{586173} = \frac{32}{781564}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{138746} = \frac{75}{416238}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{143876} = \frac{75}{431628}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{137854} = \frac{78}{413562}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{138745} = \frac{78}{416235}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{143875} = \frac{78}{431625}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{145873} = \frac{62}{347851}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{153784} = \frac{78}{461352}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{157384} = \frac{52}{314768}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{157438} = \frac{52}{314876}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{158374} = \frac{52}{316748}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{158437} = \frac{52}{316874}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{158734} = \frac{52}{317468}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{173584} = \frac{52}{347168}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{174358} = \frac{52}{348716}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{174358} = \frac{52}{348716}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{175438} = \frac{78}{526314}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{183574} = \frac{52}{367148}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{184357} = \frac{52}{368714}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{185734} = \frac{52}{371468}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{185743} = \frac{52}{371486}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{315874} = \frac{52}{631748}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{318574} = \frac{52}{637148}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{341587} = \frac{52}{683174}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{341857} = \frac{52}{683714}$

$\triangleright \frac{26}{354718} = \frac{64}{873152}$	$\triangleright \frac{26}{437158} = \frac{52}{874316}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{185643} = \frac{54}{371286}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{413658} = \frac{54}{827316}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{357184} = \frac{52}{714368}$	$\triangleright \frac{26}{438157} = \frac{52}{876314}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{315864} = \frac{54}{631728}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{415638} = \frac{54}{831276}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{357418} = \frac{52}{714836}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{135684} = \frac{54}{271368}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{318546} = \frac{73}{861254}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{415836} = \frac{54}{831672}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{358174} = \frac{52}{716348}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{136584} = \frac{54}{273168}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{318564} = \frac{54}{637128}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{415863} = \frac{54}{831726}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{358417} = \frac{52}{716834}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{138564} = \frac{36}{184752}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{341586} = \frac{54}{683172}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{416358} = \frac{54}{832716}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{371584} = \frac{52}{743168}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{143568} = \frac{54}{287136}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{341856} = \frac{54}{683712}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{418356} = \frac{54}{836712}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{374158} = \frac{52}{748316}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{143658} = \frac{54}{287316}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{356418} = \frac{54}{712836}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{418563} = \frac{54}{837126}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{381574} = \frac{52}{763148}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{156384} = \frac{54}{312768}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{356814} = \frac{54}{713628}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{431586} = \frac{54}{863172}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{384157} = \frac{52}{768314}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{156438} = \frac{54}{312876}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{356841} = \frac{54}{713682}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{431856} = \frac{54}{863712}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{415738} = \frac{52}{831476}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{158364} = \frac{54}{316728}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{358164} = \frac{54}{716328}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{435618} = \frac{54}{871236}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{415837} = \frac{52}{831674}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{158436} = \frac{54}{316872}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{358416} = \frac{54}{716832}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{435681} = \frac{54}{871362}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{415873} = \frac{52}{831746}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{158634} = \frac{54}{317268}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{358614} = \frac{36}{478152}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{435816} = \frac{54}{871632}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{417358} = \frac{52}{834716}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{158643} = \frac{54}{317286}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{361584} = \frac{54}{723168}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{436158} = \frac{54}{872316}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{418357} = \frac{52}{836714}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{163584} = \frac{54}{327168}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{364158} = \frac{54}{728316}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{436581} = \frac{54}{873162}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{418573} = \frac{52}{837146}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{164358} = \frac{54}{328716}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{365814} = \frac{54}{731628}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{438156} = \frac{54}{876312}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{431587} = \frac{52}{863174}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{183564} = \frac{54}{367128}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{365841} = \frac{54}{731682}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{564138} = \frac{36}{752184}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{431857} = \frac{52}{863714}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{184356} = \frac{54}{368712}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{384156} = \frac{54}{768312}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{586143} = \frac{36}{781524}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{435718} = \frac{52}{871436}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{184653} = \frac{67}{458213}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{385614} = \frac{38}{542716}$	$\triangleright \frac{28}{135674} = \frac{56}{271348}$
$\triangleright \frac{26}{435817} = \frac{52}{871634}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{185634} = \frac{54}{371268}$	$\triangleright \frac{27}{413568} = \frac{54}{827136}$	$\triangleright \frac{28}{136574} = \frac{56}{273148}$

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|---|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{28}{143567} = \frac{56}{287134}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{361574} = \frac{56}{723148}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{537614} = \frac{34}{652817}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{185764} = \frac{64}{371528}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{143657} = \frac{56}{287314}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{364157} = \frac{56}{728314}$ | ▶ $\frac{31}{256874} = \frac{62}{513748}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{187564} = \frac{64}{375128}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{143675} = \frac{36}{184725}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{365714} = \frac{56}{731428}$ | ▶ $\frac{31}{258674} = \frac{62}{517348}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{415678} = \frac{48}{623517}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{145376} = \frac{34}{176528}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{365741} = \frac{56}{731482}$ | ▶ $\frac{31}{265874} = \frac{62}{531748}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{415786} = \frac{64}{831572}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{156374} = \frac{56}{312748}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{367514} = \frac{36}{472518}$ | ▶ $\frac{31}{268574} = \frac{62}{537148}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{415876} = \frac{64}{831752}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{156437} = \frac{56}{312874}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{371564} = \frac{56}{743128}$ | ▶ $\frac{31}{285674} = \frac{62}{571348}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{416758} = \frac{48}{625137}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{157364} = \frac{56}{314728}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{374156} = \frac{56}{748312}$ | ▶ $\frac{31}{286574} = \frac{62}{573148}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{417586} = \frac{64}{835172}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{157436} = \frac{56}{314872}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{413567} = \frac{56}{827134}$ | ▶ $\frac{31}{425687} = \frac{62}{851374}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{418576} = \frac{64}{837152}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{163574} = \frac{56}{327148}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{413657} = \frac{56}{827314}$ | ▶ $\frac{31}{425867} = \frac{62}{851734}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{418756} = \frac{64}{837512}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{164357} = \frac{56}{328714}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{415637} = \frac{56}{831274}$ | ▶ $\frac{31}{426587} = \frac{62}{853174}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{567184} = \frac{46}{815327}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{173564} = \frac{56}{347128}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{415736} = \frac{56}{831472}$ | ▶ $\frac{31}{426857} = \frac{62}{853714}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{571648} = \frac{43}{768152}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{174356} = \frac{56}{348712}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{416357} = \frac{56}{832714}$ | ▶ $\frac{31}{428567} = \frac{62}{857134}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{125687} = \frac{68}{251374}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{175364} = \frac{41}{256783}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{417356} = \frac{56}{834712}$ | ▶ $\frac{31}{428657} = \frac{62}{857314}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{125867} = \frac{68}{251734}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{356174} = \frac{56}{712348}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{435617} = \frac{56}{871234}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{157864} = \frac{64}{315728}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{126587} = \frac{68}{253174}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{356417} = \frac{56}{712834}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{435671} = \frac{56}{871342}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{158764} = \frac{64}{317528}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{126857} = \frac{68}{253714}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{356714} = \frac{56}{713428}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{435716} = \frac{56}{871432}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{167584} = \frac{48}{251376}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{128567} = \frac{68}{257134}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{356741} = \frac{56}{713482}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{436157} = \frac{56}{872314}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{174856} = \frac{76}{415283}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{128657} = \frac{68}{257314}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{357164} = \frac{56}{714328}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{436571} = \frac{56}{873142}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{175864} = \frac{64}{351728}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{156287} = \frac{68}{312574}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28}{357416} = \frac{56}{714832}$ | ▶ $\frac{28}{437156} = \frac{56}{874312}$ | ▶ $\frac{32}{176584} = \frac{68}{375241}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{157286} = \frac{68}{314572}$ |

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|---|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{34}{158627} = \frac{68}{317254}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{215786} = \frac{68}{431572}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{268571} = \frac{68}{537142}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{264817} = \frac{85}{643127}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{158726} = \frac{68}{317452}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{215876} = \frac{68}{431752}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{271586} = \frac{68}{543172}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{142578} = \frac{54}{213867}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{158762} = \frac{68}{317524}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{216578} = \frac{51}{324867}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{271856} = \frac{68}{543712}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{145782} = \frac{54}{218673}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{162578} = \frac{51}{243867}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{217586} = \frac{68}{435172}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{285617} = \frac{68}{571234}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{147528} = \frac{63}{258174}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{162587} = \frac{68}{325174}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{217658} = \frac{51}{326487}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{285671} = \frac{68}{571342}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{147852} = \frac{63}{258741}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{162857} = \frac{68}{325714}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{218756} = \frac{68}{437512}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{285716} = \frac{68}{571432}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{157248} = \frac{63}{275184}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{165782} = \frac{51}{248673}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{256178} = \frac{51}{384267}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{286157} = \frac{68}{572314}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{157284} = \frac{72}{314568}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{172586} = \frac{68}{345172}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{256187} = \frac{68}{512374}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{286571} = \frac{68}{573142}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{157428} = \frac{72}{314856}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{172856} = \frac{68}{345712}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{256871} = \frac{68}{513742}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{287156} = \frac{68}{574312}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{157824} = \frac{72}{315648}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{175862} = \frac{68}{351724}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{257186} = \frac{68}{514372}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{561782} = \frac{51}{842673}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{157842} = \frac{72}{315684}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{176258} = \frac{51}{264387}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{257618} = \frac{51}{386427}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{562178} = \frac{51}{843267}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{158274} = \frac{72}{316548}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{176582} = \frac{51}{264873}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{257816} = \frac{51}{386724}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{576182} = \frac{51}{864273}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{158427} = \frac{72}{316854}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{178256} = \frac{51}{267384}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{258176} = \frac{51}{387264}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{576218} = \frac{51}{864327}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{158724} = \frac{38}{167542}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{182576} = \frac{51}{273864}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{258617} = \frac{68}{517234}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{578162} = \frac{51}{867243}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{172584} = \frac{72}{345168}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{185627} = \frac{68}{371254}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{258671} = \frac{68}{517342}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{578216} = \frac{51}{867324}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{174582} = \frac{54}{261873}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{185726} = \frac{68}{371452}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{258716} = \frac{68}{517432}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{581672} = \frac{42}{718536}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{175824} = \frac{72}{351648}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{186257} = \frac{68}{372514}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{261587} = \frac{68}{523174}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{581762} = \frac{51}{872643}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{175842} = \frac{72}{351684}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{187256} = \frac{68}{374512}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{261857} = \frac{68}{523714}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{582176} = \frac{51}{873264}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{178254} = \frac{54}{267381}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{187562} = \frac{68}{375124}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{265871} = \frac{68}{531742}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{681275} = \frac{38}{761425}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{178542} = \frac{54}{267813}$ |

$\triangleright \frac{36}{184257} = \frac{72}{368514}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{284517} = \frac{68}{537421}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{574218} = \frac{54}{861327}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{256814} = \frac{74}{513628}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{185742} = \frac{54}{278613}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{287514} = \frac{58}{463217}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{578142} = \frac{54}{867213}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{256841} = \frac{74}{513682}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{214578} = \frac{54}{321867}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{412578} = \frac{46}{527183}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{578214} = \frac{54}{867321}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{258164} = \frac{74}{516328}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{215784} = \frac{72}{431568}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{415728} = \frac{72}{831456}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{581742} = \frac{54}{872613}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{258416} = \frac{74}{516832}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{217458} = \frac{54}{326187}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{415782} = \frac{72}{831564}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{582174} = \frac{54}{873261}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{261584} = \frac{74}{523168}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{217584} = \frac{72}{435168}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{415827} = \frac{72}{831654}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{125684} = \frac{74}{251368}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{264158} = \frac{74}{528316}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{218574} = \frac{54}{327861}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{417258} = \frac{72}{834516}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{126584} = \frac{74}{253168}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{265814} = \frac{74}{531628}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{241578} = \frac{72}{483156}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{417582} = \frac{72}{835164}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{142568} = \frac{74}{285136}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{265841} = \frac{74}{531682}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{241758} = \frac{72}{483516}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{418257} = \frac{72}{836514}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{142658} = \frac{74}{285316}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{281564} = \frac{74}{563128}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{254178} = \frac{54}{381267}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{421578} = \frac{72}{843156}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{156284} = \frac{74}{312568}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{284156} = \frac{74}{568312}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{254871} = \frac{52}{368147}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{421758} = \frac{72}{843516}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{156428} = \frac{74}{312856}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{412568} = \frac{74}{825136}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{257184} = \frac{72}{514368}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{425718} = \frac{72}{851436}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{158264} = \frac{74}{316528}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{412658} = \frac{74}{825316}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{257814} = \frac{54}{386721}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{425817} = \frac{72}{851634}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{158426} = \frac{74}{316852}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{415628} = \frac{74}{831256}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{258417} = \frac{72}{516834}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{427158} = \frac{72}{854316}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{162584} = \frac{74}{325168}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{415826} = \frac{74}{831652}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{271584} = \frac{72}{543168}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{428157} = \frac{72}{856314}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{164258} = \frac{74}{328516}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{416258} = \frac{74}{832516}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{274158} = \frac{72}{548316}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{471852} = \frac{63}{825741}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{182564} = \frac{74}{365128}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{418256} = \frac{74}{836512}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{275184} = \frac{63}{481572}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{481572} = \frac{63}{842751}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{184256} = \frac{74}{368512}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{425618} = \frac{74}{851236}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{281574} = \frac{72}{563148}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{541782} = \frac{54}{812673}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{256184} = \frac{74}{512368}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{425681} = \frac{74}{851362}$
$\triangleright \frac{36}{284157} = \frac{72}{568314}$	$\triangleright \frac{36}{574182} = \frac{54}{861273}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{256418} = \frac{74}{512836}$	$\triangleright \frac{37}{425816} = \frac{74}{851632}$

- ▶ $\frac{37}{426158} = \frac{74}{852316}$
- ▶ $\frac{37}{426581} = \frac{74}{853162}$
- ▶ $\frac{37}{428156} = \frac{74}{856312}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{125674} = \frac{76}{251348}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{126574} = \frac{76}{253148}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{142567} = \frac{76}{285134}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{142657} = \frac{76}{285314}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{145762} = \frac{57}{218643}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{156274} = \frac{76}{312548}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{156427} = \frac{76}{312854}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{157264} = \frac{76}{314528}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{157426} = \frac{76}{314852}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{157624} = \frac{76}{315248}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{157642} = \frac{76}{315284}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{164257} = \frac{76}{328514}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{165742} = \frac{57}{248613}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{172564} = \frac{76}{345128}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{174562} = \frac{57}{261843}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{175624} = \frac{76}{351248}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{175642} = \frac{76}{351284}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{176254} = \frac{57}{264381}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{176542} = \frac{57}{264813}$
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- ▶ $\frac{38}{215764} = \frac{76}{431528}$
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- ▶ $\frac{38}{217456} = \frac{57}{326184}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{217564} = \frac{76}{435128}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{217654} = \frac{57}{326481}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{241576} = \frac{76}{483152}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{254176} = \frac{57}{381264}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{256417} = \frac{76}{512834}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{256714} = \frac{76}{513428}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{256741} = \frac{76}{513482}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{257164} = \frac{76}{514328}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{257614} = \frac{57}{386421}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{261574} = \frac{76}{523148}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{265714} = \frac{76}{531428}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{265741} = \frac{76}{531482}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{271564} = \frac{76}{543128}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{274156} = \frac{76}{548312}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{412567} = \frac{76}{825134}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{412657} = \frac{76}{825314}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{412756} = \frac{48}{521376}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{415627} = \frac{76}{831254}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{415726} = \frac{76}{831452}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{415762} = \frac{76}{831524}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{416257} = \frac{76}{832514}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{417256} = \frac{76}{834512}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{417562} = \frac{76}{835124}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{421576} = \frac{76}{843152}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{421756} = \frac{76}{843512}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{425617} = \frac{76}{851234}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{425671} = \frac{76}{851342}$
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- ▶ $\frac{38}{426157} = \frac{76}{852314}$
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- ▶ $\frac{38}{562174} = \frac{57}{843261}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{572641} = \frac{52}{783614}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{574162} = \frac{57}{861243}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{574216} = \frac{57}{861324}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{576142} = \frac{57}{864213}$
- ▶ $\frac{38}{576214} = \frac{57}{864321}$
- ▶ $\frac{41}{235678} = \frac{82}{471356}$
- ▶ $\frac{41}{235768} = \frac{82}{471536}$
- ▶ $\frac{41}{236578} = \frac{82}{473156}$
- ▶ $\frac{41}{236758} = \frac{82}{473516}$
- ▶ $\frac{41}{236857} = \frac{62}{358174}$
- ▶ $\frac{41}{237568} = \frac{82}{475136}$
- ▶ $\frac{41}{237658} = \frac{82}{475316}$
- ▶ $\frac{41}{256738} = \frac{82}{513476}$
- ▶ $\frac{41}{256837} = \frac{82}{513674}$
- ▶ $\frac{41}{256873} = \frac{82}{513746}$

$\triangleright \frac{41}{257368} = \frac{82}{514736}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{328567} = \frac{82}{657134}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{653827} = \frac{43}{685721}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{175863} = \frac{84}{351726}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{258367} = \frac{82}{516734}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{328657} = \frac{82}{657314}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{135678} = \frac{84}{271356}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{176358} = \frac{84}{352716}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{258673} = \frac{82}{517346}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{356728} = \frac{82}{713456}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{135768} = \frac{84}{271536}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{178356} = \frac{84}{356712}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{265738} = \frac{82}{531476}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{356827} = \frac{82}{713654}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{136578} = \frac{84}{273156}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{178563} = \frac{84}{357126}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{265837} = \frac{82}{531674}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{357268} = \frac{82}{714536}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{136758} = \frac{84}{273516}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{183576} = \frac{84}{367152}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{265873} = \frac{82}{531746}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{357682} = \frac{82}{715364}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{136857} = \frac{78}{254163}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{183756} = \frac{84}{367512}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{267358} = \frac{82}{534716}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{358267} = \frac{82}{716534}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{137568} = \frac{84}{275136}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{185763} = \frac{84}{371526}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{268357} = \frac{82}{536714}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{365728} = \frac{82}{731456}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{137658} = \frac{84}{275316}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{186375} = \frac{78}{346125}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{268573} = \frac{82}{537146}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{365782} = \frac{82}{731564}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{153678} = \frac{48}{175632}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{187563} = \frac{84}{375126}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{273568} = \frac{82}{547136}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{365827} = \frac{82}{731654}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{156378} = \frac{84}{312756}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{315786} = \frac{84}{631572}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{273658} = \frac{82}{547316}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{367258} = \frac{82}{734516}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{157638} = \frac{84}{315276}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{315876} = \frac{84}{631752}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{283567} = \frac{82}{567134}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{367582} = \frac{82}{735164}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{157836} = \frac{84}{315672}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{317586} = \frac{84}{635172}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{283657} = \frac{82}{567314}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{368257} = \frac{82}{736514}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{157863} = \frac{84}{315726}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{317856} = \frac{84}{635712}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{285673} = \frac{82}{571346}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{372568} = \frac{82}{745136}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{158376} = \frac{84}{316752}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{318576} = \frac{84}{637152}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{286573} = \frac{82}{573146}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{372658} = \frac{82}{745316}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{158763} = \frac{84}{317526}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{318756} = \frac{84}{637512}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{325687} = \frac{82}{651374}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{375682} = \frac{82}{751364}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{163578} = \frac{84}{327156}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{351876} = \frac{63}{527814}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{325867} = \frac{82}{651734}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{376582} = \frac{82}{753164}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{163758} = \frac{84}{327516}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{356178} = \frac{84}{712356}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{326587} = \frac{82}{653174}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{382567} = \frac{82}{765134}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{175638} = \frac{84}{351276}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{356781} = \frac{84}{713562}$
$\triangleright \frac{41}{326857} = \frac{82}{653714}$	$\triangleright \frac{41}{382657} = \frac{82}{765314}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{175836} = \frac{84}{351672}$	$\triangleright \frac{42}{357618} = \frac{84}{715236}$

$\triangleright \frac{42}{357681} = \frac{84}{715362}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{126587} = \frac{86}{253174}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{185762} = \frac{86}{371524}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{268571} = \frac{86}{537142}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{357816} = \frac{84}{715632}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{126857} = \frac{86}{253714}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{186257} = \frac{86}{372514}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{271586} = \frac{86}{543172}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{358176} = \frac{84}{716352}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{128567} = \frac{86}{257134}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{187256} = \frac{86}{374512}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{271856} = \frac{86}{543712}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{361578} = \frac{84}{723156}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{128657} = \frac{86}{257314}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{187562} = \frac{86}{375124}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{285617} = \frac{86}{571234}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{361758} = \frac{84}{723516}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{156287} = \frac{86}{312574}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{215786} = \frac{86}{431572}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{285671} = \frac{86}{571342}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{365781} = \frac{84}{731562}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{157286} = \frac{86}{314572}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{215876} = \frac{86}{431752}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{285716} = \frac{86}{571432}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{367581} = \frac{84}{735162}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{157862} = \frac{86}{315724}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{217586} = \frac{86}{435172}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{286157} = \frac{86}{572314}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{375618} = \frac{84}{751236}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{158627} = \frac{86}{317254}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{217856} = \frac{86}{435712}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{286571} = \frac{86}{573142}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{375681} = \frac{84}{751362}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{158726} = \frac{86}{317452}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{218576} = \frac{86}{437152}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{287156} = \frac{86}{574312}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{375816} = \frac{84}{751632}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{158762} = \frac{86}{317524}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{218756} = \frac{86}{437512}$	$\triangleright \frac{45}{326871} = \frac{85}{617423}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{376158} = \frac{84}{752316}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{162587} = \frac{86}{325174}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{256187} = \frac{86}{512374}$	$\triangleright \frac{46}{158723} = \frac{54}{186327}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{376581} = \frac{84}{753162}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{162857} = \frac{86}{325714}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{256871} = \frac{86}{513742}$	$\triangleright \frac{46}{231587} = \frac{54}{271863}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{378156} = \frac{84}{756312}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{172586} = \frac{86}{345172}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{257186} = \frac{86}{514372}$	$\triangleright \frac{46}{513728} = \frac{73}{815264}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{381576} = \frac{84}{763152}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{172856} = \frac{86}{345712}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{258617} = \frac{86}{517234}$	$\triangleright \frac{47}{162385} = \frac{67}{231485}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{381756} = \frac{84}{763512}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{175268} = \frac{87}{354612}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{258671} = \frac{86}{517342}$	$\triangleright \frac{47}{386152} = \frac{57}{468312}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{387516} = \frac{63}{581274}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{175862} = \frac{86}{351724}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{258716} = \frac{86}{517432}$	$\triangleright \frac{48}{123576} = \frac{72}{185364}$
$\triangleright \frac{42}{687351} = \frac{46}{752813}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{178562} = \frac{86}{357124}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{261587} = \frac{86}{523174}$	$\triangleright \frac{48}{132576} = \frac{78}{215436}$
$\triangleright \frac{43}{125687} = \frac{86}{251374}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{185627} = \frac{86}{371254}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{261857} = \frac{86}{523714}$	$\triangleright \frac{48}{156372} = \frac{84}{273651}$
$\triangleright \frac{43}{125867} = \frac{86}{251734}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{185726} = \frac{86}{371452}$	$\triangleright \frac{43}{265871} = \frac{86}{531742}$	$\triangleright \frac{48}{157236} = \frac{84}{275163}$

$\triangleright \frac{48}{215736} = \frac{76}{341582}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{186732} = \frac{63}{217854}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{382176} = \frac{81}{573264}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{234178} = \frac{84}{351267}$
$\triangleright \frac{48}{357612} = \frac{72}{536418}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{187326} = \frac{63}{218547}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{618732} = \frac{63}{721854}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{237418} = \frac{84}{356127}$
$\triangleright \frac{48}{361572} = \frac{84}{632751}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{217638} = \frac{81}{326457}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{673218} = \frac{63}{785421}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{237814} = \frac{84}{356721}$
$\triangleright \frac{48}{372156} = \frac{84}{651273}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{218376} = \frac{81}{327564}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{732186} = \frac{63}{854217}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{238174} = \frac{84}{357261}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{378624} = \frac{57}{423168}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{231768} = \frac{81}{347652}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{732618} = \frac{63}{854721}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{341782} = \frac{84}{512673}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{634287} = \frac{58}{721346}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{236178} = \frac{81}{354267}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{127834} = \frac{72}{164358}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{342178} = \frac{84}{513267}$
$\triangleright \frac{52}{384176} = \frac{56}{413728}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{237618} = \frac{81}{356427}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{142378} = \frac{84}{213567}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{374182} = \frac{84}{561273}$
$\triangleright \frac{52}{384761} = \frac{84}{621537}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{237816} = \frac{81}{356724}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{143782} = \frac{84}{215673}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{374218} = \frac{84}{561327}$
$\triangleright \frac{53}{621478} = \frac{71}{832546}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{238176} = \frac{81}{357264}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{174238} = \frac{84}{261357}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{378142} = \frac{84}{567213}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{138267} = \frac{72}{184356}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{267138} = \frac{72}{356184}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{174382} = \frac{84}{261573}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{378214} = \frac{84}{567321}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{162378} = \frac{81}{243567}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{286173} = \frac{72}{381564}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{174832} = \frac{78}{243516}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{381472} = \frac{71}{483652}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{163782} = \frac{81}{245673}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{317682} = \frac{81}{476523}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{178234} = \frac{84}{267351}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{381742} = \frac{84}{572613}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{176238} = \frac{81}{264357}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{328617} = \frac{72}{438156}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{178342} = \frac{84}{267513}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{382174} = \frac{84}{573261}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{176283} = \frac{78}{254631}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{361782} = \frac{81}{542673}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{182374} = \frac{84}{273561}$	$\triangleright \frac{57}{138264} = \frac{76}{184352}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{176382} = \frac{81}{264573}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{367281} = \frac{84}{571326}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{183742} = \frac{84}{275613}$	$\triangleright \frac{57}{283461} = \frac{87}{432651}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{178236} = \frac{81}{267354}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{376182} = \frac{81}{564273}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{214378} = \frac{84}{321567}$	$\triangleright \frac{57}{286143} = \frac{76}{381524}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{178362} = \frac{81}{267543}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{376218} = \frac{81}{564327}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{217438} = \frac{84}{326157}$	$\triangleright \frac{57}{328614} = \frac{76}{438152}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{182376} = \frac{81}{273564}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{378162} = \frac{81}{567243}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{217834} = \frac{84}{326751}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{142376} = \frac{87}{213564}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{183762} = \frac{81}{275643}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{381762} = \frac{81}{572643}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{218374} = \frac{84}{327561}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{143762} = \frac{87}{215643}$

$\triangleright \frac{58}{162374} = \frac{87}{243561}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{361742} = \frac{87}{542613}$	$\triangleright \frac{78}{421356} = \frac{81}{437562}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2475386} = \frac{3}{7426158}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{163742} = \frac{87}{245613}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{362174} = \frac{87}{543261}$	$\triangleright \frac{84}{153762} = \frac{86}{157423}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2483756} = \frac{3}{7451268}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{172463} = \frac{62}{184357}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{374162} = \frac{87}{561243}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2356784} = \frac{2}{4713568}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2485376} = \frac{3}{7456128}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{174236} = \frac{87}{261354}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{376142} = \frac{87}{564213}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2357684} = \frac{2}{4715368}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2537486} = \frac{3}{7612458}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{174362} = \frac{87}{261543}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{376214} = \frac{87}{564321}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2365784} = \frac{2}{4731568}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2538476} = \frac{3}{7615428}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{176234} = \frac{87}{264351}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{413627} = \frac{72}{513468}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2367584} = \frac{2}{4735168}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2547386} = \frac{3}{7642158}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{176342} = \frac{87}{264513}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{467132} = \frac{81}{652374}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2374856} = \frac{3}{7124568}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2548376} = \frac{3}{7645128}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{214376} = \frac{87}{321564}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{634172} = \frac{68}{743512}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2375486} = \frac{3}{7126458}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2567384} = \frac{2}{5134768}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{216374} = \frac{87}{324561}$	$\triangleright \frac{61}{247538} = \frac{78}{316524}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2375684} = \frac{2}{4751368}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2567438} = \frac{2}{5134876}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{217436} = \frac{87}{326154}$	$\triangleright \frac{62}{581374} = \frac{73}{684521}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2376584} = \frac{2}{4753168}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2568374} = \frac{2}{5136748}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{217634} = \frac{87}{326451}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{125874} = \frac{72}{143856}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2384756} = \frac{3}{7154268}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2568437} = \frac{2}{5136874}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{234176} = \frac{87}{351264}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{425187} = \frac{67}{452183}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2385476} = \frac{3}{7156428}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2568734} = \frac{2}{5137468}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{236174} = \frac{87}{354261}$	$\triangleright \frac{64}{138752} = \frac{73}{158264}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2435678} = \frac{2}{4871356}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2568743} = \frac{2}{5137486}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{237416} = \frac{87}{356124}$	$\triangleright \frac{68}{127534} = \frac{76}{142538}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2435768} = \frac{2}{4871536}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2573684} = \frac{2}{5147368}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{237614} = \frac{87}{356421}$	$\triangleright \frac{68}{143752} = \frac{83}{175462}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2436578} = \frac{2}{4873156}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2574368} = \frac{2}{5148736}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{243716} = \frac{67}{281534}$	$\triangleright \frac{68}{174352} = \frac{84}{215376}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2436758} = \frac{2}{4873516}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2583674} = \frac{2}{5167348}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{326714} = \frac{81}{456273}$	$\triangleright \frac{68}{341275} = \frac{76}{381425}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2437568} = \frac{2}{4875136}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2584367} = \frac{2}{5168734}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{341762} = \frac{87}{512643}$	$\triangleright \frac{68}{435217} = \frac{84}{537621}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2437658} = \frac{2}{4875316}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2586734} = \frac{2}{5173468}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{342176} = \frac{87}{513264}$	$\triangleright \frac{71}{652348} = \frac{82}{753416}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2473856} = \frac{3}{7421568}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2586743} = \frac{2}{5173486}$

$\triangleright \frac{1}{2657384} = \frac{2}{5314768}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2843657} = \frac{2}{5687314}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3567824} = \frac{2}{7135648}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3675842} = \frac{2}{7351684}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2657438} = \frac{2}{5314876}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2856734} = \frac{2}{5713468}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3567842} = \frac{2}{7135684}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3682574} = \frac{2}{7365148}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2658374} = \frac{2}{5316748}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2856743} = \frac{2}{5713486}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3568274} = \frac{2}{7136548}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3684257} = \frac{2}{7368514}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2658437} = \frac{2}{5316874}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2865734} = \frac{2}{5731468}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3568427} = \frac{2}{7136854}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3725684} = \frac{2}{7451368}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2658734} = \frac{2}{5317468}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{2865743} = \frac{2}{5731486}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3572684} = \frac{2}{7145368}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3726584} = \frac{2}{7453168}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2658743} = \frac{2}{5317486}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3256874} = \frac{2}{6513748}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3574268} = \frac{2}{7148536}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3742568} = \frac{2}{7485136}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2673584} = \frac{2}{5347168}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3258674} = \frac{2}{6517348}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3576824} = \frac{2}{7153648}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3742658} = \frac{2}{7485316}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2674358} = \frac{2}{5348716}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3265874} = \frac{2}{6531748}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3576842} = \frac{2}{7153684}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3756824} = \frac{2}{7513648}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2683574} = \frac{2}{5367148}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3268574} = \frac{2}{6537148}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3582674} = \frac{2}{7165348}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3756842} = \frac{2}{7513684}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2684357} = \frac{2}{5368714}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3285674} = \frac{2}{6571348}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3584267} = \frac{2}{7168534}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3765824} = \frac{2}{7531648}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2685734} = \frac{2}{5371468}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3286574} = \frac{2}{6573148}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3657284} = \frac{2}{7314568}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3765842} = \frac{2}{7531684}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2685743} = \frac{2}{5371486}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3425687} = \frac{2}{6851374}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3657428} = \frac{2}{7314856}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3825674} = \frac{2}{7651348}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2735684} = \frac{2}{5471368}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3425867} = \frac{2}{6851734}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3657824} = \frac{2}{7315648}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3826574} = \frac{2}{7653148}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2736584} = \frac{2}{5473168}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3426587} = \frac{2}{6853174}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3657842} = \frac{2}{7315684}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3842567} = \frac{2}{7685134}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2743568} = \frac{2}{5487136}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3426857} = \frac{2}{6853714}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3658274} = \frac{2}{7316548}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3842657} = \frac{2}{7685314}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2743658} = \frac{2}{5487316}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3428567} = \frac{2}{6857134}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3658427} = \frac{2}{7316854}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4235678} = \frac{2}{8471356}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2835674} = \frac{2}{5671348}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3428657} = \frac{2}{6857314}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3672584} = \frac{2}{7345168}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4235768} = \frac{2}{8471536}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2836574} = \frac{2}{5673148}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3567284} = \frac{2}{7134568}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3674258} = \frac{2}{7348516}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4236578} = \frac{2}{8473156}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{2843567} = \frac{2}{5687134}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3567428} = \frac{2}{7134856}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{3675824} = \frac{2}{7351648}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4236758} = \frac{2}{8473516}$

$\triangleright \frac{1}{4237568} = \frac{2}{8475136}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4286573} = \frac{2}{8573146}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4372568} = \frac{2}{8745136}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1437586} = \frac{6}{4312758}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4237658} = \frac{2}{8475316}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4325687} = \frac{2}{8651374}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4372658} = \frac{2}{8745316}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1437856} = \frac{3}{2156784}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4256738} = \frac{2}{8513476}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4325867} = \frac{2}{8651734}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4375682} = \frac{2}{8751364}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1456378} = \frac{3}{2184567}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4256837} = \frac{2}{8513674}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4326587} = \frac{2}{8653174}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4376582} = \frac{2}{8753164}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1457386} = \frac{6}{4372158}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4256873} = \frac{2}{8513746}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4326857} = \frac{2}{8653714}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4382567} = \frac{2}{8765134}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1457638} = \frac{3}{2186457}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4257368} = \frac{2}{8514736}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4328567} = \frac{2}{8657134}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4382657} = \frac{2}{8765314}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1457836} = \frac{3}{2186754}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4258367} = \frac{2}{8516734}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4328657} = \frac{2}{8657314}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1357684} = \frac{4}{2715368}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1537846} = \frac{7}{5382461}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4258673} = \frac{2}{8517346}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4356728} = \frac{2}{8713456}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1365784} = \frac{4}{2731568}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1563784} = \frac{4}{3127568}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4265738} = \frac{2}{8531476}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4356782} = \frac{2}{8713564}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1367584} = \frac{4}{2735168}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1564378} = \frac{4}{3128756}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4265837} = \frac{2}{8531674}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4356827} = \frac{2}{8713654}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1374586} = \frac{6}{4123758}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1573846} = \frac{6}{4721538}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4265873} = \frac{2}{8531746}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4357268} = \frac{2}{8714536}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1375684} = \frac{4}{2751368}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1574386} = \frac{6}{4723158}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4267358} = \frac{2}{8534716}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4357682} = \frac{2}{8715364}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1375846} = \frac{6}{4127538}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1576384} = \frac{4}{3152768}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4268357} = \frac{2}{8536714}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4358267} = \frac{2}{8716534}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1376584} = \frac{4}{2753168}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1576438} = \frac{4}{3152876}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4268573} = \frac{2}{8537146}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4365728} = \frac{2}{8731456}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1384576} = \frac{6}{4153728}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1578364} = \frac{4}{3156728}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4273568} = \frac{2}{8547136}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4365782} = \frac{2}{8731564}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1385746} = \frac{6}{4157238}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1578436} = \frac{4}{3156872}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4273658} = \frac{2}{8547316}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4365827} = \frac{2}{8731654}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1435678} = \frac{4}{2871356}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1578634} = \frac{4}{3157268}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4283567} = \frac{2}{8567134}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4367258} = \frac{2}{8734516}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1435768} = \frac{4}{2871536}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1583746} = \frac{6}{4751238}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4283657} = \frac{2}{8567314}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4367582} = \frac{2}{8735164}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1436758} = \frac{4}{2873516}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1583764} = \frac{4}{3167528}$
$\triangleright \frac{1}{4285673} = \frac{2}{8571346}$	$\triangleright \frac{1}{4368257} = \frac{2}{8736514}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1437568} = \frac{4}{2875136}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1587634} = \frac{4}{3175268}$

$\triangleright \frac{2}{1587643} = \frac{4}{3175286}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1758364} = \frac{4}{3516728}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1837564} = \frac{4}{3675128}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3187564} = \frac{4}{6375128}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1634578} = \frac{3}{2451867}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1758436} = \frac{4}{3516872}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1837654} = \frac{3}{2756481}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3415786} = \frac{4}{6831572}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1635784} = \frac{4}{3271568}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1758634} = \frac{4}{3517268}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1843576} = \frac{4}{3687152}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3415876} = \frac{4}{6831752}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1637458} = \frac{3}{2456187}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1758643} = \frac{4}{3517286}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1843756} = \frac{4}{3687512}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3416578} = \frac{3}{5124867}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1637584} = \frac{4}{3275168}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1763458} = \frac{3}{2645187}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1854376} = \frac{3}{2781564}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3417586} = \frac{4}{6835172}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1637854} = \frac{3}{2456781}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1763584} = \frac{4}{3527168}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1856374} = \frac{3}{2784561}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3417658} = \frac{3}{5126487}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1638574} = \frac{3}{2457861}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1763854} = \frac{3}{2645781}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1857436} = \frac{3}{2786154}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3418756} = \frac{4}{6837512}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1643758} = \frac{4}{3287516}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1764358} = \frac{4}{3528716}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1857643} = \frac{4}{3715286}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3456178} = \frac{3}{5184267}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1654378} = \frac{3}{2481567}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1765438} = \frac{3}{2648157}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1875634} = \frac{4}{3751268}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3457618} = \frac{3}{5186427}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1657438} = \frac{3}{2486157}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1765834} = \frac{3}{2648751}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1875643} = \frac{4}{3751286}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3457816} = \frac{3}{5186724}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1657834} = \frac{3}{2486751}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1783456} = \frac{3}{2675184}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3145768} = \frac{3}{4718652}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3458176} = \frac{3}{5187264}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1658374} = \frac{3}{2487561}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1783654} = \frac{3}{2675481}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3157864} = \frac{4}{6315728}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3518764} = \frac{3}{5278146}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1743658} = \frac{3}{2615487}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1784356} = \frac{4}{3568712}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3158764} = \frac{4}{6317528}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3561784} = \frac{4}{7123568}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1743856} = \frac{3}{2615784}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1785436} = \frac{3}{2678154}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3168574} = \frac{3}{4752861}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3564178} = \frac{4}{7128356}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1745638} = \frac{3}{2618457}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1785643} = \frac{4}{3571286}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3174568} = \frac{3}{4761852}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3567814} = \frac{4}{7135628}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1745836} = \frac{3}{2618754}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1834576} = \frac{3}{2751864}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3175864} = \frac{4}{6351728}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3567841} = \frac{4}{7135682}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1753864} = \frac{7}{6138524}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1835764} = \frac{4}{3671528}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3176854} = \frac{3}{4765281}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3576184} = \frac{4}{7152368}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1756384} = \frac{4}{3512768}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1836574} = \frac{3}{2754861}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3178564} = \frac{4}{6357128}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3576418} = \frac{4}{7152836}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{1756438} = \frac{4}{3512876}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{1837456} = \frac{3}{2756184}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3185764} = \frac{4}{6371528}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3576814} = \frac{4}{7153628}$

$\triangleright \frac{2}{3576841} = \frac{4}{7153682}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3741658} = \frac{3}{5612487}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3784156} = \frac{4}{7568312}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4136758} = \frac{4}{8273516}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3578164} = \frac{4}{7156328}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3741856} = \frac{3}{5612784}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3785416} = \frac{3}{5678124}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4137568} = \frac{4}{8275136}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3578416} = \frac{4}{7156832}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3745618} = \frac{3}{5618427}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3785614} = \frac{3}{5678421}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4137658} = \frac{4}{8275316}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3581764} = \frac{4}{7163528}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3745816} = \frac{3}{5618724}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3814576} = \frac{3}{5721864}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4156378} = \frac{4}{8312756}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3584176} = \frac{4}{7168352}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3756184} = \frac{4}{7512368}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3815764} = \frac{4}{7631528}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4157638} = \frac{4}{8315276}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3614578} = \frac{3}{5421867}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3756418} = \frac{4}{7512836}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3816574} = \frac{3}{5724861}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4157836} = \frac{4}{8315672}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3615784} = \frac{4}{7231568}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3756814} = \frac{4}{7513628}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3817456} = \frac{3}{5726184}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4157863} = \frac{4}{8315726}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3617458} = \frac{3}{5426187}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3756841} = \frac{4}{7513682}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3817564} = \frac{4}{7635128}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4158376} = \frac{4}{8316752}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3617584} = \frac{4}{7235168}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3758164} = \frac{4}{7516328}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3817654} = \frac{3}{5726481}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4158763} = \frac{4}{8317526}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3617854} = \frac{3}{5426781}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3758416} = \frac{4}{7516832}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3841576} = \frac{4}{7683152}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4163578} = \frac{4}{8327156}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3618574} = \frac{3}{5427861}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3761458} = \frac{3}{5642187}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3841756} = \frac{4}{7683512}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4163758} = \frac{4}{8327516}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3641578} = \frac{4}{7283156}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3761584} = \frac{4}{7523168}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3854176} = \frac{3}{5781264}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4175638} = \frac{4}{8351276}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3641758} = \frac{4}{7283516}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3761854} = \frac{3}{5642781}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3856174} = \frac{3}{5784261}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4175836} = \frac{4}{8351672}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3654178} = \frac{3}{5481267}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3764158} = \frac{4}{7528316}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3857416} = \frac{3}{5786124}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4175863} = \frac{4}{8351726}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3657418} = \frac{3}{5486127}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3765418} = \frac{3}{5648127}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3857614} = \frac{3}{5786421}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4176358} = \frac{4}{8352716}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3657841} = \frac{4}{7315682}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3765841} = \frac{4}{7531682}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3875164} = \frac{3}{5812746}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4178356} = \frac{4}{8356712}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3658174} = \frac{3}{5487261}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3781456} = \frac{3}{5672184}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4135678} = \frac{4}{8271356}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4178563} = \frac{4}{8357126}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3675814} = \frac{4}{7351628}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3781564} = \frac{4}{7563128}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4135768} = \frac{4}{8271536}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4183576} = \frac{4}{8367152}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{3675841} = \frac{4}{7351682}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{3781654} = \frac{3}{5672481}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4136578} = \frac{4}{8273156}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4183756} = \frac{4}{8367512}$

$\triangleright \frac{2}{4185763} = \frac{4}{8371526}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4375618} = \frac{4}{8751236}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5617438} = \frac{3}{8426157}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5781634} = \frac{3}{8672451}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4187563} = \frac{4}{8375126}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4375681} = \frac{4}{8751362}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5617834} = \frac{3}{8426751}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5783416} = \frac{3}{8675124}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4315786} = \frac{4}{8631572}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4375816} = \frac{4}{8751632}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5618374} = \frac{3}{8427561}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5783614} = \frac{3}{8675421}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4315876} = \frac{4}{8631752}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4376158} = \frac{4}{8752316}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5634178} = \frac{3}{8451267}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5814376} = \frac{3}{8721564}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4317586} = \frac{4}{8635172}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4376581} = \frac{4}{8753162}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5637418} = \frac{3}{8456127}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5816374} = \frac{3}{8724561}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4317856} = \frac{4}{8635712}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4378156} = \frac{4}{8756312}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5637814} = \frac{3}{8456721}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5817436} = \frac{3}{8726154}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4318576} = \frac{4}{8637152}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4381576} = \frac{4}{8763152}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5638174} = \frac{3}{8457261}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5817634} = \frac{3}{8726451}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4318756} = \frac{4}{8637512}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4381756} = \frac{4}{8763512}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5683174} = \frac{3}{8524761}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5834176} = \frac{3}{8751264}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4351876} = \frac{3}{6527814}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{4387516} = \frac{3}{6581274}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5741638} = \frac{3}{8612457}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5836174} = \frac{3}{8754261}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4356178} = \frac{4}{8712356}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5416378} = \frac{3}{8124567}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5741836} = \frac{3}{8612754}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5837416} = \frac{3}{8756124}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4356781} = \frac{4}{8713562}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5417638} = \frac{3}{8126457}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5743168} = \frac{3}{8614752}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5837614} = \frac{3}{8756421}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4357618} = \frac{4}{8715236}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5417836} = \frac{3}{8126754}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5743618} = \frac{3}{8615427}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1258674} = \frac{6}{2517348}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4357681} = \frac{4}{8715362}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5418376} = \frac{3}{8127564}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5743816} = \frac{3}{8615724}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1258764} = \frac{4}{1678352}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4357816} = \frac{4}{8715632}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5431768} = \frac{3}{8147652}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5761438} = \frac{3}{8642157}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1265874} = \frac{6}{2531748}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4358176} = \frac{4}{8716352}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5436178} = \frac{3}{8154267}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5761834} = \frac{3}{8642751}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1268574} = \frac{6}{2537148}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4361578} = \frac{4}{8723156}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5437618} = \frac{3}{8156427}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5763418} = \frac{3}{8645127}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1285674} = \frac{6}{2571348}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4361758} = \frac{4}{8723516}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5437816} = \frac{3}{8156724}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5763814} = \frac{3}{8645721}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1286574} = \frac{6}{2573148}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4365781} = \frac{4}{8731562}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5438176} = \frac{3}{8157264}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5768314} = \frac{3}{8652471}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1425687} = \frac{6}{2851374}$
$\triangleright \frac{2}{4367581} = \frac{4}{8735162}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5614378} = \frac{3}{8421567}$	$\triangleright \frac{2}{5781436} = \frac{3}{8672154}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1425867} = \frac{6}{2851734}$

$\triangleright \frac{3}{1426587} = \frac{6}{2853174}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1642587} = \frac{6}{3285174}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1857642} = \frac{6}{3715284}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2564187} = \frac{6}{5128374}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1426857} = \frac{6}{2853714}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1642857} = \frac{6}{3285714}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1862574} = \frac{6}{3725148}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2568714} = \frac{6}{5137428}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1428567} = \frac{6}{2857134}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1652748} = \frac{7}{3856412}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1864257} = \frac{6}{3728514}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2568741} = \frac{6}{5137482}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1428657} = \frac{6}{2857314}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1725864} = \frac{6}{3451728}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1872564} = \frac{6}{3745128}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2571864} = \frac{6}{5143728}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1547826} = \frac{8}{4127536}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1728564} = \frac{6}{3457128}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1874256} = \frac{6}{3748512}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2574186} = \frac{6}{5148372}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1562874} = \frac{6}{3125748}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1742586} = \frac{6}{3485172}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1875624} = \frac{6}{3751248}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2586174} = \frac{6}{5172348}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1564287} = \frac{6}{3128574}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1742856} = \frac{6}{3485712}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1875642} = \frac{6}{3751284}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2586417} = \frac{6}{5172834}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1572864} = \frac{6}{3145728}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1758624} = \frac{6}{3517248}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2158764} = \frac{6}{4317528}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2586714} = \frac{6}{5173428}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1574286} = \frac{6}{3148572}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1758642} = \frac{6}{3517284}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2175864} = \frac{6}{4351728}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2586741} = \frac{6}{5173482}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1578624} = \frac{6}{3157248}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1782456} = \frac{8}{4753216}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2178564} = \frac{6}{4357128}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2587164} = \frac{6}{5174328}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1578642} = \frac{6}{3157284}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1784265} = \frac{7}{4163285}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2185764} = \frac{6}{4371528}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2587416} = \frac{6}{5174832}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1586274} = \frac{6}{3172548}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1785624} = \frac{6}{3571248}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2415786} = \frac{6}{4831572}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2615874} = \frac{6}{5231748}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1586427} = \frac{6}{3172854}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1785642} = \frac{6}{3571284}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2415876} = \frac{6}{4831752}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2618574} = \frac{6}{5237148}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1587264} = \frac{6}{3174528}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1786425} = \frac{7}{4168325}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2417586} = \frac{6}{4835172}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2641587} = \frac{6}{5283174}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1587426} = \frac{6}{3174852}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1856274} = \frac{6}{3712548}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2417856} = \frac{6}{4835712}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2641857} = \frac{6}{5283714}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1587624} = \frac{6}{3175248}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1856427} = \frac{6}{3712854}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2418576} = \frac{6}{4837152}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2658714} = \frac{6}{5317428}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1587642} = \frac{6}{3175284}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1857264} = \frac{6}{3714528}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2418756} = \frac{6}{4837512}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2658741} = \frac{6}{5317482}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1625874} = \frac{6}{3251748}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1857426} = \frac{6}{3714852}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2458617} = \frac{4}{3278156}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2685714} = \frac{6}{5371428}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{1628574} = \frac{6}{3257148}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{1857624} = \frac{6}{3715248}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2561874} = \frac{6}{5123748}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2685741} = \frac{6}{5371482}$

$\triangleright \frac{3}{2715864} = \frac{6}{5431728}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{2874156} = \frac{6}{5748312}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4185627} = \frac{6}{8371254}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4261857} = \frac{6}{8523714}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2718564} = \frac{6}{5437128}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4125687} = \frac{6}{8251374}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4185726} = \frac{6}{8371452}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4265871} = \frac{6}{8531742}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2741586} = \frac{6}{5483172}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4125867} = \frac{6}{8251734}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4185762} = \frac{6}{8371524}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4268571} = \frac{6}{8537142}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2741856} = \frac{6}{5483712}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4126587} = \frac{6}{8253174}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4186257} = \frac{6}{8372514}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4271586} = \frac{6}{8543172}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2748165} = \frac{7}{6412385}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4126857} = \frac{6}{8253714}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4187256} = \frac{6}{8374512}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4271856} = \frac{6}{8543712}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2758614} = \frac{4}{3678152}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4128567} = \frac{6}{8257134}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4187562} = \frac{6}{8375124}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4285617} = \frac{6}{8571234}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2856174} = \frac{6}{5712348}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4128657} = \frac{6}{8257314}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4215786} = \frac{6}{8431572}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4285671} = \frac{6}{8571342}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2856417} = \frac{6}{5712834}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4156287} = \frac{6}{8312574}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4215876} = \frac{6}{8431752}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4285716} = \frac{6}{8571432}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2856714} = \frac{6}{5713428}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4157286} = \frac{6}{8314572}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4217586} = \frac{6}{8435172}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4286157} = \frac{6}{8572314}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2856741} = \frac{6}{5713482}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4157862} = \frac{6}{8315724}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4217856} = \frac{6}{8435712}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4286571} = \frac{6}{8573142}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2857164} = \frac{6}{5714328}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4158627} = \frac{6}{8317254}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4218576} = \frac{6}{8437152}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4287156} = \frac{6}{8574312}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2857416} = \frac{6}{5714832}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4158726} = \frac{6}{8317452}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4218756} = \frac{6}{8437512}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{5428617} = \frac{4}{7238156}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2861457} = \frac{4}{3815276}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4158762} = \frac{6}{8317524}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4256187} = \frac{6}{8512374}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{5687412} = \frac{4}{7583216}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2861574} = \frac{6}{5723148}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4162587} = \frac{6}{8325174}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4256871} = \frac{6}{8513742}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{5728614} = \frac{4}{7638152}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2861754} = \frac{4}{3815672}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4162857} = \frac{6}{8325714}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4257186} = \frac{6}{8514372}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{5861427} = \frac{4}{7815236}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2864157} = \frac{6}{5728314}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4172586} = \frac{6}{8345172}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4258617} = \frac{6}{8517234}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{5861724} = \frac{4}{7815632}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2865714} = \frac{6}{5731428}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4172856} = \frac{6}{8345712}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4258671} = \frac{6}{8517342}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{5876412} = \frac{4}{7835216}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2865741} = \frac{6}{5731482}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4175862} = \frac{6}{8351724}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4258716} = \frac{6}{8517432}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1235678} = \frac{8}{2471356}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{2871564} = \frac{6}{5743128}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4178562} = \frac{6}{8357124}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{4261587} = \frac{6}{8523174}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1235768} = \frac{8}{2471536}$

$\triangleright \frac{4}{1236578} = \frac{8}{2473156}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1283657} = \frac{8}{2567314}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1367582} = \frac{8}{2735164}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1572863} = \frac{8}{3145726}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1236758} = \frac{8}{2473516}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1285673} = \frac{8}{2571346}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1368257} = \frac{8}{2736514}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1573286} = \frac{8}{3146572}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1237568} = \frac{8}{2475136}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1286573} = \frac{8}{2573146}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1372568} = \frac{8}{2745136}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1573628} = \frac{8}{3147256}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1237658} = \frac{8}{2475316}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1325687} = \frac{8}{2651374}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1372658} = \frac{8}{2745316}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1573826} = \frac{8}{3147652}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1256738} = \frac{8}{2513476}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1325867} = \frac{8}{2651734}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1375682} = \frac{8}{2751364}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1576238} = \frac{8}{3152476}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1256837} = \frac{8}{2513674}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1326587} = \frac{8}{2653174}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1376582} = \frac{8}{2753164}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1576382} = \frac{8}{3152764}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1256873} = \frac{8}{2513746}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1326857} = \frac{8}{2653714}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1382567} = \frac{8}{2765134}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1578236} = \frac{8}{3156472}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1257368} = \frac{8}{2514736}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1328567} = \frac{8}{2657134}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1382657} = \frac{8}{2765314}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1578362} = \frac{8}{3156724}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1258367} = \frac{8}{2516734}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1328657} = \frac{8}{2657314}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1562378} = \frac{8}{3124756}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1578623} = \frac{8}{3157246}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1258673} = \frac{8}{2517346}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1356728} = \frac{8}{2713456}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1562738} = \frac{8}{3125476}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1578632} = \frac{8}{3157264}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1265738} = \frac{8}{2531476}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1356782} = \frac{8}{2713564}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1562837} = \frac{8}{3125674}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1582376} = \frac{8}{3164752}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1265837} = \frac{8}{2531674}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1356827} = \frac{8}{2713654}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1562873} = \frac{8}{3125746}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1582637} = \frac{8}{3165274}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1265873} = \frac{8}{2531746}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1357268} = \frac{8}{2714536}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1563287} = \frac{8}{3126574}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1582736} = \frac{8}{3165472}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1267358} = \frac{8}{2534716}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1357682} = \frac{8}{2715364}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1563728} = \frac{8}{3127456}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1583627} = \frac{8}{3167254}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1268357} = \frac{8}{2536714}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1358267} = \frac{8}{2716534}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1563782} = \frac{8}{3127564}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1583726} = \frac{8}{3167452}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1268573} = \frac{8}{2537146}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1365728} = \frac{8}{2731456}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1563827} = \frac{8}{3127654}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1583762} = \frac{8}{3167524}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1273568} = \frac{8}{2547136}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1365782} = \frac{8}{2731564}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1567832} = \frac{6}{2351748}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1586273} = \frac{8}{3172546}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1273658} = \frac{8}{2547316}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1365827} = \frac{8}{2731654}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1572638} = \frac{8}{3145276}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1586327} = \frac{8}{3172654}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1283567} = \frac{8}{2567134}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1367258} = \frac{8}{2734516}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1572836} = \frac{8}{3145672}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1587263} = \frac{8}{3174526}$

$\triangleright \frac{4}{1587326} = \frac{8}{3174652}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1725638} = \frac{8}{3451276}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1763582} = \frac{8}{3527164}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1856372} = \frac{7}{3248651}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1587623} = \frac{8}{3175246}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1725836} = \frac{8}{3451672}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1782356} = \frac{8}{3564712}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1857263} = \frac{8}{3714526}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1587632} = \frac{8}{3175264}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1725863} = \frac{8}{3451726}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1783562} = \frac{8}{3567124}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1857326} = \frac{8}{3714652}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1623578} = \frac{8}{3247156}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1726358} = \frac{8}{3452716}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1785623} = \frac{8}{3571246}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1857623} = \frac{8}{3715246}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1623758} = \frac{8}{3247516}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1728356} = \frac{8}{3456712}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1823576} = \frac{8}{3647152}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1857632} = \frac{8}{3715264}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1625738} = \frac{8}{3251476}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1728563} = \frac{8}{3457126}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1823756} = \frac{8}{3647512}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1862573} = \frac{8}{3725146}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1625837} = \frac{8}{3251674}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1732586} = \frac{8}{3465172}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1825637} = \frac{8}{3651274}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1863257} = \frac{8}{3726514}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1625873} = \frac{8}{3251746}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1732856} = \frac{8}{3465712}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1825736} = \frac{8}{3651472}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1872563} = \frac{8}{3745126}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1627358} = \frac{8}{3254716}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1735628} = \frac{8}{3471256}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1826357} = \frac{8}{3652714}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1873256} = \frac{8}{3746512}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1628357} = \frac{8}{3256714}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1735826} = \frac{8}{3471652}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1827356} = \frac{8}{3654712}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1875623} = \frac{8}{3751246}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1628573} = \frac{8}{3257146}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1736258} = \frac{8}{3472516}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1835627} = \frac{8}{3671254}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1875632} = \frac{8}{3751264}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1632587} = \frac{8}{3265174}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1738256} = \frac{8}{3476512}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1835726} = \frac{8}{3671452}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2135678} = \frac{8}{4271356}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1632857} = \frac{8}{3265714}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1756238} = \frac{8}{3512476}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1835762} = \frac{8}{3671524}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2135768} = \frac{8}{4271536}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1635728} = \frac{8}{3271456}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1756382} = \frac{8}{3512764}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1836257} = \frac{8}{3672514}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2136578} = \frac{8}{4273156}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1635782} = \frac{8}{3271564}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1758236} = \frac{8}{3516472}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1837256} = \frac{8}{3674512}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2136758} = \frac{8}{4273516}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1635827} = \frac{8}{3271654}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1758362} = \frac{8}{3516724}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1837562} = \frac{8}{3675124}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2137568} = \frac{8}{4275136}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1637258} = \frac{8}{3274516}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1758623} = \frac{8}{3517246}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1852376} = \frac{7}{3241658}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2137658} = \frac{8}{4275316}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1637582} = \frac{8}{3275164}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1758632} = \frac{8}{3517264}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1856273} = \frac{8}{3712546}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2156378} = \frac{8}{4312756}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{1638257} = \frac{8}{3276514}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1762358} = \frac{8}{3524716}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{1856327} = \frac{8}{3712654}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2157638} = \frac{8}{4315276}$

$\triangleright \frac{4}{2157836} = \frac{8}{4315672}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2317856} = \frac{8}{4635712}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2378156} = \frac{8}{4756312}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2571863} = \frac{8}{5143726}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2157863} = \frac{8}{4315726}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2318576} = \frac{8}{4637152}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2381576} = \frac{8}{4763152}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2573186} = \frac{8}{5146372}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2158376} = \frac{8}{4316752}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2318756} = \frac{8}{4637512}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2381756} = \frac{8}{4763512}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2573618} = \frac{8}{5147236}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2158763} = \frac{8}{4317526}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2351876} = \frac{6}{3527814}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2387516} = \frac{6}{3581274}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2573681} = \frac{8}{5147362}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2163578} = \frac{8}{4327156}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2356178} = \frac{8}{4712356}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2561738} = \frac{8}{5123476}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2573816} = \frac{8}{5147632}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2163758} = \frac{8}{4327516}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2356781} = \frac{8}{4713562}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2561837} = \frac{8}{5123674}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2581367} = \frac{8}{5162734}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2175638} = \frac{8}{4351276}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2357618} = \frac{8}{4715236}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2561873} = \frac{8}{5123746}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2581637} = \frac{8}{5163274}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2175836} = \frac{8}{4351672}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2357681} = \frac{8}{4715362}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2563187} = \frac{8}{5126374}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2581736} = \frac{8}{5163472}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2175863} = \frac{8}{4351726}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2357816} = \frac{8}{4715632}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2563718} = \frac{8}{5127436}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2583617} = \frac{8}{5167234}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2176358} = \frac{8}{4352716}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2358176} = \frac{8}{4716352}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2563817} = \frac{8}{5127634}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2583671} = \frac{8}{5167342}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2178356} = \frac{8}{4356712}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2361578} = \frac{8}{4723156}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2567138} = \frac{8}{5134276}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2583716} = \frac{8}{5167432}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2178563} = \frac{8}{4357126}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2361758} = \frac{8}{4723516}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2567381} = \frac{8}{5134762}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2586173} = \frac{8}{5172346}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2183576} = \frac{8}{4367152}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2365781} = \frac{8}{4731562}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2568137} = \frac{8}{5136274}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2586317} = \frac{8}{5172634}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2183756} = \frac{8}{4367512}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2367581} = \frac{8}{4735162}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2568371} = \frac{8}{5136742}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2586713} = \frac{8}{5173426}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2185763} = \frac{8}{4371526}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2375618} = \frac{8}{4751236}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2568713} = \frac{8}{5137426}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2586731} = \frac{8}{5173462}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2187563} = \frac{8}{4375126}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2375681} = \frac{8}{4751362}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2568731} = \frac{8}{5137462}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2587163} = \frac{8}{5174326}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2315786} = \frac{8}{4631572}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2375816} = \frac{8}{4751632}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2571368} = \frac{8}{5142736}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2587316} = \frac{8}{5174632}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2315876} = \frac{8}{4631752}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2376158} = \frac{8}{4752316}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2571638} = \frac{8}{5143276}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2615738} = \frac{8}{5231476}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2317586} = \frac{8}{4635172}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2376581} = \frac{8}{4753162}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2571836} = \frac{8}{5143672}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2615837} = \frac{8}{5231674}$

$\triangleright \frac{4}{2615873} = \frac{8}{5231746}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2683571} = \frac{8}{5367142}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2813657} = \frac{8}{5627314}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2865713} = \frac{8}{5731426}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2617358} = \frac{8}{5234716}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2685713} = \frac{8}{5371426}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2815637} = \frac{8}{5631274}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2865731} = \frac{8}{5731462}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2618357} = \frac{8}{5236714}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2685731} = \frac{8}{5371462}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2815736} = \frac{8}{5631472}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2871563} = \frac{8}{5743126}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2618573} = \frac{8}{5237146}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2713658} = \frac{8}{5427316}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2816357} = \frac{8}{5632714}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3125687} = \frac{8}{6251374}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2631587} = \frac{8}{5263174}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2715638} = \frac{8}{5431276}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2817356} = \frac{8}{5634712}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3125867} = \frac{8}{6251734}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2631857} = \frac{8}{5263714}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2715836} = \frac{8}{5431672}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2835617} = \frac{8}{5671234}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3126587} = \frac{8}{6253174}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2635718} = \frac{8}{5271436}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2715863} = \frac{8}{5431726}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2835671} = \frac{8}{5671342}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3126857} = \frac{8}{6253714}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2635817} = \frac{8}{5271634}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2716358} = \frac{8}{5432716}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2835716} = \frac{8}{5671432}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3128567} = \frac{8}{6257134}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2637158} = \frac{8}{5274316}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2718356} = \frac{8}{5436712}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2836157} = \frac{8}{5672314}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3128657} = \frac{8}{6257314}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2638157} = \frac{8}{5276314}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2718563} = \frac{8}{5437126}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2836571} = \frac{8}{5673142}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3156287} = \frac{8}{6312574}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2657138} = \frac{8}{5314276}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2731586} = \frac{8}{5463172}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2837156} = \frac{8}{5674312}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3157862} = \frac{8}{6315724}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2657381} = \frac{8}{5314762}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2731856} = \frac{8}{5463712}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2856173} = \frac{8}{5712346}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3158627} = \frac{8}{6317254}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2658137} = \frac{8}{5316274}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2735618} = \frac{8}{5471236}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2856317} = \frac{8}{5712634}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3158726} = \frac{8}{6317452}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2658371} = \frac{8}{5316742}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2735681} = \frac{8}{5471362}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2856713} = \frac{8}{5713426}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3158762} = \frac{8}{6317524}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2658713} = \frac{8}{5317426}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2735816} = \frac{8}{5471632}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2856731} = \frac{8}{5713462}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3162587} = \frac{8}{6325174}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2658731} = \frac{8}{5317462}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2736158} = \frac{8}{5472316}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2857163} = \frac{8}{5714326}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3162857} = \frac{8}{6325714}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2671358} = \frac{8}{5342716}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2736581} = \frac{8}{5473162}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2857316} = \frac{8}{5714632}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3172586} = \frac{8}{6345172}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2673581} = \frac{8}{5347162}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2738156} = \frac{8}{5476312}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2861573} = \frac{8}{5723146}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3172856} = \frac{8}{6345712}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{2681357} = \frac{8}{5362714}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2813567} = \frac{8}{5627134}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{2863157} = \frac{8}{5726314}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3175862} = \frac{8}{6351724}$

$\triangleright \frac{4}{3178562} = \frac{8}{6357124}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3258716} = \frac{8}{6517432}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3567281} = \frac{8}{7134562}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3581762} = \frac{8}{7163524}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3185627} = \frac{8}{6371254}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3261587} = \frac{8}{6523174}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3567812} = \frac{8}{7135624}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3582176} = \frac{8}{7164352}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3185726} = \frac{8}{6371452}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3261857} = \frac{8}{6523714}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3567821} = \frac{8}{7135642}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3582617} = \frac{8}{7165234}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3185762} = \frac{8}{6371524}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3265871} = \frac{8}{6531742}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3568127} = \frac{8}{7136254}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3582671} = \frac{8}{7165342}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3186257} = \frac{8}{6372514}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3268571} = \frac{8}{6537142}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3568271} = \frac{8}{7136542}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3582716} = \frac{8}{7165432}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3187256} = \frac{8}{6374512}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3271586} = \frac{8}{6543172}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3571628} = \frac{8}{7143256}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3615728} = \frac{8}{7231456}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3187562} = \frac{8}{6375124}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3271856} = \frac{8}{6543712}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3571826} = \frac{8}{7143652}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3615782} = \frac{8}{7231564}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3215678} = \frac{6}{4823517}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3285617} = \frac{8}{6571234}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3572618} = \frac{8}{7145236}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3615827} = \frac{8}{7231654}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3215786} = \frac{8}{6431572}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3285671} = \frac{8}{6571342}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3572681} = \frac{8}{7145362}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3617258} = \frac{8}{7234516}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3215876} = \frac{8}{6431752}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3285716} = \frac{8}{6571432}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3572816} = \frac{8}{7145632}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3617582} = \frac{8}{7235164}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3216758} = \frac{6}{4825137}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3286157} = \frac{8}{6572314}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3576182} = \frac{8}{7152364}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3618257} = \frac{8}{7236514}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3217586} = \frac{8}{6435172}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3286571} = \frac{8}{6573142}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3576218} = \frac{8}{7152436}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3621578} = \frac{8}{7243156}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3218576} = \frac{8}{6437152}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3518762} = \frac{6}{5278143}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3576812} = \frac{8}{7153624}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3621758} = \frac{8}{7243516}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3218756} = \frac{8}{6437512}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3561728} = \frac{8}{7123456}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3576821} = \frac{8}{7153642}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3625718} = \frac{8}{7251436}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3256187} = \frac{8}{6512374}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3561782} = \frac{8}{7123564}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3578162} = \frac{8}{7156324}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3625817} = \frac{8}{7251634}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3256871} = \frac{8}{6513742}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3561827} = \frac{8}{7123654}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3578216} = \frac{8}{7156432}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3627158} = \frac{8}{7254316}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3257186} = \frac{8}{6514372}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3562178} = \frac{8}{7124356}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3581267} = \frac{8}{7162534}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3628157} = \frac{8}{7256314}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3258617} = \frac{8}{6517234}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3562718} = \frac{8}{7125436}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3581627} = \frac{8}{7163254}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3657128} = \frac{8}{7314256}$
$\triangleright \frac{4}{3258671} = \frac{8}{6517342}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3562817} = \frac{8}{7125634}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3581726} = \frac{8}{7163452}$	$\triangleright \frac{4}{3657281} = \frac{8}{7314562}$

▶ $\frac{4}{3657812} = \frac{8}{7315624}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3725681} = \frac{8}{7451362}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3812567} = \frac{8}{7625134}$	▶ $\frac{6}{1258734} = \frac{7}{1468523}$
▶ $\frac{4}{3657821} = \frac{8}{7315642}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3725816} = \frac{8}{7451632}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3812657} = \frac{8}{7625314}$	▶ $\frac{6}{1582734} = \frac{7}{1846523}$
▶ $\frac{4}{3658127} = \frac{8}{7316254}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3726158} = \frac{8}{7452316}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3815627} = \frac{8}{7631254}$	▶ $\frac{6}{1854732} = \frac{7}{2163854}$
▶ $\frac{4}{3658271} = \frac{8}{7316542}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3726581} = \frac{8}{7453162}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3815726} = \frac{8}{7631452}$	▶ $\frac{6}{1873254} = \frac{7}{2185463}$
▶ $\frac{4}{3671258} = \frac{8}{7342516}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3728156} = \frac{8}{7456312}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3815762} = \frac{8}{7631524}$	▶ $\frac{6}{5384172} = \frac{7}{6281534}$
▶ $\frac{4}{3672581} = \frac{8}{7345162}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3756182} = \frac{8}{7512364}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3816257} = \frac{8}{7632514}$	▶ $\frac{6}{5387412} = \frac{7}{6285314}$
▶ $\frac{4}{3675812} = \frac{8}{7351624}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3756218} = \frac{8}{7512436}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3817256} = \frac{8}{7634512}$	▶ $\frac{6}{5418732} = \frac{7}{6321854}$
▶ $\frac{4}{3675821} = \frac{8}{7351642}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3756812} = \frac{8}{7513624}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3817562} = \frac{8}{7635124}$	▶ $\frac{6}{5473218} = \frac{7}{6385421}$
▶ $\frac{4}{3681257} = \frac{8}{7362514}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3756821} = \frac{8}{7513642}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3821576} = \frac{8}{7643152}$	▶ $\frac{6}{5873412} = \frac{7}{6852314}$
▶ $\frac{4}{3682571} = \frac{8}{7365142}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3758162} = \frac{8}{7516324}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3821756} = \frac{8}{7643512}$	▶ $\frac{6}{7321854} = \frac{7}{8542163}$
▶ $\frac{4}{3712568} = \frac{8}{7425136}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3758216} = \frac{8}{7516432}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3825617} = \frac{8}{7651234}$	▶ $\frac{6}{7325418} = \frac{7}{8546321}$
▶ $\frac{4}{3712658} = \frac{8}{7425316}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3761582} = \frac{8}{7523164}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3825671} = \frac{8}{7651342}$	▶ $\frac{7}{3125864} = \frac{8}{3572416}$
▶ $\frac{4}{3715628} = \frac{8}{7431256}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3761852} = \frac{7}{6583241}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3825716} = \frac{8}{7651432}$	▶ $\frac{7}{3812564} = \frac{8}{4357216}$
▶ $\frac{4}{3715826} = \frac{8}{7431652}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3762158} = \frac{8}{7524316}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3826157} = \frac{8}{7652314}$	▶ $\frac{7}{6532148} = \frac{8}{7465312}$
▶ $\frac{4}{3716258} = \frac{8}{7432516}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3765812} = \frac{8}{7531624}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3826571} = \frac{8}{7653142}$	
▶ $\frac{4}{3718256} = \frac{8}{7436512}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3765821} = \frac{8}{7531642}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3827156} = \frac{8}{7654312}$	
▶ $\frac{4}{3721856} = \frac{7}{6513248}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3781562} = \frac{8}{7563124}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3875162} = \frac{6}{5812743}$	
▶ $\frac{4}{3725618} = \frac{8}{7451236}$	▶ $\frac{4}{3782156} = \frac{8}{7564312}$	▶ $\frac{6}{1253874} = \frac{7}{1462853}$	

5.2.1 More Than Two Equivalent Fractions

There are total 185 possibilities of equivalent fractions with the digits 1 to 8 with more than one equivalent fractions.

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{1248}{3756} = \frac{1872}{5634} = \frac{2184}{6573} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1254}{3876} = \frac{1573}{4862} = \frac{2761}{8534} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1258}{4736} = \frac{1428}{5376} = \frac{1734}{6528} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1436}{8257} = \frac{1456}{8372} = \frac{1524}{8763} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1458}{2376} = \frac{2187}{3564} = \frac{5346}{8712} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1536}{2784} = \frac{3168}{5742} = \frac{4752}{8613} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1584}{3267} = \frac{1728}{3564} = \frac{3456}{7128} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1586}{2743} = \frac{3172}{5486} = \frac{3782}{6541} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1587}{2346} = \frac{1863}{2754} = \frac{3864}{5712} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1683}{2754} = \frac{2178}{3564} = \frac{4356}{7128} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1746}{5238} = \frac{1782}{5346} = \frac{2178}{6534} = \frac{2538}{7614} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1748}{2356} = \frac{2714}{3658} = \frac{5428}{7316} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1756}{2438} = \frac{3512}{4876} = \frac{5268}{7314} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1758}{2364} = \frac{3516}{4728} = \frac{6153}{8274} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1764}{2358} = \frac{3528}{4716} = \frac{6174}{8253} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1764}{3582} = \frac{2156}{4378} = \frac{3528}{7164} = \frac{4312}{8756} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1782}{4356} = \frac{2187}{5346} = \frac{3564}{8712} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1836}{2574} = \frac{2754}{3861} = \frac{3672}{5148} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1876}{2345} = \frac{3812}{4765} = \frac{6732}{8415} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{2146}{3857} = \frac{3478}{6251} = \frac{4736}{8512} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2178}{3654} = \frac{3146}{5278} = \frac{3267}{5481} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2178}{5436} = \frac{3146}{7852} = \frac{3267}{8154} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2574}{3618} = \frac{3861}{5427} = \frac{5148}{7236} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2574}{3816} = \frac{3861}{5724} = \frac{5148}{7632} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2618}{4573} = \frac{3542}{6187} = \frac{4158}{7263} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2871}{3654} = \frac{3267}{4158} = \frac{5643}{7182} \\ &\triangleright \frac{3478}{6512} = \frac{3854}{7216} = \frac{4653}{8712} \\ &\triangleright \frac{3756}{4812} = \frac{5634}{7218} = \frac{6573}{8421} \\ &\triangleright \frac{5841}{6372} = \frac{6534}{7128} = \frac{6831}{7452} \\ &\triangleright \frac{142}{36578} = \frac{213}{54867} = \frac{284}{73156} \\ &\triangleright \frac{142}{37658} = \frac{213}{56487} = \frac{284}{75316} \\ &\triangleright \frac{153}{28764} = \frac{257}{48316} = \frac{437}{82156} \\ &\triangleright \frac{154}{26873} = \frac{186}{32457} = \frac{358}{62471} \\ &\triangleright \frac{154}{27368} = \frac{217}{38564} = \frac{273}{48516} \\ &\triangleright \frac{154}{36872} = \frac{182}{43576} = \frac{364}{87152} \\ &\triangleright \frac{156}{23478} = \frac{276}{41538} = \frac{546}{82173} \\ &\triangleright \frac{156}{23784} = \frac{312}{47568} = \frac{468}{71352} \\ &\triangleright \frac{156}{28437} = \frac{312}{56874} = \frac{416}{75832} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{156}{28743} = \frac{312}{57486} = \frac{372}{68541} \\ &\triangleright \frac{174}{25638} = \frac{261}{38457} = \frac{348}{51276} \\ &\triangleright \frac{174}{25836} = \frac{261}{38754} = \frac{348}{51672} \\ &\triangleright \frac{174}{36258} = \frac{261}{54387} = \frac{348}{72516} \\ &\triangleright \frac{174}{38256} = \frac{261}{57384} = \frac{348}{76512} \\ &\triangleright \frac{176}{25438} = \frac{264}{38157} = \frac{528}{76314} \\ &\triangleright \frac{176}{43582} = \frac{216}{53487} = \frac{352}{87164} \\ &\triangleright \frac{214}{36578} = \frac{321}{54867} = \frac{428}{73156} \\ &\triangleright \frac{214}{37658} = \frac{321}{56487} = \frac{428}{75316} \\ &\triangleright \frac{216}{35748} = \frac{436}{72158} = \frac{512}{84736} \\ &\triangleright \frac{216}{37854} = \frac{312}{54678} = \frac{324}{56781} \\ &\triangleright \frac{216}{54378} = \frac{312}{78546} = \frac{324}{81567} \\ &\triangleright \frac{234}{17586} = \frac{247}{18563} = \frac{468}{35172} \\ &\triangleright \frac{234}{17856} = \frac{351}{26784} = \frac{468}{35712} \\ &\triangleright \frac{234}{18576} = \frac{351}{27864} = \frac{468}{37152} \\ &\triangleright \frac{238}{17456} = \frac{357}{26184} = \frac{714}{52368} \\ &\triangleright \frac{246}{13578} = \frac{574}{31682} = \frac{861}{47523} \\ &\triangleright \frac{246}{31857} = \frac{416}{53872} = \frac{438}{56721} \\ &\triangleright \frac{256}{18374} = \frac{384}{27561} = \frac{512}{36748} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{37184} = \frac{364}{52871} = \frac{512}{74368}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{37418} = \frac{384}{56127} = \frac{512}{74836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{38174} = \frac{384}{57261} = \frac{512}{76348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{16374} = \frac{387}{24561} = \frac{516}{32748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{17436} = \frac{387}{26154} = \frac{516}{34872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{36174} = \frac{387}{54261} = \frac{516}{72348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{37416} = \frac{387}{56124} = \frac{516}{74832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{15873} = \frac{528}{31746} = \frac{624}{37518}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{15743} = \frac{572}{31486} = \frac{682}{37541}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{15876} = \frac{342}{16758} = \frac{648}{31752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{17856} = \frac{567}{31248} = \frac{648}{35712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{18576} = \frac{513}{27864} = \frac{684}{37152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{17856} = \frac{513}{26784} = \frac{684}{35712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{17864} = \frac{468}{23751} = \frac{752}{38164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{18256} = \frac{561}{27384} = \frac{748}{36512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{25618} = \frac{561}{38427} = \frac{748}{51236}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{25816} = \frac{561}{38724} = \frac{748}{51632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{14852} = \frac{386}{15247} = \frac{586}{23147}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{21654} = \frac{546}{31278} = \frac{567}{32481}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{54216} = \frac{546}{78312} = \frac{567}{81324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{432}{15876} = \frac{684}{25137} = \frac{864}{31752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{452}{13786} = \frac{534}{16287} = \frac{568}{17324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{456}{17328} = \frac{651}{24738} = \frac{753}{28614}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{532}{48716} = \frac{714}{65382} = \frac{812}{74356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{642}{57138} = \frac{732}{65148} = \frac{826}{73514}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{124}{38657} = \frac{152}{47386} = \frac{168}{52374} = \frac{184}{57362}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{127}{68453} = \frac{142}{76538} = \frac{153}{82467} = \frac{157}{84623}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{37468} = \frac{234}{57681} = \frac{236}{58174} = \frac{354}{87261}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{15674} = \frac{651}{42873} = \frac{784}{51632} = \frac{812}{53476}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{18573} = \frac{572}{43186} = \frac{726}{54813} = \frac{842}{63571}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{17438} = \frac{384}{26157} = \frac{512}{34876} = \frac{768}{52314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{18564} = \frac{417}{28356} = \frac{546}{37128} = \frac{834}{56712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{16258} = \frac{561}{24387} = \frac{748}{32516} = \frac{816}{35472}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{15624} = \frac{432}{17856} = \frac{756}{31248} = \frac{864}{35712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{16254} = \frac{432}{18576} = \frac{567}{24381} = \frac{864}{37152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{375648} = \frac{18}{563472} = \frac{21}{657384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{483756} = \frac{18}{725634} = \frac{21}{846573}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{236578} = \frac{21}{354867} = \frac{28}{473156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{237658} = \frac{21}{356487} = \frac{28}{475316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{237856} = \frac{21}{356784} = \frac{42}{713568}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{285376} = \frac{17}{346528} = \frac{43}{876512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{365782} = \frac{21}{548673} = \frac{28}{731564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{376582} = \frac{21}{564873} = \frac{28}{753164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{237854} = \frac{24}{356781} = \frac{48}{713562}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{257438} = \frac{24}{386157} = \frac{32}{514876}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{258374} = \frac{24}{387561} = \frac{32}{516748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{345728} = \frac{21}{453768} = \frac{27}{583416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{374258} = \frac{24}{561387} = \frac{32}{748516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{382574} = \frac{24}{573861} = \frac{32}{765148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{235764} = \frac{36}{471528} = \frac{63}{825174}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{237456} = \frac{27}{356184} = \frac{54}{712368}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{243756} = \frac{36}{487512} = \frac{54}{731268}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{254376} = \frac{27}{381564} = \frac{54}{763128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{256374} = \frac{27}{384561} = \frac{36}{512748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{257436} = \frac{27}{386154} = \frac{36}{514872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{362574} = \frac{27}{543861} = \frac{36}{725148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{374256} = \frac{27}{561384} = \frac{36}{748512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{165784} = \frac{52}{374816} = \frac{73}{526184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{176358} = \frac{48}{352716} = \frac{84}{617253}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{351876} = \frac{36}{527814} = \frac{42}{615783}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{387516} = \frac{36}{581274} = \frac{42}{678153}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{153478} = \frac{46}{271538} = \frac{54}{318762}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{158743} = \frac{52}{317486} = \frac{62}{378541}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{174538} = \frac{57}{382641} = \frac{78}{523614}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{156784} = \frac{48}{235176} = \frac{86}{421357}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{178564} = \frac{56}{312487} = \frac{64}{357128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{417856} = \frac{56}{731248} = \frac{64}{835712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{178562} = \frac{51}{267843} = \frac{68}{357124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{185762} = \frac{51}{278643} = \frac{68}{371524}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{217856} = \frac{51}{326784} = \frac{68}{435712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{218576} = \frac{51}{327864} = \frac{68}{437152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{174258} = \frac{54}{261387} = \frac{72}{348516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{175248} = \frac{71}{345628} = \frac{87}{423516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{182574} = \frac{54}{273861} = \frac{72}{365148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{217854} = \frac{52}{314678} = \frac{54}{326781}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{257418} = \frac{54}{386127} = \frac{72}{514836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{258174} = \frac{54}{387261} = \frac{72}{516348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{542178} = \frac{52}{783146} = \frac{54}{813267}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{162574} = \frac{57}{243861} = \frac{76}{325148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{174256} = \frac{57}{261384} = \frac{76}{348512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{241756} = \frac{76}{483512} = \frac{86}{547132}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{245176} = \frac{58}{374216} = \frac{87}{561324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{256174} = \frac{57}{384261} = \frac{76}{512348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{257416} = \frac{57}{386124} = \frac{76}{514832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{264157} = \frac{52}{361478} = \frac{76}{528314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{356782} = \frac{56}{487312} = \frac{82}{713564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{123756} = \frac{72}{185634} = \frac{84}{216573}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{375612} = \frac{72}{563418} = \frac{84}{657321}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{216378} = \frac{78}{312546} = \frac{81}{324567}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{217836} = \frac{78}{314652} = \frac{81}{326754}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{362178} = \frac{78}{523146} = \frac{81}{543267}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{378216} = \frac{78}{546312} = \frac{81}{567324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{264138} = \frac{76}{352184} = \frac{78}{361452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{462173} = \frac{78}{621543} = \frac{82}{653417}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{134572} = \frac{78}{154362} = \frac{83}{164257}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{258674} = \frac{26}{517348} = \frac{38}{756124} = \frac{42}{835716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{183576} = \frac{48}{367152} = \frac{67}{512483} = \frac{76}{581324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{127568} = \frac{38}{142576} = \frac{57}{213864} = \frac{67}{251384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52}{147368} = \frac{58}{164372} = \frac{63}{178542} = \frac{76}{215384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{1356784} = \frac{4}{2713568} = \frac{8}{5427136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{1437658} = \frac{3}{2156487} = \frac{4}{2875316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{1438576} = \frac{3}{2157864} = \frac{6}{4315728}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{1458376} = \frac{3}{2187564} = \frac{6}{4375128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{1578643} = \frac{4}{3157286} = \frac{8}{6314572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{1584376} = \frac{4}{3168752} = \frac{6}{4753128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{1643578} = \frac{4}{3287156} = \frac{8}{6574312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{1783564} = \frac{4}{3567128} = \frac{8}{7134256}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{1857634} = \frac{3}{2786451} = \frac{4}{3715268}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{3417856} = \frac{3}{5126784} = \frac{4}{6835712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{3418576} = \frac{3}{5127864} = \frac{4}{6837152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{3657814} = \frac{3}{5486721} = \frac{4}{7315628}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{3765814} = \frac{3}{5648721} = \frac{4}{7531628}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{1256874} = \frac{4}{1675832} = \frac{6}{2513748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{1785632} = \frac{7}{3124856} = \frac{8}{3571264}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{3217856} = \frac{7}{5631248} = \frac{8}{6435712} \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{2}{1785634} = \frac{3}{2678451} = \frac{4}{3571268} = \frac{8}{7142536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{1436578} = \frac{3}{2154867} = \frac{4}{2873156} = \frac{8}{5746312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1576}{2384} = \frac{2561}{3874} = \frac{3152}{4768} = \frac{4137}{6258} = \frac{5713}{8642}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1638}{2574} = \frac{2457}{3861} = \frac{3276}{5148} = \frac{4536}{7128} = \frac{4851}{7623}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1476}{2583} = \frac{2376}{4158} = \frac{3528}{6174} = \frac{3852}{6741} = \frac{4716}{8253} = \frac{4752}{8316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1734}{2856} = \frac{2176}{3584} = \frac{3417}{5628} = \frac{3468}{5712} = \frac{4352}{7168} = \frac{5321}{8764}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1568}{3724} = \frac{1584}{3762} = \frac{1624}{3857} = \frac{2416}{5738} = \frac{2584}{6137} = \frac{3152}{7486} = \frac{3168}{7524} = \frac{3184}{7562}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1584}{2376} = \frac{1638}{2457} = \frac{1836}{2754} = \frac{2574}{3861} = \frac{3168}{4752} = \frac{3618}{5427} = \frac{3816}{5724} = \frac{4158}{6237} = \frac{5742}{8613}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1728}{3456} = \frac{1764}{3528} = \frac{1782}{3564} = \frac{1827}{3654} = \frac{2178}{4356} = \frac{2358}{4716} = \frac{2718}{5436} = \frac{2817}{5634} = \frac{3564}{7128} = \frac{3582}{7164} = \frac{4176}{8352} = \frac{4356}{8712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{26418} = \frac{618}{45732} = \frac{714}{52836} = \frac{732}{54168} = \frac{738}{54612}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{23864} = \frac{167}{25384} = \frac{361}{54872} = \frac{516}{78432} = \frac{536}{81472} = \frac{537}{81624}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{13674} = \frac{354}{18762} = \frac{516}{27348} = \frac{537}{28461} = \frac{541}{28673} = \frac{618}{32754} = \frac{657}{34821}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{23584} = \frac{281}{37654} = \frac{352}{47168} = \frac{386}{51724} = \frac{457}{61238} = \frac{458}{61372} = \frac{513}{68742} = \frac{536}{71824} = \frac{651}{87234}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{14756} = \frac{248}{15376} = \frac{283}{17546} = \frac{348}{21576} = \frac{438}{27156} = \frac{561}{34782} = \frac{617}{38254} = \frac{728}{45136} = \frac{873}{54126} = \frac{876}{54312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{148576} = \frac{34}{157862} = \frac{46}{213578} = \frac{68}{315724} = \frac{78}{362154}$$

5.3 8-Digits: 2 to 9

There are total 47 possibilities of equivalent fractions with the digits 2 to 9. Out of them there are only 4 having more than one possibility.

▶ $\frac{2478}{5369} = \frac{2694}{5837}$	▶ $\frac{329}{65847} = \frac{392}{78456}$	▶ $\frac{658}{32947} = \frac{784}{39256}$	▶ $\frac{47}{329658} = \frac{56}{392784}$
▶ $\frac{2853}{6974} = \frac{3258}{7964}$	▶ $\frac{348}{27956} = \frac{672}{53984}$	▶ $\frac{658}{47329} = \frac{784}{56392}$	▶ $\frac{47}{658329} = \frac{56}{784392}$
▶ $\frac{3289}{4576} = \frac{4738}{6592}$	▶ $\frac{438}{59276} = \frac{546}{73892}$	▶ $\frac{698}{32457} = \frac{752}{34968}$	▶ $\frac{57}{432896} = \frac{84}{637952}$
▶ $\frac{3762}{4598} = \frac{7326}{8954}$	▶ $\frac{439}{76825} = \frac{493}{86275}$	▶ $\frac{728}{59436} = \frac{854}{69723}$	▶ $\frac{58}{637942} = \frac{76}{835924}$
▶ $\frac{3978}{5642} = \frac{6732}{9548}$	▶ $\frac{469}{38257} = \frac{784}{63952}$	▶ $\frac{856}{49327} = \frac{928}{53476}$	▶ $\frac{62}{458397} = \frac{98}{724563}$
▶ $\frac{4235}{6897} = \frac{4865}{7923}$	▶ $\frac{482}{37596} = \frac{689}{53742}$	▶ $\frac{937}{82456} = \frac{973}{85624}$	▶ $\frac{68}{572934} = \frac{86}{724593}$
▶ $\frac{4532}{6798} = \frac{5324}{7986}$	▶ $\frac{493}{25687} = \frac{754}{39286}$	▶ $\frac{28}{347956} = \frac{64}{795328}$	▶ $\frac{89}{675243} = \frac{98}{743526}$
▶ $\frac{5327}{6849} = \frac{7532}{9684}$	▶ $\frac{524}{79386} = \frac{632}{95748}$	▶ $\frac{29}{365748} = \frac{38}{479256}$	▶ $\frac{286}{39754} = \frac{358}{49762} = \frac{493}{68527}$
▶ $\frac{5496}{7328} = \frac{6549}{8732}$	▶ $\frac{584}{36792} = \frac{872}{54936}$	▶ $\frac{38}{257469} = \frac{56}{379428}$	▶ $\frac{32}{458976} = \frac{59}{846237} = \frac{68}{975324}$
▶ $\frac{5928}{7436} = \frac{6954}{8723}$	▶ $\frac{627}{35948} = \frac{789}{45236}$	▶ $\frac{38}{459762} = \frac{74}{895326}$	▶ $\frac{367}{24589} = \frac{934}{62578} = \frac{952}{63784}$
▶ $\frac{239}{48756} = \frac{284}{57936}$	▶ $\frac{638}{57942} = \frac{836}{75924}$	▶ $\frac{39}{274586} = \frac{93}{654782}$	▶ $\frac{536}{29748} = \frac{968}{53724} = \frac{986}{54723}$
▶ $\frac{329}{47658} = \frac{392}{56784}$	▶ $\frac{649}{25783} = \frac{946}{37582}$	▶ $\frac{39}{287456} = \frac{93}{685472}$	

6 9-Digits

This section deals with equivalent fractions for 9 digits, 0 to 8 and 1 to 9. digits in each cases. Total we have 34543 for the digits 0 to 8 and 33673 for the digits 1 to 9. Since this number is high to put in a paper, we decided to put only those equivalent fractions those having at least 3 possibilities, instead of 2. In this case we have 1291 possibilities for the digits 0 to 8 and 1191 for the digits 1 to 9. Following subsections are written in decreasing order of equivalent possibilities, i.e., starting from higher equivalent expressions lower. This is divided in two subsections, first for the digits 0 to 8 and then for the digits 1 to 9.

6.1 9-Digits: 0 to 8

This subsection bring equivalent fractions for the digits 0 to 8, starting from higher to lower equivalent expressions in each case.

6.1.1 30 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have only one example, and in this situation it has maximum expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2073}{16584} &= \frac{2307}{18456} = \frac{2345}{18760} = \frac{3071}{24568} = \frac{3107}{24856} = \frac{3176}{25408} = \frac{3451}{27608} = \frac{4071}{32568} = \frac{4107}{32856} = \frac{4651}{37208} = \frac{4752}{38016} \\ &= \frac{4765}{4765} = \frac{6273}{6273} = \frac{6341}{6341} = \frac{6378}{6378} = \frac{6384}{6384} = \frac{7023}{7023} = \frac{7031}{7031} = \frac{7041}{7041} = \frac{7103}{7103} = \frac{7104}{7104} \\ &= \frac{38120}{7263} = \frac{50184}{7302} = \frac{50728}{7523} = \frac{51024}{7531} = \frac{51072}{7541} = \frac{56184}{7813} = \frac{56248}{8134} = \frac{56328}{8213} = \frac{56824}{8415} = \frac{56832}{8415} \\ &= \frac{58104}{58104} = \frac{58416}{58416} = \frac{60184}{60184} = \frac{60248}{60248} = \frac{60328}{60328} = \frac{62504}{62504} = \frac{65072}{65072} = \frac{65704}{65704} = \frac{67320}{67320} \end{aligned}$$

6.1.2 22 Equivalent Expressions

In this case also we have only one example:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3456}{17280} &= \frac{3528}{17640} = \frac{3564}{17820} = \frac{3654}{18270} = \frac{4137}{20685} = \frac{4167}{20835} = \frac{4173}{20865} = \frac{4356}{21780} = \frac{4617}{23085} = \frac{4716}{23580} = \frac{4761}{23805} = \frac{5436}{27180} \\ &= \frac{5634}{28170} = \frac{6417}{32085} = \frac{7128}{35640} = \frac{7164}{35820} = \frac{7281}{36405} = \frac{7641}{38205} = \frac{8127}{40635} = \frac{8352}{41760} = \frac{8712}{43560} = \frac{8721}{43605} \end{aligned}$$

6.1.3 18 Equivalent Expressions

In this case also we have only one example:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1534}{26078} &= \frac{2051}{34867} = \frac{2104}{35768} = \frac{2753}{46801} = \frac{2803}{47651} = \frac{3028}{51476} = \frac{3046}{51782} = \frac{3104}{52768} = \frac{3178}{54026} = \frac{3218}{54706} \\ &= \frac{3416}{58072} = \frac{4021}{68357} = \frac{4031}{68527} = \frac{4208}{71536} = \frac{4603}{78251} = \frac{4736}{80512} = \frac{5073}{86241} = \frac{5102}{86734} \end{aligned}$$

6.1.4 12 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 3 examples, each one with 12 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1728}{34560} &= \frac{1764}{35280} = \frac{1782}{35640} = \frac{1827}{36540} = \frac{2178}{43560} = \frac{2358}{47160} = \frac{2718}{54360} = \frac{2817}{56340} = \frac{3564}{71280} = \frac{3582}{71640} = \frac{4176}{83520} = \frac{4356}{87120} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2380}{14756} &= \frac{2480}{15376} = \frac{2830}{17546} = \frac{3480}{21576} = \frac{3485}{21607} = \frac{4380}{27156} = \frac{5610}{34782} = \frac{6170}{38254} = \frac{6205}{38471} = \frac{7280}{45136} = \frac{8730}{54126} = \frac{8760}{54312} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5238}{10476} &= \frac{5364}{10728} = \frac{5382}{10764} = \frac{5436}{10872} = \frac{6354}{12708} = \frac{6435}{12870} = \frac{6852}{13704} = \frac{8235}{16470} = \frac{8352}{16704} = \frac{8523}{17046} = \frac{8532}{17064} = \frac{8652}{17304} \end{aligned}$$

6.1.5 11 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have only 2 examples, each one with 11 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1365}{20748} &= \frac{1570}{23864} = \frac{1670}{25384} = \frac{1805}{27436} = \frac{2415}{36708} = \frac{3175}{48260} = \frac{3205}{48716} = \frac{3610}{54872} = \frac{5160}{78432} = \frac{5360}{81472} = \frac{5370}{81624} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1568}{37240} &= \frac{1584}{37620} = \frac{1620}{38475} = \frac{1624}{38570} = \frac{2416}{57380} = \frac{2584}{61370} = \frac{2708}{64315} = \frac{3152}{74860} = \frac{3168}{75240} = \frac{3184}{75620} = \frac{3460}{82175} \end{aligned}$$

6.1.6 10 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 4 examples, each one with 10 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1467}{20538} &= \frac{1647}{23058} = \frac{1704}{23856} = \frac{1836}{25704} = \frac{2184}{30576} = \frac{3648}{51072} = \frac{3672}{51408} = \frac{4017}{56238} = \frac{4083}{57162} = \frac{5724}{80136} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1584}{23760} &= \frac{1638}{24570} = \frac{1836}{27540} = \frac{2574}{38610} = \frac{2871}{43065} = \frac{3168}{47520} = \frac{3618}{54270} = \frac{3816}{57240} = \frac{4158}{62370} = \frac{5742}{86130} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1760}{23584} &= \frac{2810}{37654} = \frac{3520}{47168} = \frac{3860}{51724} = \frac{4570}{61238} = \frac{4580}{61372} = \frac{5130}{68742} = \frac{5360}{71824} = \frac{6205}{83147} = \frac{6510}{87234} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{238}{147560} &= \frac{248}{153760} = \frac{283}{175460} = \frac{348}{215760} = \frac{438}{271560} = \frac{561}{347820} = \frac{617}{382540} = \frac{728}{451360} = \frac{873}{541260} = \frac{876}{543120} \end{aligned}$$

6.1.7 9 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 3 examples, each one with 9 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1638}{20475} &= \frac{1846}{23075} = \frac{1876}{23450} = \frac{2486}{31075} = \frac{3286}{41075} = \frac{3810}{47625} = \frac{3812}{47650} = \frac{6730}{84125} = \frac{6732}{84150} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{15840} &= \frac{2457}{16380} = \frac{2754}{18360} = \frac{3861}{25740} = \frac{4752}{31680} = \frac{5427}{36180} = \frac{5724}{38160} = \frac{6237}{41580} = \frac{8613}{57420} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{235840} &= \frac{281}{376540} = \frac{352}{471680} = \frac{386}{517240} = \frac{457}{612380} = \frac{458}{613720} = \frac{513}{687420} = \frac{536}{718240} = \frac{651}{872340} \end{aligned}$$

6.1.8 8 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have only one example:

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3724}{15680} = \frac{3762}{15840} = \frac{3857}{16240} = \frac{5738}{24160} = \frac{6137}{25840} = \frac{7486}{31520} = \frac{7524}{31680} = \frac{7562}{31840}$$

6.1.9 7 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 6 examples, each one with 7 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1037}{45628} &= \frac{1038}{45672} = \frac{1083}{47652} = \frac{1478}{65032} = \frac{1532}{67408} = \frac{1645}{72380} = \frac{1683}{74052} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2580}{13674} &= \frac{3540}{18762} = \frac{5160}{27348} = \frac{5370}{28461} = \frac{5410}{28673} = \frac{6180}{32754} = \frac{6570}{34821} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2856}{17340} &= \frac{3584}{21760} = \frac{5628}{34170} = \frac{5712}{34680} = \frac{7168}{43520} = \frac{7182}{43605} = \frac{8764}{53210} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{3670}{12845} &= \frac{4578}{16023} = \frac{4582}{16037} = \frac{6710}{23485} = \frac{7018}{24563} = \frac{7458}{26103} = \frac{8726}{30541} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{136740} &= \frac{354}{187620} = \frac{516}{273480} = \frac{537}{284610} = \frac{541}{286730} = \frac{618}{327540} = \frac{657}{348210} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{324}{107568} &= \frac{327}{108564} = \frac{476}{158032} = \frac{504}{167328} = \frac{507}{168324} = \frac{543}{180276} = \frac{738}{245016} \end{aligned}$$

6.1.10 6 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 14 examples, each one with 6 expressions.

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1407}{36582} = \frac{1657}{43082} = \frac{2071}{53846} = \frac{2103}{54678} = \frac{3021}{78546} = \frac{3271}{85046}.$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1476}{25830} = \frac{2376}{41580} = \frac{3528}{61740} = \frac{3852}{67410} = \frac{4716}{82530} = \frac{4752}{83160}.$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1674}{38502} = \frac{1872}{43056} = \frac{2037}{46851} = \frac{2481}{57063} = \frac{3567}{82041} = \frac{3702}{85146}.$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1734}{28560} = \frac{2176}{35840} = \frac{3417}{56280} = \frac{3468}{57120} = \frac{4352}{71680} = \frac{5321}{87640}.$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2384}{15760} = \frac{3874}{25610} = \frac{4768}{31520} = \frac{6258}{41370} = \frac{7301}{48265} = \frac{8642}{57130}.$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2583}{14760} = \frac{4158}{23760} = \frac{6174}{35280} = \frac{6741}{38520} = \frac{8253}{47160} = \frac{8316}{47520}.$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3048}{17526} = \frac{3260}{18745} = \frac{5248}{30176} = \frac{6508}{37421} = \frac{7620}{43815} = \frac{8724}{50163}.$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3470}{15268} = \frac{3805}{16742} = \frac{6145}{27038} = \frac{7240}{31856} = \frac{8275}{36410} = \frac{8415}{37026}.$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3570}{26418} = \frac{6180}{45732} = \frac{7140}{52836} = \frac{7320}{54168} = \frac{7380}{54612} = \frac{8145}{60273}.$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{307856} = \frac{201}{435768} = \frac{263}{570184} = \frac{314}{680752} = \frac{346}{750128} = \frac{402}{871536}.$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{238640} = \frac{167}{253840} = \frac{361}{548720} = \frac{516}{784320} = \frac{536}{814720} = \frac{537}{816240}.$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{157384} = \frac{347}{265108} = \frac{361}{275804} = \frac{501}{382764} = \frac{537}{410268} = \frac{672}{513408}.$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{401268} = \frac{367}{412508} = \frac{538}{604712} = \frac{714}{802536} = \frac{734}{825016} = \frac{735}{826140}.$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{452}{308716} = \frac{476}{325108} = \frac{507}{346281} = \frac{542}{370186} = \frac{782}{534106} = \frac{821}{560743}.$$

6.1.11 5 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 40 examples, each one with 5 expressions.

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1203}{74586} = \frac{1234}{76508} = \frac{1265}{78430} = \frac{1356}{84072} = \frac{1372}{85064}.$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1520}{36784} = \frac{1540}{37268} = \frac{2015}{48763} = \frac{2485}{60137} = \frac{3605}{87241}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1530}{28764} = \frac{1745}{32806} = \frac{2570}{48316} = \frac{4165}{78302} = \frac{4370}{82156} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1576}{23840} = \frac{2561}{38740} = \frac{3152}{47680} = \frac{4137}{62580} = \frac{5713}{86420} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1587}{46023} = \frac{1638}{47502} = \frac{1734}{50286} = \frac{1806}{52374} = \frac{1863}{54027} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1638}{25740} = \frac{2457}{38610} = \frac{3276}{51480} = \frac{4536}{71280} = \frac{4851}{76230} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1804}{36572} = \frac{2156}{43708} = \frac{2618}{53074} = \frac{3542}{71806} = \frac{4257}{86301} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{2016}{35784} = \frac{3204}{56871} = \frac{3216}{57084} = \frac{3804}{67521} = \frac{4032}{71568} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{2064}{15738} = \frac{2304}{17568} = \frac{3504}{26718} = \frac{4728}{36051} = \frac{5016}{38247} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{2304}{17856} = \frac{4068}{31527} = \frac{4608}{35712} = \frac{6804}{52731} = \frac{7812}{60543} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{2475}{16830} = \frac{2730}{18564} = \frac{4170}{28356} = \frac{5460}{37128} = \frac{8340}{56712} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{16380} = \frac{3861}{24570} = \frac{5148}{32760} = \frac{7128}{45360} = \frac{7623}{48510} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{2637}{10548} = \frac{3627}{14508} = \frac{3762}{15048} = \frac{5184}{20736} = \frac{7542}{30168} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{3078}{21546} = \frac{4581}{32067} = \frac{5823}{40761} = \frac{7263}{50841} = \frac{7803}{54621} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{3276}{14508} = \frac{4032}{17856} = \frac{5607}{24831} = \frac{7056}{31248} = \frac{8064}{35712} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{4026}{15738} = \frac{4356}{17028} = \frac{8052}{31476} = \frac{8074}{31562} = \frac{8712}{34056} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{4736}{12580} = \frac{5376}{14280} = \frac{6432}{17085} = \frac{6528}{17340} = \frac{7648}{20315} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{136}{250784} = \frac{145}{267380} = \frac{174}{320856} = \frac{316}{582704} = \frac{381}{702564} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{153}{468027} = \frac{157}{480263} = \frac{234}{715806} = \frac{256}{783104} = \frac{263}{804517} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{156}{234780} = \frac{267}{401835} = \frac{273}{410865} = \frac{276}{415380} = \frac{546}{821730} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{157}{346028} = \frac{162}{357048} = \frac{215}{473860} = \frac{326}{718504} = \frac{354}{780216} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{167}{235804} = \frac{248}{350176} = \frac{265}{374180} = \frac{367}{518204} = \frac{431}{608572} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{187}{365024} = \frac{352}{687104} = \frac{364}{710528} = \frac{365}{712480} = \frac{436}{851072} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{208}{154376} = \frac{364}{270158} = \frac{416}{308752} = \frac{728}{540316} = \frac{832}{617504} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{237}{108546} = \frac{506}{231748} = \frac{583}{267014} = \frac{613}{280754} = \frac{678}{310524} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{245}{178360} = \frac{427}{310856} = \frac{501}{364728} = \frac{601}{437528} = \frac{834}{607152} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{246}{185730} = \frac{572}{431860} = \frac{726}{548130} = \frac{831}{627405} = \frac{842}{635710} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{108654} = \frac{357}{142086} = \frac{372}{148056} = \frac{387}{154026} = \frac{546}{217308} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{247086} = \frac{345}{270618} = \frac{405}{317682} = \frac{480}{376512} = \frac{825}{647130} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{320}{148576} = \frac{340}{157862} = \frac{460}{213578} = \frac{680}{315724} = \frac{780}{362154} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{324}{160785} = \frac{340}{168725} = \frac{352}{174680} = \frac{372}{184605} = \frac{648}{321570} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{340}{127568} = \frac{380}{142576} = \frac{570}{213864} = \frac{615}{230748} = \frac{670}{251384} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{264180} = \frac{618}{457320} = \frac{714}{528360} = \frac{732}{541680} = \frac{738}{546120} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{358}{102746} = \frac{438}{125706} = \frac{456}{130872} = \frac{582}{167034} = \frac{734}{210658} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{104528} = \frac{384}{106752} = \frac{583}{162074} = \frac{738}{205164} = \frac{768}{213504} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{384}{120576} = \frac{532}{167048} = \frac{574}{180236} = \frac{647}{203158} = \frac{861}{270354} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{385}{162470} = \frac{423}{178506} = \frac{508}{214376} = \frac{573}{241806} = \frac{846}{357012} \cdot \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{573}{104286} = \frac{576}{104832} = \frac{687}{125034} = \frac{783}{142506} = \frac{786}{143052} \cdot \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1485760} = \frac{34}{1578620} = \frac{46}{2135780} = \frac{68}{3157240} = \frac{78}{3621540} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17530864} = \frac{4}{35061728} = \frac{5}{43827160} = \frac{7}{61358024} = \frac{8}{70123456} \end{aligned}$$

6.1.12 4 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 124 examples, each one with 4 expressions.

$\blacktriangleright \frac{1024}{37568} = \frac{1056}{38742} = \frac{1376}{50482} = \frac{2048}{75136}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1582}{37064} = \frac{1652}{38704} = \frac{3185}{74620} = \frac{3507}{82164}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1056}{37824} = \frac{2145}{76830} = \frac{2365}{84710} = \frac{2376}{85104}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1608}{34572} = \frac{2376}{51084} = \frac{2704}{58136} = \frac{3012}{64758}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1068}{32574} = \frac{1764}{53802} = \frac{2134}{65087} = \frac{2670}{81435}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1746}{52380} = \frac{1782}{53460} = \frac{2178}{65340} = \frac{2538}{76140}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1240}{38657} = \frac{1520}{47386} = \frac{1680}{52374} = \frac{1840}{57362}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{23580} = \frac{3087}{41265} = \frac{3528}{47160} = \frac{6174}{82530}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1254}{36708} = \frac{1386}{40572} = \frac{2453}{71806} = \frac{2508}{73416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{35820} = \frac{2156}{43780} = \frac{3528}{71640} = \frac{4312}{87560}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1270}{68453} = \frac{1420}{76538} = \frac{1530}{82467} = \frac{1570}{84623}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{18376} = \frac{3081}{27564} = \frac{4108}{36752} = \frac{8216}{73504}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1302}{74865} = \frac{1436}{82570} = \frac{1456}{83720} = \frac{1524}{87630}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2086}{15347} = \frac{2506}{18437} = \frac{5012}{36874} = \frac{8470}{62315}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1320}{48576} = \frac{1325}{48760} = \frac{1460}{53728} = \frac{1725}{63480}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2178}{36054} = \frac{3146}{52078} = \frac{3267}{54081} = \frac{4356}{72108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1368}{40752} = \frac{1786}{53204} = \frac{2356}{70184} = \frac{2736}{81504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{41850} = \frac{4136}{72850} = \frac{4180}{73625} = \frac{4620}{81375}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1430}{28756} = \frac{1705}{34286} = \frac{3410}{68572} = \frac{3685}{74102}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2380}{15674} = \frac{6510}{42873} = \frac{7840}{51632} = \frac{8120}{53476}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1458}{32076} = \frac{1485}{32670} = \frac{2637}{58014} = \frac{3546}{78012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2407}{15863} = \frac{3154}{20786} = \frac{5478}{36102} = \frac{6308}{41572}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1508}{37642} = \frac{2418}{60357} = \frac{2730}{68145} = \frac{3016}{75284}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2436}{10875} = \frac{3864}{17250} = \frac{6748}{30125} = \frac{7084}{31625}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1520}{37468} = \frac{2340}{57681} = \frac{2360}{58174} = \frac{3540}{87261}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2436}{18705} = \frac{5376}{41280} = \frac{5712}{43860} = \frac{6132}{47085}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1526}{30847} = \frac{1708}{34526} = \frac{2170}{43865} = \frac{4270}{86315}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2460}{18573} = \frac{5720}{43186} = \frac{7260}{54813} = \frac{8420}{63571}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1534}{20768} = \frac{3601}{48752} = \frac{5408}{73216} = \frac{6435}{87120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2475}{13860} = \frac{3765}{21084} = \frac{7185}{40236} = \frac{7530}{42168}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1536}{27840} = \frac{1768}{32045} = \frac{3168}{57420} = \frac{4752}{86130}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2560}{17438} = \frac{3840}{26157} = \frac{5120}{34876} = \frac{7680}{52314}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2568}{30174} = \frac{3576}{42018} = \frac{6384}{75012} = \frac{7152}{84036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2650}{17384} = \frac{3675}{24108} = \frac{6375}{41820} = \frac{7350}{48216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2750}{13684} = \frac{2875}{14306} = \frac{6125}{30478} = \frac{6875}{34210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2754}{16830} = \frac{3564}{21780} = \frac{6723}{41085} = \frac{7128}{43560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2806}{13754} = \frac{2867}{14053} = \frac{5063}{24817} = \frac{5734}{28106}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3024}{15876} = \frac{4068}{21357} = \frac{6048}{31752} = \frac{6804}{35721}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3408}{15762} = \frac{3472}{16058} = \frac{5704}{26381} = \frac{7104}{32856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3458}{20176} = \frac{5187}{30264} = \frac{6517}{38024} = \frac{7315}{42680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3475}{10286} = \frac{4350}{12876} = \frac{6025}{17834} = \frac{8350}{24716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3478}{21056} = \frac{6401}{38752} = \frac{7215}{43680} = \frac{8436}{51072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3582}{17640} = \frac{4378}{21560} = \frac{7164}{35280} = \frac{8756}{43120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3608}{17425} = \frac{6248}{30175} = \frac{7216}{34850} = \frac{7480}{36125}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3740}{16258} = \frac{5610}{24387} = \frac{7480}{32516} = \frac{8160}{35472}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3780}{15624} = \frac{4320}{17856} = \frac{7560}{31248} = \frac{8640}{35712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3780}{16254} = \frac{4320}{18576} = \frac{5670}{24381} = \frac{8640}{37152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3784}{26015} = \frac{4680}{32175} = \frac{6280}{43175} = \frac{7016}{48235}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3876}{12540} = \frac{4267}{13805} = \frac{4862}{15730} = \frac{8534}{27610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4218}{35076} = \frac{5073}{42186} = \frac{7581}{63042} = \frac{8436}{70152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4560}{17328} = \frac{6510}{24738} = \frac{7530}{28614} = \frac{8265}{31407}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4730}{12685} = \frac{6732}{18054} = \frac{7854}{21063} = \frac{8074}{21653}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4873}{15062} = \frac{5632}{17408} = \frac{7865}{24310} = \frac{8316}{25704}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5238}{17460} = \frac{5346}{17820} = \frac{6534}{21780} = \frac{7614}{25380}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{267435} = \frac{176}{435820} = \frac{216}{534870} = \frac{352}{871640}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{124}{386570} = \frac{152}{473860} = \frac{168}{523740} = \frac{184}{573620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{127}{684530} = \frac{142}{765380} = \frac{153}{824670} = \frac{157}{846230}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{130}{258674} = \frac{260}{517348} = \frac{380}{756124} = \frac{420}{835716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{143}{287056} = \frac{208}{417536} = \frac{273}{548016} = \frac{416}{835072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{374680} = \frac{234}{576810} = \frac{236}{581740} = \frac{354}{872610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{268730} = \frac{186}{324570} = \frac{358}{624710} = \frac{413}{720685}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{287430} = \frac{186}{342705} = \frac{312}{574860} = \frac{372}{685410}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{162}{407835} = \frac{216}{543780} = \frac{312}{785460} = \frac{324}{815670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{164}{327508} = \frac{208}{415376} = \frac{314}{627058} = \frac{416}{830752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{235048} = \frac{376}{502148} = \frac{402}{536871} = \frac{532}{710486}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{236054} = \frac{267}{354081} = \frac{356}{472108} = \frac{534}{708162}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{186}{354702} = \frac{278}{530146} = \frac{341}{650287} = \frac{403}{768521}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{158746} = \frac{538}{420716} = \frac{561}{438702} = \frac{743}{581026}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{135768} = \frac{408}{271536} = \frac{731}{486502} = \frac{816}{543072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{357816} = \frac{326}{571804} = \frac{352}{617408} = \frac{408}{715632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{134576} = \frac{318}{205746} = \frac{381}{246507} = \frac{631}{408257}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{368475} = \frac{238}{417605} = \frac{406}{712385} = \frac{476}{835210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{378054} = \frac{312}{546078} = \frac{324}{567081} = \frac{432}{756108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{218}{347056} = \frac{258}{410736} = \frac{306}{487152} = \frac{517}{823064}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{160875} = \frac{468}{321750} = \frac{602}{413875} = \frac{628}{431750}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{236}{178054} = \frac{354}{267081} = \frac{472}{356108} = \frac{708}{534162}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{156740} = \frac{651}{428730} = \frac{784}{516320} = \frac{812}{534760}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{183576} = \frac{480}{367152} = \frac{670}{512483} = \frac{760}{581324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{241}{370658} = \frac{245}{376810} = \frac{415}{638270} = \frac{456}{701328}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{174380} = \frac{384}{261570} = \frac{512}{348760} = \frac{768}{523140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{185640} = \frac{417}{283560} = \frac{546}{371280} = \frac{834}{567120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{145038} = \frac{354}{186027} = \frac{476}{250138} = \frac{534}{280617}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{164730} = \frac{618}{357204} = \frac{645}{372810} = \frac{654}{378012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{218576} = \frac{608}{437152} = \frac{627}{450813} = \frac{658}{473102}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{315}{274680} = \frac{501}{436872} = \frac{617}{538024} = \frac{715}{623480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{175608} = \frac{504}{273168} = \frac{513}{278046} = \frac{753}{408126}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{358}{160742} = \frac{514}{230786} = \frac{714}{320586} = \frac{784}{352016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{175248} = \frac{710}{345628} = \frac{715}{348062} = \frac{870}{423516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{162580} = \frac{561}{243870} = \frac{748}{325160} = \frac{816}{354720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{148520} = \frac{386}{152470} = \frac{423}{167085} = \frac{586}{231470}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{156240} = \frac{432}{178560} = \frac{756}{312480} = \frac{864}{357120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{162540} = \frac{432}{185760} = \frac{567}{243810} = \frac{864}{371520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{164052} = \frac{504}{218736} = \frac{726}{315084} = \frac{756}{328104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{216054} = \frac{546}{312078} = \frac{567}{324081} = \frac{756}{432108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{382}{140576} = \frac{502}{184736} = \frac{563}{207184} = \frac{573}{210864}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{160752} = \frac{752}{314806} = \frac{768}{321504} = \frac{872}{365041}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{386}{154207} = \frac{586}{234107} = \frac{710}{283645} = \frac{764}{305218}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{403}{561782} = \frac{438}{610572} = \frac{532}{741608} = \frac{561}{782034}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{173826} = \frac{435}{186702} = \frac{540}{231768} = \frac{810}{347652}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{427}{360815} = \frac{713}{602485} = \frac{732}{618540} = \frac{854}{721630}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{430}{187265} = \frac{782}{340561} = \frac{852}{371046} = \frac{862}{375401}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{432}{107865} = \frac{576}{143820} = \frac{816}{203745} = \frac{864}{215730}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{452}{137860} = \frac{534}{162870} = \frac{568}{173240} = \frac{807}{246135}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{520}{147368} = \frac{580}{164372} = \frac{630}{178542} = \frac{760}{215384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{123840} = \frac{627}{134805} = \frac{736}{158240} = \frac{803}{172645}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2586740} = \frac{26}{5173480} = \frac{38}{7561240} = \frac{42}{8357160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2708654} = \frac{17}{3542086} = \frac{26}{5417308} = \frac{42}{8751036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{2538406} = \frac{27}{4031586} = \frac{34}{5076812} = \frac{54}{8063172}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{1436578} = \frac{30}{2154867} = \frac{40}{2873156} = \frac{80}{5746312} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{1785634} = \frac{30}{2678451} = \frac{40}{3571268} = \frac{80}{7142536} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1835760} = \frac{48}{3671520} = \frac{67}{5124830} = \frac{76}{5813240} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{3051786} = \frac{28}{3560417} = \frac{48}{6103572} = \frac{56}{7120834} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{1578304} = \frac{45}{2731680} = \frac{54}{3278016} = \frac{57}{3460128} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{1735084} = \frac{31}{2068754} = \frac{52}{3470168} = \frac{62}{4137508} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1567840} = \frac{43}{2106785} = \frac{48}{2351760} = \frac{86}{4213570} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{4017856} = \frac{54}{6780132} = \frac{56}{7031248} = \frac{64}{8035712} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{1275680} = \frac{38}{1425760} = \frac{57}{2138640} = \frac{67}{2513840} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2178054} = \frac{52}{3146078} = \frac{54}{3267081} = \frac{72}{4356108} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{3267085} = \frac{58}{4621730} = \frac{78}{6215430} = \frac{82}{6534170} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{52}{1473680} = \frac{58}{1643720} = \frac{63}{1785420} = \frac{76}{2153840} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14365780} = \frac{3}{21548670} = \frac{4}{28731560} = \frac{8}{57463120} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15437608} = \frac{4}{30875216} = \frac{7}{54031628} = \frac{8}{61750432} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17856340} = \frac{3}{26784510} = \frac{4}{35712680} = \frac{8}{71425360} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{18376054} = \frac{3}{27564081} = \frac{4}{36752108} = \frac{8}{73504216} \end{aligned}$$

6.1.13 3 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 1091 examples, each one with 3 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{1026}{54378} = \frac{1082}{57346} = \frac{1368}{72504} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1078}{24563} = \frac{1582}{36047} = \frac{2086}{47531} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1260}{37485} = \frac{2460}{73185} = \frac{2508}{74613} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1034}{26587} = \frac{1504}{38672} = \frac{2068}{53174} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1078}{36542} = \frac{1372}{46508} = \frac{2156}{73084} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1275}{34068} = \frac{1425}{38076} = \frac{3075}{82164} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1037}{42568} = \frac{2074}{85136} = \frac{2135}{87640} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1085}{32674} = \frac{2170}{65348} = \frac{2345}{70618} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1320}{67584} = \frac{1325}{67840} = \frac{1485}{76032} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1045}{28367} = \frac{1705}{46283} = \frac{2805}{76143} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1208}{46357} = \frac{1376}{52804} = \frac{2176}{83504} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1352}{40768} = \frac{2704}{81536} = \frac{2756}{83104} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1053}{26487} = \frac{2457}{61803} = \frac{3042}{76518} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1248}{35760} = \frac{1872}{53640} = \frac{3042}{87165} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1354}{20768} = \frac{2708}{41536} = \frac{5416}{83072} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1053}{28674} = \frac{1287}{35046} = \frac{2106}{57348} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1248}{37560} = \frac{1872}{56340} = \frac{2184}{65730} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1360}{74528} = \frac{1365}{74802} = \frac{1380}{75624} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1056}{38472} = \frac{1804}{65723} = \frac{2068}{75341} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1254}{38760} = \frac{1573}{48620} = \frac{2761}{85340} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1365}{28470} = \frac{1568}{32704} = \frac{1708}{35624} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1065}{43782} = \frac{1420}{58376} = \frac{2130}{87564} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1258}{47360} = \frac{1428}{53760} = \frac{1734}{65280} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1365}{40782} = \frac{1820}{54376} = \frac{2730}{81564} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1368}{20754} = \frac{2736}{41508} = \frac{5472}{83016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1402}{36578} = \frac{2103}{54867} = \frac{2804}{73156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1402}{37658} = \frac{2103}{56487} = \frac{2804}{75316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1420}{36578} = \frac{2130}{54867} = \frac{2840}{73156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1420}{37658} = \frac{2130}{56487} = \frac{2840}{75316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1425}{67830} = \frac{1645}{78302} = \frac{1745}{83062}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1428}{36750} = \frac{1802}{46375} = \frac{1836}{47250}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1456}{28730} = \frac{3472}{68510} = \frac{3640}{71825}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1457}{20863} = \frac{2867}{41053} = \frac{5734}{82106}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1458}{23760} = \frac{2187}{35640} = \frac{5346}{87120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1504}{23876} = \frac{2760}{43815} = \frac{4608}{73152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1504}{26837} = \frac{1536}{27408} = \frac{3072}{54816}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1506}{28437} = \frac{3012}{56874} = \frac{4016}{75832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1508}{23764} = \frac{2581}{40673} = \frac{3016}{47528}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1540}{26873} = \frac{1860}{32457} = \frac{3580}{62471}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1540}{27368} = \frac{2170}{38564} = \frac{2730}{48516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1540}{36872} = \frac{1820}{43576} = \frac{3640}{87152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1543}{20876} = \frac{3086}{41752} = \frac{6172}{83504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{23478} = \frac{2760}{41538} = \frac{5460}{82173}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{23784} = \frac{3120}{47568} = \frac{4680}{71352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{28437} = \frac{3120}{56874} = \frac{4160}{75832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{28743} = \frac{3120}{57486} = \frac{3720}{68541}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1562}{43807} = \frac{2046}{57381} = \frac{2310}{64785}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1563}{40287} = \frac{2084}{53716} = \frac{3126}{80574}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1564}{20378} = \frac{1870}{24365} = \frac{3128}{40756}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1564}{28037} = \frac{3128}{56074} = \frac{4352}{78016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1576}{20438} = \frac{3152}{40876} = \frac{6304}{81752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1580}{27436} = \frac{2765}{48013} = \frac{3160}{54872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1584}{32670} = \frac{1728}{35640} = \frac{3456}{71280}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1586}{27430} = \frac{3172}{54860} = \frac{3782}{65410}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1587}{23046} = \frac{1863}{27054} = \frac{3726}{54108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1587}{23460} = \frac{1863}{27540} = \frac{3864}{57120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1602}{58473} = \frac{1782}{65043} = \frac{2016}{73584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1605}{43782} = \frac{2140}{58376} = \frac{3210}{87564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1632}{40785} = \frac{2176}{54380} = \frac{3264}{81570}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1635}{40782} = \frac{2180}{54376} = \frac{3270}{81564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1643}{20785} = \frac{3286}{41570} = \frac{6572}{83140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1647}{25083} = \frac{2074}{31586} = \frac{5124}{78036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1683}{25047} = \frac{1734}{25806} = \frac{3162}{47058}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1683}{27540} = \frac{2178}{35640} = \frac{4356}{71280}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1708}{25436} = \frac{3416}{50872} = \frac{5124}{76308}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1725}{43608} = \frac{3175}{80264} = \frac{3450}{87216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1728}{43560} = \frac{3240}{81675} = \frac{3456}{87120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1736}{25048} = \frac{4032}{58176} = \frac{5068}{73124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1740}{25638} = \frac{2610}{38457} = \frac{3480}{51276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1740}{25836} = \frac{2610}{38754} = \frac{3480}{51672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1740}{36258} = \frac{2610}{54387} = \frac{3480}{72516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1740}{38256} = \frac{2610}{57384} = \frac{3480}{76512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1748}{23560} = \frac{2714}{36580} = \frac{5428}{73160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1753}{20864} = \frac{3506}{41728} = \frac{7012}{83456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1754}{20863} = \frac{3508}{41726} = \frac{7016}{83452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1756}{20384} = \frac{3512}{40768} = \frac{7024}{81536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1756}{24380} = \frac{3512}{48760} = \frac{5268}{73140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1758}{20364} = \frac{3516}{40728} = \frac{7032}{81456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1758}{20436} = \frac{3516}{40872} = \frac{5274}{61308}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1758}{23640} = \frac{3516}{47280} = \frac{6153}{82740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1760}{25438} = \frac{2640}{38157} = \frac{5280}{76314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1760}{43582} = \frac{2160}{53487} = \frac{3520}{87164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1762}{38054} = \frac{2643}{57081} = \frac{3524}{76108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1763}{20854} = \frac{3526}{41708} = \frac{7052}{83416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1763}{24805} = \frac{5246}{73810} = \frac{5418}{76230}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{20358} = \frac{3528}{40716} = \frac{7056}{81432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{20853} = \frac{3528}{41706} = \frac{7056}{83412}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1768}{23504} = \frac{2601}{34578} = \frac{3842}{51076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1782}{36054} = \frac{2673}{54081} = \frac{3564}{72108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1782}{40635} = \frac{2376}{54180} = \frac{3564}{81270}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1782}{43560} = \frac{2187}{53460} = \frac{3564}{87120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1782}{43605} = \frac{2376}{58140} = \frac{3564}{87210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1783}{62405} = \frac{1807}{63245} = \frac{2183}{76405}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1784}{20635} = \frac{3568}{41270} = \frac{7136}{82540}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1785}{20634} = \frac{3570}{41268} = \frac{7140}{82536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1785}{32640} = \frac{3507}{64128} = \frac{4158}{76032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1785}{40632} = \frac{2380}{54176} = \frac{3570}{81264}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1785}{43062} = \frac{2380}{57416} = \frac{3570}{86124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1786}{43052} = \frac{3154}{76028} = \frac{3572}{86104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1807}{25436} = \frac{3614}{50872} = \frac{5421}{76308}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1836}{25740} = \frac{2754}{38610} = \frac{3672}{51480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1853}{20764} = \frac{3706}{41528} = \frac{7412}{83056}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1854}{20763} = \frac{3708}{41526} = \frac{7416}{83052}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1860}{27435} = \frac{5028}{74163} = \frac{5036}{74281}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1862}{30457} = \frac{3486}{57021} = \frac{4018}{65723}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1863}{20754} = \frac{3726}{41508} = \frac{7452}{83016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1864}{20753} = \frac{3728}{41506} = \frac{7456}{83012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1870}{26435} = \frac{2156}{30478} = \frac{5236}{74018}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1876}{20534} = \frac{3752}{41068} = \frac{7504}{82136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2014}{36578} = \frac{3021}{54867} = \frac{4028}{73156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2014}{37658} = \frac{3021}{56487} = \frac{4028}{75316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{15786} = \frac{4068}{31572} = \frac{6102}{47358}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{17856} = \frac{3051}{26784} = \frac{4068}{35712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{18576} = \frac{3051}{27864} = \frac{4068}{37152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{18756} = \frac{4068}{37512} = \frac{8136}{75024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2036}{15784} = \frac{4072}{31568} = \frac{6108}{47352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2036}{17458} = \frac{3054}{26187} = \frac{6108}{52374}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2043}{15876} = \frac{4086}{31752} = \frac{8172}{63504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{16378} = \frac{3081}{24567} = \frac{4108}{32756}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{17638} = \frac{3081}{26457} = \frac{4108}{35276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{17836} = \frac{3081}{26754} = \frac{4108}{35672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{36178} = \frac{3081}{54267} = \frac{4108}{72356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{37618} = \frac{3081}{56427} = \frac{4108}{75236}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{37816} = \frac{3081}{56724} = \frac{4108}{75632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{38176} = \frac{3081}{57264} = \frac{4108}{76352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2058}{17346} = \frac{6174}{52038} = \frac{7182}{60534}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2058}{17436} = \frac{3087}{26154} = \frac{6174}{52308}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2064}{17835} = \frac{4128}{35670} = \frac{8256}{71340}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2067}{15834} = \frac{3657}{28014} = \frac{7314}{56028}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2076}{15438} = \frac{4152}{30876} = \frac{8304}{61752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2078}{14365} = \frac{4156}{28730} = \frac{8312}{57460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2078}{16435} = \frac{4156}{32870} = \frac{8312}{65740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2108}{36754} = \frac{2356}{41078} = \frac{4216}{73508}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2140}{36578} = \frac{3210}{54867} = \frac{4280}{73156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2140}{37658} = \frac{3210}{56487} = \frac{4280}{75316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2146}{38570} = \frac{3478}{62510} = \frac{4736}{85120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2154}{30786} = \frac{4308}{61572} = \frac{5026}{71834}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2160}{35748} = \frac{4360}{72158} = \frac{5120}{84736}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2160}{37854} = \frac{3120}{54678} = \frac{3240}{56781}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2160}{54378} = \frac{3120}{78546} = \frac{3240}{81567}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2176}{34085} = \frac{4352}{68170} = \frac{5376}{84210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2176}{38054} = \frac{3264}{57081} = \frac{4352}{76108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2178}{34056} = \frac{3267}{51084} = \frac{5016}{78432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2178}{36540} = \frac{3146}{52780} = \frac{3267}{54810}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2178}{54036} = \frac{3146}{78052} = \frac{3267}{81054}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2178}{54360} = \frac{3146}{78520} = \frac{3267}{81540}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{17586} = \frac{2470}{18563} = \frac{4680}{35172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{17856} = \frac{3510}{26784} = \frac{4680}{35712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{18576} = \frac{3510}{27864} = \frac{4680}{37152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2346}{15870} = \frac{2754}{18630} = \frac{5712}{38640}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2354}{17806} = \frac{4708}{35612} = \frac{7062}{53418}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2356}{17480} = \frac{3658}{27140} = \frac{7316}{54280}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2356}{17804} = \frac{4712}{35608} = \frac{7068}{53412}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2358}{17640} = \frac{4716}{35280} = \frac{8253}{61740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{17580} = \frac{4728}{35160} = \frac{8274}{61530}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{14058} = \frac{3564}{21087} = \frac{5184}{30672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{14580} = \frac{3564}{21870} = \frac{8712}{53460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{15048} = \frac{2538}{16074} = \frac{5076}{32148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{18054} = \frac{3564}{27081} = \frac{4752}{36108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{14065} = \frac{4018}{23765} = \frac{4756}{28130}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{16054} = \frac{3567}{24081} = \frac{4756}{32108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2380}{17456} = \frac{3570}{26184} = \frac{7140}{52368}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2403}{56871} = \frac{3024}{71568} = \frac{3186}{75402}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2405}{17836} = \frac{4810}{35672} = \frac{8325}{61740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2415}{30786} = \frac{2760}{35184} = \frac{4830}{61572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2438}{17560} = \frac{4876}{35120} = \frac{7314}{52680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2450}{13876} = \frac{3675}{20814} = \frac{7350}{41628}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2457}{13806} = \frac{5103}{28674} = \frac{7182}{40356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2460}{13578} = \frac{5740}{31682} = \frac{8610}{47523}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2460}{17835} = \frac{6012}{43587} = \frac{7068}{51243}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2460}{31857} = \frac{4160}{53872} = \frac{4380}{56721}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2475}{13806} = \frac{3025}{16874} = \frac{3850}{21476}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2475}{31680} = \frac{3270}{41856} = \frac{6540}{83712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2486}{10735} = \frac{4026}{17385} = \frac{8602}{37145}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2508}{13674} = \frac{5016}{27348} = \frac{6270}{34185}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2508}{34617} = \frac{3268}{45107} = \frac{4712}{65038}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2508}{37164} = \frac{4257}{63081} = \frac{5016}{74328}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2541}{37068} = \frac{4235}{61780} = \frac{5082}{74136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2560}{18374} = \frac{3840}{27561} = \frac{5120}{36748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2560}{37184} = \frac{3640}{52871} = \frac{5120}{74368}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2560}{37418} = \frac{3840}{56127} = \frac{5120}{74836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2560}{38174} = \frac{3840}{57261} = \frac{5120}{76348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2568}{37041} = \frac{4280}{61735} = \frac{5136}{74082}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2573}{14608} = \frac{4185}{23760} = \frac{7285}{41360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{16038} = \frac{3861}{24057} = \frac{5148}{32076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{18036} = \frac{3861}{27054} = \frac{5148}{36072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{18360} = \frac{3861}{27540} = \frac{5148}{36720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{36018} = \frac{3861}{54027} = \frac{5148}{72036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{36180} = \frac{3861}{54270} = \frac{5148}{72360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{38016} = \frac{3861}{57024} = \frac{5148}{76032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{38160} = \frac{3861}{57240} = \frac{5148}{76320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2576}{14308} = \frac{5704}{31682} = \frac{8372}{46501}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2580}{16374} = \frac{3870}{24561} = \frac{5160}{32748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2580}{17436} = \frac{3870}{26154} = \frac{5160}{34872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2580}{36174} = \frac{3870}{54261} = \frac{5160}{72348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2580}{37416} = \frac{3870}{56124} = \frac{5160}{74832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2618}{45730} = \frac{3542}{61870} = \frac{4158}{72630}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2640}{15873} = \frac{5280}{31746} = \frac{6240}{37518}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2670}{41385} = \frac{3684}{57102} = \frac{5046}{78213}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2704}{18356} = \frac{5408}{36712} = \frac{7384}{50126}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2736}{15408} = \frac{5472}{30816} = \frac{8037}{45261}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2736}{40518} = \frac{5016}{74283} = \frac{5472}{81036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2743}{15860} = \frac{5486}{31720} = \frac{6541}{37820}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2748}{16530} = \frac{6412}{38570} = \frac{6870}{41325}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2784}{15360} = \frac{5742}{31680} = \frac{8613}{47520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2786}{13405} = \frac{4378}{21065} = \frac{8756}{42130}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2835}{16740} = \frac{3024}{17856} = \frac{6048}{35712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2856}{17034} = \frac{5712}{34068} = \frac{8736}{52104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2856}{17430} = \frac{5712}{34860} = \frac{6732}{41085}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2856}{71043} = \frac{3152}{78406} = \frac{3504}{87162}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2860}{15743} = \frac{5720}{31486} = \frac{6820}{37541}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2865}{14307} = \frac{5730}{28614} = \frac{7640}{38152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2867}{13054} = \frac{5734}{26108} = \frac{6157}{28034}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2871}{36540} = \frac{3267}{41580} = \frac{5643}{71820}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2875}{13064} = \frac{3250}{14768} = \frac{6875}{31240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3021}{46587} = \frac{3762}{58014} = \frac{5643}{87021}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3024}{15687} = \frac{5872}{30461} = \frac{7104}{36852}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3024}{18765} = \frac{4368}{27105} = \frac{8736}{54210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3045}{26187} = \frac{4170}{35862} = \frac{5370}{46182}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3054}{21786} = \frac{6108}{43572} = \frac{7126}{50834}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3054}{28617} = \frac{4072}{38156} = \frac{6108}{57234}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3057}{28614} = \frac{4076}{38152} = \frac{8152}{76304}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3075}{26814} = \frac{3150}{27468} = \frac{7150}{62348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3087}{42651} = \frac{4851}{67023} = \frac{6174}{85302}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3150}{24876} = \frac{4025}{31786} = \frac{6125}{48370}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3154}{26087} = \frac{6308}{52174} = \frac{7802}{64531}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3156}{40287} = \frac{4208}{53716} = \frac{6312}{80574}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{318}{240567} = \frac{354}{267801} = \frac{504}{381276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3204}{17856} = \frac{5607}{31248} = \frac{6408}{35712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3240}{15876} = \frac{3420}{16758} = \frac{6480}{31752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3240}{17856} = \frac{5670}{31248} = \frac{6480}{35712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3248}{57610} = \frac{3480}{61725} = \frac{3712}{65840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3264}{17085} = \frac{5376}{28140} = \frac{6528}{34170}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3267}{15840} = \frac{3564}{17280} = \frac{7128}{34560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3286}{40517} = \frac{3816}{47052} = \frac{6572}{81034}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3402}{17856} = \frac{5103}{26784} = \frac{6804}{35712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3402}{18576} = \frac{5103}{27864} = \frac{6804}{37152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3416}{57820} = \frac{3782}{64015} = \frac{5124}{86730}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3420}{17856} = \frac{5130}{26784} = \frac{6840}{35712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3420}{18576} = \frac{5130}{27864} = \frac{6840}{37152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3478}{65120} = \frac{3854}{72160} = \frac{4653}{87120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3506}{17284} = \frac{7012}{34568} = \frac{8765}{43210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3516}{20784} = \frac{7032}{41568} = \frac{7618}{45032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3520}{17864} = \frac{4680}{23751} = \frac{7520}{38164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3546}{18702} = \frac{6501}{34287} = \frac{7683}{40521}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3568}{12704} = \frac{4237}{15086} = \frac{7136}{25408}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3568}{27104} = \frac{6021}{45738} = \frac{7136}{54208}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3618}{25740} = \frac{5427}{38610} = \frac{7236}{51480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3645}{21870} = \frac{4635}{27810} = \frac{6417}{38502}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3654}{21780} = \frac{5278}{31460} = \frac{5481}{32670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3654}{28710} = \frac{4158}{32670} = \frac{7182}{56430}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3675}{14280} = \frac{4305}{16728} = \frac{4725}{18360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3704}{18256} = \frac{4167}{20538} = \frac{7408}{36512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3705}{41268} = \frac{7215}{80364} = \frac{7410}{82536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3718}{25064} = \frac{6721}{45308} = \frac{7436}{50128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3720}{18456} = \frac{4185}{20763} = \frac{8370}{41526}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3740}{18256} = \frac{5610}{27384} = \frac{7480}{36512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3740}{25618} = \frac{5610}{38427} = \frac{7480}{51236}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3740}{25816} = \frac{5610}{38724} = \frac{7480}{51632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3741}{25068} = \frac{6235}{41780} = \frac{7482}{50136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3741}{50826} = \frac{4321}{58706} = \frac{6235}{84710}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3752}{41608} = \frac{5427}{60183} = \frac{7504}{83216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3756}{12048} = \frac{5634}{18072} = \frac{6573}{21084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3756}{12480} = \frac{5634}{18720} = \frac{6573}{21840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3756}{48012} = \frac{5634}{72018} = \frac{6573}{84021}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3756}{48120} = \frac{5634}{72180} = \frac{6573}{84210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3760}{14852} = \frac{3860}{15247} = \frac{5860}{23147}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3762}{14058} = \frac{4503}{16827} = \frac{5643}{21087}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3762}{18054} = \frac{5643}{27081} = \frac{7524}{36108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3765}{12048} = \frac{4275}{13680} = \frac{5760}{18432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3768}{14052} = \frac{5024}{18736} = \frac{7536}{28104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3780}{21654} = \frac{5460}{31278} = \frac{5670}{32481}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3780}{54216} = \frac{5460}{78312} = \frac{5670}{81324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3782}{16054} = \frac{5673}{24081} = \frac{7564}{32108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3784}{21560} = \frac{7568}{43120} = \frac{8127}{46305}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3816}{25740} = \frac{5724}{38610} = \frac{7632}{51480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3825}{14076} = \frac{3875}{14260} = \frac{8625}{31740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3841}{50267} = \frac{4301}{56287} = \frac{5428}{71036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3856}{12704} = \frac{5302}{17468} = \frac{6507}{21438}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3857}{21460} = \frac{6251}{34780} = \frac{8512}{47360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4026}{15873} = \frac{4270}{16835} = \frac{8052}{31746}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4032}{15786} = \frac{5376}{21048} = \frac{8064}{31572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4032}{17568} = \frac{5418}{23607} = \frac{8274}{36051}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4062}{17835} = \frac{5416}{23780} = \frac{8124}{35670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4065}{13782} = \frac{5420}{18376} = \frac{8130}{27564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4107}{23865} = \frac{5476}{31820} = \frac{6512}{37840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4108}{25376} = \frac{4503}{27816} = \frac{8137}{50264}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4172}{36058} = \frac{6734}{58201} = \frac{8162}{70543}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4176}{23580} = \frac{7308}{41265} = \frac{8352}{47160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4180}{32756} = \frac{5280}{41376} = \frac{6215}{48703}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4302}{15786} = \frac{5736}{21048} = \frac{8604}{31572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4305}{17862} = \frac{5740}{23816} = \frac{8610}{35724}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4307}{28615} = \frac{8176}{54320} = \frac{8614}{57230}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4320}{15876} = \frac{6840}{25137} = \frac{8640}{31752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4356}{17820} = \frac{5346}{21870} = \frac{8712}{35640}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4356}{21087} = \frac{7128}{34506} = \frac{8316}{40257}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4362}{17805} = \frac{5816}{23740} = \frac{8724}{35610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4365}{10782} = \frac{5820}{14376} = \frac{8730}{21564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4508}{23716} = \frac{5014}{26378} = \frac{5083}{26741}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4520}{13786} = \frac{5340}{16287} = \frac{5680}{17324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4573}{26180} = \frac{6187}{35420} = \frac{7263}{41580}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4623}{17085} = \frac{6578}{24310} = \frac{8671}{32045}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4706}{21358} = \frac{8047}{36521} = \frac{8164}{37052}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4763}{10825} = \frac{7238}{16450} = \frac{7403}{16825}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4807}{31625} = \frac{4826}{31750} = \frac{6213}{40875}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4812}{37560} = \frac{7218}{56340} = \frac{8421}{65730}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4830}{12765} = \frac{5208}{13764} = \frac{5376}{14208}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5024}{13876} = \frac{6280}{17345} = \frac{7536}{20814}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5168}{42370} = \frac{5712}{46830} = \frac{7480}{61325}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5208}{43176} = \frac{7254}{60138} = \frac{7843}{65021}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5287}{14306} = \frac{6358}{17204} = \frac{8517}{23046}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5304}{16728} = \frac{5486}{17302} = \frac{8073}{25461}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5320}{48716} = \frac{7140}{65382} = \frac{8120}{74356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5436}{21780} = \frac{7852}{31460} = \frac{8154}{32670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5472}{13680} = \frac{7362}{18405} = \frac{7452}{18630}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5642}{10738} = \frac{7068}{13452} = \frac{7254}{13806}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5746}{38012} = \frac{7631}{50482} = \frac{8632}{57104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5841}{63720} = \frac{6534}{71280} = \frac{6831}{74520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{6120}{37485} = \frac{7056}{43218} = \frac{7152}{43806}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{6372}{58410} = \frac{7128}{65340} = \frac{7452}{68310}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{6420}{57138} = \frac{7320}{65148} = \frac{8260}{73514}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{6501}{73284} = \frac{6512}{73408} = \frac{7315}{82460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{6512}{34780} = \frac{7216}{38540} = \frac{8712}{46530}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{6538}{10274} = \frac{6734}{10582} = \frac{7658}{12034}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{7035}{12864} = \frac{7420}{13568} = \frac{7560}{13824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{7463}{51802} = \frac{7803}{54162} = \frac{8721}{60534}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{8257}{14360} = \frac{8372}{14560} = \frac{8763}{15240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{368475} = \frac{132}{476850} = \frac{178}{643025}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{235768} = \frac{178}{403526} = \frac{208}{471536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{267358} = \frac{180}{462735} = \frac{208}{534716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{365728} = \frac{143}{502876} = \frac{208}{731456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{436782} = \frac{140}{582376} = \frac{210}{873564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{234865} = \frac{356}{781420} = \frac{372}{816540}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{482356} = \frac{156}{703248} = \frac{165}{743820}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{253674} = \frac{216}{507348} = \frac{270}{634185}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{273654} = \frac{216}{547308} = \frac{270}{684135}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{120}{375648} = \frac{180}{563472} = \frac{210}{657384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{120}{483756} = \frac{180}{725634} = \frac{210}{846573}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{124}{376805} = \frac{176}{534820} = \frac{248}{753610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{126}{357084} = \frac{152}{430768} = \frac{204}{578136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{128}{365704} = \frac{176}{502843} = \frac{256}{731408}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{128}{453760} = \frac{214}{758630} = \frac{237}{840165}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{130}{287456} = \frac{310}{685472} = \frac{325}{718640}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{132}{406785} = \frac{176}{542380} = \frac{264}{813570}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{132}{407865} = \frac{176}{543820} = \frac{264}{815730}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{134}{206785} = \frac{268}{413570} = \frac{536}{827140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{206784} = \frac{270}{413568} = \frac{540}{827136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{247806} = \frac{165}{302874} = \frac{210}{385476}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{406782} = \frac{180}{542376} = \frac{270}{813564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{136}{204578} = \frac{420}{631785} = \frac{572}{860431}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{264057} = \frac{184}{352076} = \frac{368}{704152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{267054} = \frac{184}{356072} = \frac{276}{534108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{270564} = \frac{184}{360752} = \frac{368}{721504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{236578} = \frac{210}{354867} = \frac{280}{473156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{237658} = \frac{210}{356487} = \frac{280}{475316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{237856} = \frac{210}{356784} = \frac{420}{713568}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{285376} = \frac{170}{346528} = \frac{430}{876512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{365782} = \frac{210}{548673} = \frac{280}{731564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{376582} = \frac{210}{564873} = \frac{280}{753164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{365780} = \frac{213}{548670} = \frac{284}{731560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{376580} = \frac{213}{564870} = \frac{284}{753160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{143}{207865} = \frac{286}{415730} = \frac{572}{831460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{143}{267085} = \frac{154}{287630} = \frac{286}{534170}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{437608} = \frac{204}{587316} = \frac{304}{875216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{287640} = \frac{257}{483160} = \frac{437}{821560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{230678} = \frac{374}{560218} = \frac{561}{840327}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{273680} = \frac{217}{385640} = \frac{273}{485160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{308726} = \frac{308}{617452} = \frac{427}{856013}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{368720} = \frac{182}{435760} = \frac{364}{871520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{237840} = \frac{312}{475680} = \frac{468}{713520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{274380} = \frac{273}{480165} = \frac{312}{548760}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{284370} = \frac{312}{568740} = \frac{416}{758320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{340287} = \frac{208}{453716} = \frac{312}{680574}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{402873} = \frac{208}{537164} = \frac{312}{805746}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{204376} = \frac{316}{408752} = \frac{632}{817504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{372406} = \frac{241}{568037} = \frac{304}{716528}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{237854} = \frac{240}{356781} = \frac{480}{713562}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{257438} = \frac{240}{386157} = \frac{320}{514876}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{258374} = \frac{240}{387561} = \frac{320}{516748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{345728} = \frac{210}{453768} = \frac{270}{583416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{374258} = \frac{240}{561387} = \frac{320}{748516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{382574} = \frac{240}{573861} = \frac{320}{765148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{162}{378054} = \frac{243}{567081} = \frac{324}{756108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{162}{430785} = \frac{216}{574380} = \frac{324}{861570}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{162}{437805} = \frac{216}{583740} = \frac{324}{875610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{164}{308752} = \frac{287}{540316} = \frac{328}{617504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{164}{385072} = \frac{165}{387420} = \frac{172}{403856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{165}{247830} = \frac{167}{250834} = \frac{257}{386014}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{165}{342870} = \frac{301}{625478} = \frac{415}{862370}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{340725} = \frac{216}{438075} = \frac{432}{876150}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{357042} = \frac{284}{603571} = \frac{412}{875603}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{308654} = \frac{210}{376845} = \frac{408}{732156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{206538} = \frac{361}{428507} = \frac{632}{750184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{250386} = \frac{318}{457602} = \frac{506}{728134}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{256038} = \frac{261}{384057} = \frac{348}{512076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{256380} = \frac{261}{384570} = \frac{348}{512760}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{258036} = \frac{261}{387054} = \frac{348}{516072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{258360} = \frac{261}{387540} = \frac{348}{516720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{360258} = \frac{261}{540387} = \frac{348}{720516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{362580} = \frac{261}{543870} = \frac{348}{725160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{380256} = \frac{261}{570384} = \frac{348}{760512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{382560} = \frac{261}{573840} = \frac{348}{765120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{175}{324086} = \frac{325}{601874} = \frac{350}{648172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{203458} = \frac{264}{305187} = \frac{528}{610374}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{204358} = \frac{352}{408716} = \frac{528}{613074}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{205384} = \frac{352}{410768} = \frac{704}{821536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{205438} = \frac{264}{308157} = \frac{352}{410876}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{234058} = \frac{264}{351087} = \frac{384}{510672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{235804} = \frac{308}{412657} = \frac{352}{471608}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{238054} = \frac{264}{357081} = \frac{352}{476108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{254380} = \frac{264}{381570} = \frac{528}{763140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{320584} = \frac{204}{371586} = \frac{284}{517306}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{380542} = \frac{264}{570813} = \frac{352}{761084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{382054} = \frac{264}{573081} = \frac{352}{764108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{423580} = \frac{308}{741265} = \frac{352}{847160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{205436} = \frac{267}{308154} = \frac{356}{410872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{234056} = \frac{267}{351084} = \frac{534}{702168}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{235406} = \frac{356}{470812} = \frac{534}{706218}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{235604} = \frac{356}{471208} = \frac{534}{706812}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{240356} = \frac{356}{480712} = \frac{534}{721068}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{240536} = \frac{356}{481072} = \frac{534}{721608}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{254036} = \frac{267}{381054} = \frac{534}{762108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{256034} = \frac{267}{384051} = \frac{534}{768102}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{360542} = \frac{267}{540813} = \frac{356}{721084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{362054} = \frac{267}{543081} = \frac{356}{724108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{235764} = \frac{360}{471528} = \frac{630}{825174}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{237456} = \frac{270}{356184} = \frac{540}{712368}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{243756} = \frac{360}{487512} = \frac{540}{731268}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{254376} = \frac{270}{381564} = \frac{540}{763128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{256374} = \frac{270}{384561} = \frac{360}{512748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{257436} = \frac{270}{386154} = \frac{360}{514872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{276435} = \frac{428}{657301} = \frac{512}{786304}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{362574} = \frac{270}{543861} = \frac{360}{725148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{374256} = \frac{270}{561384} = \frac{360}{748512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{376054} = \frac{273}{564081} = \frac{364}{752108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{203756} = \frac{368}{407512} = \frac{736}{815024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{205376} = \frac{368}{410752} = \frac{736}{821504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{256703} = \frac{328}{457601} = \frac{416}{580372}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{370256} = \frac{207}{416538} = \frac{368}{740512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{187}{236045} = \frac{418}{527630} = \frac{462}{583170}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{175864} = \frac{406}{351728} = \frac{812}{703456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{185764} = \frac{406}{371528} = \frac{812}{743056}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{136578} = \frac{408}{273156} = \frac{630}{421785}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{136758} = \frac{408}{273516} = \frac{816}{547032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{157836} = \frac{408}{315672} = \frac{612}{473508}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{158763} = \frac{408}{317526} = \frac{804}{625713}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{175863} = \frac{408}{351726} = \frac{816}{703452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{176358} = \frac{408}{352716} = \frac{816}{705432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{183756} = \frac{408}{367512} = \frac{816}{735024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{185763} = \frac{408}{371526} = \frac{816}{743052}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{136784} = \frac{410}{273568} = \frac{820}{547136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{178364} = \frac{410}{356728} = \frac{820}{713456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{178634} = \frac{410}{357268} = \frac{820}{714536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{175384} = \frac{412}{350768} = \frac{824}{701536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{183754} = \frac{412}{367508} = \frac{824}{735016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{187534} = \frac{412}{375068} = \frac{824}{750136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{713584} = \frac{234}{810576} = \frac{236}{817504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{136754} = \frac{416}{273508} = \frac{832}{547016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{175364} = \frac{416}{350728} = \frac{832}{701456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{176354} = \frac{416}{352708} = \frac{832}{705416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{347865} = \frac{216}{357804} = \frac{432}{715608}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{367584} = \frac{275}{481360} = \frac{420}{735168}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{365780} = \frac{321}{548670} = \frac{428}{731560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{376580} = \frac{321}{564870} = \frac{428}{753160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{384076} = \frac{320}{571648} = \frac{430}{768152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{307854} = \frac{432}{615708} = \frac{504}{718326}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{357480} = \frac{436}{721580} = \frac{512}{847360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{370548} = \frac{270}{463185} = \frac{342}{586701}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{378540} = \frac{312}{546780} = \frac{324}{567810}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{540378} = \frac{312}{780546} = \frac{324}{810567}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{217}{634508} = \frac{235}{687140} = \frac{245}{716380}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{218}{346075} = \frac{276}{438150} = \frac{402}{638175}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{218}{376054} = \frac{327}{564081} = \frac{436}{752108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{165784} = \frac{520}{374816} = \frac{730}{526184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{174685} = \frac{672}{510384} = \frac{716}{543802}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{406875} = \frac{418}{736250} = \frac{462}{813750}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{604758} = \frac{285}{746130} = \frac{315}{824670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{165087} = \frac{456}{321708} = \frac{728}{513604}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{175860} = \frac{247}{185630} = \frac{468}{351720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{178056} = \frac{351}{267084} = \frac{702}{534168}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{178560} = \frac{351}{267840} = \frac{468}{357120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{185760} = \frac{351}{278640} = \frac{468}{371520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{586170} = \frac{243}{608715} = \frac{342}{856710}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{235}{106784} = \frac{325}{147680} = \frac{470}{213568}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{236}{154780} = \frac{413}{270865} = \frac{826}{541730}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{174560} = \frac{357}{261840} = \frac{714}{523680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{176054} = \frac{357}{264081} = \frac{476}{352108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{137568} = \frac{305}{174826} = \frac{480}{275136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{137856} = \frac{285}{163704} = \frac{720}{413568}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{176358} = \frac{480}{352716} = \frac{840}{617253}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{351876} = \frac{360}{527814} = \frac{420}{615783}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{387516} = \frac{360}{581274} = \frac{420}{678153}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{135780} = \frac{574}{316820} = \frac{861}{475230}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{318570} = \frac{416}{538720} = \frac{438}{567210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{178036} = \frac{381}{267054} = \frac{762}{534108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{174038} = \frac{384}{261057} = \frac{512}{348076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{178034} = \frac{384}{267051} = \frac{768}{534102}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{178304} = \frac{682}{475013} = \frac{742}{516803}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{180374} = \frac{384}{270561} = \frac{512}{360748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{183740} = \frac{384}{275610} = \frac{512}{367480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{310784} = \frac{372}{451608} = \frac{417}{506238}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{371840} = \frac{364}{528710} = \frac{512}{743680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{374018} = \frac{384}{561027} = \frac{512}{748036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{374180} = \frac{384}{561270} = \frac{512}{748360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{380174} = \frac{384}{570261} = \frac{512}{760348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{381740} = \frac{384}{572610} = \frac{512}{763480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{143706} = \frac{378}{210546} = \frac{572}{318604}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{160374} = \frac{387}{240561} = \frac{516}{320748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{163740} = \frac{387}{245610} = \frac{516}{327480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{174036} = \frac{387}{261054} = \frac{516}{348072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{174360} = \frac{387}{261540} = \frac{516}{348720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{360174} = \frac{387}{540261} = \frac{516}{720348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{361740} = \frac{387}{542610} = \frac{516}{723480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{374016} = \frac{387}{561024} = \frac{516}{748032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{374160} = \frac{387}{561240} = \frac{516}{748320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{260}{153478} = \frac{460}{271538} = \frac{540}{318762}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{260}{157384} = \frac{520}{314768} = \frac{715}{432806}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{260}{158743} = \frac{520}{317486} = \frac{620}{378541}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{260}{174538} = \frac{570}{382641} = \frac{780}{523614}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{138057} = \frac{352}{184076} = \frac{704}{368152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{153780} = \frac{306}{178245} = \frac{816}{475320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{158730} = \frac{528}{317460} = \frac{624}{375180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{173085} = \frac{384}{251760} = \frac{528}{346170}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{371580} = \frac{528}{743160} = \frac{602}{847315}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{265}{370841} = \frac{305}{426817} = \frac{530}{741682}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{267}{138054} = \frac{356}{184072} = \frac{534}{276108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{267}{340158} = \frac{501}{638274} = \frac{645}{821730}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{268}{135407} = \frac{536}{270814} = \frac{724}{365801}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{268}{410375} = \frac{308}{471625} = \frac{412}{630875}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{271}{348506} = \frac{485}{623710} = \frac{563}{724018}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{185406} = \frac{385}{261470} = \frac{546}{370812}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{406185} = \frac{378}{562410} = \frac{546}{812370}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{541086} = \frac{354}{701628} = \frac{435}{862170}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{274}{136508} = \frac{548}{273016} = \frac{685}{341270}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{145376} = \frac{325}{168740} = \frac{340}{176528}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{284}{153706} = \frac{568}{307412} = \frac{710}{384265}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{104367} = \frac{465}{170283} = \frac{765}{280143}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{147630} = \frac{582}{301476} = \frac{678}{351204}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{163740} = \frac{437}{251068} = \frac{874}{502136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{164307} = \frac{570}{328614} = \frac{760}{438152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{174306} = \frac{570}{348612} = \frac{675}{412830}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{157430} = \frac{572}{314860} = \frac{682}{375410}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{158672} = \frac{342}{178506} = \frac{684}{357012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{176852} = \frac{528}{307164} = \frac{564}{328107}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{217856} = \frac{361}{258704} = \frac{608}{435712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{217854} = \frac{612}{435708} = \frac{714}{508326}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{425187} = \frac{416}{578032} = \frac{612}{850374}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{307}{615842} = \frac{417}{836502} = \frac{435}{872610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{315}{240786} = \frac{360}{275184} = \frac{630}{481572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{320}{156784} = \frac{480}{235176} = \frac{860}{421357}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{320}{178564} = \frac{560}{312487} = \frac{640}{357128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{320}{417856} = \frac{560}{731248} = \frac{640}{835712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{158760} = \frac{342}{167580} = \frac{648}{317520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{178560} = \frac{567}{312480} = \frac{648}{357120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{460187} = \frac{425}{601783} = \frac{450}{637182}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{187450} = \frac{762}{438150} = \frac{803}{461725}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{178562} = \frac{510}{267843} = \frac{680}{357124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{185762} = \frac{510}{278643} = \frac{680}{371524}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{217856} = \frac{510}{326784} = \frac{680}{435712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{218576} = \frac{510}{327864} = \frac{680}{437152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{581672} = \frac{420}{718536} = \frac{475}{812630}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{178560} = \frac{513}{267840} = \frac{684}{357120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{180576} = \frac{513}{270864} = \frac{576}{304128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{185760} = \frac{513}{278640} = \frac{684}{371520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{205178} = \frac{604}{358172} = \frac{726}{430518}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{178640} = \frac{468}{237510} = \frac{752}{381640}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{127086} = \frac{356}{127804} = \frac{586}{210374}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{178062} = \frac{538}{270614} = \frac{708}{356124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{358}{207461} = \frac{526}{304817} = \frac{756}{438102}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{174258} = \frac{540}{261387} = \frac{720}{348516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{182574} = \frac{540}{273861} = \frac{720}{365148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{217854} = \frac{520}{314678} = \frac{540}{326781}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{257418} = \frac{540}{386127} = \frac{720}{514836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{258174} = \frac{540}{387261} = \frac{720}{516348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{542178} = \frac{520}{783146} = \frac{540}{813267}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{362}{178054} = \frac{543}{267081} = \frac{724}{356108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{364}{178052} = \frac{728}{356104} = \frac{871}{426053}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{365}{128407} = \frac{485}{170623} = \frac{730}{256814}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{368}{125704} = \frac{506}{172843} = \frac{736}{251408}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{368}{257140} = \frac{468}{327015} = \frac{736}{514280}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{160258} = \frac{561}{240387} = \frac{748}{320516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{180256} = \frac{561}{270384} = \frac{748}{360512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{182560} = \frac{561}{273840} = \frac{748}{365120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{256018} = \frac{561}{384027} = \frac{748}{512036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{256180} = \frac{561}{384270} = \frac{748}{512360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{258016} = \frac{561}{387024} = \frac{748}{516032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{258160} = \frac{561}{387240} = \frac{748}{516320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{180542} = \frac{564}{270813} = \frac{752}{361084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{182054} = \frac{564}{273081} = \frac{752}{364108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{184052} = \frac{716}{350482} = \frac{752}{368104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{205418} = \frac{564}{308127} = \frac{752}{410836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{214508} = \frac{470}{268135} = \frac{614}{350287}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{218054} = \frac{564}{327081} = \frac{752}{436108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{140562} = \frac{567}{210843} = \frac{826}{307154}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{160542} = \frac{567}{240813} = \frac{756}{321084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{162054} = \frac{567}{243081} = \frac{756}{324108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{205416} = \frac{567}{308124} = \frac{756}{410832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{216405} = \frac{756}{432810} = \frac{810}{463725}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{216540} = \frac{546}{312780} = \frac{567}{324810}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{540162} = \frac{567}{810243} = \frac{576}{823104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{540216} = \frac{546}{780312} = \frac{567}{810324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{542160} = \frac{546}{783120} = \frac{567}{813240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{162574} = \frac{570}{243861} = \frac{760}{325148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{174256} = \frac{570}{261384} = \frac{760}{348512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{241756} = \frac{760}{483512} = \frac{860}{547132}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{245176} = \frac{580}{374216} = \frac{870}{561324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{256174} = \frac{570}{384261} = \frac{760}{512348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{257416} = \frac{570}{386124} = \frac{760}{514832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{264157} = \frac{520}{361478} = \frac{760}{528314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{382}{176054} = \frac{573}{264081} = \frac{764}{352108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{386}{421705} = \frac{642}{701385} = \frac{742}{810635}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{403}{261857} = \frac{702}{456138} = \frac{806}{523714}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{136782} = \frac{540}{182376} = \frac{810}{273564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{163782} = \frac{540}{218376} = \frac{810}{327564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{178362} = \frac{540}{237816} = \frac{810}{356724}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{178632} = \frac{540}{238176} = \frac{810}{357264}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{405}{326187} = \frac{580}{467132} = \frac{810}{652374}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{408}{253716} = \frac{612}{380574} = \frac{816}{507432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{408}{257136} = \frac{612}{385704} = \frac{765}{482130}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{356782} = \frac{560}{487312} = \frac{820}{713564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{413}{265087} = \frac{784}{503216} = \frac{826}{530174}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{253708} = \frac{456}{278103} = \frac{832}{507416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{358072} = \frac{508}{437261} = \frac{624}{537108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{417}{256038} = \frac{834}{512076} = \frac{843}{517602}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{426}{173805} = \frac{568}{231740} = \frac{852}{347610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{427}{156038} = \frac{483}{176502} = \frac{854}{312076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{427}{308651} = \frac{671}{485023} = \frac{854}{617302}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{427}{316085} = \frac{732}{541860} = \frac{854}{632170}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{427}{318605} = \frac{732}{546180} = \frac{854}{637210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{427}{381605} = \frac{732}{654180} = \frac{854}{763210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{432}{106785} = \frac{576}{142380} = \frac{864}{213570}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{432}{158760} = \frac{684}{251370} = \frac{864}{317520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{432}{160785} = \frac{576}{214380} = \frac{864}{321570}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{432}{165780} = \frac{604}{231785} = \frac{820}{314675}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{432}{178605} = \frac{576}{238140} = \frac{864}{357210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{435}{106782} = \frac{580}{142376} = \frac{870}{213564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{435}{128760} = \frac{543}{160728} = \frac{835}{247160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{435}{160782} = \frac{580}{214376} = \frac{870}{321564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{435}{178062} = \frac{580}{237416} = \frac{870}{356124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{435}{261708} = \frac{725}{436180} = \frac{870}{523416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{436}{128075} = \frac{472}{138650} = \frac{804}{236175}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{436}{170258} = \frac{784}{306152} = \frac{872}{340516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{438}{206517} = \frac{652}{307418} = \frac{658}{310247}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{438}{261705} = \frac{706}{421835} = \frac{876}{523410}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{451}{372608} = \frac{638}{527104} = \frac{704}{581632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{456}{137028} = \frac{834}{250617} = \frac{870}{261435}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{456}{173280} = \frac{651}{247380} = \frac{753}{286140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{460}{513728} = \frac{730}{815264} = \frac{745}{832016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{470}{162385} = \frac{506}{174823} = \frac{670}{231485}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{123756} = \frac{720}{185634} = \frac{840}{216573}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{375612} = \frac{720}{563418} = \frac{840}{657321}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{485}{326017} = \frac{715}{480623} = \frac{780}{524316} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{508}{312674} = \frac{670}{412385} = \frac{846}{520713} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{527}{431086} = \frac{628}{513704} = \frac{785}{642130} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{532}{487160} = \frac{714}{653820} = \frac{812}{743560} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{147802} = \frac{672}{185304} = \frac{860}{237145} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{216378} = \frac{780}{312546} = \frac{810}{324567} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{217836} = \frac{780}{314652} = \frac{810}{326754} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{362178} = \frac{780}{523146} = \frac{810}{543267} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{540}{378216} = \frac{780}{546312} = \frac{810}{567324} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{547}{102836} = \frac{658}{123704} = \frac{765}{143820} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{570}{264138} = \frac{760}{352184} = \frac{780}{361452} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{580}{462173} = \frac{780}{621543} = \frac{820}{653417} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{612}{308754} = \frac{678}{342051} = \frac{756}{381402} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{642}{571380} = \frac{732}{651480} = \frac{826}{735140} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{130572} = \frac{672}{135408} = \frac{830}{167245} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{680}{134572} = \frac{780}{154362} = \frac{830}{164257} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{680}{341275} = \frac{760}{381425} = \frac{832}{417560} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{2348765} = \frac{16}{3758024} = \frac{32}{7516048} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{2485376} = \frac{15}{3728064} = \frac{30}{7456128} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{3056874} = \frac{16}{4075832} = \frac{30}{7642185} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{3058764} = \frac{16}{4078352} = \frac{32}{8156704} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{3756048} = \frac{18}{5634072} = \frac{21}{6573084} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{3756480} = \frac{18}{5634720} = \frac{21}{6573840} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{4067835} = \frac{16}{5423780} = \frac{24}{8135670} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{4078365} = \frac{16}{5437820} = \frac{24}{8156730} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{4306785} = \frac{16}{5742380} = \frac{24}{8613570} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{4307865} = \frac{16}{5743820} = \frac{24}{8615730} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{4367805} = \frac{16}{5823740} = \frac{24}{8735610} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{4378065} = \frac{16}{5837420} = \frac{24}{8756130} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{4803756} = \frac{18}{7205634} = \frac{21}{8406573} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{4837560} = \frac{18}{7256340} = \frac{21}{8465730} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2067845} = \frac{24}{3817560} = \frac{48}{7635120} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2076854} = \frac{26}{4153708} = \frac{52}{8307416} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2086754} = \frac{26}{4173508} = \frac{52}{8347016} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2604875} = \frac{34}{6812750} = \frac{38}{7614250} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2035768} = \frac{28}{4071536} = \frac{56}{8143072} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2036578} = \frac{21}{3054867} = \frac{28}{4073156} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2036758} = \frac{28}{4073516} = \frac{56}{8147032} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2037658} = \frac{21}{3056487} = \frac{28}{4075316} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2057836} = \frac{21}{3086754} = \frac{42}{6173508} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2067835} = \frac{28}{4135670} = \frac{56}{8271340} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2075368} = \frac{28}{4150736} = \frac{56}{8301472} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2076853} = \frac{28}{4153706} = \frac{56}{8307412} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2086753} = \frac{28}{4173506} = \frac{56}{8347012} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2365780} = \frac{21}{3548670} = \frac{28}{4731560} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2376580} = \frac{21}{3564870} = \frac{28}{4753160} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2378560} = \frac{21}{3567840} = \frac{42}{7135680} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2736508} = \frac{28}{5473016} = \frac{35}{6841270} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2805376} = \frac{17}{3406528} = \frac{27}{5410368} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2836750} = \frac{18}{3647250} = \frac{41}{8307625} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2853760} = \frac{17}{3465280} = \frac{43}{8765120} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{3657802} = \frac{21}{5486703} = \frac{28}{7315604} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{3657820} = \frac{21}{5486730} = \frac{28}{7315640} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{3765802} = \frac{21}{5648703} = \frac{28}{7531604} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{3765820} = \frac{21}{5648730} = \frac{28}{7531640} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{5087236} = \frac{18}{6540732} = \frac{21}{7630854} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{2078643} = \frac{30}{4157286} = \frac{60}{8314572} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{2348760} = \frac{24}{3758016} = \frac{48}{7516032} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2530874} = \frac{32}{5061748} = \frac{40}{6327185} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3742508} = \frac{20}{4678135} = \frac{32}{7485016} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{2843706} = \frac{30}{5687412} = \frac{40}{7583216} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2574038} = \frac{24}{3861057} = \frac{32}{5148076} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3742580} = \frac{24}{5613870} = \frac{32}{7485160} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{2864307} = \frac{30}{5728614} = \frac{40}{7638152} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2574380} = \frac{24}{3861570} = \frac{32}{5148760} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3780542} = \frac{24}{5670813} = \frac{32}{7561084} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{4063782} = \frac{20}{5418376} = \frac{30}{8127564} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2580374} = \frac{24}{3870561} = \frac{32}{5160748} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3782054} = \frac{24}{5673081} = \frac{32}{7564108} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{4073826} = \frac{20}{5431768} = \frac{30}{8147652} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2583740} = \frac{24}{3875610} = \frac{32}{5167480} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3802574} = \frac{24}{5703861} = \frac{32}{7605148} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{4078362} = \frac{20}{5437816} = \frac{30}{8156724} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2730854} = \frac{32}{5461708} = \frac{40}{6827135} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3825740} = \frac{24}{5738610} = \frac{32}{7651480} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{4078632} = \frac{20}{5438176} = \frac{30}{8157264} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2735408} = \frac{32}{5470816} = \frac{47}{8035261} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{4308752} = \frac{28}{7540316} = \frac{32}{8617504} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{4307862} = \frac{20}{5743816} = \frac{30}{8615724} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2835704} = \frac{32}{5671408} = \frac{34}{6025871} & \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{2046358} = \frac{43}{5176082} = \frac{65}{7824310} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{4360782} = \frac{20}{5814376} = \frac{30}{8721564} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2850734} = \frac{32}{5701468} = \frac{40}{7126835} & \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{2543608} = \frac{34}{5087216} = \frac{51}{7630824} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15}{4378062} = \frac{20}{5837416} = \frac{30}{8756124} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2853074} = \frac{32}{5706148} = \frac{40}{7132685} & \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{2856034} = \frac{34}{5712068} = \frac{52}{8736104} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2035784} = \frac{32}{4071568} = \frac{48}{6107352} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2873054} = \frac{32}{5746108} = \frac{40}{7182635} & \blacktriangleright \frac{17}{3264085} = \frac{28}{5376140} = \frac{34}{6528170} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2043758} = \frac{32}{4087516} = \frac{64}{8175032} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3052874} = \frac{32}{6105748} = \frac{40}{7632185} & \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2034576} = \frac{27}{3051864} = \frac{54}{6103728} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2054378} = \frac{24}{3081567} = \frac{32}{4108756} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3072854} = \frac{32}{6145708} = \frac{40}{7682135} & \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2035764} = \frac{36}{4071528} = \frac{72}{8143056} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2057834} = \frac{24}{3086751} = \frac{48}{6173502} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3087524} = \frac{28}{5403167} = \frac{32}{6175048} & \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2043576} = \frac{36}{4087152} = \frac{54}{6130728} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2075438} = \frac{32}{4150876} = \frac{64}{8301752} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3287054} = \frac{32}{6574108} = \frac{40}{8217635} & \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2054376} = \frac{27}{3081564} = \frac{36}{4108752} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2087543} = \frac{32}{4175086} = \frac{64}{8350172} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3457280} = \frac{21}{4537680} = \frac{27}{5834160} & \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2057436} = \frac{27}{3086154} = \frac{54}{6172308} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2378054} = \frac{24}{3567081} = \frac{32}{4756108} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3582704} = \frac{27}{6045813} = \frac{32}{7165408} & \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2075364} = \frac{36}{4150728} = \frac{72}{8301456} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2378540} = \frac{24}{3567810} = \frac{48}{7135620} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3705428} = \frac{20}{4631785} = \frac{32}{7410856} & \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2076354} = \frac{36}{4152708} = \frac{72}{8305416} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2508734} = \frac{32}{5017468} = \frac{40}{6271835} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3740258} = \frac{24}{5610387} = \frac{32}{7480516} & \blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2357640} = \frac{36}{4715280} = \frac{63}{8251740} \end{array}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2374560} = \frac{27}{3561840} = \frac{54}{7123680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2376054} = \frac{27}{3564081} = \frac{36}{4752108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2403576} = \frac{36}{4807152} = \frac{38}{5074216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2437560} = \frac{36}{4875120} = \frac{54}{7312680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2543607} = \frac{36}{5087214} = \frac{54}{7630821}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2543760} = \frac{27}{3815640} = \frac{54}{7631280}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2560374} = \frac{27}{3840561} = \frac{36}{5120748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2563740} = \frac{27}{3845610} = \frac{36}{5127480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2574036} = \frac{27}{3861054} = \frac{36}{5148072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2574360} = \frac{27}{3861540} = \frac{36}{5148720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3602574} = \frac{27}{5403861} = \frac{36}{7205148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3625740} = \frac{27}{5438610} = \frac{36}{7251480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3740256} = \frac{27}{5610384} = \frac{36}{7480512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3742560} = \frac{27}{5613840} = \frac{36}{7485120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3760542} = \frac{27}{5640813} = \frac{36}{7521084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3762054} = \frac{27}{5643081} = \frac{36}{7524108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3764052} = \frac{24}{5018736} = \frac{36}{7528104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{1356784} = \frac{40}{2713568} = \frac{80}{5427136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{1437658} = \frac{30}{2156487} = \frac{40}{2875316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{1438576} = \frac{30}{2157864} = \frac{60}{4315728}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{1458376} = \frac{30}{2187564} = \frac{60}{4375128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{1578643} = \frac{40}{3157286} = \frac{80}{6314572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{1584376} = \frac{40}{3168752} = \frac{60}{4753128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{1643578} = \frac{40}{3287156} = \frac{80}{6574312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{1783564} = \frac{40}{3567128} = \frac{80}{7134256}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{1857634} = \frac{30}{2786451} = \frac{40}{3715268}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{3417856} = \frac{30}{5126784} = \frac{40}{6835712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{3418576} = \frac{30}{5127864} = \frac{40}{6837152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{3657814} = \frac{30}{5486721} = \frac{40}{7315628}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{3765814} = \frac{30}{5648721} = \frac{40}{7531628}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1587046} = \frac{27}{1863054} = \frac{54}{3726108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1657840} = \frac{52}{3748160} = \frac{73}{5261840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1387056} = \frac{27}{1560438} = \frac{54}{3120876}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1753086} = \frac{48}{3506172} = \frac{60}{4382715}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1763580} = \frac{48}{3527160} = \frac{84}{6172530}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1780356} = \frac{48}{3560712} = \frac{72}{5341068}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1780536} = \frac{48}{3561072} = \frac{72}{5341608}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{3078516} = \frac{48}{6157032} = \frac{56}{7183204}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{3510768} = \frac{48}{7021536} = \frac{51}{7460382}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{3518760} = \frac{36}{5278140} = \frac{42}{6157830}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{3578016} = \frac{48}{7156032} = \frac{51}{7603284}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{3580176} = \frac{45}{6712830} = \frac{48}{7160352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{3875160} = \frac{36}{5812740} = \frac{42}{6781530}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25}{1473860} = \frac{40}{2358176} = \frac{80}{4716352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{1304758} = \frac{47}{2358601} = \frac{57}{2860431}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{1304875} = \frac{68}{3412750} = \frac{76}{3814250}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{1380457} = \frac{54}{2867103} = \frac{76}{4035182}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{1534780} = \frac{46}{2715380} = \frac{54}{3187620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{1537084} = \frac{52}{3074168} = \frac{65}{3842710}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{1587430} = \frac{52}{3174860} = \frac{62}{3785410}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{1745380} = \frac{57}{3826410} = \frac{78}{5236140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26}{1840735} = \frac{36}{2548710} = \frac{52}{3681470}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{1380564} = \frac{36}{1840752} = \frac{72}{3681504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{1430865} = \frac{54}{2861730} = \frac{72}{3815640}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{1643085} = \frac{54}{3286170} = \frac{72}{4381560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{1836405} = \frac{54}{3672810} = \frac{84}{5713260}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{1854306} = \frac{37}{2541086} = \frac{54}{3708612}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{3058614} = \frac{36}{4078152} = \frac{72}{8156304}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{1053674} = \frac{56}{2107348} = \frac{70}{2634185}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{1073654} = \frac{56}{2147308} = \frac{70}{2684135}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{1356740} = \frac{56}{2713480} = \frac{83}{4021765}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{1365074} = \frac{56}{2730148} = \frac{70}{3412685}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{1374506} = \frac{30}{1472685} = \frac{32}{1570864}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{1405376} = \frac{34}{1706528} = \frac{54}{2710368}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{1507436} = \frac{56}{3014872} = \frac{61}{3284057}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{1570436} = \frac{51}{2860437} = \frac{56}{3140872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{4017356} = \frac{53}{7604281} = \frac{56}{8034712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{4137056} = \frac{41}{6057832} = \frac{52}{7683104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30}{1256874} = \frac{40}{1675832} = \frac{60}{2513748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30}{1486725} = \frac{72}{3568140} = \frac{82}{4063715}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30}{1648725} = \frac{32}{1758640} = \frac{64}{3517280}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30}{1784265} = \frac{70}{4163285} = \frac{76}{4520138}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1748560} = \frac{38}{2076415} = \frac{76}{4152830}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1750864} = \frac{64}{3501728} = \frac{76}{4158302}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1765840} = \frac{34}{1876205} = \frac{68}{3752410}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1785604} = \frac{56}{3124807} = \frac{64}{3571208}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1785640} = \frac{56}{3124870} = \frac{64}{3571280}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1804576} = \frac{37}{2086541} = \frac{51}{2876043}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{4178560} = \frac{56}{7312480} = \frac{64}{8357120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{4185760} = \frac{63}{8240715} = \frac{64}{8371520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{1275068} = \frac{38}{1425076} = \frac{82}{3075164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{1785602} = \frac{51}{2678403} = \frac{68}{3571204}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{1785620} = \frac{51}{2678430} = \frac{68}{3571240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{1857602} = \frac{51}{2786403} = \frac{68}{3715204}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{1857620} = \frac{51}{2786430} = \frac{68}{3715240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{1876052} = \frac{37}{2041586} = \frac{68}{3752104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2017856} = \frac{51}{3026784} = \frac{68}{4035712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2018576} = \frac{51}{3027864} = \frac{68}{4037152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2176085} = \frac{68}{4352170} = \frac{84}{5376210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2178560} = \frac{51}{3267840} = \frac{68}{4357120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2185760} = \frac{51}{3278640} = \frac{68}{4371520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2578016} = \frac{51}{3867024} = \frac{53}{4018672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2687105} = \frac{36}{2845170} = \frac{68}{5374210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35}{2476810} = \frac{71}{5024386} = \frac{81}{5732046}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35}{2786140} = \frac{58}{4617032} = \frac{68}{5413072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1457802} = \frac{54}{2186703} = \frac{70}{2834615}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1740258} = \frac{54}{2610387} = \frac{72}{3480516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1742580} = \frac{54}{2613870} = \frac{72}{3485160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1752480} = \frac{71}{3456280} = \frac{87}{4235160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1780542} = \frac{54}{2670813} = \frac{72}{3561084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1782054} = \frac{54}{2673081} = \frac{72}{3564108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1802574} = \frac{54}{2703861} = \frac{72}{3605148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1825740} = \frac{54}{2738610} = \frac{72}{3651480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2054178} = \frac{54}{3081267} = \frac{72}{4108356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2178540} = \frac{52}{3146780} = \frac{54}{3267810}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2487150} = \frac{46}{3178025} = \frac{70}{4836125}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2574018} = \frac{54}{3861027} = \frac{72}{5148036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2574180} = \frac{54}{3861270} = \frac{72}{5148360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2580174} = \frac{54}{3870261} = \frac{72}{5160348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2581740} = \frac{54}{3872610} = \frac{72}{5163480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{4280571} = \frac{52}{6183047} = \frac{60}{7134285}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{5402178} = \frac{52}{7803146} = \frac{54}{8103267}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{5421780} = \frac{52}{7831460} = \frac{54}{8132670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{2856104} = \frac{48}{3705216} = \frac{71}{5480632}$$

- | | | |
|--|--|--|
| ▶ $\frac{38}{1602574} = \frac{57}{2403861} = \frac{76}{3205148}$ | ▶ $\frac{41}{3567820} = \frac{56}{4873120} = \frac{82}{7135640}$ | ▶ $\frac{48}{1203756} = \frac{72}{1805634} = \frac{84}{2106573}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{1625740} = \frac{57}{2438610} = \frac{76}{3251480}$ | ▶ $\frac{41}{3620587} = \frac{53}{4680271} = \frac{72}{6358104}$ | ▶ $\frac{48}{1237560} = \frac{72}{1856340} = \frac{84}{2165730}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{1740256} = \frac{57}{2610384} = \frac{76}{3480512}$ | ▶ $\frac{42}{1067835} = \frac{56}{1423780} = \frac{84}{2135670}$ | ▶ $\frac{48}{2503176} = \frac{54}{2816073} = \frac{58}{3024671}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{1742560} = \frac{57}{2613840} = \frac{76}{3485120}$ | ▶ $\frac{42}{1075368} = \frac{84}{2150736} = \frac{85}{2176340}$ | ▶ $\frac{48}{3756012} = \frac{72}{5634018} = \frac{84}{6573021}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{1760542} = \frac{57}{2640813} = \frac{76}{3521084}$ | ▶ $\frac{42}{1078365} = \frac{56}{1437820} = \frac{84}{2156730}$ | ▶ $\frac{48}{3756120} = \frac{72}{5634180} = \frac{84}{6573210}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{1762054} = \frac{57}{2643081} = \frac{76}{3524108}$ | ▶ $\frac{42}{1306785} = \frac{56}{1742380} = \frac{84}{2613570}$ | ▶ $\frac{51}{6708234} = \frac{54}{7102836} = \frac{61}{8023574}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{2054176} = \frac{57}{3081264} = \frac{76}{4108352}$ | ▶ $\frac{42}{1307865} = \frac{56}{1743820} = \frac{84}{2615730}$ | ▶ $\frac{54}{2160378} = \frac{78}{3120546} = \frac{81}{3240567}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{2176054} = \frac{57}{3264081} = \frac{76}{4352108}$ | ▶ $\frac{42}{1367805} = \frac{56}{1823740} = \frac{84}{2735610}$ | ▶ $\frac{54}{2163780} = \frac{78}{3125460} = \frac{81}{3245670}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{2417560} = \frac{76}{4835120} = \frac{86}{5471320}$ | ▶ $\frac{42}{1378065} = \frac{56}{1837420} = \frac{84}{2756130}$ | ▶ $\frac{54}{2178036} = \frac{78}{3146052} = \frac{81}{3267054}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{2451760} = \frac{58}{3742160} = \frac{87}{5613240}$ | ▶ $\frac{42}{1607835} = \frac{56}{2143780} = \frac{84}{3215670}$ | ▶ $\frac{54}{2178360} = \frac{78}{3146520} = \frac{81}{3267540}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{2541706} = \frac{48}{3210576} = \frac{76}{5083412}$ | ▶ $\frac{42}{1630785} = \frac{56}{2174380} = \frac{84}{3261570}$ | ▶ $\frac{54}{3602178} = \frac{78}{5203146} = \frac{81}{5403267}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{2560174} = \frac{57}{3840261} = \frac{76}{5120348}$ | ▶ $\frac{42}{1637805} = \frac{56}{2183740} = \frac{84}{3275610}$ | ▶ $\frac{54}{3621780} = \frac{78}{5231460} = \frac{81}{5432670}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{2561740} = \frac{57}{3842610} = \frac{76}{5123480}$ | ▶ $\frac{42}{1780635} = \frac{56}{2374180} = \frac{84}{3561270}$ | ▶ $\frac{54}{3780216} = \frac{78}{5460312} = \frac{81}{5670324}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{2574016} = \frac{57}{3861024} = \frac{76}{5148032}$ | ▶ $\frac{42}{1783605} = \frac{56}{2378140} = \frac{84}{3567210}$ | ▶ $\frac{54}{3782160} = \frac{78}{5463120} = \frac{81}{5673240}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{2574160} = \frac{57}{3861240} = \frac{76}{5148320}$ | ▶ $\frac{42}{1786305} = \frac{56}{2381740} = \frac{84}{3572610}$ | ▶ $\frac{56}{3417820} = \frac{62}{3784015} = \frac{84}{5126730}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{2641570} = \frac{52}{3614780} = \frac{76}{5283140}$ | ▶ $\frac{42}{3107685} = \frac{52}{3847610} = \frac{84}{6215370}$ | ▶ $\frac{57}{2641380} = \frac{76}{3521840} = \frac{78}{3614520}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{38}{4126705} = \frac{74}{8036215} = \frac{76}{8253410}$ | ▶ $\frac{43}{1278605} = \frac{58}{1724630} = \frac{62}{1843570}$ | ▶ $\frac{68}{1345720} = \frac{78}{1543620} = \frac{83}{1642570}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{40}{1785632} = \frac{70}{3124856} = \frac{80}{3571264}$ | ▶ $\frac{43}{1528607} = \frac{48}{1706352} = \frac{86}{3057214}$ | ▶ $\frac{68}{2543710} = \frac{82}{3067415} = \frac{86}{3217045}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{40}{3217856} = \frac{70}{5631248} = \frac{80}{6435712}$ | ▶ $\frac{47}{1803625} = \frac{61}{2340875} = \frac{82}{3146750}$ | |
| ▶ $\frac{41}{2067835} = \frac{43}{2168705} = \frac{82}{4135670}$ | ▶ $\frac{47}{6021358} = \frac{58}{7430612} = \frac{65}{8327410}$ | |

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{1}{20375684} = \frac{2}{40751368} = \frac{4}{81502736} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1}{20437658} = \frac{2}{40875316} = \frac{4}{81750632} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1}{20537684} = \frac{2}{41075368} = \frac{4}{82150736} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1}{20675384} = \frac{2}{41350768} = \frac{4}{82701536} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1}{20683754} = \frac{2}{41367508} = \frac{4}{82735016} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1}{20687534} = \frac{2}{41375068} = \frac{4}{82750136} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1}{20765438} = \frac{2}{41530876} = \frac{4}{83061752} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1}{20876543} = \frac{2}{41753086} = \frac{4}{83506172} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{10375684} = \frac{4}{20751368} = \frac{8}{41502736} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{10437658} = \frac{4}{20875316} = \frac{8}{41750632} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{10485736} = \frac{3}{15728604} = \frac{6}{31457208} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{10537684} = \frac{4}{21075368} = \frac{8}{42150736} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{10675384} = \frac{4}{21350768} = \frac{8}{42701536} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{10683754} = \frac{4}{21367508} = \frac{8}{42735016} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{10687534} = \frac{4}{21375068} = \frac{8}{42750136} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{10765438} = \frac{4}{21530876} = \frac{8}{43061752} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{10876543} = \frac{4}{21753086} = \frac{8}{43506172} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{13076854} = \frac{4}{26153708} = \frac{8}{52307416} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{13086754} = \frac{4}{26173508} = \frac{8}{52347016} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{2}{13406785} = \frac{4}{26813570} = \frac{8}{53627140} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{13506784} = \frac{4}{27013568} = \frac{8}{54027136} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{13540768} = \frac{4}{27081536} = \frac{8}{54163072} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{13567840} = \frac{4}{27135680} = \frac{8}{54271360} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{13576804} = \frac{4}{27153608} = \frac{8}{54307216} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{13675408} = \frac{4}{27350816} = \frac{8}{54701632} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{13675804} = \frac{4}{27351608} = \frac{8}{54703216} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{13678405} = \frac{4}{27356810} = \frac{8}{54713620} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{13680754} = \frac{4}{27361508} = \frac{8}{54723016} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{14035768} = \frac{4}{28071536} = \frac{8}{56143072} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{14036578} = \frac{3}{21054867} = \frac{4}{28073156} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{14036758} = \frac{4}{28073516} = \frac{8}{56147032} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{14037658} = \frac{3}{21056487} = \frac{4}{28075316} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{14057836} = \frac{3}{21086754} = \frac{6}{42173508} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{14067835} = \frac{4}{28135670} = \frac{8}{56271340} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{14075368} = \frac{4}{28150736} = \frac{8}{56301472} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{14076853} = \frac{4}{28153706} = \frac{8}{56307412} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{14086753} = \frac{4}{28173506} = \frac{8}{56347012} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{14307865} = \frac{4}{28615730} = \frac{8}{57231460} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{2}{14365078} = \frac{4}{28730156} = \frac{8}{57460312} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{14376580} = \frac{3}{21564870} = \frac{4}{28753160} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{14385760} = \frac{3}{21578640} = \frac{6}{43157280} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{14583760} = \frac{3}{21875640} = \frac{6}{43751280} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{15078643} = \frac{4}{30157286} = \frac{8}{60314572} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{15430876} = \frac{4}{30861752} = \frac{8}{61723504} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{15438076} = \frac{4}{30876152} = \frac{8}{61752304} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{15760438} = \frac{4}{31520876} = \frac{8}{63041752} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{15783604} = \frac{4}{31567208} = \frac{6}{47350812} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{15784036} = \frac{4}{31568072} = \frac{6}{47352108} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{15786034} = \frac{4}{31572068} = \frac{6}{47358102} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{15786430} = \frac{4}{31572860} = \frac{8}{63145720} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{15804376} = \frac{4}{31608752} = \frac{8}{63217504} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{15843760} = \frac{4}{31687520} = \frac{6}{47531280} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{15876043} = \frac{4}{31752086} = \frac{8}{63504172} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{16035784} = \frac{4}{32071568} = \frac{6}{48107352} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{16043758} = \frac{4}{32087516} = \frac{8}{64175032} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{16054378} = \frac{3}{24081567} = \frac{4}{32108756} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{16057834} = \frac{3}{24086751} = \frac{6}{48173502} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{2}{16075438} = \frac{4}{32150876} = \frac{8}{64301752} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{16087543} = \frac{4}{32175086} = \frac{8}{64350172} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{16378054} = \frac{3}{24567081} = \frac{4}{32756108} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{16430785} = \frac{4}{32861570} = \frac{8}{65723140} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{16435078} = \frac{4}{32870156} = \frac{8}{65740312} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{16435780} = \frac{4}{32871560} = \frac{8}{65743120} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{17436058} = \frac{3}{26154087} = \frac{6}{52308174} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{17458036} = \frac{3}{26187054} = \frac{6}{52374108} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{17536408} = \frac{4}{35072816} = \frac{8}{70145632} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{17538406} = \frac{4}{35076812} = \frac{8}{70153624} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{17540863} = \frac{4}{35081726} = \frac{8}{70163452} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{17560384} = \frac{4}{35120768} = \frac{8}{70241536} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{17580364} = \frac{4}{35160728} = \frac{8}{70321456} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{17580436} = \frac{4}{35160872} = \frac{6}{52741308} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{17586304} = \frac{4}{35172608} = \frac{8}{70345216} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{17586403} = \frac{4}{35172806} = \frac{8}{70345612} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{17603458} = \frac{3}{26405187} = \frac{6}{52810374} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{17604358} = \frac{4}{35208716} = \frac{6}{52813074} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{17605384} = \frac{4}{35210768} = \frac{8}{70421536} \end{aligned}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17605438} = \frac{3}{26408157} = \frac{4}{35210876}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17630854} = \frac{4}{35261708} = \frac{8}{70523416}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17635408} = \frac{4}{35270816} = \frac{8}{70541632}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17635804} = \frac{4}{35271608} = \frac{8}{70543216}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17638054} = \frac{3}{26457081} = \frac{4}{35276108}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17640358} = \frac{4}{35280716} = \frac{8}{70561432}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17640853} = \frac{4}{35281706} = \frac{8}{70563412}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17805436} = \frac{3}{26708154} = \frac{4}{35610872}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17835064} = \frac{4}{35670128} = \frac{8}{71340256}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17835640} = \frac{4}{35671280} = \frac{8}{71342560}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17836054} = \frac{3}{26754081} = \frac{4}{35672108}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17836405} = \frac{4}{35672810} = \frac{8}{71345620}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17840635} = \frac{4}{35681270} = \frac{8}{71362540}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17850634} = \frac{4}{35701268} = \frac{8}{71402536}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17856034} = \frac{3}{26784051} = \frac{4}{35712068}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17863405} = \frac{4}{35726810} = \frac{8}{71453620}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18034576} = \frac{3}{27051864} = \frac{6}{54103728}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18035764} = \frac{4}{36071528} = \frac{8}{72143056}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18043576} = \frac{4}{36087152} = \frac{6}{54130728}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18054376} = \frac{3}{27081564} = \frac{4}{36108752}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18057436} = \frac{3}{27086154} = \frac{6}{54172308}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18075364} = \frac{4}{36150728} = \frac{8}{72301456}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18076354} = \frac{4}{36152708} = \frac{8}{72305416}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18375406} = \frac{4}{36750812} = \frac{8}{73501624}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18375604} = \frac{4}{36751208} = \frac{8}{73502416}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18403756} = \frac{4}{36807512} = \frac{8}{73615024}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18405376} = \frac{4}{36810752} = \frac{8}{73621504}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18530764} = \frac{4}{37061528} = \frac{8}{74123056}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18540763} = \frac{4}{37081526} = \frac{8}{74163052}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18576034} = \frac{3}{27864051} = \frac{4}{37152068}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18576304} = \frac{4}{37152608} = \frac{8}{74305216}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18576340} = \frac{3}{27864510} = \frac{4}{37152680}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18576403} = \frac{4}{37152806} = \frac{8}{74305612}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18630754} = \frac{4}{37261508} = \frac{8}{74523016}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18640753} = \frac{4}{37281506} = \frac{8}{74563012}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18753406} = \frac{4}{37506812} = \frac{8}{75013624}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18756034} = \frac{4}{37512068} = \frac{8}{75024136}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{18760534} = \frac{4}{37521068} = \frac{8}{75042136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{34017856} = \frac{3}{51026784} = \frac{4}{68035712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{34018576} = \frac{3}{51027864} = \frac{4}{68037152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{34178560} = \frac{3}{51267840} = \frac{4}{68357120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{34185760} = \frac{3}{51278640} = \frac{4}{68371520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{36054178} = \frac{3}{54081267} = \frac{4}{72108356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{36178054} = \frac{3}{54267081} = \frac{4}{72356108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{36578014} = \frac{3}{54867021} = \frac{4}{73156028}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{36578140} = \frac{3}{54867210} = \frac{4}{73156280}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{37605418} = \frac{3}{56408127} = \frac{4}{75210836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{37618054} = \frac{3}{56427081} = \frac{4}{75236108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{37658014} = \frac{3}{56487021} = \frac{4}{75316028}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{37658140} = \frac{3}{56487210} = \frac{4}{75316280}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{37805416} = \frac{3}{56708124} = \frac{4}{75610832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{37816054} = \frac{3}{56724081} = \frac{4}{75632108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{38054176} = \frac{3}{57081264} = \frac{4}{76108352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{38176054} = \frac{3}{57264081} = \frac{4}{76352108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{12058764} = \frac{4}{16078352} = \frac{8}{32156704}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{12568740} = \frac{4}{16758320} = \frac{6}{25137480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{15640287} = \frac{4}{20853716} = \frac{6}{31280574}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{18764052} = \frac{4}{25018736} = \frac{6}{37528104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{21540786} = \frac{6}{43081572} = \frac{7}{50261834}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{21607854} = \frac{6}{43215708} = \frac{7}{50418326}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{21785406} = \frac{6}{43570812} = \frac{7}{50832614}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{21786054} = \frac{6}{43572108} = \frac{7}{50834126}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{24051786} = \frac{6}{48103572} = \frac{7}{56120834}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{24078516} = \frac{6}{48157032} = \frac{7}{56183204}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{27058614} = \frac{4}{36078152} = \frac{8}{72156304}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{28614057} = \frac{4}{38152076} = \frac{8}{76304152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{28617054} = \frac{4}{38156072} = \frac{6}{57234108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{40287156} = \frac{4}{53716208} = \frac{6}{80574312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{42857016} = \frac{5}{71428360} = \frac{6}{85714032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{16308752} = \frac{7}{28540316} = \frac{8}{32617504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{17623580} = \frac{7}{30841265} = \frac{8}{35247160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{17856032} = \frac{7}{31248056} = \frac{8}{35712064}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{17856320} = \frac{7}{31248560} = \frac{8}{35712640}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{23580176} = \frac{7}{41265308} = \frac{8}{47160352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{25371608} = \frac{6}{38057412} = \frac{8}{50743216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{32017856} = \frac{7}{56031248} = \frac{8}{64035712}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4}{32178560} &= \frac{7}{56312480} = \frac{8}{64357120} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4}{37102568} &= \frac{5}{46378210} = \frac{8}{74205136} \end{aligned}$$

6.1.14 2 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 33252 examples, each one with 2 expressions. Since, this number is too high to write here, below are just few examples:

$\blacktriangleright \frac{5016}{43287} = \frac{8360}{72145}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5072}{38416} = \frac{5706}{43218}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5178}{24306} = \frac{6041}{28357}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5247}{16830} = \frac{5724}{18360}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5028}{13764} = \frac{6704}{18352}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5076}{13824} = \frac{6345}{17280}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5178}{24630} = \frac{6041}{28735}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5248}{17630} = \frac{7104}{23865}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5034}{17268} = \frac{5873}{20146}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5076}{14382} = \frac{6372}{18054}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5178}{30246} = \frac{6041}{35287}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5264}{10387} = \frac{7280}{14365}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5037}{68241} = \frac{5402}{73186}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5076}{43281} = \frac{8460}{72135}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5178}{30624} = \frac{6041}{35728}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5274}{38601} = \frac{7032}{51468}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5038}{16742} = \frac{6183}{20547}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5082}{36741} = \frac{8470}{61235}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5178}{62430} = \frac{6041}{72835}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5278}{10643} = \frac{6370}{12845}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5038}{24167} = \frac{6412}{30758}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5104}{63278} = \frac{6512}{80734}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5178}{63024} = \frac{6041}{73528}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5278}{14630} = \frac{8671}{24035}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5038}{26147} = \frac{8702}{45163}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5106}{72483} = \frac{5382}{76401}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5187}{63042} = \frac{6435}{78210}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5278}{40136} = \frac{6734}{51208}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5042}{13876} = \frac{7563}{20814}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5120}{36784} = \frac{5760}{41382}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5206}{31784} = \frac{7068}{43152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5278}{63104} = \frac{6734}{80512}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5042}{18736} = \frac{7563}{28104}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5130}{28647} = \frac{8170}{45623}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5208}{17346} = \frac{7068}{23541}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5283}{17640} = \frac{7631}{25480}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5046}{27318} = \frac{5742}{31086}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5134}{20687} = \frac{5406}{21783}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5214}{67308} = \frac{6237}{80514}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5301}{26784} = \frac{7524}{38016}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5048}{31672} = \frac{8203}{51467}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5134}{67082} = \frac{5436}{71028}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5217}{60348} = \frac{7215}{83460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5301}{46872} = \frac{7182}{63504}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5061}{38274} = \frac{6748}{51032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5146}{37820} = \frac{7138}{52460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5236}{18704} = \frac{7106}{25384}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5304}{17628} = \frac{7854}{26103}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5064}{13728} = \frac{6752}{18304}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5168}{37240} = \frac{6732}{48510}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5236}{40817} = \frac{7832}{61054}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5328}{47160} = \frac{8362}{74015}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5068}{31472} = \frac{8326}{51704}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5178}{20364} = \frac{6041}{23758}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5238}{14607} = \frac{6402}{17853}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5328}{64170} = \frac{6512}{78430}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5072}{16384} = \frac{5706}{18432}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5178}{23604} = \frac{6041}{27538}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5240}{31768} = \frac{7205}{43681}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5328}{71460} = \frac{6512}{87340}$

▶ $\frac{5346}{12078} = \frac{6804}{15372}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{18376} = \frac{8103}{27564}$	▶ $\frac{5418}{67320} = \frac{6321}{78540}$	▶ $\frac{5438}{17620} = \frac{8157}{26430}$
▶ $\frac{5346}{21780} = \frac{6318}{25740}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{31768} = \frac{8103}{47652}$	▶ $\frac{5418}{73206} = \frac{6321}{85407}$	▶ $\frac{5438}{20176} = \frac{8157}{30264}$
▶ $\frac{5346}{71280} = \frac{6534}{87120}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{36178} = \frac{8103}{54267}$	▶ $\frac{5418}{73260} = \frac{6321}{85470}$	▶ $\frac{5438}{21760} = \frac{8157}{32640}$
▶ $\frac{5362}{47810} = \frac{8426}{75130}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{37618} = \frac{8103}{56427}$	▶ $\frac{5420}{16378} = \frac{8130}{24567}$	▶ $\frac{5460}{12873} = \frac{5720}{13486}$
▶ $\frac{5372}{16048} = \frac{8374}{25016}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{37816} = \frac{8103}{56724}$	▶ $\frac{5420}{17638} = \frac{8130}{26457}$	▶ $\frac{5460}{13872} = \frac{6825}{17340}$
▶ $\frac{5376}{10248} = \frac{8064}{15372}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{38176} = \frac{8103}{57264}$	▶ $\frac{5420}{17836} = \frac{8130}{26754}$	▶ $\frac{5460}{18732} = \frac{6370}{21854}$
▶ $\frac{5376}{10482} = \frac{8064}{15723}$	▶ $\frac{5403}{28617} = \frac{7204}{38156}$	▶ $\frac{5420}{31768} = \frac{8130}{47652}$	▶ $\frac{5460}{73218} = \frac{6370}{85421}$
▶ $\frac{5376}{14028} = \frac{6528}{17034}$	▶ $\frac{5406}{18732} = \frac{6307}{21854}$	▶ $\frac{5420}{36178} = \frac{8130}{54267}$	▶ $\frac{5472}{13860} = \frac{6840}{17325}$
▶ $\frac{5376}{24810} = \frac{8064}{37215}$	▶ $\frac{5406}{73218} = \frac{6307}{85421}$	▶ $\frac{5420}{37618} = \frac{8130}{56427}$	▶ $\frac{5472}{36081} = \frac{8064}{53172}$
▶ $\frac{5376}{28014} = \frac{6528}{34017}$	▶ $\frac{5408}{16237} = \frac{6240}{18735}$	▶ $\frac{5420}{37816} = \frac{8130}{56724}$	▶ $\frac{5601}{38274} = \frac{7468}{51032}$
▶ $\frac{5376}{48102} = \frac{8064}{72153}$	▶ $\frac{5416}{20378} = \frac{8124}{30567}$	▶ $\frac{5420}{38176} = \frac{8130}{57264}$	▶ $\frac{5602}{14378} = \frac{8403}{21567}$
▶ $\frac{5376}{48210} = \frac{8064}{72315}$	▶ $\frac{5416}{37802} = \frac{8124}{56703}$	▶ $\frac{5423}{17806} = \frac{8415}{27630}$	▶ $\frac{5602}{17438} = \frac{8403}{26157}$
▶ $\frac{5380}{14672} = \frac{6725}{18340}$	▶ $\frac{5416}{37820} = \frac{8124}{56730}$	▶ $\frac{5428}{10736} = \frac{6785}{13420}$	▶ $\frac{5602}{17834} = \frac{8403}{26751}$
▶ $\frac{5382}{17460} = \frac{6578}{21340}$	▶ $\frac{5418}{20376} = \frac{8127}{30564}$	▶ $\frac{5430}{28617} = \frac{7240}{38156}$	▶ $\frac{5602}{18374} = \frac{8403}{27561}$
▶ $\frac{5382}{41067} = \frac{6210}{47385}$	▶ $\frac{5418}{23760} = \frac{8127}{35640}$	▶ $\frac{5432}{81760} = \frac{5723}{86140}$	▶ $\frac{5602}{34178} = \frac{8403}{51267}$
▶ $\frac{5384}{10276} = \frac{6730}{12845}$	▶ $\frac{5418}{36702} = \frac{7826}{53014}$	▶ $\frac{5436}{17802} = \frac{8154}{26703}$	▶ $\frac{5602}{37418} = \frac{8403}{56127}$
▶ $\frac{5402}{16378} = \frac{8103}{24567}$	▶ $\frac{5418}{37602} = \frac{8127}{56403}$	▶ $\frac{5436}{17820} = \frac{8154}{26730}$	▶ $\frac{5602}{37814} = \frac{8403}{56721}$
▶ $\frac{5402}{17638} = \frac{8103}{26457}$	▶ $\frac{5418}{37620} = \frac{8127}{56430}$	▶ $\frac{5436}{20178} = \frac{8154}{30267}$	▶ $\frac{5602}{38174} = \frac{8403}{57261}$
▶ $\frac{5402}{17836} = \frac{8103}{26754}$	▶ $\frac{5418}{60732} = \frac{6321}{70854}$	▶ $\frac{5438}{17602} = \frac{8157}{26403}$	▶ $\frac{5604}{23178} = \frac{6538}{27041}$

$\triangleright \frac{5604}{31872} = \frac{6071}{34528}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{37418} = \frac{8430}{56127}$	$\triangleright \frac{5670}{13824} = \frac{7560}{18432}$	$\triangleright \frac{5714}{30682} = \frac{8571}{46023}$
$\triangleright \frac{5607}{14238} = \frac{6853}{17402}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{37814} = \frac{8430}{56721}$	$\triangleright \frac{5670}{24138} = \frac{7560}{32184}$	$\triangleright \frac{5720}{14638} = \frac{6820}{17453}$
$\triangleright \frac{5607}{18423} = \frac{7056}{23184}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{38174} = \frac{8430}{57261}$	$\triangleright \frac{5673}{18042} = \frac{8601}{27354}$	$\triangleright \frac{5720}{48136} = \frac{7410}{62358}$
$\triangleright \frac{5607}{32841} = \frac{7056}{41328}$	$\triangleright \frac{5621}{37084} = \frac{7315}{48260}$	$\triangleright \frac{5680}{23174} = \frac{8520}{34761}$	$\triangleright \frac{5720}{63184} = \frac{6435}{71082}$
$\triangleright \frac{5610}{24378} = \frac{7260}{31548}$	$\triangleright \frac{5624}{37810} = \frac{6512}{43780}$	$\triangleright \frac{5680}{31742} = \frac{8520}{47613}$	$\triangleright \frac{5736}{10248} = \frac{8604}{15372}$
$\triangleright \frac{5610}{28743} = \frac{7140}{36582}$	$\triangleright \frac{5627}{43180} = \frac{7613}{58420}$	$\triangleright \frac{5681}{37240} = \frac{6578}{43120}$	$\triangleright \frac{5736}{10482} = \frac{8604}{15723}$
$\triangleright \frac{5614}{20378} = \frac{8421}{30567}$	$\triangleright \frac{5634}{17802} = \frac{8451}{26703}$	$\triangleright \frac{5682}{30714} = \frac{8523}{46071}$	$\triangleright \frac{5736}{24810} = \frac{8604}{37215}$
$\triangleright \frac{5614}{23780} = \frac{8421}{35670}$	$\triangleright \frac{5634}{17820} = \frac{8451}{26730}$	$\triangleright \frac{5682}{31740} = \frac{8523}{47610}$	$\triangleright \frac{5736}{48102} = \frac{8604}{72153}$
$\triangleright \frac{5614}{37802} = \frac{8421}{56703}$	$\triangleright \frac{5634}{20178} = \frac{8451}{30267}$	$\triangleright \frac{5684}{13720} = \frac{5742}{13860}$	$\triangleright \frac{5736}{48210} = \frac{8604}{72315}$
$\triangleright \frac{5614}{37820} = \frac{8421}{56730}$	$\triangleright \frac{5634}{21780} = \frac{8451}{32670}$	$\triangleright \frac{5687}{43021} = \frac{6721}{50843}$	$\triangleright \frac{5738}{26410} = \frac{7852}{36140}$
$\triangleright \frac{5618}{20374} = \frac{8427}{30561}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{17402} = \frac{8457}{26103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5703}{28614} = \frac{7604}{38152}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{16238} = \frac{8610}{24357}$
$\triangleright \frac{5618}{23740} = \frac{8427}{35610}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{17420} = \frac{8457}{26130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5704}{13826} = \frac{7452}{18063}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{16382} = \frac{8610}{24573}$
$\triangleright \frac{5618}{37402} = \frac{8427}{56103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{20174} = \frac{8457}{30261}$	$\triangleright \frac{5704}{38612} = \frac{7130}{48265}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{18236} = \frac{8610}{27354}$
$\triangleright \frac{5618}{37420} = \frac{8427}{56130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{21740} = \frac{8457}{32610}$	$\triangleright \frac{5712}{38046} = \frac{8064}{53712}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{18362} = \frac{8610}{27543}$
$\triangleright \frac{5620}{14378} = \frac{8430}{21567}$	$\triangleright \frac{5640}{13827} = \frac{7520}{18436}$	$\triangleright \frac{5712}{38064} = \frac{6783}{45201}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{21638} = \frac{8610}{32457}$
$\triangleright \frac{5620}{17438} = \frac{8430}{26157}$	$\triangleright \frac{5640}{27138} = \frac{7520}{36184}$	$\triangleright \frac{5712}{43680} = \frac{6732}{51480}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{21836} = \frac{8610}{32754}$
$\triangleright \frac{5620}{17834} = \frac{8430}{26751}$	$\triangleright \frac{5643}{28710} = \frac{7182}{36540}$	$\triangleright \frac{5712}{43806} = \frac{8024}{61537}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{23168} = \frac{8610}{34752}$
$\triangleright \frac{5620}{18374} = \frac{8430}{27561}$	$\triangleright \frac{5648}{10237} = \frac{5872}{10643}$	$\triangleright \frac{5712}{46308} = \frac{8652}{70143}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{23618} = \frac{8610}{35427}$
$\triangleright \frac{5620}{34178} = \frac{8430}{51267}$	$\triangleright \frac{5670}{13284} = \frac{7035}{16482}$	$\triangleright \frac{5714}{23068} = \frac{8571}{34602}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{36182} = \frac{8610}{54273}$

- | | | | |
|---|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{5740}{36218} = \frac{8610}{54327}$ | ▶ $\frac{5760}{21834} = \frac{8640}{32751}$ | ▶ $\frac{5768}{23140} = \frac{8652}{34710}$ | ▶ $\frac{5782}{14360} = \frac{8673}{21540}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5740}{38162} = \frac{8610}{57243}$ | ▶ $\frac{5760}{23184} = \frac{6840}{27531}$ | ▶ $\frac{5768}{31402} = \frac{8652}{47103}$ | ▶ $\frac{5782}{16034} = \frac{8673}{24051}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5740}{38216} = \frac{8610}{57324}$ | ▶ $\frac{5760}{23418} = \frac{8640}{35127}$ | ▶ $\frac{5768}{31420} = \frac{8652}{47130}$ | ▶ $\frac{5782}{16340} = \frac{8673}{24510}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5742}{16038} = \frac{8613}{24057}$ | ▶ $\frac{5760}{23814} = \frac{8640}{35721}$ | ▶ $\frac{5768}{32410} = \frac{6180}{34725}$ | ▶ $\frac{5782}{34016} = \frac{8673}{51024}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5742}{16380} = \frac{8613}{24570}$ | ▶ $\frac{5760}{34182} = \frac{8640}{51273}$ | ▶ $\frac{5780}{14236} = \frac{8670}{21354}$ | ▶ $\frac{5782}{34160} = \frac{8673}{51240}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5742}{16830} = \frac{6873}{20145}$ | ▶ $\frac{5760}{34218} = \frac{8640}{51327}$ | ▶ $\frac{5780}{14362} = \frac{8670}{21543}$ | ▶ $\frac{5782}{36014} = \frac{8673}{54021}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5742}{18036} = \frac{8613}{27054}$ | ▶ $\frac{5760}{38142} = \frac{8640}{57213}$ | ▶ $\frac{5780}{16234} = \frac{8670}{24351}$ | ▶ $\frac{5782}{36140} = \frac{8673}{54210}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5742}{18360} = \frac{8613}{27540}$ | ▶ $\frac{5760}{38214} = \frac{8640}{57321}$ | ▶ $\frac{5780}{16342} = \frac{8670}{24513}$ | ▶ $\frac{5786}{12430} = \frac{7364}{15820}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5742}{36018} = \frac{8613}{54027}$ | ▶ $\frac{5761}{32480} = \frac{6584}{37120}$ | ▶ $\frac{5780}{21436} = \frac{8670}{32154}$ | ▶ $\frac{5802}{14376} = \frac{8703}{21564}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5742}{36180} = \frac{8613}{54270}$ | ▶ $\frac{5762}{14038} = \frac{8643}{21057}$ | ▶ $\frac{5780}{21634} = \frac{8670}{32451}$ | ▶ $\frac{5802}{16374} = \frac{8703}{24561}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5742}{38016} = \frac{8613}{57024}$ | ▶ $\frac{5762}{14380} = \frac{8643}{21570}$ | ▶ $\frac{5780}{23416} = \frac{8670}{35124}$ | ▶ $\frac{5802}{17436} = \frac{8703}{26154}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5742}{38160} = \frac{8613}{57240}$ | ▶ $\frac{5762}{18034} = \frac{8643}{27051}$ | ▶ $\frac{5780}{23614} = \frac{8670}{35421}$ | ▶ $\frac{5802}{17634} = \frac{8703}{26451}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5760}{12384} = \frac{7360}{15824}$ | ▶ $\frac{5762}{18340} = \frac{8643}{27510}$ | ▶ $\frac{5780}{24361} = \frac{7480}{31526}$ | ▶ $\frac{5802}{34176} = \frac{8703}{51264}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5760}{13248} = \frac{6840}{15732}$ | ▶ $\frac{5762}{30418} = \frac{6708}{35412}$ | ▶ $\frac{5780}{32164} = \frac{7820}{43516}$ | ▶ $\frac{5802}{36174} = \frac{8703}{54261}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5760}{14238} = \frac{8640}{21357}$ | ▶ $\frac{5762}{34018} = \frac{8643}{51027}$ | ▶ $\frac{5780}{34162} = \frac{8670}{51243}$ | ▶ $\frac{5802}{37416} = \frac{8703}{56124}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5760}{14382} = \frac{8640}{21573}$ | ▶ $\frac{5762}{34180} = \frac{8643}{51270}$ | ▶ $\frac{5780}{34216} = \frac{8670}{51324}$ | ▶ $\frac{5802}{37614} = \frac{8703}{56421}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5760}{18234} = \frac{8640}{27351}$ | ▶ $\frac{5762}{38014} = \frac{8643}{57021}$ | ▶ $\frac{5780}{36142} = \frac{8670}{54213}$ | ▶ $\frac{5812}{67304} = \frac{7265}{84130}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5760}{18342} = \frac{8640}{27513}$ | ▶ $\frac{5762}{38140} = \frac{8643}{57210}$ | ▶ $\frac{5780}{36214} = \frac{8670}{54321}$ | ▶ $\frac{5814}{20376} = \frac{8721}{30564}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5760}{21438} = \frac{8640}{32157}$ | ▶ $\frac{5768}{20314} = \frac{8652}{30471}$ | ▶ $\frac{5782}{14036} = \frac{8673}{21054}$ | ▶ $\frac{5814}{23760} = \frac{8721}{35640}$ |

▶ $\frac{5814}{36720} = \frac{7182}{45360}$	▶ $\frac{5832}{61074} = \frac{6804}{71253}$	▶ $\frac{5876}{23140} = \frac{8701}{34265}$	▶ $\frac{6120}{34785} = \frac{6528}{37104}$
▶ $\frac{5814}{37602} = \frac{8721}{56403}$	▶ $\frac{5834}{17602} = \frac{8751}{26403}$	▶ $\frac{6012}{53874} = \frac{7014}{62853}$	▶ $\frac{6120}{53874} = \frac{7140}{62853}$
▶ $\frac{5814}{37620} = \frac{8721}{56430}$	▶ $\frac{5834}{17620} = \frac{8751}{26430}$	▶ $\frac{6012}{58734} = \frac{7014}{68523}$	▶ $\frac{6120}{57384} = \frac{7310}{68542}$
▶ $\frac{5816}{20374} = \frac{8724}{30561}$	▶ $\frac{5834}{20176} = \frac{8751}{30264}$	▶ $\frac{6017}{23485} = \frac{8752}{34160}$	▶ $\frac{6120}{58734} = \frac{7140}{68523}$
▶ $\frac{5816}{37402} = \frac{8724}{56103}$	▶ $\frac{5834}{21760} = \frac{8751}{32640}$	▶ $\frac{6017}{28435} = \frac{8752}{41360}$	▶ $\frac{6132}{70548} = \frac{7154}{82306}$
▶ $\frac{5816}{37420} = \frac{8724}{56130}$	▶ $\frac{5836}{17402} = \frac{8754}{26103}$	▶ $\frac{6018}{27435} = \frac{8126}{37045}$	▶ $\frac{6137}{28405} = \frac{8721}{40365}$
▶ $\frac{5820}{16374} = \frac{8730}{24561}$	▶ $\frac{5836}{17420} = \frac{8754}{26130}$	▶ $\frac{6018}{54732} = \frac{7021}{63854}$	▶ $\frac{6138}{47025} = \frac{8370}{64125}$
▶ $\frac{5820}{17436} = \frac{8730}{26154}$	▶ $\frac{5836}{20174} = \frac{8754}{30261}$	▶ $\frac{6018}{73254} = \frac{7021}{85463}$	▶ $\frac{6153}{40287} = \frac{8204}{53716}$
▶ $\frac{5820}{17634} = \frac{8730}{26451}$	▶ $\frac{5836}{21740} = \frac{8754}{32610}$	▶ $\frac{6045}{32178} = \frac{7215}{38406}$	▶ $\frac{6180}{54732} = \frac{7210}{63854}$
▶ $\frac{5820}{34176} = \frac{8730}{51264}$	▶ $\frac{5840}{12736} = \frac{6570}{14328}$	▶ $\frac{6054}{18732} = \frac{7063}{21854}$	▶ $\frac{6180}{73254} = \frac{7210}{85463}$
▶ $\frac{5820}{36174} = \frac{8730}{54261}$	▶ $\frac{5840}{17632} = \frac{6205}{18734}$	▶ $\frac{6054}{73218} = \frac{7063}{85421}$	▶ $\frac{6183}{47520} = \frac{8473}{65120}$
▶ $\frac{5820}{37416} = \frac{8730}{56124}$	▶ $\frac{5840}{32176} = \frac{6205}{34187}$	▶ $\frac{6072}{18354} = \frac{6204}{18753}$	▶ $\frac{6187}{50324} = \frac{7801}{63452}$
▶ $\frac{5820}{37614} = \frac{8730}{56421}$	▶ $\frac{5860}{13472} = \frac{7325}{16840}$	▶ $\frac{6072}{51348} = \frac{7452}{63018}$	▶ $\frac{6201}{47853} = \frac{8427}{65031}$
▶ $\frac{5820}{47316} = \frac{8245}{67031}$	▶ $\frac{5871}{43260} = \frac{6213}{45780}$	▶ $\frac{6075}{23814} = \frac{8175}{32046}$	▶ $\frac{6205}{41378} = \frac{6570}{43812}$
▶ $\frac{5824}{13076} = \frac{7280}{16345}$	▶ $\frac{5872}{13460} = \frac{7340}{16825}$	▶ $\frac{6102}{34578} = \frac{8127}{46053}$	▶ $\frac{6210}{58374} = \frac{7245}{68103}$
▶ $\frac{5824}{71360} = \frac{6734}{82510}$	▶ $\frac{5874}{10326} = \frac{6853}{12047}$	▶ $\frac{6102}{37854} = \frac{8136}{50472}$	▶ $\frac{6213}{84075} = \frac{6431}{87025}$
▶ $\frac{5831}{27064} = \frac{6517}{30248}$	▶ $\frac{5874}{61032} = \frac{6853}{71204}$	▶ $\frac{6102}{54378} = \frac{8136}{72504}$	▶ $\frac{6214}{30875} = \frac{8126}{40375}$
▶ $\frac{5832}{10746} = \frac{6804}{12537}$	▶ $\frac{5876}{12430} = \frac{7384}{15620}$	▶ $\frac{6104}{38572} = \frac{7630}{48215}$	▶ $\frac{6215}{38740} = \frac{8701}{54236}$
▶ $\frac{5832}{46170} = \frac{7128}{56430}$	▶ $\frac{5876}{13024} = \frac{7345}{16280}$	▶ $\frac{6107}{38254} = \frac{8471}{53062}$	▶ $\frac{6240}{38571} = \frac{6720}{41538}$

▶ $\frac{6240}{38715} = \frac{8736}{54201}$	▶ $\frac{6378}{54102} = \frac{8504}{72136}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{18540} = \frac{7854}{21630}$	▶ $\frac{7038}{14265} = \frac{8602}{17435}$
▶ $\frac{6240}{53781} = \frac{7520}{64813}$	▶ $\frac{6380}{47125} = \frac{8712}{64350}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{50184} = \frac{8415}{62730}$	▶ $\frac{7038}{52164} = \frac{8415}{62370}$
▶ $\frac{6241}{35708} = \frac{6715}{38420}$	▶ $\frac{6380}{54172} = \frac{7480}{63512}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{54018} = \frac{7854}{63021}$	▶ $\frac{7046}{21385} = \frac{8130}{24675}$
▶ $\frac{6241}{57038} = \frac{7031}{64258}$	▶ $\frac{6402}{15873} = \frac{8730}{21645}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{54180} = \frac{7854}{63210}$	▶ $\frac{7065}{14238} = \frac{8635}{17402}$
▶ $\frac{6248}{13750} = \frac{7384}{16250}$	▶ $\frac{6405}{17382} = \frac{8540}{23176}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{58104} = \frac{8415}{72630}$	▶ $\frac{7085}{14326} = \frac{7630}{15428}$
▶ $\frac{6248}{57013} = \frac{7128}{65043}$	▶ $\frac{6413}{50827} = \frac{8107}{64253}$	▶ $\frac{6734}{12580} = \frac{8372}{15640}$	▶ $\frac{7085}{21346} = \frac{8175}{24630}$
▶ $\frac{6270}{53184} = \frac{7315}{62048}$	▶ $\frac{6417}{53280} = \frac{7843}{65120}$	▶ $\frac{6743}{18502} = \frac{7356}{20184}$	▶ $\frac{7085}{26143} = \frac{7630}{28154}$
▶ $\frac{6285}{14370} = \frac{6704}{15328}$	▶ $\frac{6432}{15708} = \frac{7504}{18326}$	▶ $\frac{6745}{28310} = \frac{8165}{34270}$	▶ $\frac{7106}{24358} = \frac{8041}{27563}$
▶ $\frac{6315}{40287} = \frac{8420}{53716}$	▶ $\frac{6475}{21830} = \frac{7805}{26314}$	▶ $\frac{6784}{13520} = \frac{7208}{14365}$	▶ $\frac{7106}{53428} = \frac{8415}{63270}$
▶ $\frac{6320}{17854} = \frac{7640}{21583}$	▶ $\frac{6501}{38247} = \frac{7683}{45201}$	▶ $\frac{6817}{43520} = \frac{8421}{53760}$	▶ $\frac{7106}{53482} = \frac{8531}{64207}$
▶ $\frac{6324}{15708} = \frac{7502}{18634}$	▶ $\frac{6504}{37812} = \frac{8130}{47265}$	▶ $\frac{6831}{50274} = \frac{7084}{52136}$	▶ $\frac{7125}{36480} = \frac{7425}{38016}$
▶ $\frac{6324}{57018} = \frac{7130}{64285}$	▶ $\frac{6534}{28017} = \frac{7128}{30564}$	▶ $\frac{6831}{52074} = \frac{8073}{61542}$	▶ $\frac{7128}{53460} = \frac{8712}{65340}$
▶ $\frac{6340}{12785} = \frac{7608}{15342}$	▶ $\frac{6540}{18732} = \frac{7630}{21854}$	▶ $\frac{6831}{52704} = \frac{7843}{60512}$	▶ $\frac{7128}{63450} = \frac{8316}{74025}$
▶ $\frac{6348}{71250} = \frac{7406}{83125}$	▶ $\frac{6540}{73218} = \frac{7630}{85421}$	▶ $\frac{6834}{12750} = \frac{7638}{14250}$	▶ $\frac{7130}{52486} = \frac{8215}{60473}$
▶ $\frac{6352}{10784} = \frac{7543}{12806}$	▶ $\frac{6572}{38104} = \frac{8215}{47630}$	▶ $\frac{6853}{12740} = \frac{7832}{14560}$	▶ $\frac{7136}{40528} = \frac{7582}{43061}$
▶ $\frac{6357}{12480} = \frac{7824}{15360}$	▶ $\frac{6580}{13724} = \frac{7840}{16352}$	▶ $\frac{6874}{12530} = \frac{7856}{14320}$	▶ $\frac{7136}{58240} = \frac{8251}{67340}$
▶ $\frac{6375}{14280} = \frac{7325}{16408}$	▶ $\frac{6720}{13584} = \frac{8540}{17263}$	▶ $\frac{7015}{43286} = \frac{7320}{45168}$	▶ $\frac{7146}{53280} = \frac{8734}{65120}$
▶ $\frac{6375}{24810} = \frac{8075}{31426}$	▶ $\frac{6720}{31584} = \frac{7620}{35814}$	▶ $\frac{7015}{46238} = \frac{7360}{48512}$	▶ $\frac{7168}{30254} = \frac{7680}{32415}$
▶ $\frac{6378}{10254} = \frac{8504}{13672}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{10548} = \frac{7854}{12306}$	▶ $\frac{7018}{32654} = \frac{8712}{40536}$	▶ $\frac{7168}{52304} = \frac{8704}{63512}$

▶ $\frac{7185}{62340} = \frac{8143}{70652}$	▶ $\frac{7326}{18054} = \frac{8547}{21063}$	▶ $\frac{7623}{15840} = \frac{7854}{16320}$	▶ $\frac{501}{384267} = \frac{561}{430287}$
▶ $\frac{7208}{16354} = \frac{7420}{16835}$	▶ $\frac{7326}{18540} = \frac{8547}{21630}$	▶ $\frac{7648}{15320} = \frac{8604}{17235}$	▶ $\frac{501}{384762} = \frac{835}{641270}$
▶ $\frac{7250}{38164} = \frac{7625}{40138}$	▶ $\frac{7326}{54018} = \frac{8547}{63021}$	▶ $\frac{7650}{14382} = \frac{8725}{16403}$	▶ $\frac{501}{432876} = \frac{835}{721460}$
▶ $\frac{7254}{18603} = \frac{8370}{21465}$	▶ $\frac{7326}{54180} = \frac{8547}{63210}$	▶ $\frac{7680}{14325} = \frac{8704}{16235}$	▶ $\frac{502}{138764} = \frac{753}{208146}$
▶ $\frac{7254}{80631} = \frac{7410}{82365}$	▶ $\frac{7328}{54160} = \frac{8702}{64315}$	▶ $\frac{7683}{21450} = \frac{8471}{23650}$	▶ $\frac{502}{187364} = \frac{753}{281046}$
▶ $\frac{7260}{34815} = \frac{7524}{36081}$	▶ $\frac{7358}{12064} = \frac{8207}{13456}$	▶ $\frac{7684}{51302} = \frac{8602}{57431}$	▶ $\frac{502}{413876} = \frac{753}{620814}$
▶ $\frac{7268}{40135} = \frac{8216}{45370}$	▶ $\frac{7360}{14528} = \frac{7820}{15436}$	▶ $\frac{8052}{47136} = \frac{8723}{51064}$	▶ $\frac{502}{418736} = \frac{753}{628104}$
▶ $\frac{7304}{12865} = \frac{8360}{14725}$	▶ $\frac{7360}{21584} = \frac{8740}{25631}$	▶ $\frac{8073}{14526} = \frac{8372}{15064}$	▶ $\frac{504}{137628} = \frac{672}{183504}$
▶ $\frac{7310}{46852} = \frac{8170}{52364}$	▶ $\frac{7381}{52460} = \frac{7623}{54180}$	▶ $\frac{8145}{32760} = \frac{8507}{34216}$	▶ $\frac{504}{138276} = \frac{630}{172845}$
▶ $\frac{7315}{26840} = \frac{8645}{31720}$	▶ $\frac{7416}{32058} = \frac{8652}{37401}$	▶ $\frac{8162}{30475} = \frac{8470}{31625}$	▶ $\frac{504}{138762} = \frac{756}{208143}$
▶ $\frac{7320}{15648} = \frac{8235}{17604}$	▶ $\frac{7425}{13860} = \frac{8370}{15624}$	▶ $\frac{8162}{50743} = \frac{8374}{52061}$	▶ $\frac{504}{186732} = \frac{576}{213408}$
▶ $\frac{7320}{18546} = \frac{8540}{21637}$	▶ $\frac{7425}{68310} = \frac{8310}{76452}$	▶ $\frac{8172}{30645} = \frac{8460}{31725}$	▶ $\frac{504}{187362} = \frac{756}{281043}$
▶ $\frac{7320}{18654} = \frac{8540}{21763}$	▶ $\frac{7486}{12350} = \frac{8274}{13650}$	▶ $\frac{8176}{30254} = \frac{8760}{32415}$	▶ $\frac{504}{213876} = \frac{756}{320814}$
▶ $\frac{7320}{54186} = \frac{8540}{63217}$	▶ $\frac{7514}{23608} = \frac{7803}{24516}$	▶ $\frac{8276}{10345} = \frac{8372}{10465}$	▶ $\frac{504}{273861} = \frac{648}{352107}$
▶ $\frac{7320}{54618} = \frac{8540}{63721}$	▶ $\frac{7543}{18620} = \frac{8734}{21560}$	▶ $\frac{8372}{14605} = \frac{8736}{15240}$	▶ $\frac{504}{376281} = \frac{840}{627135}$
▶ $\frac{7320}{61854} = \frac{8540}{72163}$	▶ $\frac{7562}{10348} = \frac{7638}{10452}$	▶ $\frac{8576}{23104} = \frac{8710}{23465}$	▶ $\frac{504}{382761} = \frac{672}{510348}$
▶ $\frac{7320}{65418} = \frac{8540}{76321}$	▶ $\frac{7562}{18430} = \frac{8756}{21340}$	▶ $\frac{501}{367482} = \frac{835}{612470}$	▶ $\frac{504}{386172} = \frac{630}{482715}$
▶ $\frac{7326}{10548} = \frac{8547}{12306}$	▶ $\frac{7568}{34012} = \frac{8256}{37104}$	▶ $\frac{501}{374826} = \frac{835}{624710}$	▶ $\frac{504}{387162} = \frac{532}{408671}$
▶ $\frac{7326}{15840} = \frac{7548}{16320}$	▶ $\frac{7618}{34502} = \frac{8204}{37156}$	▶ $\frac{501}{376284} = \frac{835}{627140}$	▶ $\frac{506}{127834} = \frac{627}{158403}$

▶ $\frac{506}{134872} = \frac{528}{140736}$	▶ $\frac{520}{431768} = \frac{845}{701623}$	▶ $\frac{536}{187240} = \frac{871}{304265}$	▶ $\frac{540}{328617} = \frac{720}{438156}$
▶ $\frac{506}{312478} = \frac{847}{523061}$	▶ $\frac{520}{438176} = \frac{845}{712036}$	▶ $\frac{536}{401872} = \frac{871}{653042}$	▶ $\frac{540}{361782} = \frac{810}{542673}$
▶ $\frac{507}{381264} = \frac{708}{532416}$	▶ $\frac{523}{140687} = \frac{874}{235106}$	▶ $\frac{540}{138267} = \frac{720}{184356}$	▶ $\frac{540}{367281} = \frac{840}{571326}$
▶ $\frac{507}{432816} = \frac{845}{721360}$	▶ $\frac{524}{317806} = \frac{842}{510673}$	▶ $\frac{540}{162378} = \frac{810}{243567}$	▶ $\frac{540}{376182} = \frac{810}{564273}$
▶ $\frac{508}{142736} = \frac{635}{178420}$	▶ $\frac{526}{307184} = \frac{612}{357408}$	▶ $\frac{540}{163782} = \frac{810}{245673}$	▶ $\frac{540}{376218} = \frac{810}{564327}$
▶ $\frac{510}{237864} = \frac{675}{314820}$	▶ $\frac{527}{601834} = \frac{736}{840512}$	▶ $\frac{540}{176238} = \frac{810}{264357}$	▶ $\frac{540}{378162} = \frac{810}{567243}$
▶ $\frac{510}{378624} = \frac{570}{423168}$	▶ $\frac{528}{143760} = \frac{847}{230615}$	▶ $\frac{540}{176283} = \frac{780}{254631}$	▶ $\frac{540}{381762} = \frac{810}{572643}$
▶ $\frac{510}{634287} = \frac{580}{721346}$	▶ $\frac{528}{430176} = \frac{627}{510834}$	▶ $\frac{540}{176382} = \frac{810}{264573}$	▶ $\frac{540}{382176} = \frac{810}{573264}$
▶ $\frac{512}{367840} = \frac{576}{413820}$	▶ $\frac{530}{241786} = \frac{805}{367241}$	▶ $\frac{540}{178236} = \frac{810}{267354}$	▶ $\frac{540}{618732} = \frac{630}{721854}$
▶ $\frac{513}{286470} = \frac{817}{456230}$	▶ $\frac{530}{427816} = \frac{835}{674012}$	▶ $\frac{540}{178362} = \frac{810}{267543}$	▶ $\frac{540}{673218} = \frac{630}{785421}$
▶ $\frac{513}{647082} = \frac{532}{671048}$	▶ $\frac{530}{621478} = \frac{710}{832546}$	▶ $\frac{540}{183762} = \frac{810}{275643}$	▶ $\frac{540}{732186} = \frac{630}{854217}$
▶ $\frac{514}{702638} = \frac{524}{716308}$	▶ $\frac{532}{416708} = \frac{602}{471538}$	▶ $\frac{540}{186732} = \frac{630}{217854}$	▶ $\frac{540}{732618} = \frac{630}{854721}$
▶ $\frac{516}{270384} = \frac{576}{301824}$	▶ $\frac{532}{418076} = \frac{742}{583106}$	▶ $\frac{540}{187326} = \frac{630}{218547}$	▶ $\frac{542}{160378} = \frac{813}{240567}$
▶ $\frac{516}{387204} = \frac{602}{451738}$	▶ $\frac{532}{478610} = \frac{826}{743105}$	▶ $\frac{540}{217638} = \frac{810}{326457}$	▶ $\frac{542}{163780} = \frac{813}{245670}$
▶ $\frac{516}{432807} = \frac{860}{721345}$	▶ $\frac{534}{271806} = \frac{678}{345102}$	▶ $\frac{540}{236178} = \frac{810}{354267}$	▶ $\frac{542}{176038} = \frac{813}{264057}$
▶ $\frac{517}{420368} = \frac{781}{635024}$	▶ $\frac{534}{687210} = \frac{623}{801745}$	▶ $\frac{540}{237618} = \frac{810}{356427}$	▶ $\frac{542}{176380} = \frac{813}{264570}$
▶ $\frac{520}{316784} = \frac{685}{417302}$	▶ $\frac{536}{102748} = \frac{670}{128435}$	▶ $\frac{540}{267138} = \frac{720}{356184}$	▶ $\frac{542}{178036} = \frac{813}{267054}$
▶ $\frac{520}{384176} = \frac{560}{413728}$	▶ $\frac{536}{107428} = \frac{670}{134285}$	▶ $\frac{540}{286173} = \frac{720}{381564}$	▶ $\frac{542}{178360} = \frac{813}{267540}$
▶ $\frac{520}{384761} = \frac{840}{621537}$	▶ $\frac{536}{127048} = \frac{871}{206453}$	▶ $\frac{540}{317682} = \frac{810}{476523}$	▶ $\frac{542}{180376} = \frac{813}{270564}$

▶ $\frac{542}{183760} = \frac{813}{275640}$	▶ $\frac{546}{173082} = \frac{654}{207318}$	▶ $\frac{560}{214378} = \frac{840}{321567}$	▶ $\frac{562}{174038} = \frac{843}{261057}$
▶ $\frac{542}{307168} = \frac{813}{460752}$	▶ $\frac{546}{173208} = \frac{741}{235068}$	▶ $\frac{560}{217438} = \frac{840}{326157}$	▶ $\frac{562}{174380} = \frac{843}{261570}$
▶ $\frac{542}{316708} = \frac{813}{475062}$	▶ $\frac{546}{180732} = \frac{637}{210854}$	▶ $\frac{560}{217834} = \frac{840}{326751}$	▶ $\frac{562}{178034} = \frac{843}{267051}$
▶ $\frac{542}{317068} = \frac{813}{475602}$	▶ $\frac{546}{187320} = \frac{637}{218540}$	▶ $\frac{560}{218374} = \frac{840}{327561}$	▶ $\frac{562}{178340} = \frac{843}{267510}$
▶ $\frac{542}{317680} = \frac{813}{476520}$	▶ $\frac{546}{378102} = \frac{728}{504136}$	▶ $\frac{560}{234178} = \frac{840}{351267}$	▶ $\frac{562}{180374} = \frac{843}{270561}$
▶ $\frac{542}{360178} = \frac{813}{540267}$	▶ $\frac{546}{732018} = \frac{637}{854021}$	▶ $\frac{560}{237418} = \frac{840}{356127}$	▶ $\frac{562}{183740} = \frac{843}{275610}$
▶ $\frac{542}{361780} = \frac{813}{542670}$	▶ $\frac{546}{732180} = \frac{637}{854210}$	▶ $\frac{560}{237814} = \frac{840}{356721}$	▶ $\frac{562}{340178} = \frac{843}{510267}$
▶ $\frac{542}{376018} = \frac{813}{564027}$	▶ $\frac{546}{821037} = \frac{572}{860134}$	▶ $\frac{560}{238174} = \frac{840}{357261}$	▶ $\frac{562}{341780} = \frac{843}{512670}$
▶ $\frac{542}{376180} = \frac{813}{564270}$	▶ $\frac{560}{127834} = \frac{720}{164358}$	▶ $\frac{560}{341782} = \frac{840}{512673}$	▶ $\frac{562}{374018} = \frac{843}{561027}$
▶ $\frac{542}{378016} = \frac{813}{567024}$	▶ $\frac{560}{142378} = \frac{840}{213567}$	▶ $\frac{560}{342178} = \frac{840}{513267}$	▶ $\frac{562}{374180} = \frac{843}{561270}$
▶ $\frac{542}{378160} = \frac{813}{567240}$	▶ $\frac{560}{143782} = \frac{840}{215673}$	▶ $\frac{560}{374182} = \frac{840}{561273}$	▶ $\frac{562}{378014} = \frac{843}{567021}$
▶ $\frac{542}{380176} = \frac{813}{570264}$	▶ $\frac{560}{174238} = \frac{840}{261357}$	▶ $\frac{560}{374218} = \frac{840}{561327}$	▶ $\frac{562}{378140} = \frac{843}{567210}$
▶ $\frac{542}{381760} = \frac{813}{572640}$	▶ $\frac{560}{174382} = \frac{840}{261573}$	▶ $\frac{560}{378142} = \frac{840}{567213}$	▶ $\frac{562}{380174} = \frac{843}{570261}$
▶ $\frac{543}{286170} = \frac{724}{381560}$	▶ $\frac{560}{174832} = \frac{780}{243516}$	▶ $\frac{560}{378214} = \frac{840}{567321}$	▶ $\frac{562}{381740} = \frac{843}{572610}$
▶ $\frac{543}{602187} = \frac{726}{805134}$	▶ $\frac{560}{178234} = \frac{840}{267351}$	▶ $\frac{560}{381472} = \frac{710}{483652}$	▶ $\frac{564}{120837} = \frac{576}{123408}$
▶ $\frac{546}{102378} = \frac{728}{136504}$	▶ $\frac{560}{178342} = \frac{840}{267513}$	▶ $\frac{560}{381742} = \frac{840}{572613}$	▶ $\frac{564}{138027} = \frac{752}{184036}$
▶ $\frac{546}{102837} = \frac{832}{156704}$	▶ $\frac{560}{182374} = \frac{840}{273561}$	▶ $\frac{560}{382174} = \frac{840}{573261}$	▶ $\frac{564}{138270} = \frac{752}{184360}$
▶ $\frac{546}{107832} = \frac{637}{125804}$	▶ $\frac{560}{183472} = \frac{805}{263741}$	▶ $\frac{562}{140378} = \frac{843}{210567}$	▶ $\frac{564}{203178} = \frac{658}{237041}$
▶ $\frac{546}{128730} = \frac{572}{134860}$	▶ $\frac{560}{183742} = \frac{840}{275613}$	▶ $\frac{562}{143780} = \frac{843}{215670}$	▶ $\frac{564}{270138} = \frac{752}{360184}$

- ▶ $\frac{564}{271380} = \frac{752}{361840}$ ▶ $\frac{572}{146380} = \frac{682}{174530}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{203618} = \frac{861}{305427}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{380216} = \frac{861}{570324}$
- ▶ $\frac{567}{138024} = \frac{756}{184032}$ ▶ $\frac{572}{310648} = \frac{627}{340518}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{203816} = \frac{861}{305724}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{381602} = \frac{861}{572403}$
- ▶ $\frac{567}{138240} = \frac{756}{184320}$ ▶ $\frac{572}{386104} = \frac{715}{482630}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{216038} = \frac{861}{324057}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{381620} = \frac{861}{572430}$
- ▶ $\frac{567}{240138} = \frac{756}{320184}$ ▶ $\frac{572}{481360} = \frac{741}{623580}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{216380} = \frac{861}{324570}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{382016} = \frac{861}{573024}$
- ▶ $\frac{567}{241380} = \frac{756}{321840}$ ▶ $\frac{573}{286140} = \frac{764}{381520}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{218036} = \frac{861}{327054}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{382160} = \frac{861}{573240}$
- ▶ $\frac{567}{280341} = \frac{861}{425703}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{160238} = \frac{861}{240357}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{218360} = \frac{861}{327540}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{816032} = \frac{615}{874320}$
- ▶ $\frac{568}{130427} = \frac{672}{154308}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{160382} = \frac{861}{240573}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{231680} = \frac{861}{347520}$ ▶ $\frac{576}{132480} = \frac{684}{157320}$
- ▶ $\frac{568}{143207} = \frac{816}{205734}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{162038} = \frac{861}{243057}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{236018} = \frac{861}{354027}$ ▶ $\frac{576}{134208} = \frac{584}{136072}$
- ▶ $\frac{568}{203174} = \frac{852}{304761}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{162380} = \frac{861}{243570}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{236180} = \frac{861}{354270}$ ▶ $\frac{576}{140238} = \frac{864}{210357}$
- ▶ $\frac{568}{230714} = \frac{852}{346071}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{163802} = \frac{861}{245703}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{238016} = \frac{861}{357024}$ ▶ $\frac{576}{140382} = \frac{864}{210573}$
- ▶ $\frac{568}{307142} = \frac{852}{460713}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{163820} = \frac{861}{245730}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{238160} = \frac{861}{357240}$ ▶ $\frac{576}{142038} = \frac{864}{213057}$
- ▶ $\frac{568}{317240} = \frac{781}{436205}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{180362} = \frac{861}{270543}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{316802} = \frac{861}{475203}$ ▶ $\frac{576}{143802} = \frac{864}{215703}$
- ▶ $\frac{568}{317402} = \frac{852}{476103}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{182036} = \frac{861}{273054}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{360182} = \frac{861}{540273}$ ▶ $\frac{576}{180234} = \frac{864}{270351}$
- ▶ $\frac{568}{317420} = \frac{852}{476130}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{182360} = \frac{861}{273540}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{360218} = \frac{861}{540327}$ ▶ $\frac{576}{180342} = \frac{864}{270513}$
- ▶ $\frac{570}{132468} = \frac{705}{163842}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{183602} = \frac{861}{275403}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{361802} = \frac{861}{542703}$ ▶ $\frac{576}{182034} = \frac{864}{273051}$
- ▶ $\frac{570}{138264} = \frac{760}{184352}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{183620} = \frac{861}{275430}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{361820} = \frac{861}{542730}$ ▶ $\frac{576}{182340} = \frac{864}{273510}$
- ▶ $\frac{570}{283461} = \frac{870}{432651}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{201638} = \frac{861}{302457}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{362018} = \frac{861}{543027}$ ▶ $\frac{576}{183402} = \frac{864}{275103}$
- ▶ $\frac{570}{286143} = \frac{760}{381524}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{201836} = \frac{861}{302754}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{362180} = \frac{861}{543270}$ ▶ $\frac{576}{183420} = \frac{864}{275130}$
- ▶ $\frac{572}{134068} = \frac{702}{164538}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{203168} = \frac{861}{304752}$ ▶ $\frac{574}{380162} = \frac{861}{570243}$ ▶ $\frac{576}{201438} = \frac{864}{302157}$

$\triangleright \frac{576}{201834} = \frac{864}{302751}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{380142} = \frac{864}{570213}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{163420} = \frac{867}{245130}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{342016} = \frac{867}{513024}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{203418} = \frac{864}{305127}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{380214} = \frac{864}{570321}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{201436} = \frac{867}{302154}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{342160} = \frac{867}{513240}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{203814} = \frac{864}{305721}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{381402} = \frac{864}{572103}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{201634} = \frac{867}{302451}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{360142} = \frac{867}{540213}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{214038} = \frac{864}{321057}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{381420} = \frac{864}{572130}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{203416} = \frac{867}{305124}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{360214} = \frac{867}{540321}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{218034} = \frac{864}{327051}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{382014} = \frac{864}{573021}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{203614} = \frac{867}{305421}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{361402} = \frac{867}{542103}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{218340} = \frac{864}{327510}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{382140} = \frac{864}{573210}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{214036} = \frac{867}{321054}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{361420} = \frac{867}{542130}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{231840} = \frac{684}{275310}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{438120} = \frac{632}{480715}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{214360} = \frac{867}{321540}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{362014} = \frac{867}{543021}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{234018} = \frac{864}{351027}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{103462} = \frac{752}{134608}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{216034} = \frac{867}{324051}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{362140} = \frac{867}{543210}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{234180} = \frac{864}{351270}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{140236} = \frac{867}{210354}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{216340} = \frac{867}{324510}$	$\triangleright \frac{580}{134672} = \frac{725}{168340}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{238014} = \frac{864}{357021}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{140362} = \frac{867}{210543}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{234016} = \frac{867}{351024}$	$\triangleright \frac{580}{143762} = \frac{870}{215643}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{284301} = \frac{832}{410657}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{142036} = \frac{867}{213054}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{234160} = \frac{867}{351240}$	$\triangleright \frac{580}{162374} = \frac{870}{243561}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{314028} = \frac{736}{401258}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{142360} = \frac{867}{213540}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{236014} = \frac{867}{354021}$	$\triangleright \frac{580}{163742} = \frac{870}{245613}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{321480} = \frac{728}{406315}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{143602} = \frac{867}{215403}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{236140} = \frac{867}{354210}$	$\triangleright \frac{580}{172463} = \frac{620}{184357}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{340182} = \frac{864}{510273}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{143620} = \frac{867}{215430}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{243610} = \frac{748}{315260}$	$\triangleright \frac{580}{174236} = \frac{870}{261354}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{340218} = \frac{864}{510327}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{160234} = \frac{867}{240351}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{321640} = \frac{782}{435160}$	$\triangleright \frac{580}{174362} = \frac{870}{261543}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{341802} = \frac{864}{512703}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{160342} = \frac{867}{240513}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{340162} = \frac{867}{510243}$	$\triangleright \frac{580}{176234} = \frac{870}{264351}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{341820} = \frac{864}{512730}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{162034} = \frac{867}{243051}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{340216} = \frac{867}{510324}$	$\triangleright \frac{580}{176342} = \frac{870}{264513}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{342018} = \frac{864}{513027}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{162340} = \frac{867}{243510}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{341602} = \frac{867}{512403}$	$\triangleright \frac{580}{216374} = \frac{870}{324561}$
$\triangleright \frac{576}{342180} = \frac{864}{513270}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{163402} = \frac{867}{245103}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{341620} = \frac{867}{512430}$	$\triangleright \frac{580}{217436} = \frac{870}{326154}$

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|---|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{580}{217634} = \frac{870}{326451}$ | ▶ $\frac{582}{174036} = \frac{873}{261054}$ | ▶ $\frac{584}{673012} = \frac{730}{841265}$ | ▶ $\frac{612}{587340} = \frac{714}{685230}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{580}{234176} = \frac{870}{351264}$ | ▶ $\frac{582}{174360} = \frac{873}{261540}$ | ▶ $\frac{602}{173548} = \frac{714}{205836}$ | ▶ $\frac{612}{708543} = \frac{736}{852104}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{580}{236174} = \frac{870}{354261}$ | ▶ $\frac{582}{176034} = \frac{873}{264051}$ | ▶ $\frac{604}{125783} = \frac{780}{162435}$ | ▶ $\frac{612}{730548} = \frac{714}{852306}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{580}{237614} = \frac{870}{356421}$ | ▶ $\frac{582}{176340} = \frac{873}{264510}$ | ▶ $\frac{605}{172348} = \frac{715}{203684}$ | ▶ $\frac{615}{340287} = \frac{820}{453716}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{580}{243716} = \frac{670}{281534}$ | ▶ $\frac{582}{340176} = \frac{873}{510264}$ | ▶ $\frac{605}{182347} = \frac{840}{253176}$ | ▶ $\frac{615}{402873} = \frac{820}{537164}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{580}{326714} = \frac{810}{456273}$ | ▶ $\frac{582}{341760} = \frac{873}{512640}$ | ▶ $\frac{605}{271348} = \frac{715}{320684}$ | ▶ $\frac{615}{407382} = \frac{820}{543176}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{580}{341762} = \frac{870}{512643}$ | ▶ $\frac{582}{360174} = \frac{873}{540261}$ | ▶ $\frac{605}{318472} = \frac{725}{381640}$ | ▶ $\frac{615}{420783} = \frac{705}{482361}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{580}{342176} = \frac{870}{513264}$ | ▶ $\frac{582}{361740} = \frac{873}{542610}$ | ▶ $\frac{605}{327184} = \frac{705}{381264}$ | ▶ $\frac{618}{245037} = \frac{768}{304512}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{580}{361742} = \frac{870}{542613}$ | ▶ $\frac{582}{374016} = \frac{873}{561024}$ | ▶ $\frac{605}{713482} = \frac{715}{843206}$ | ▶ $\frac{618}{350274} = \frac{721}{408653}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{580}{362174} = \frac{870}{543261}$ | ▶ $\frac{582}{374160} = \frac{873}{561240}$ | ▶ $\frac{605}{817234} = \frac{615}{830742}$ | ▶ $\frac{618}{540732} = \frac{721}{630854}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{580}{374162} = \frac{870}{561243}$ | ▶ $\frac{582}{376014} = \frac{873}{564021}$ | ▶ $\frac{608}{174352} = \frac{874}{250631}$ | ▶ $\frac{618}{547320} = \frac{721}{638540}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{580}{376142} = \frac{870}{564213}$ | ▶ $\frac{582}{376140} = \frac{873}{564210}$ | ▶ $\frac{608}{452713} = \frac{736}{548021}$ | ▶ $\frac{618}{732054} = \frac{721}{854063}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{580}{376214} = \frac{870}{564321}$ | ▶ $\frac{582}{403617} = \frac{726}{503481}$ | ▶ $\frac{608}{471352} = \frac{684}{530271}$ | ▶ $\frac{618}{732540} = \frac{721}{854630}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{580}{413627} = \frac{720}{513468}$ | ▶ $\frac{582}{641073} = \frac{654}{720381}$ | ▶ $\frac{608}{473512} = \frac{684}{532701}$ | ▶ $\frac{620}{581374} = \frac{730}{684521}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{580}{634172} = \frac{680}{743512}$ | ▶ $\frac{584}{127360} = \frac{657}{143280}$ | ▶ $\frac{610}{247538} = \frac{780}{316524}$ | ▶ $\frac{621}{387504} = \frac{738}{460512}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{582}{140376} = \frac{873}{210564}$ | ▶ $\frac{584}{130276} = \frac{730}{162845}$ | ▶ $\frac{612}{538740} = \frac{714}{628530}$ | ▶ $\frac{621}{753408} = \frac{713}{865024}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{582}{143760} = \frac{873}{215640}$ | ▶ $\frac{584}{170236} = \frac{602}{175483}$ | ▶ $\frac{612}{570384} = \frac{801}{746532}$ | ▶ $\frac{624}{105378} = \frac{760}{128345}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{582}{160374} = \frac{873}{240561}$ | ▶ $\frac{584}{370621} = \frac{760}{482315}$ | ▶ $\frac{612}{573840} = \frac{731}{685420}$ | ▶ $\frac{624}{158730} = \frac{840}{213675}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{582}{163740} = \frac{873}{245610}$ | ▶ $\frac{584}{670213} = \frac{752}{863014}$ | ▶ $\frac{612}{583074} = \frac{714}{680253}$ | ▶ $\frac{624}{305178} = \frac{728}{356041}$ |

- | | | | |
|---|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{624}{385710} = \frac{672}{415380}$ | ▶ $\frac{642}{173805} = \frac{856}{231740}$ | ▶ $\frac{654}{732018} = \frac{763}{854021}$ | ▶ $\frac{702}{345816} = \frac{741}{365028}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{624}{513708} = \frac{780}{642135}$ | ▶ $\frac{642}{715830} = \frac{723}{806145}$ | ▶ $\frac{654}{732180} = \frac{763}{854210}$ | ▶ $\frac{702}{513864} = \frac{738}{540216}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{624}{517830} = \frac{728}{604135}$ | ▶ $\frac{643}{520187} = \frac{748}{605132}$ | ▶ $\frac{658}{137240} = \frac{784}{163520}$ | ▶ $\frac{702}{613548} = \frac{738}{645012}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{624}{537810} = \frac{752}{648130}$ | ▶ $\frac{645}{107328} = \frac{785}{130624}$ | ▶ $\frac{670}{428135} = \frac{804}{513762}$ | ▶ $\frac{702}{631584} = \frac{715}{643280}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{625}{318470} = \frac{750}{382164}$ | ▶ $\frac{645}{281370} = \frac{817}{356402}$ | ▶ $\frac{671}{502348} = \frac{732}{548016}$ | ▶ $\frac{708}{123546} = \frac{748}{130526}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{627}{438501} = \frac{781}{546203}$ | ▶ $\frac{648}{103572} = \frac{756}{120834}$ | ▶ $\frac{671}{532048} = \frac{732}{580416}$ | ▶ $\frac{710}{386425} = \frac{852}{463710}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{630}{125874} = \frac{720}{143856}$ | ▶ $\frac{648}{157032} = \frac{756}{183204}$ | ▶ $\frac{672}{130548} = \frac{784}{152306}$ | ▶ $\frac{710}{652348} = \frac{820}{753416}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{630}{245178} = \frac{735}{286041}$ | ▶ $\frac{650}{231478} = \frac{675}{240381}$ | ▶ $\frac{672}{134085} = \frac{768}{153240}$ | ▶ $\frac{714}{302568} = \frac{765}{324180}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{630}{425187} = \frac{670}{452183}$ | ▶ $\frac{650}{431782} = \frac{725}{481603}$ | ▶ $\frac{672}{135840} = \frac{854}{172630}$ | ▶ $\frac{714}{826350} = \frac{731}{846025}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{630}{481725} = \frac{672}{513840}$ | ▶ $\frac{650}{782314} = \frac{675}{812403}$ | ▶ $\frac{672}{185340} = \frac{840}{231675}$ | ▶ $\frac{715}{603482} = \frac{845}{713206}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{630}{517824} = \frac{735}{604128}$ | ▶ $\frac{651}{273048} = \frac{812}{340576}$ | ▶ $\frac{672}{315840} = \frac{762}{358140}$ | ▶ $\frac{725}{108634} = \frac{850}{127364}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{632}{178540} = \frac{764}{215830}$ | ▶ $\frac{651}{340872} = \frac{682}{357104}$ | ▶ $\frac{678}{240351} = \frac{876}{310542}$ | ▶ $\frac{725}{384610} = \frac{870}{461532}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{635}{127840} = \frac{762}{153408}$ | ▶ $\frac{652}{370184} = \frac{815}{462730}$ | ▶ $\frac{680}{127534} = \frac{760}{142538}$ | ▶ $\frac{726}{130548} = \frac{847}{152306}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{635}{417820} = \frac{762}{501384}$ | ▶ $\frac{652}{378104} = \frac{815}{472630}$ | ▶ $\frac{680}{134725} = \frac{736}{145820}$ | ▶ $\frac{728}{135460} = \frac{742}{138065}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{635}{428170} = \frac{762}{513804}$ | ▶ $\frac{654}{102378} = \frac{872}{136504}$ | ▶ $\frac{680}{143752} = \frac{830}{175462}$ | ▶ $\frac{728}{136045} = \frac{768}{143520}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{638}{541720} = \frac{748}{635120}$ | ▶ $\frac{654}{107832} = \frac{763}{125804}$ | ▶ $\frac{680}{174352} = \frac{840}{215376}$ | ▶ $\frac{728}{413056} = \frac{806}{457312}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{638}{714502} = \frac{726}{813054}$ | ▶ $\frac{654}{180732} = \frac{763}{210854}$ | ▶ $\frac{680}{435217} = \frac{840}{537621}$ | ▶ $\frac{728}{631540} = \frac{738}{640215}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{640}{127835} = \frac{768}{153402}$ | ▶ $\frac{654}{187320} = \frac{763}{218540}$ | ▶ $\frac{680}{741352} = \frac{765}{834021}$ | ▶ $\frac{731}{468520} = \frac{817}{523640}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{640}{138752} = \frac{730}{158264}$ | ▶ $\frac{654}{378102} = \frac{872}{504136}$ | ▶ $\frac{687}{205413} = \frac{786}{235014}$ | ▶ $\frac{732}{105486} = \frac{854}{123067}$ |

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{154086} = \frac{784}{165032}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{605418} = \frac{854}{706321}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{742}{135680} = \frac{756}{138240}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{807}{236451} = \frac{867}{254031}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{180546} = \frac{854}{210637}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{610548} = \frac{854}{712306}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{748}{231506} = \frac{758}{234601}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{810}{732564} = \frac{825}{746130}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{180654} = \frac{854}{210763}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{618054} = \frac{854}{721063}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{752}{308461} = \frac{768}{315024}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{810}{734265} = \frac{834}{756021}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{185406} = \frac{854}{216307}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{654018} = \frac{854}{763021}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{754}{231608} = \frac{783}{240516}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{816}{237405} = \frac{864}{251370}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{185460} = \frac{854}{216370}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{735}{146280} = \frac{784}{156032}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{760}{328415} = \frac{824}{356071}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{825}{307164} = \frac{850}{316472}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{186054} = \frac{854}{217063}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{735}{264810} = \frac{847}{305162}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{765}{123840} = \frac{867}{140352}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{840}{153762} = \frac{860}{157423}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{186540} = \frac{854}{217630}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{735}{286140} = \frac{784}{305216}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{768}{135420} = \frac{832}{146705}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{843}{125607} = \frac{876}{130524}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{540186} = \frac{854}{630217}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{736}{145280} = \frac{782}{154360}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{780}{351624} = \frac{815}{367402}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{845}{721630} = \frac{856}{731024}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{540618} = \frac{854}{630721}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{736}{182045} = \frac{864}{213705}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{780}{421356} = \frac{810}{437562}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{846}{307521} = \frac{870}{316245}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{541806} = \frac{854}{632107}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{736}{215840} = \frac{874}{256310}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{782}{453016} = \frac{874}{506312}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{546018} = \frac{854}{637021}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{738}{254610} = \frac{801}{276345}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{782}{541603} = \frac{874}{605321}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{601854} = \frac{854}{702163}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{741}{308256} = \frac{765}{318240}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{805}{146372} = \frac{840}{152736}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{50}{1387624} = \frac{75}{2081436}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{50}{2418736} = \frac{75}{3628104}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{51}{2370684} = \frac{81}{3765204}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{50}{1387642} = \frac{75}{2081463}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{50}{4138762} = \frac{75}{6208143}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{51}{2476038} = \frac{85}{4126730}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{50}{1873624} = \frac{75}{2810436}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{50}{4187362} = \frac{75}{6281043}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{51}{2648073} = \frac{81}{4205763}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{50}{1873642} = \frac{75}{2810463}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{50}{4213876} = \frac{75}{6320814}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{51}{2736048} = \frac{65}{3487120}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{50}{2138764} = \frac{75}{3208146}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{50}{4218736} = \frac{75}{6328104}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{51}{3467082} = \frac{54}{3671028}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{50}{2187364} = \frac{75}{3281046}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{51}{2036478} = \frac{68}{2715304}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{51}{3674082} = \frac{85}{6123470}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{50}{2413876} = \frac{75}{3620814}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{51}{2063478} = \frac{68}{2751304}$$

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$\triangleright \frac{51}{3762804} = \frac{85}{6271340}$

$\triangleright \frac{52}{3841760} = \frac{56}{4137280}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1623780} = \frac{81}{2435670}$

$\triangleright \frac{51}{3764208} = \frac{71}{5240368}$

$\triangleright \frac{52}{3861704} = \frac{65}{4827130}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1637802} = \frac{81}{2456703}$

$\triangleright \frac{51}{3786240} = \frac{57}{4231680}$

$\triangleright \frac{52}{6730184} = \frac{65}{8412730}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1637820} = \frac{81}{2456730}$

$\triangleright \frac{51}{3804762} = \frac{85}{6341270}$

$\triangleright \frac{52}{7016438} = \frac{54}{7286301}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1760238} = \frac{81}{2640357}$

$\triangleright \frac{51}{3827604} = \frac{68}{5103472}$

$\triangleright \frac{53}{1068427} = \frac{76}{1532084}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1760382} = \frac{81}{2640573}$

$\triangleright \frac{51}{3860274} = \frac{68}{5147032}$

$\triangleright \frac{53}{1074628} = \frac{85}{1723460}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1762038} = \frac{81}{2643057}$

$\triangleright \frac{51}{4328076} = \frac{85}{7213460}$

$\triangleright \frac{53}{2786104} = \frac{82}{4310576}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1762380} = \frac{81}{2643570}$

$\triangleright \frac{51}{4673028} = \frac{83}{7605124}$

$\triangleright \frac{53}{6172804} = \frac{73}{8502164}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1762830} = \frac{78}{2546310}$

$\triangleright \frac{51}{6042378} = \frac{72}{8530416}$

$\triangleright \frac{53}{6214780} = \frac{71}{8325460}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1763802} = \frac{81}{2645703}$

$\triangleright \frac{51}{6042837} = \frac{72}{8531064}$

$\triangleright \frac{53}{6410827} = \frac{67}{8104253}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1763820} = \frac{81}{2645730}$

$\triangleright \frac{51}{6342870} = \frac{58}{7213460}$

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$\triangleright \frac{54}{1780236} = \frac{81}{2670354}$

$\triangleright \frac{52}{1038674} = \frac{54}{1078623}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1026378} = \frac{72}{1368504}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1780362} = \frac{81}{2670543}$

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$\triangleright \frac{54}{1078326} = \frac{63}{1258047}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1782036} = \frac{81}{2673054}$

$\triangleright \frac{52}{1048736} = \frac{63}{1270584}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1328670} = \frac{87}{2140635}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1782360} = \frac{81}{2673540}$

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$\triangleright \frac{54}{1382670} = \frac{72}{1843560}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1783620} = \frac{81}{2675430}$

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$\triangleright \frac{54}{1602378} = \frac{81}{2403567}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{1802376} = \frac{81}{2703564}$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{1823760} = \frac{81}{2735640}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{1827063} = \frac{70}{2368415}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{1860732} = \frac{63}{2170854}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{1867320} = \frac{63}{2178540}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{1873260} = \frac{63}{2185470}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{2018376} = \frac{81}{3027564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{2031768} = \frac{81}{3047652}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{2036178} = \frac{81}{3054267}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{2037618} = \frac{81}{3056427}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{2038716} = \frac{71}{2680534}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{2176380} = \frac{81}{3264570}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{2307168} = \frac{81}{3460752}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{2671380} = \frac{72}{3561840}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{3617802} = \frac{81}{5426703}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{3620178} = \frac{81}{5430267}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{3670218} = \frac{78}{5301426}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{3760182} = \frac{81}{5640273}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{3760218} = \frac{81}{5640327}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{3761802} = \frac{81}{5642703}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{3761820} = \frac{81}{5642730}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{3762018} = \frac{81}{5643027}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{3762180} = \frac{81}{5643270}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{54}{3780162} = \frac{81}{5670243}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{54}{3781026} = \frac{72}{5041368}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{54}{3781602} = \frac{81}{5672403}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{54}{3781620} = \frac{81}{5672430}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{54}{3782016} = \frac{81}{5673024}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{54}{3786102} = \frac{72}{5048136}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{54}{3801762} = \frac{81}{5702643}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{54}{3802176} = \frac{81}{5703264}$$

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$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1437802} = \frac{84}{2156703}$$

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$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1740382} = \frac{84}{2610573}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1742038} = \frac{84}{2613057}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1743802} = \frac{84}{2615703}$$

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$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1780234} = \frac{84}{2670351}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1780342} = \frac{84}{2670513}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1782034} = \frac{84}{2673051}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1782340} = \frac{84}{2673510}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1783402} = \frac{84}{2675103}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1783420} = \frac{84}{2675130}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1802374} = \frac{84}{2703561}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1803742} = \frac{84}{2705613}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1820374} = \frac{84}{2730561}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1837402} = \frac{84}{2756103}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{1843720} = \frac{63}{2074185}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{2014378} = \frac{84}{3021567}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{2017438} = \frac{84}{3026157}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{2017834} = \frac{84}{3026751}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{2018374} = \frac{84}{3027561}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{2034178} = \frac{84}{3051267}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{2037418} = \frac{84}{3056127}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{2037814} = \frac{84}{3056721}$$

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$$\triangleright \frac{56}{2178340} = \frac{84}{3267510}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{2180374} = \frac{84}{3270561}$$

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$$\triangleright \frac{561}{287430} = \frac{714}{365820}$$

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$$\triangleright \frac{58}{1403762} = \frac{87}{2105643}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{1406732} = \frac{62}{1503748}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{1420376} = \frac{87}{2130564}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{1423760} = \frac{87}{2135640}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{1437602} = \frac{87}{2156403}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{1437620} = \frac{87}{2156430}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{1602374} = \frac{87}{2403561}$$

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$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2016374} = \frac{87}{3024561}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2017436} = \frac{87}{3026154}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2017634} = \frac{87}{3026451}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2034176} = \frac{87}{3051264}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2036174} = \frac{87}{3054261}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2037416} = \frac{87}{3056124}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2037614} = \frac{87}{3056421}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2140376} = \frac{87}{3210564}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2143760} = \frac{87}{3215640}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2160374} = \frac{87}{3240561}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2163740} = \frac{87}{3245610}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2174036} = \frac{87}{3261054}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2174360} = \frac{87}{3261540}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2176034} = \frac{87}{3264051}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2176340} = \frac{87}{3264510}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2340176} = \frac{87}{3510264}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2341760} = \frac{87}{3512640}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2346071} = \frac{70}{2831465}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{58}{2360174} = \frac{87}{3540261}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{2361740} = \frac{87}{3542610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{2374016} = \frac{87}{3561024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{2374160} = \frac{87}{3561240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{2376014} = \frac{87}{3564021}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{2376140} = \frac{87}{3564210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{2437160} = \frac{67}{2815340}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3267140} = \frac{81}{4562730}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3401762} = \frac{87}{5102643}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3402176} = \frac{87}{5103264}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3417602} = \frac{87}{5126403}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3417620} = \frac{87}{5126430}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3420176} = \frac{87}{5130264}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3421760} = \frac{87}{5132640}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3601742} = \frac{87}{5402613}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3602174} = \frac{87}{5403261}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3617402} = \frac{87}{5426103}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3617420} = \frac{87}{5426130}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3620174} = \frac{87}{5430261}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3621740} = \frac{87}{5432610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3740162} = \frac{87}{5610243}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3740216} = \frac{87}{5610324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3741602} = \frac{87}{5612403}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3741620} = \frac{87}{5612430}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3742016} = \frac{87}{5613024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3760142} = \frac{87}{5640213}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3760214} = \frac{87}{5640321}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3761402} = \frac{87}{5642103}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3761420} = \frac{87}{5642130}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3762014} = \frac{87}{5643021}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3762140} = \frac{87}{5643210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{4136270} = \frac{72}{5134680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{4312706} = \frac{73}{5428061}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{4671320} = \frac{81}{6523740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{6341720} = \frac{68}{7435120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{1253874} = \frac{70}{1462853}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{1258734} = \frac{70}{1468523}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{1345872} = \frac{75}{1682340}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{1582734} = \frac{70}{1846523}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{1853472} = \frac{75}{2316840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{1854732} = \frac{70}{2163854}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{1873254} = \frac{70}{2185463}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{2387145} = \frac{68}{2705431}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{2573184} = \frac{75}{3216480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{2834715} = \frac{72}{3401658}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{4823715} = \frac{84}{6753201}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{5384172} = \frac{70}{6281534}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{5387412} = \frac{70}{6285314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{5418732} = \frac{70}{6321854}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{5473218} = \frac{70}{6385421}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{5873412} = \frac{70}{6852314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{7321854} = \frac{70}{8542163}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{60}{7325418} = \frac{70}{8546321}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{61}{2475380} = \frac{78}{3165240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{61}{2874503} = \frac{64}{3015872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{61}{3025478} = \frac{87}{4315026}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{61}{3082574} = \frac{65}{3284710}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{61}{4037285} = \frac{78}{5162430}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62}{3718450} = \frac{67}{4018325}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62}{4305187} = \frac{78}{5416203}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62}{4751308} = \frac{81}{6207354}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{62}{5813740} = \frac{73}{6845210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{1258740} = \frac{72}{1438560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{1540287} = \frac{84}{2053716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{1578024} = \frac{72}{1803456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{2047185} = \frac{78}{2534610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{2740815} = \frac{82}{3567410}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{4028715} = \frac{84}{5371620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{4251870} = \frac{67}{4521830}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{4270581} = \frac{74}{5016238}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{5720841} = \frac{72}{6538104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{63}{7015428} = \frac{65}{7238140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{1078352} = \frac{76}{1280543}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{1387520} = \frac{73}{1582640}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{2517380} = \frac{80}{3146725}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{2531780} = \frac{80}{3164725}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{2573180} = \frac{80}{3216475}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{3701852} = \frac{80}{4627315}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{3781052} = \frac{80}{4726315}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{3785012} = \frac{80}{4731265}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{3810572} = \frac{80}{4763215}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{5018732} = \frac{80}{6273415}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{5103872} = \frac{73}{5821604}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{5810732} = \frac{80}{7263415}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{64}{5873012} = \frac{80}{7341265}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{1247038} = \frac{85}{1630742}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{1407328} = \frac{75}{1623840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{2348710} = \frac{86}{3107524}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{2417038} = \frac{85}{3160742}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{2834710} = \frac{78}{3401652}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{3087214} = \frac{85}{4037126}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{3714802} = \frac{75}{4286310}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{4283071} = \frac{70}{4612538}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{7048132} = \frac{75}{8132460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67}{1083524} = \frac{85}{1374620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67}{3452108} = \frac{71}{3658204}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67}{4532081} = \frac{71}{4802653}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67}{5308142} = \frac{85}{6734210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67}{8023451} = \frac{71}{8502463}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67}{8120534} = \frac{71}{8605342}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{1275034} = \frac{76}{1425038}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{1275340} = \frac{76}{1425380}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{1375402} = \frac{72}{1456308}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{1437520} = \frac{83}{1754620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{1543702} = \frac{72}{1634508}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{1704352} = \frac{84}{2105376}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{1743520} = \frac{84}{2153760}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{2315740} = \frac{73}{2486015}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{3401275} = \frac{76}{3801425}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{4352017} = \frac{84}{5376021}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{4703152} = \frac{83}{5740612}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{68}{5302147} = \frac{72}{5614038}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70}{1243865} = \frac{76}{1350482}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70}{1438625} = \frac{84}{1726350}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{70}{1483265} = \frac{74}{1568023}$$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{70}{1523648} = \frac{75}{1632480}$ | ▶ $\frac{73}{5240816} = \frac{74}{5312608}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{14237860} = \frac{6}{17085432}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{70}{3125864} = \frac{80}{3572416}$ | ▶ $\frac{73}{6210548} = \frac{85}{7231460}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{14382760} = \frac{7}{20135864}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{70}{3142685} = \frac{76}{3412058}$ | ▶ $\frac{74}{1063528} = \frac{87}{1250364}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{14736820} = \frac{7}{20631548}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{70}{3561824} = \frac{75}{3816240}$ | ▶ $\frac{75}{1432680} = \frac{85}{1623704}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{14836270} = \frac{6}{17803524}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{70}{3812564} = \frac{80}{4357216}$ | ▶ $\frac{76}{2350148} = \frac{81}{2504763}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{18472360} = \frac{7}{25861304}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{70}{6532148} = \frac{80}{7465312}$ | ▶ $\frac{76}{3405218} = \frac{82}{3674051}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{21843760} = \frac{7}{30581264}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{71}{2064538} = \frac{85}{2471630}$ | ▶ $\frac{76}{4531082} = \frac{78}{4650321}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{23146870} = \frac{7}{32405618}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{71}{2340586} = \frac{73}{2406518}$ | ▶ $\frac{78}{1453062} = \frac{83}{1546207}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{23186470} = \frac{7}{32461058}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{71}{4603285} = \frac{82}{5316470}$ | ▶ $\frac{78}{2314650} = \frac{81}{2403675}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{26438170} = \frac{6}{31725804}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{71}{5608432} = \frac{85}{6714320}$ | ▶ $\frac{78}{3241056} = \frac{87}{3615024}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{26483710} = \frac{6}{31780452}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{71}{6523480} = \frac{82}{7534160}$ | ▶ $\frac{78}{4013256} = \frac{83}{4270516}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{27436180} = \frac{7}{38410652}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{72}{1305486} = \frac{84}{1523067}$ | ▶ $\frac{78}{4213560} = \frac{81}{4375620}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{31267840} = \frac{6}{37521408}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{72}{6130548} = \frac{84}{7152306}$ | ▶ $\frac{78}{5621304} = \frac{84}{6053712}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{31482760} = \frac{8}{50372416}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{73}{1042586} = \frac{76}{1085432}$ | ▶ $\frac{78}{6502314} = \frac{81}{6752403}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{31728460} = \frac{6}{38074152}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{73}{1204865} = \frac{76}{1254380}$ | ▶ $\frac{80}{1324576} = \frac{85}{1407362}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{31876420} = \frac{6}{38251704}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{73}{1502486} = \frac{74}{1523068}$ | ▶ $\frac{81}{5603742} = \frac{83}{5742106}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{34721680} = \frac{7}{48610352}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{73}{4016825} = \frac{86}{4732150}$ | ▶ $\frac{83}{4056127} = \frac{87}{4251603}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{37241860} = \frac{7}{52138604}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{73}{4062158} = \frac{81}{4507326}$ | ▶ $\frac{84}{1537620} = \frac{86}{1574230}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{38146720} = \frac{8}{61034752}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{73}{4062815} = \frac{82}{4563710}$ | ▶ $\frac{85}{1732640} = \frac{86}{1753024}$ | ▶ $\frac{5}{38472160} = \frac{7}{53861024}$ |

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{5}{41872360} = \frac{7}{58621304}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{12380574} = \frac{8}{16507432}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{17382405} = \frac{8}{23176540}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5}{42317860} = \frac{6}{50781432}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{12435708} = \frac{7}{14508326}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{18054732} = \frac{7}{21063854}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5}{42367810} = \frac{6}{50841372}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{12538740} = \frac{7}{14628530}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{18073254} = \frac{7}{21085463}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5}{43172860} = \frac{6}{51807432}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{12583074} = \frac{7}{14680253}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{18350274} = \frac{7}{21408653}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5}{43716820} = \frac{7}{61203548}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{12587340} = \frac{7}{14685230}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{18540732} = \frac{7}{21630854}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5}{48372610} = \frac{6}{58047132}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{12730548} = \frac{7}{14852306}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{18547320} = \frac{7}{21638540}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5}{48723610} = \frac{7}{68213054}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{13054872} = \frac{7}{15230684}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{18732054} = \frac{7}{21854063}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5}{72834610} = \frac{6}{87401532}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{13270548} = \frac{7}{15482306}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{18732540} = \frac{7}{21854630}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{6}{10237854} = \frac{8}{13650472}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{15340287} = \frac{8}{20453716}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{21058374} = \frac{7}{24568103}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{6}{10254378} = \frac{8}{13672504}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{15402873} = \frac{8}{20537164}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{23014578} = \frac{7}{26850341}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{6}{10325874} = \frac{7}{12046853}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{15407382} = \frac{8}{20543176}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{24305178} = \frac{7}{28356041}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{6}{10357248} = \frac{7}{12083456}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{15703248} = \frac{7}{18320456}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{24517830} = \frac{7}{28604135}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{6}{10358274} = \frac{7}{12084653}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{15708432} = \frac{7}{18326504}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{25841370} = \frac{7}{30148265}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{6}{10548732} = \frac{7}{12306854}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{15724308} = \frac{7}{18345026}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{27053184} = \frac{7}{31562048}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{6}{10745832} = \frac{7}{12536804}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{15784032} = \frac{8}{21045376}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{27583410} = \frac{7}{32180645}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{6}{10783254} = \frac{7}{12580463}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{15784302} = \frac{8}{21045736}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{30245178} = \frac{7}{35286041}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{6}{10843572} = \frac{7}{12650834}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{15823074} = \frac{7}{18460253}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{30517824} = \frac{7}{35604128}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{6}{12053874} = \frac{7}{14062853}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{15827340} = \frac{7}{18465230}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{31540287} = \frac{8}{42053716}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{6}{12058734} = \frac{7}{14068523}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{17380542} = \frac{8}{23174056}$ | ▶ $\frac{6}{34028715} = \frac{8}{45371620}$ |

▶ $\frac{6}{34507128} = \frac{7}{40258316}$	▶ $\frac{6}{52731804} = \frac{7}{61520438}$	▶ $\frac{6}{58417032} = \frac{7}{68153204}$
▶ $\frac{6}{34871250} = \frac{7}{40683125}$	▶ $\frac{6}{53184270} = \frac{7}{62048315}$	▶ $\frac{6}{58734012} = \frac{7}{68523014}$
▶ $\frac{6}{35027418} = \frac{7}{40865321}$	▶ $\frac{6}{53271804} = \frac{7}{62150438}$	▶ $\frac{6}{58734120} = \frac{7}{68523140}$
▶ $\frac{6}{37810254} = \frac{8}{50413672}$	▶ $\frac{6}{53841720} = \frac{7}{62815340}$	▶ $\frac{6}{58741032} = \frac{7}{68531204}$
▶ $\frac{6}{37854102} = \frac{8}{50472136}$	▶ $\frac{6}{53874012} = \frac{7}{62853014}$	▶ $\frac{6}{70548132} = \frac{7}{82306154}$
▶ $\frac{6}{38752014} = \frac{7}{45210683}$	▶ $\frac{6}{53874120} = \frac{7}{62853140}$	▶ $\frac{6}{71250348} = \frac{7}{83125406}$
▶ $\frac{6}{40287153} = \frac{8}{53716204}$	▶ $\frac{6}{54018732} = \frac{7}{63021854}$	▶ $\frac{6}{71283450} = \frac{7}{83164025}$
▶ $\frac{6}{40287315} = \frac{8}{53716420}$	▶ $\frac{6}{54073218} = \frac{7}{63085421}$	▶ $\frac{6}{72130548} = \frac{7}{84152306}$
▶ $\frac{6}{40321578} = \frac{8}{53762104}$	▶ $\frac{6}{54102378} = \frac{8}{72136504}$	▶ $\frac{6}{73054812} = \frac{7}{85230614}$
▶ $\frac{6}{40517382} = \frac{8}{54023176}$	▶ $\frac{6}{54107832} = \frac{7}{63125804}$	▶ $\frac{6}{73201854} = \frac{7}{85402163}$
▶ $\frac{6}{40738215} = \frac{8}{54317620}$	▶ $\frac{6}{54180732} = \frac{7}{63210854}$	▶ $\frac{6}{73205418} = \frac{7}{85406321}$
▶ $\frac{6}{41370258} = \frac{7}{48265301}$	▶ $\frac{6}{54187320} = \frac{7}{63218540}$	▶ $\frac{6}{73210548} = \frac{7}{85412306}$
▶ $\frac{6}{42173805} = \frac{8}{56231740}$	▶ $\frac{6}{54378102} = \frac{8}{72504136}$	▶ $\frac{6}{73218054} = \frac{7}{85421063}$
▶ $\frac{6}{43021578} = \frac{8}{57362104}$	▶ $\frac{6}{54732018} = \frac{7}{63854021}$	▶ $\frac{6}{73218540} = \frac{7}{85421630}$
▶ $\frac{6}{43102578} = \frac{7}{50286341}$	▶ $\frac{6}{54732180} = \frac{7}{63854210}$	▶ $\frac{6}{73254018} = \frac{7}{85463021}$
▶ $\frac{6}{47035128} = \frac{8}{62713504}$	▶ $\frac{6}{58304172} = \frac{7}{68021534}$	▶ $\frac{6}{73254180} = \frac{7}{85463210}$
▶ $\frac{6}{47051328} = \frac{8}{62735104}$	▶ $\frac{6}{58307412} = \frac{7}{68025314}$	▶ $\frac{7}{12840653} = \frac{8}{14675032}$
▶ $\frac{6}{51782430} = \frac{7}{60412835}$	▶ $\frac{6}{58321074} = \frac{7}{68041253}$	▶ $\frac{7}{31258640} = \frac{8}{35724160}$
▶ $\frac{6}{51783024} = \frac{7}{60413528}$	▶ $\frac{6}{58374210} = \frac{7}{68103245}$	▶ $\frac{7}{32506481} = \frac{8}{37150264}$

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{7}{38125640} = \frac{8}{43572160} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{7}{40265183} = \frac{8}{46017352} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{7}{41256803} = \frac{8}{47150632} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{7}{41568023} = \frac{8}{47506312} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{7}{46502813} = \frac{8}{53146072} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{7}{65321480} = \frac{8}{74653120} \end{array}$$

6.2 9-Digits: 1 to 9

This subsection bring equivalent fractions for the digits 1 to 9, starting from higher to lower equivalent expressions in each case.

6.2.1 46 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have only one example, and in this situation it has maximum expressions.

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{3187}{25496} = \frac{4589}{36712} = \frac{4591}{36728} = \frac{4689}{37512} = \frac{4691}{37528} = \frac{4769}{38152} = \frac{5237}{41896} = \frac{5371}{42968} = \frac{5789}{46312} = \frac{5791}{46328} = \frac{5839}{46712} \\ \qquad = \frac{5892}{47136} = \frac{5916}{47328} = \frac{5921}{47368} = \frac{5932}{51832} = \frac{5938}{53928} = \frac{6479}{54312} = \frac{6789}{54328} = \frac{6791}{54712} = \frac{6839}{56984} = \frac{7123}{58496} \\ \qquad = \frac{7364}{58912} = \frac{7416}{59328} = \frac{7421}{59368} = \frac{7421}{63152} = \frac{7421}{63528} = \frac{7894}{65392} = \frac{7941}{65432} = \frac{8174}{67152} = \frac{8179}{67352} = \frac{8394}{67512} \\ \qquad = \frac{8394}{8932} = \frac{8942}{8942} = \frac{8953}{8953} = \frac{8954}{8954} = \frac{9156}{9156} = \frac{9158}{9158} = \frac{9182}{9182} = \frac{9316}{9316} = \frac{9321}{9321} = \frac{9352}{9352} \\ \qquad = \frac{71456}{9416} = \frac{71536}{9421} = \frac{71624}{9523} = \frac{71632}{9531} = \frac{73248}{9541} = \frac{73264}{9541} = \frac{73456}{9541} = \frac{74528}{9541} = \frac{74568}{9541} = \frac{74816}{9541} \\ \qquad = \frac{75328}{75328} = \frac{75368}{75368} = \frac{76184}{76184} = \frac{76248}{76248} = \frac{76328}{76328} \end{array}$$

6.2.2 27 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have only one example:

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{1579}{26843} = \frac{1679}{28543} = \frac{1738}{29546} = \frac{2174}{36958} = \frac{2689}{45713} = \frac{2693}{45781} = \frac{3217}{54689} = \frac{3478}{59126} = \frac{3821}{64957} = \frac{3841}{65297} \\ \qquad = \frac{3952}{67184} = \frac{3954}{67218} = \frac{4519}{76823} = \frac{4523}{76891} = \frac{4596}{78132} = \frac{4619}{78523} = \frac{4623}{78591} = \frac{4796}{81532} = \frac{4916}{83572} \\ \qquad = \frac{4921}{83657} = \frac{5261}{89437} = \frac{5263}{89471} = \frac{5273}{89641} = \frac{5378}{91426} = \frac{5461}{92837} = \frac{5463}{92871} = \frac{5478}{93126} \end{array}$$

6.2.3 12 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 2 examples, each one with 12 expressions.

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{2697}{13485} = \frac{2769}{13845} = \frac{2937}{14685} = \frac{2967}{14835} = \frac{2973}{14865} = \frac{3297}{16485} = \frac{3729}{18645} = \frac{6297}{31485} = \frac{7629}{38145} = \frac{9237}{46185} = \frac{9627}{48135} = \frac{9723}{48615} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{6729}{13458} = \frac{6792}{13584} = \frac{6927}{13854} = \frac{7269}{14538} = \frac{7293}{14586} = \frac{7329}{14658} = \frac{7692}{15384} = \frac{7923}{15846} = \frac{7932}{15864} = \frac{9267}{18534} = \frac{9273}{18546} = \frac{9327}{18654} \end{array}$$

6.2.4 9 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 2 examples, each one with 9 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1653}{42978} &= \frac{2173}{56498} = \frac{2379}{61854} = \frac{2589}{67314} = \frac{2593}{67418} = \frac{2943}{76518} = \frac{3179}{82654} = \frac{3451}{89726} = \frac{3571}{92846} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2764}{15893} &= \frac{3456}{19872} = \frac{4156}{23897} = \frac{6172}{35489} = \frac{6712}{38594} = \frac{6872}{39514} = \frac{8132}{46759} = \frac{8576}{49312} = \frac{9248}{53176} \end{aligned}$$

6.2.5 8 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 2 examples, each one with 8 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1839}{25746} &= \frac{1956}{27384} = \frac{2967}{41538} = \frac{3297}{46158} = \frac{3678}{51492} = \frac{3912}{54768} = \frac{4398}{61572} = \frac{4713}{65982} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1894}{23675} &= \frac{2894}{36175} = \frac{2918}{36475} = \frac{4938}{61725} = \frac{6314}{78925} = \frac{6714}{83925} = \frac{7146}{89325} = \frac{7346}{91825} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{183}{256749} &= \frac{258}{361974} = \frac{329}{461587} = \frac{387}{542961} = \frac{516}{723948} = \frac{543}{761829} = \frac{658}{923174} = \frac{678}{951234} \end{aligned}$$

6.2.6 7 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 7 examples, each one with 7 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2394}{16758} &= \frac{2637}{18459} = \frac{4527}{31689} = \frac{5274}{36918} = \frac{5418}{37926} = \frac{5976}{41832} = \frac{7614}{53298} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2438}{17596} &= \frac{4876}{35192} = \frac{5428}{39176} = \frac{5796}{41832} = \frac{6279}{45318} = \frac{6371}{45982} = \frac{7429}{53618} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2538}{16497} &= \frac{3876}{25194} = \frac{3918}{25467} = \frac{4518}{29367} = \frac{6972}{45318} = \frac{7896}{51324} = \frac{8196}{53274} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2576}{13984} &= \frac{3976}{21584} = \frac{5376}{29184} = \frac{5789}{31426} = \frac{7952}{43168} = \frac{9786}{53124} = \frac{9814}{53276} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{3278}{15496} &= \frac{3927}{18564} = \frac{4598}{21736} = \frac{6754}{31928} = \frac{7612}{35984} = \frac{8756}{41392} = \frac{9218}{43576} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{3549}{26871} &= \frac{3759}{28461} = \frac{4851}{36729} = \frac{5124}{38796} = \frac{6321}{47859} = \frac{8421}{63759} = \frac{9534}{72186} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{137984} &= \frac{287}{154693} = \frac{471}{253869} = \frac{489}{263571} = \frac{716}{385924} = \frac{768}{413952} = \frac{857}{461923} \end{aligned}$$

6.2.7 6 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 15 examples, each one with 6 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{1376}{29584} = \frac{1384}{29756} = \frac{1672}{35948} = \frac{2138}{45967} = \frac{2158}{46397} = \frac{2716}{58394}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1596}{24738} = \frac{2514}{38967} = \frac{3954}{61287} = \frac{3984}{61752} = \frac{4218}{65379} = \frac{4596}{71238}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1972}{34568} = \frac{2159}{37846} = \frac{3247}{56918} = \frac{4318}{75692} = \frac{5236}{91784} = \frac{5372}{94168}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3458}{21679} = \frac{5928}{37164} = \frac{6214}{38957} = \frac{6578}{41239} = \frac{7358}{46129} = \frac{8762}{54931}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3471}{28569} = \frac{4758}{39162} = \frac{5187}{42693} = \frac{6942}{57138} = \frac{7839}{64521} = \frac{9516}{78324}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3654}{12789} = \frac{3674}{12859} = \frac{5342}{18697} = \frac{7418}{25963} = \frac{9786}{34251} = \frac{9862}{34517}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{263958} = \frac{321}{486957} = \frac{348}{527916} = \frac{417}{632589} = \frac{537}{814629} = \frac{573}{869241}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{163758} = \frac{463}{257891} = \frac{578}{321946} = \frac{621}{345897} = \frac{712}{396584} = \frac{829}{461753}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{196854} = \frac{328}{197456} = \frac{459}{276318} = \frac{581}{349762} = \frac{867}{521934} = \frac{967}{582134}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{347}{158926} = \frac{382}{174956} = \frac{432}{197856} = \frac{641}{293578} = \frac{694}{317852} = \frac{864}{395712}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{347}{168295} = \frac{487}{236195} = \frac{489}{237165} = \frac{721}{349685} = \frac{817}{396245} = \frac{879}{426315}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{275416} = \frac{413}{285796} = \frac{459}{317628} = \frac{548}{379216} = \frac{769}{532148} = \frac{786}{543912}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{418}{356972} = \frac{419}{357826} = \frac{578}{493612} = \frac{854}{729316} = \frac{861}{735294} = \frac{921}{786534}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{358176} = \frac{547}{398216} = \frac{576}{419328} = \frac{651}{473928} = \frac{983}{715624} = \frac{984}{716352}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{145236} = \frac{846}{153972} = \frac{876}{159432} = \frac{897}{163254} = \frac{948}{172536} = \frac{954}{173628}. \end{aligned}$$

6.2.8 5 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 42 examples, each one with 5 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1329}{58476} &= \frac{1347}{59268} = \frac{1543}{67892} = \frac{1578}{69432} = \frac{2167}{95348} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1379}{48265} &= \frac{1827}{63945} = \frac{1837}{64295} = \frac{2139}{74865} = \frac{2671}{93485} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1458}{26973} &= \frac{2658}{49173} = \frac{2874}{53169} = \frac{3162}{58497} = \frac{4158}{76923} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1576}{23984} &= \frac{2561}{38974} = \frac{3152}{47968} = \frac{4137}{62958} = \frac{5713}{86942} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1584}{23976} &= \frac{2574}{38961} = \frac{3168}{47952} = \frac{4158}{62937} = \frac{5742}{86913} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1638}{25974} &= \frac{2457}{38961} = \frac{3276}{51948} = \frac{4536}{71928} = \frac{4851}{76923} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1648}{53972} &= \frac{1824}{59736} = \frac{1972}{64583} = \frac{2316}{75849} = \frac{2564}{83971} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1958}{23674} &= \frac{6281}{75943} = \frac{6743}{81529} = \frac{7546}{91238} = \frac{7821}{94563} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{15984} &= \frac{3861}{25974} = \frac{4752}{31968} = \frac{6237}{41958} = \frac{8613}{57942} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2384}{15976} &= \frac{3874}{25961} = \frac{4768}{31952} = \frac{6258}{41937} = \frac{8642}{57913} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2584}{17936} &= \frac{5678}{39412} = \frac{5712}{39648} = \frac{6137}{42598} = \frac{9418}{65372} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2768}{14359} &= \frac{2976}{15438} = \frac{3456}{17928} = \frac{4976}{25813} = \frac{6784}{35192} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{3249}{16758} &= \frac{3287}{16954} = \frac{4579}{23618} = \frac{4598}{23716} = \frac{9158}{47236} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{3569}{24817} &= \frac{3698}{25714} = \frac{4687}{32591} = \frac{7396}{51428} = \frac{9374}{65182} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4368}{51792} &= \frac{6342}{75198} = \frac{6349}{75281} = \frac{7196}{85324} = \frac{7854}{93126} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5148}{36972} &= \frac{5269}{37841} = \frac{6589}{47321} = \frac{6853}{49217} = \frac{8316}{59724} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5432}{61789} &= \frac{5928}{67431} = \frac{8136}{92547} = \frac{8216}{93457} = \frac{8416}{95732} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{134}{279658} &= \frac{158}{329746} = \frac{167}{348529} = \frac{172}{358964} = \frac{294}{613578} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{253869} &= \frac{214}{369578} = \frac{382}{659714} = \frac{428}{739156} = \frac{532}{918764} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{159}{267438} &= \frac{273}{459186} = \frac{346}{581972} = \frac{546}{918372} = \frac{548}{921736} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{176}{395824} &= \frac{263}{591487} = \frac{342}{769158} = \frac{352}{791648} = \frac{432}{971568} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{192}{384576} &= \frac{219}{438657} = \frac{273}{546819} = \frac{327}{654981} = \frac{384}{769152} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{247}{319865} &= \frac{291}{376845} = \frac{297}{384615} = \frac{637}{824915} = \frac{743}{962185} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{249}{356817} &= \frac{258}{369714} = \frac{327}{468591} = \frac{516}{739428} = \frac{654}{937182} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{253}{197846} &= \frac{419}{327658} = \frac{529}{413678} = \frac{941}{735862} = \frac{951}{743682} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{319}{246587} &= \frac{567}{438291} = \frac{623}{481579} = \frac{946}{731258} = \frac{961}{742853} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{327}{514698} &= \frac{329}{517846} = \frac{376}{591824} = \frac{418}{657932} = \frac{583}{917642} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{357}{294168} &= \frac{459}{378216} = \frac{783}{645192} = \frac{918}{756432} = \frac{951}{783624} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{372}{156984} &= \frac{458}{193276} = \frac{549}{231678} = \frac{578}{243916} = \frac{769}{324518} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{378}{215649} &= \frac{516}{294378} = \frac{756}{431298} = \frac{792}{451836} = \frac{984}{561372} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{384}{192576} &= \frac{438}{219657} = \frac{546}{273819} = \frac{654}{327981} = \frac{912}{457368} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{389}{125647} &= \frac{426}{137598} = \frac{429}{138567} = \frac{819}{264537} = \frac{976}{315248} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{397}{124658} &= \frac{498}{156372} = \frac{549}{172386} = \frac{749}{235186} = \frac{761}{238954} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{571896} &= \frac{438}{592176} = \frac{534}{721968} = \frac{546}{738192} = \frac{714}{965328} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{429}{385671} &= \frac{521}{468379} = \frac{759}{682341} = \frac{839}{754261} = \frac{849}{763251} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{176952} &= \frac{537}{216948} = \frac{574}{231896} = \frac{591}{238764} = \frac{796}{321584} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{491}{538627} &= \frac{591}{648327} = \frac{683}{749251} = \frac{749}{821653} = \frac{762}{835914} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{548}{196732} &= \frac{683}{245197} = \frac{689}{247351} = \frac{952}{341768} = \frac{968}{347512} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{125489} = \frac{649}{127853} = \frac{756}{148932} = \frac{758}{149326} = \frac{849}{167253}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1754896} = \frac{36}{1974258} = \frac{54}{2961387} = \frac{68}{3729154} = \frac{72}{3948516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{194285} = \frac{793}{241865} = \frac{813}{247965} = \frac{913}{278465} = \frac{943}{287615}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1548976} = \frac{36}{1742598} = \frac{54}{2613897} = \frac{68}{3291574} = \frac{72}{3485196}$$

6.2.9 4 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 119 examples, each one with 4 expressions.

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1243}{65879} = \frac{1432}{75896} = \frac{1592}{84376} = \frac{1746}{92538}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1837}{46259} = \frac{1936}{48752} = \frac{2541}{63987} = \frac{3674}{92518}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1278}{64539} = \frac{1458}{73629} = \frac{1854}{93627} = \frac{1872}{94536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1864}{25397} = \frac{5816}{79243} = \frac{5832}{79461} = \frac{5976}{81423}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1396}{42578} = \frac{1736}{52948} = \frac{1768}{53924} = \frac{1926}{58743}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1938}{25764} = \frac{3519}{46782} = \frac{5389}{71642} = \frac{7412}{98536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1398}{26574} = \frac{2563}{48719} = \frac{2796}{53148} = \frac{5126}{97438}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1952}{36478} = \frac{2576}{48139} = \frac{3968}{74152} = \frac{5264}{98371}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1476}{39852} = \frac{1836}{49572} = \frac{2583}{69741} = \frac{3582}{96714}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1963}{28574} = \frac{2718}{39564} = \frac{3926}{57148} = \frac{5436}{79128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1573}{28496} = \frac{2178}{39456} = \frac{3267}{59184} = \frac{4356}{78912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{25384} = \frac{4381}{56279} = \frac{4823}{61957} = \frac{7254}{93186}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1578}{24936} = \frac{2893}{45716} = \frac{3156}{49872} = \frac{5786}{91432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2489}{16375} = \frac{6289}{41375} = \frac{7391}{48625} = \frac{9481}{62375}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1587}{36294} = \frac{1978}{45236} = \frac{2369}{54178} = \frac{4186}{95732}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2639}{17458} = \frac{3718}{24596} = \frac{5278}{34916} = \frac{6279}{41538}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1736}{25984} = \frac{3472}{51968} = \frac{5239}{78416} = \frac{5673}{84912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2658}{13974} = \frac{4873}{25619} = \frac{5316}{27948} = \frac{9746}{51238}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1742}{38659} = \frac{1976}{43852} = \frac{2678}{59431} = \frac{4316}{95782}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2754}{16983} = \frac{3564}{21978} = \frac{7128}{43956} = \frac{7398}{45621}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{35982} = \frac{2156}{43978} = \frac{3528}{71964} = \frac{4312}{87956}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2856}{17493} = \frac{5712}{34986} = \frac{7128}{43659} = \frac{7368}{45129}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1782}{35964} = \frac{2178}{43956} = \frac{3564}{71928} = \frac{4356}{87912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2968}{57134} = \frac{3528}{67914} = \frac{3928}{75614} = \frac{5124}{98637}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1827}{39564} = \frac{2378}{51496} = \frac{2639}{57148} = \frac{3654}{79128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3478}{12596} = \frac{4329}{15678} = \frac{5476}{19832} = \frac{6549}{23718}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1827}{45936} = \frac{1932}{48576} = \frac{3654}{91872} = \frac{3864}{97152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3478}{29516} = \frac{4218}{35796} = \frac{6179}{52438} = \frac{8436}{71592}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \triangleright \frac{3564}{17982} = \frac{4356}{21978} = \frac{7128}{35964} = \frac{8712}{43956} \\ & \triangleright \frac{3582}{17964} = \frac{4378}{21956} = \frac{7164}{35928} = \frac{8756}{43912} \\ & \triangleright \frac{3598}{26471} = \frac{5124}{37698} = \frac{8372}{61594} = \frac{8932}{65714} \\ & \triangleright \frac{3612}{47859} = \frac{4812}{63759} = \frac{5124}{67893} = \frac{7284}{96513} \\ & \triangleright \frac{3782}{65941} = \frac{4526}{78913} = \frac{5146}{89723} = \frac{5642}{98371} \\ & \triangleright \frac{3816}{45792} = \frac{6129}{73548} = \frac{7461}{89532} = \frac{7632}{91584} \\ & \triangleright \frac{3942}{15768} = \frac{4392}{17568} = \frac{5796}{23184} = \frac{7956}{31824} \\ & \triangleright \frac{3978}{12546} = \frac{5382}{16974} = \frac{7514}{23698} = \frac{8541}{26937} \\ & \triangleright \frac{4257}{18963} = \frac{7689}{34251} = \frac{8514}{37926} = \frac{9768}{43512} \\ & \triangleright \frac{4529}{18763} = \frac{4536}{18792} = \frac{6594}{27318} = \frac{7154}{29638} \\ & \triangleright \frac{4972}{15368} = \frac{5478}{16932} = \frac{5973}{18462} = \frac{9174}{28356} \\ & \triangleright \frac{5136}{48792} = \frac{5238}{49761} = \frac{7254}{68913} = \frac{9132}{86754} \\ & \triangleright \frac{5497}{13862} = \frac{6279}{15834} = \frac{6923}{17458} = \frac{8579}{21634} \\ & \triangleright \frac{5687}{34921} = \frac{6897}{42351} = \frac{8349}{51267} = \frac{8712}{53496} \\ & \triangleright \frac{5983}{46127} = \frac{6293}{48517} = \frac{6789}{52341} = \frac{9548}{73612} \\ & \triangleright \frac{6289}{35417} = \frac{7581}{42693} = \frac{8132}{45796} = \frac{8512}{47936} \\ & \triangleright \frac{6395}{74182} = \frac{7195}{83462} = \frac{7215}{83694} = \frac{7865}{91234} \\ & \triangleright \frac{7856}{14239} = \frac{9536}{17284} = \frac{9568}{17342} = \frac{9632}{17458} \\ & \triangleright \frac{124}{367598} = \frac{128}{379456} = \frac{248}{735196} = \frac{294}{871563} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \triangleright \frac{142}{357698} = \frac{154}{387926} = \frac{284}{715396} = \frac{354}{891726} \\ & \triangleright \frac{143}{295867} = \frac{168}{347592} = \frac{286}{591734} = \frac{318}{657942} \\ & \triangleright \frac{143}{296857} = \frac{286}{593714} = \frac{351}{728649} = \frac{468}{971532} \\ & \triangleright \frac{147}{359268} = \frac{234}{571896} = \frac{294}{718536} = \frac{324}{791856} \\ & \triangleright \frac{156}{249378} = \frac{286}{457193} = \frac{312}{498756} = \frac{572}{914386} \\ & \triangleright \frac{156}{284973} = \frac{216}{394578} = \frac{324}{591867} = \frac{432}{789156} \\ & \triangleright \frac{156}{392478} = \frac{286}{719543} = \frac{312}{784956} = \frac{364}{915782} \\ & \triangleright \frac{162}{349758} = \frac{184}{397256} = \frac{213}{459867} = \frac{368}{794512} \\ & \triangleright \frac{164}{298357} = \frac{328}{596714} = \frac{432}{785916} = \frac{532}{967841} \\ & \triangleright \frac{164}{372895} = \frac{348}{791265} = \frac{412}{936785} = \frac{428}{973165} \\ & \triangleright \frac{167}{258349} = \frac{321}{496587} = \frac{386}{597142} = \frac{541}{836927} \\ & \triangleright \frac{187}{253946} = \frac{379}{514682} = \frac{683}{927514} = \frac{713}{968254} \\ & \triangleright \frac{187}{354926} = \frac{251}{476398} = \frac{261}{495378} = \frac{354}{671892} \\ & \triangleright \frac{192}{576384} = \frac{219}{657438} = \frac{273}{819546} = \frac{327}{981654} \\ & \triangleright \frac{216}{347598} = \frac{372}{598641} = \frac{384}{617952} = \frac{468}{753129} \\ & \triangleright \frac{234}{165978} = \frac{351}{248967} = \frac{637}{451829} = \frac{793}{562481} \\ & \triangleright \frac{243}{196587} = \frac{341}{275869} = \frac{642}{519378} = \frac{671}{542839} \\ & \triangleright \frac{246}{175398} = \frac{378}{269514} = \frac{738}{526194} = \frac{957}{682341} \\ & \triangleright \frac{249}{168573} = \frac{357}{241689} = \frac{792}{536184} = \frac{951}{643827} \end{aligned}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{256}{174398} = \frac{384}{261597} = \frac{512}{348796} = \frac{768}{523194}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{256}{197438} = \frac{384}{296157} = \frac{512}{394876} = \frac{768}{592314}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{196348} = \frac{356}{271984} = \frac{478}{365192} = \frac{712}{543968}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{257}{418396} = \frac{297}{483516} = \frac{349}{568172} = \frac{514}{836792}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{267}{485139} = \frac{423}{768591} = \frac{469}{852173} = \frac{531}{964827}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{268}{357914} = \frac{394}{526187} = \frac{546}{729183} = \frac{642}{857391}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{273}{158496} = \frac{378}{219456} = \frac{567}{329184} = \frac{756}{438912}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{274}{381956} = \frac{519}{723486} = \frac{548}{763912} = \frac{678}{945132}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{286}{345917} = \frac{438}{529761} = \frac{572}{691834} = \frac{756}{914382}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{297}{153846} = \frac{357}{184926} = \frac{573}{296814} = \frac{714}{369852}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{347}{261985} = \frac{379}{286145} = \frac{893}{674215} = \frac{983}{742165}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{357}{419628} = \frac{693}{814572} = \frac{714}{839256} = \frac{784}{921536}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{369}{214758} = \frac{459}{267138} = \frac{738}{429516} = \frac{918}{534276}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{369}{451287} = \frac{621}{759483} = \frac{697}{852431} = \frac{746}{912358}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{376}{142598} = \frac{456}{172938} = \frac{564}{213897} = \frac{912}{345876}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{376}{219584} = \frac{752}{439168} = \frac{921}{537864} = \frac{927}{541368}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{384}{576192} = \frac{438}{657219} = \frac{546}{819273} = \frac{654}{981327}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{387}{529416} = \frac{396}{541728} = \frac{639}{874152} = \frac{684}{935712}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{396}{145728} = \frac{432}{158976} = \frac{536}{197248} = \frac{864}{317952}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{451}{283679} = \frac{598}{376142} = \frac{897}{564213} = \frac{912}{573648}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{517}{329846} = \frac{571}{364298} = \frac{842}{537196} = \frac{983}{627154}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{526}{378194} = \frac{659}{473821} = \frac{736}{529184} = \frac{827}{594613}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{531}{478962} = \frac{831}{749562} = \frac{927}{836154} = \frac{957}{863214}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{532}{147896} = \frac{537}{149286} = \frac{589}{163742} = \frac{951}{264378}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{574}{216398} = \frac{683}{257491} = \frac{759}{286143} = \frac{861}{324597}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{576}{192384} = \frac{657}{219438} = \frac{819}{273546} = \frac{981}{327654}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{576}{384192} = \frac{657}{438219} = \frac{819}{546273} = \frac{981}{654327}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{586}{379142} = \frac{614}{397258} = \frac{756}{489132} = \frac{954}{617238}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{648}{159732} = \frac{784}{193256} = \frac{876}{215934} = \frac{958}{236147}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{13}{2586974} = \frac{26}{5173948} = \frac{38}{7561924} = \frac{42}{8357916}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{13}{2598674} = \frac{26}{5197348} = \frac{38}{7596124} = \frac{42}{8395716}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{13}{2894567} = \frac{21}{4675839} = \frac{26}{5789134} = \frac{42}{9351678}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{16}{2379458} = \frac{24}{3569187} = \frac{32}{4758916} = \frac{64}{9517832}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{16}{2394578} = \frac{24}{3591867} = \frac{32}{4789156} = \frac{64}{9578312}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{17}{3285964} = \frac{18}{3479256} = \frac{19}{3672548} = \frac{34}{6571928}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{18}{2745639} = \frac{36}{5491278} = \frac{52}{7931846} = \frac{54}{8236917}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{18}{3276594} = \frac{19}{3458627} = \frac{23}{4186759} = \frac{38}{6917254}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{23}{1576489} = \frac{46}{3152978} = \frac{67}{4592381} = \frac{87}{5963241}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{24}{1835976} = \frac{48}{3671952} = \frac{69}{5278431} = \frac{76}{5813924}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{26}{1584973} = \frac{36}{2194578} = \frac{54}{3291867} = \frac{72}{4389156}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{27}{1839564} = \frac{39}{2657148} = \frac{54}{3679128} = \frac{78}{5314296}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{32}{1679584} = \frac{48}{2519376} = \frac{49}{2571863} = \frac{98}{5143726}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{34}{2197658} = \frac{51}{3296487} = \frac{61}{3942857} = \frac{87}{5623419}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{38}{2194576} = \frac{57}{3291864} = \frac{73}{4215896} = \frac{76}{4389152}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{46}{2589317} = \frac{58}{3264791} = \frac{82}{4615739} = \frac{92}{5178634}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{49}{2815736} = \frac{56}{3217984} = \frac{83}{4769512} = \frac{98}{5631472}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{56}{4378192} = \frac{59}{4612738} = \frac{67}{5238194} = \frac{76}{5941832}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{14365798} = \frac{3}{21548697} = \frac{4}{28731596} = \frac{8}{57463192}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{14365978} = \frac{3}{21548967} = \frac{4}{28731956} = \frac{8}{57463912}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17639458} = \frac{3}{26459187} = \frac{4}{35278916} = \frac{6}{52918374}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{17985634} = \frac{3}{26978451} = \frac{4}{35971268} = \frac{8}{71942536}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{19457638} = \frac{3}{29186457} = \frac{4}{38915276} = \frac{6}{58372914}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{2}{19785634} = \frac{3}{29678451} = \frac{4}{39571268} = \frac{8}{79142536}$$

6.2.10 3 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 949 examples, each one with 3 expressions.

$$\triangleright \frac{1236}{47895} = \frac{1932}{74865} = \frac{2316}{89745}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1347}{28569} = \frac{2694}{57138} = \frac{3592}{76184}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1452}{73689} = \frac{1456}{73892} = \frac{1764}{89523}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1236}{84975} = \frac{1348}{92675} = \frac{1436}{98725}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1348}{56279} = \frac{1432}{59786} = \frac{1528}{63794}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1456}{39728} = \frac{1974}{53862} = \frac{2149}{58637}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1239}{48675} = \frac{1869}{73425} = \frac{2163}{84975}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1358}{24679} = \frac{2716}{49358} = \frac{5432}{98716}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1458}{23679} = \frac{2916}{47358} = \frac{5832}{94716}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1248}{37596} = \frac{1872}{56394} = \frac{2184}{65793}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1359}{24678} = \frac{2718}{49356} = \frac{5436}{98712}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1458}{23976} = \frac{2187}{35964} = \frac{5346}{87912}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1248}{39756} = \frac{1872}{59634} = \frac{2184}{69573}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1364}{25978} = \frac{2398}{45671} = \frac{3916}{74582}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1459}{23678} = \frac{2918}{47356} = \frac{5836}{94712}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1267}{39458} = \frac{1729}{53846} = \frac{2534}{78916}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1368}{24579} = \frac{2736}{49158} = \frac{5472}{98316}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1468}{23579} = \frac{2936}{47158} = \frac{5872}{94316}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1269}{34857} = \frac{2397}{65841} = \frac{2538}{69714}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1369}{24578} = \frac{2738}{49156} = \frac{5476}{98312}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1469}{23578} = \frac{2938}{47156} = \frac{5876}{94312}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1276}{34958} = \frac{2146}{58793} = \frac{2378}{65149}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1374}{26598} = \frac{2519}{48763} = \frac{2748}{53196}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1548}{37926} = \frac{1782}{43659} = \frac{2364}{57918}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1286}{73945} = \frac{1298}{74635} = \frac{1382}{79465}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1435}{26978} = \frac{3715}{69842} = \frac{4235}{79618}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{1568}{34792} = \frac{2156}{47839} = \frac{4312}{95678}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1573}{24986} = \frac{2178}{34596} = \frac{3267}{51894}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1736}{28954} = \frac{4172}{69583} = \frac{5824}{97136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1946}{23758} = \frac{3892}{47516} = \frac{5143}{62789}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1578}{23946} = \frac{3156}{47892} = \frac{6312}{95784}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1736}{45829} = \frac{1984}{52376} = \frac{3472}{91658}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1947}{32568} = \frac{2739}{45816} = \frac{5478}{91632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1578}{24396} = \frac{3156}{48792} = \frac{6312}{97584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1756}{24398} = \frac{3512}{48796} = \frac{5268}{73194}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1952}{34768} = \frac{3172}{56498} = \frac{3294}{58671}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1578}{24639} = \frac{3156}{49278} = \frac{3682}{57491}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1762}{39458} = \frac{2643}{59187} = \frac{3524}{78916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1953}{48267} = \frac{2184}{53976} = \frac{2597}{64183}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1578}{36294} = \frac{3549}{81627} = \frac{3564}{81972}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{23598} = \frac{3528}{47196} = \frac{6174}{82593}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1956}{23784} = \frac{3912}{47568} = \frac{7824}{95136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1578}{39246} = \frac{3156}{78492} = \frac{3682}{91574}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1782}{39456} = \frac{2673}{59184} = \frac{3564}{78912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1958}{37642} = \frac{3916}{75284} = \frac{4539}{87261}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1584}{32967} = \frac{1728}{35964} = \frac{3456}{71928}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1782}{43956} = \frac{2187}{53946} = \frac{3564}{87912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1964}{23578} = \frac{3928}{47156} = \frac{7856}{94312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1584}{37296} = \frac{3168}{74592} = \frac{3641}{85729}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1784}{23956} = \frac{3568}{47912} = \frac{7136}{95824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{25638} = \frac{2961}{38457} = \frac{3948}{51276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1586}{24973} = \frac{2196}{34578} = \frac{3294}{51867}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1786}{34592} = \frac{3572}{69184} = \frac{4123}{79856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{25836} = \frac{2961}{38754} = \frac{3948}{51672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1596}{24378} = \frac{3192}{48756} = \frac{6384}{97512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1789}{23456} = \frac{3578}{46912} = \frac{7156}{93824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{35826} = \frac{3948}{71652} = \frac{5217}{94683}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1598}{36472} = \frac{3468}{79152} = \frac{3791}{86524}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1792}{43568} = \frac{2384}{57961} = \frac{2416}{58739}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{36258} = \frac{2961}{54387} = \frac{3948}{72516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1639}{25487} = \frac{3129}{48657} = \frac{6258}{97314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1794}{25638} = \frac{2691}{38457} = \frac{5382}{76914}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{38256} = \frac{2961}{57384} = \frac{3948}{76512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1643}{57982} = \frac{1798}{63452} = \frac{2139}{75486}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1824}{35796} = \frac{3648}{71592} = \frac{4872}{95613}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1975}{32864} = \frac{3725}{61984} = \frac{4325}{71968}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1674}{23598} = \frac{1798}{25346} = \frac{5921}{83467}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1836}{25974} = \frac{2754}{38961} = \frac{3672}{51948}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{23584} = \frac{3952}{47168} = \frac{7163}{85492}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1694}{28357} = \frac{2178}{36459} = \frac{4356}{72918}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1859}{37642} = \frac{3549}{71862} = \frac{4732}{95816}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{25438} = \frac{2964}{38157} = \frac{5928}{76314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1694}{35728} = \frac{2178}{45936} = \frac{4356}{91872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1863}{24579} = \frac{3726}{49158} = \frac{7452}{98316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{43562} = \frac{3612}{79548} = \frac{3956}{87124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1728}{49356} = \frac{1872}{53469} = \frac{3456}{98712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1876}{32495} = \frac{3892}{67415} = \frac{4732}{81965}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{45623} = \frac{3542}{81697} = \frac{3726}{85941}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{38456} = \frac{3458}{76912} = \frac{4368}{97152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1879}{23456} = \frac{3758}{46912} = \frac{7516}{93824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1984}{23576} = \frac{3968}{47152} = \frac{7192}{85463}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{45836} = \frac{1976}{52384} = \frac{3458}{91672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1936}{25784} = \frac{4598}{61237} = \frac{5368}{71492}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1984}{37256} = \frac{3472}{65198} = \frac{3968}{74512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2146}{53798} = \frac{2378}{59614} = \frac{3567}{89421}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2158}{34697} = \frac{5146}{82739} = \frac{6142}{98753}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2158}{39674} = \frac{2639}{48517} = \frac{3419}{62857}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2163}{47895} = \frac{2793}{61845} = \frac{3941}{87265}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2176}{39458} = \frac{3264}{59187} = \frac{4352}{78916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2184}{37596} = \frac{4368}{75192} = \frac{5418}{93267}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2315}{47689} = \frac{2365}{48719} = \frac{3945}{81267}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2354}{17869} = \frac{5786}{43921} = \frac{6842}{51937}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2358}{14679} = \frac{4716}{29358} = \frac{9432}{58716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2358}{17964} = \frac{4716}{35928} = \frac{9432}{71856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2358}{19764} = \frac{4716}{39528} = \frac{8253}{69174}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2359}{14678} = \frac{4718}{29356} = \frac{9436}{58712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{17598} = \frac{4728}{35196} = \frac{8274}{61593}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{17958} = \frac{4728}{35916} = \frac{9456}{71832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{19578} = \frac{4728}{39156} = \frac{9456}{78312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{19758} = \frac{4728}{39516} = \frac{8274}{69153}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2368}{14579} = \frac{4736}{29158} = \frac{9472}{58316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2369}{14578} = \frac{4738}{29156} = \frac{9476}{58312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{15849} = \frac{4136}{27589} = \frac{4752}{31698}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{19458} = \frac{3564}{29187} = \frac{4752}{38916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{15946} = \frac{4756}{31892} = \frac{9512}{63784}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{19456} = \frac{3567}{29184} = \frac{4756}{38912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{19564} = \frac{4756}{39128} = \frac{7134}{58692}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{19654} = \frac{3567}{29481} = \frac{7134}{58962}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2379}{18456} = \frac{4758}{36912} = \frac{9516}{73824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2384}{17956} = \frac{4768}{35912} = \frac{9536}{71824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2397}{14586} = \frac{4371}{26598} = \frac{8742}{53196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2398}{17456} = \frac{3597}{26184} = \frac{7194}{52368}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2436}{15978} = \frac{4872}{31956} = \frac{5278}{34619}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2436}{17598} = \frac{4872}{35196} = \frac{5916}{42738}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2438}{15796} = \frac{4876}{31592} = \frac{9752}{63184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2438}{19756} = \frac{4876}{39512} = \frac{7314}{59268}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2456}{17839} = \frac{4912}{35678} = \frac{9824}{71356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2456}{18379} = \frac{4912}{36758} = \frac{9824}{73516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2457}{18369} = \frac{3591}{26847} = \frac{7182}{53694}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2458}{13679} = \frac{4916}{27358} = \frac{9832}{54716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2459}{13678} = \frac{4918}{27356} = \frac{9836}{54712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2459}{17863} = \frac{4918}{35726} = \frac{9836}{71452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2463}{17859} = \frac{4926}{35718} = \frac{9852}{71436}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2463}{18579} = \frac{4926}{37158} = \frac{9852}{74316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2468}{13579} = \frac{4936}{27158} = \frac{9872}{54316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2469}{13578} = \frac{4938}{27156} = \frac{9876}{54312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2478}{15639} = \frac{4956}{31278} = \frac{5782}{36491}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2478}{39156} = \frac{4956}{78312} = \frac{5782}{91364}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2496}{15873} = \frac{3456}{21978} = \frac{5184}{32967}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2573}{16849} = \frac{3689}{24157} = \frac{9827}{64351}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{16398} = \frac{3861}{24597} = \frac{5148}{32796}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{18396} = \frac{3861}{27594} = \frac{5148}{36792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{19638} = \frac{3861}{29457} = \frac{5148}{39276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{19836} = \frac{3861}{29754} = \frac{5148}{39672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{19863} = \frac{4862}{37519} = \frac{5148}{39726}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{36198} = \frac{3861}{54297} = \frac{5148}{72396}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{38196} = \frac{3861}{57294} = \frac{5148}{76392}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{39618} = \frac{3861}{59427} = \frac{5148}{79236}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{39816} = \frac{3861}{59724} = \frac{5148}{79632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2583}{16974} = \frac{7938}{52164} = \frac{8694}{57132}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2596}{17438} = \frac{3894}{26157} = \frac{5192}{34876}$$

▶ $\frac{3816}{25974} = \frac{5724}{38961} = \frac{7632}{51948}$

▶ $\frac{3854}{19762} = \frac{5781}{29643} = \frac{8319}{42657}$

▶ $\frac{3859}{47216} = \frac{5916}{72384} = \frac{5984}{73216}$

▶ $\frac{3861}{45279} = \frac{7326}{85914} = \frac{8316}{97524}$

▶ $\frac{3872}{51964} = \frac{4312}{57869} = \frac{6512}{87394}$

▶ $\frac{3927}{14586} = \frac{6783}{25194} = \frac{9618}{35724}$

▶ $\frac{3948}{17625} = \frac{8764}{39125} = \frac{9268}{41375}$

▶ $\frac{3974}{16258} = \frac{5961}{24387} = \frac{7948}{32516}$

▶ $\frac{3974}{18256} = \frac{5961}{27384} = \frac{7948}{36512}$

▶ $\frac{3974}{25618} = \frac{5961}{38427} = \frac{7948}{51236}$

▶ $\frac{3974}{25816} = \frac{5961}{38724} = \frac{7948}{51632}$

▶ $\frac{3984}{25716} = \frac{4316}{27859} = \frac{7968}{51432}$

▶ $\frac{4137}{29568} = \frac{7683}{54912} = \frac{8274}{59136}$

▶ $\frac{4257}{19638} = \frac{7568}{34912} = \frac{8514}{39276}$

▶ $\frac{4387}{29561} = \frac{6527}{43981} = \frac{8132}{54796}$

▶ $\frac{4521}{39867} = \frac{7392}{65184} = \frac{9361}{82547}$

▶ $\frac{4563}{18279} = \frac{4732}{18956} = \frac{8619}{34527}$

▶ $\frac{4576}{18392} = \frac{9152}{36784} = \frac{9516}{38247}$

▶ $\frac{4582}{31679} = \frac{5278}{36491} = \frac{8932}{61754}$

▶ $\frac{4582}{36917} = \frac{6478}{52193} = \frac{7426}{59831}$

▶ $\frac{4587}{31692} = \frac{5973}{41268} = \frac{7689}{53124}$

▶ $\frac{4589}{32617} = \frac{7413}{52689} = \frac{9178}{65234}$

▶ $\frac{4598}{71632} = \frac{5643}{87912} = \frac{6251}{97384}$

▶ $\frac{4716}{25938} = \frac{9432}{51876} = \frac{9486}{52173}$

▶ $\frac{4758}{36192} = \frac{5124}{38976} = \frac{9516}{72384}$

▶ $\frac{4765}{12389} = \frac{8345}{21697} = \frac{8365}{21749}$

▶ $\frac{4812}{37596} = \frac{7218}{56394} = \frac{8421}{65793}$

▶ $\frac{4812}{39756} = \frac{7218}{59634} = \frac{8421}{69573}$

▶ $\frac{4832}{61759} = \frac{5312}{67894} = \frac{5632}{71984}$

▶ $\frac{4913}{25687} = \frac{7514}{39286} = \frac{9826}{51374}$

▶ $\frac{4928}{15736} = \frac{5632}{17984} = \frac{9856}{31472}$

▶ $\frac{4956}{23187} = \frac{7812}{36549} = \frac{9156}{42837}$

▶ $\frac{5124}{37968} = \frac{7381}{54692} = \frac{8357}{61924}$

▶ $\frac{5184}{67392} = \frac{6273}{81549} = \frac{7281}{94653}$

▶ $\frac{5192}{38764} = \frac{5782}{43169} = \frac{8732}{65194}$

▶ $\frac{5243}{17869} = \frac{5684}{19372} = \frac{6958}{23714}$

▶ $\frac{5267}{34891} = \frac{8473}{56129} = \frac{9847}{65231}$

▶ $\frac{5267}{48319} = \frac{7429}{68153} = \frac{9453}{86721}$

▶ $\frac{5291}{38467} = \frac{5476}{39812} = \frac{8547}{62139}$

▶ $\frac{5324}{81796} = \frac{5379}{82641} = \frac{6413}{98527}$

▶ $\frac{5368}{12749} = \frac{5864}{13927} = \frac{5872}{13946}$

▶ $\frac{5382}{64791} = \frac{5928}{71364} = \frac{6942}{83571}$

▶ $\frac{5423}{61897} = \frac{6351}{72489} = \frac{8526}{97314}$

▶ $\frac{5487}{26319} = \frac{7198}{34526} = \frac{9853}{47261}$

▶ $\frac{5728}{61934} = \frac{5872}{63491} = \frac{8752}{94631}$

▶ $\frac{5782}{14396} = \frac{6958}{17324} = \frac{8673}{21594}$

▶ $\frac{5974}{21836} = \frac{8961}{32754} = \frac{9512}{34768}$

▶ $\frac{5984}{12376} = \frac{6952}{14378} = \frac{8492}{17563}$

▶ $\frac{6372}{58941} = \frac{7128}{65934} = \frac{7452}{68931}$

▶ $\frac{6381}{57429} = \frac{6471}{58239} = \frac{8361}{75249}$

▶ $\frac{6752}{48319} = \frac{7264}{51983} = \frac{9184}{65723}$

▶ $\frac{6783}{12495} = \frac{6973}{12845} = \frac{7429}{13685}$

▶ $\frac{6894}{17235} = \frac{8694}{21735} = \frac{9486}{23715}$

▶ $\frac{7598}{13624} = \frac{8352}{14976} = \frac{8497}{15236}$

▶ $\frac{7598}{64321} = \frac{8642}{73159} = \frac{8932}{75614}$

▶ $\frac{9174}{35862} = \frac{9427}{36851} = \frac{9614}{37582}$

▶ $\frac{123}{587694} = \frac{164}{783592} = \frac{173}{826594}$

▶ $\frac{124}{359786} = \frac{234}{678951} = \frac{254}{736981}$

▶ $\frac{126}{358974} = \frac{261}{743589} = \frac{297}{846153}$

▶ $\frac{129}{437568} = \frac{169}{573248} = \frac{218}{739456}$

▶ $\frac{132}{495768} = \frac{198}{743652} = \frac{231}{867594}$

▶ $\frac{134}{267598} = \frac{358}{714926} = \frac{429}{856713}$

▶ $\frac{136}{579428} = \frac{186}{792453} = \frac{194}{826537}$

▶ $\frac{137}{264958} = \frac{154}{297836} = \frac{186}{359724}$

▶ $\frac{138}{265974} = \frac{253}{487619} = \frac{276}{531948}$

▶ $\frac{138}{269457} = \frac{184}{359276} = \frac{276}{538914}$

▶ $\frac{138}{294567} = \frac{184}{392756} = \frac{276}{589134}$

▶ $\frac{142}{358976} = \frac{192}{485376} = \frac{291}{735648}$

▶ $\frac{142}{365798} = \frac{213}{548697} = \frac{284}{731596}$

▶ $\frac{142}{365978} = \frac{213}{548967} = \frac{284}{731956}$

▶ $\frac{142}{376598} = \frac{213}{564897} = \frac{284}{753196}$

▶ $\frac{142}{379658} = \frac{213}{569487} = \frac{284}{759316}$

▶ $\frac{142}{396578} = \frac{213}{594867} = \frac{284}{793156}$

▶ $\frac{142}{397658} = \frac{213}{596487} = \frac{284}{795316}$

▶ $\frac{146}{579328} = \frac{147}{583296} = \frac{193}{765824}$

▶ $\frac{147}{283569} = \frac{294}{567138} = \frac{392}{756184}$

▶ $\frac{149}{235867} = \frac{369}{584127} = \frac{397}{628451}$

▶ $\frac{152}{379468} = \frac{236}{589174} = \frac{238}{594167}$

▶ $\frac{154}{792638} = \frac{182}{936754} = \frac{186}{957342}$

▶ $\frac{156}{237984} = \frac{312}{475968} = \frac{468}{713952}$

▶ $\frac{156}{239784} = \frac{312}{479568} = \frac{468}{719352}$

▶ $\frac{156}{247839} = \frac{312}{495678} = \frac{364}{578291}$

▶ $\frac{156}{249873} = \frac{216}{345978} = \frac{324}{518967}$

▶ $\frac{156}{284397} = \frac{312}{568794} = \frac{416}{758392}$

▶ $\frac{156}{284937} = \frac{312}{569874} = \frac{416}{759832}$

▶ $\frac{156}{293847} = \frac{312}{587694} = \frac{416}{783592}$

▶ $\frac{156}{298437} = \frac{312}{596874} = \frac{416}{795832}$

▶ $\frac{156}{329784} = \frac{321}{678594} = \frac{391}{826574}$

▶ $\frac{156}{493728} = \frac{169}{534872} = \frac{312}{987456}$

▶ $\frac{158}{237946} = \frac{316}{475892} = \frac{632}{951784}$

▶ $\frac{158}{243796} = \frac{316}{487592} = \frac{632}{975184}$

▶ $\frac{158}{493276} = \frac{172}{536984} = \frac{239}{746158}$

▶ $\frac{162}{379458} = \frac{243}{569187} = \frac{324}{758916}$

▶ $\frac{162}{394578} = \frac{243}{591867} = \frac{324}{789156}$

$$\begin{array}{l} \triangleright \frac{162}{458379} = \frac{254}{718693} = \frac{324}{916758} \\ \triangleright \frac{164}{257398} = \frac{328}{514796} = \frac{364}{571298} \\ \triangleright \frac{164}{279538} = \frac{174}{296583} = \frac{258}{439761} \\ \triangleright \frac{168}{234759} = \frac{176}{245938} = \frac{352}{491876} \\ \triangleright \frac{168}{294357} = \frac{216}{378459} = \frac{432}{756918} \\ \triangleright \frac{168}{357294} = \frac{216}{459378} = \frac{432}{918756} \\ \triangleright \frac{174}{256398} = \frac{261}{384597} = \frac{348}{512796} \\ \triangleright \frac{174}{258396} = \frac{261}{387594} = \frac{348}{516792} \\ \triangleright \frac{174}{259638} = \frac{261}{389457} = \frac{348}{519276} \\ \triangleright \frac{174}{259836} = \frac{261}{389754} = \frac{348}{519672} \\ \triangleright \frac{174}{289536} = \frac{429}{713856} = \frac{524}{871936} \\ \triangleright \frac{174}{362598} = \frac{261}{543897} = \frac{348}{725196} \\ \triangleright \frac{174}{382596} = \frac{261}{573894} = \frac{348}{765192} \\ \triangleright \frac{174}{396258} = \frac{261}{594387} = \frac{348}{792516} \\ \triangleright \frac{174}{398256} = \frac{261}{597384} = \frac{348}{796512} \\ \triangleright \frac{176}{239458} = \frac{264}{359187} = \frac{352}{478916} \\ \triangleright \frac{176}{254398} = \frac{264}{381597} = \frac{528}{763194} \\ \triangleright \frac{176}{348592} = \frac{352}{697184} = \frac{451}{893267} \\ \triangleright \frac{176}{394582} = \frac{264}{591873} = \frac{352}{789164} \\ \triangleright \frac{176}{438592} = \frac{318}{792456} = \frac{351}{874692} \\ \triangleright \frac{176}{439582} = \frac{216}{539487} = \frac{352}{879164} \\ \triangleright \frac{178}{235964} = \frac{356}{471928} = \frac{712}{943856} \\ \triangleright \frac{178}{236459} = \frac{356}{472918} = \frac{712}{945836} \\ \triangleright \frac{178}{239456} = \frac{267}{359184} = \frac{356}{478912} \\ \triangleright \frac{178}{239564} = \frac{356}{479128} = \frac{534}{718692} \\ \triangleright \frac{178}{239654} = \frac{267}{359481} = \frac{534}{718962} \\ \triangleright \frac{178}{246359} = \frac{356}{492718} = \frac{712}{985436} \\ \triangleright \frac{178}{256394} = \frac{267}{384591} = \frac{534}{769182} \\ \triangleright \frac{178}{394562} = \frac{267}{591843} = \frac{356}{789124} \\ \triangleright \frac{178}{456392} = \frac{294}{753816} = \frac{356}{912784} \\ \triangleright \frac{179}{236458} = \frac{358}{472916} = \frac{716}{945832} \\ \triangleright \frac{179}{238456} = \frac{358}{476912} = \frac{716}{953824} \\ \triangleright \frac{179}{245863} = \frac{358}{491726} = \frac{716}{983452} \\ \triangleright \frac{179}{246358} = \frac{358}{492716} = \frac{716}{985432} \\ \triangleright \frac{182}{367549} = \frac{356}{718942} = \frac{478}{965321} \\ \triangleright \frac{182}{379456} = \frac{273}{569184} = \frac{364}{758912} \\ \triangleright \frac{182}{394576} = \frac{273}{591864} = \frac{364}{789152} \\ \triangleright \frac{182}{457639} = \frac{316}{794582} = \frac{364}{915278} \end{array}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{576394} = \frac{243}{769581} = \frac{273}{864591}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{235796} = \frac{368}{471592} = \frac{438}{561297}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{235976} = \frac{368}{471952} = \frac{529}{678431}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{237956} = \frac{368}{475912} = \frac{736}{951824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{293756} = \frac{482}{769513} = \frac{516}{823794}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{365792} = \frac{194}{385672} = \frac{382}{759416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{186}{459327} = \frac{356}{879142} = \frac{372}{918654}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{187}{432956} = \frac{352}{814976} = \frac{374}{865912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{274563} = \frac{378}{549126} = \frac{546}{793182}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{342657} = \frac{297}{538461} = \frac{459}{832167}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{473256} = \frac{219}{548376} = \frac{378}{946512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{354768} = \frac{312}{576498} = \frac{324}{598671}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{256378} = \frac{291}{384567} = \frac{582}{769134}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{257348} = \frac{649}{852137} = \frac{712}{934856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{257438} = \frac{294}{386157} = \frac{392}{514876}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{258374} = \frac{294}{387561} = \frac{392}{516748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{374258} = \frac{294}{561387} = \frac{392}{748516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{382574} = \frac{294}{573861} = \frac{392}{765148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{235764} = \frac{396}{471528} = \frac{693}{825174}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{237456} = \frac{297}{356184} = \frac{594}{712368}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{243756} = \frac{396}{487512} = \frac{594}{731268}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{254376} = \frac{297}{381564} = \frac{594}{763128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{256374} = \frac{297}{384561} = \frac{396}{512748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{257436} = \frac{297}{386154} = \frac{396}{514872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{362574} = \frac{297}{543861} = \frac{396}{725148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{374256} = \frac{297}{561384} = \frac{396}{748512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{365798} = \frac{321}{548697} = \frac{428}{731596}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{365978} = \frac{321}{548967} = \frac{428}{731956}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{376598} = \frac{321}{564897} = \frac{428}{753196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{379658} = \frac{321}{569487} = \frac{428}{759316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{396578} = \frac{321}{594867} = \frac{428}{793156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{397658} = \frac{321}{596487} = \frac{428}{795316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{379458} = \frac{324}{569187} = \frac{432}{758916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{218}{379456} = \frac{327}{569184} = \frac{436}{758912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{218}{394576} = \frac{327}{591864} = \frac{436}{789152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{219}{568743} = \frac{237}{615489} = \frac{294}{763518}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{178596} = \frac{351}{267894} = \frac{468}{357192}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{178956} = \frac{468}{357912} = \frac{936}{715824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{179586} = \frac{247}{189563} = \frac{468}{359172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{179856} = \frac{351}{269784} = \frac{468}{359712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{185796} = \frac{351}{278694} = \frac{468}{371592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{185976} = \frac{351}{278964} = \frac{468}{371952}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{187956} = \frac{468}{375912} = \frac{936}{751824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{197856} = \frac{351}{296784} = \frac{468}{395712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{198576} = \frac{351}{297864} = \frac{468}{397152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{236}{179458} = \frac{354}{269187} = \frac{472}{358916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{236}{194578} = \frac{354}{291867} = \frac{472}{389156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{157946} = \frac{476}{315892} = \frac{952}{631784}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{179456} = \frac{357}{269184} = \frac{476}{358912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{179564} = \frac{476}{359128} = \frac{714}{538692}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{179654} = \frac{357}{269481} = \frac{714}{538962}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{194576} = \frac{357}{291864} = \frac{476}{389152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{197456} = \frac{357}{296184} = \frac{714}{592368}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{156784} = \frac{453}{297168} = \frac{819}{537264}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{178456} = \frac{478}{356912} = \frac{956}{713824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{157896} = \frac{486}{315792} = \frac{972}{631584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{158796} = \frac{486}{317592} = \frac{972}{635184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{586197} = \frac{324}{781596} = \frac{351}{846729}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{157839} = \frac{492}{315678} = \frac{574}{368291}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{157893} = \frac{492}{315786} = \frac{984}{631572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{157938} = \frac{492}{315876} = \frac{984}{631752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{158793} = \frac{492}{317586} = \frac{984}{635172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{159378} = \frac{492}{318756} = \frac{984}{637512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{391578} = \frac{492}{783156} = \frac{574}{913682}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{248}{359176} = \frac{496}{718352} = \frac{651}{942837}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{249}{365781} = \frac{396}{581724} = \frac{498}{731562}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{251}{487693} = \frac{451}{876293} = \frac{461}{895723}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{179638} = \frac{381}{269457} = \frac{762}{538914}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{183769} = \frac{586}{423971} = \frac{942}{681537}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{196378} = \frac{381}{294567} = \frac{762}{589134}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{183974} = \frac{384}{275961} = \frac{512}{367948}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{198374} = \frac{384}{297561} = \frac{512}{396748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{374198} = \frac{384}{561297} = \frac{512}{748396}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{381974} = \frac{384}{572961} = \frac{512}{763948}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{397184} = \frac{512}{794368} = \frac{562}{871943}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{397418} = \frac{384}{596127} = \frac{512}{794836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{398174} = \frac{384}{597261} = \frac{512}{796348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{163974} = \frac{387}{245961} = \frac{516}{327948}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{174396} = \frac{387}{261594} = \frac{516}{348792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{196374} = \frac{387}{294561} = \frac{516}{392748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{197436} = \frac{387}{296154} = \frac{516}{394872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{374196} = \frac{387}{561294} = \frac{516}{748392}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{396174} = \frac{387}{594261} = \frac{516}{792348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{397416} = \frac{387}{596124} = \frac{516}{794832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{261}{453879} = \frac{297}{516483} = \frac{516}{897324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{263}{574918} = \frac{289}{631754} = \frac{391}{854726}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{267}{138594} = \frac{356}{184792} = \frac{712}{369584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{154986} = \frac{378}{214596} = \frac{567}{321894}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{186459} = \frac{546}{372918} = \frac{671}{458293}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{416598} = \frac{453}{691278} = \frac{537}{819462}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{645918} = \frac{321}{759486} = \frac{387}{915642}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{274}{136589} = \frac{574}{286139} = \frac{918}{457623}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{284}{173596} = \frac{568}{347192} = \frac{923}{564187}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{284}{356917} = \frac{472}{593186} = \frac{476}{598213}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{154973} = \frac{396}{214578} = \frac{594}{321867}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{173459} = \frac{572}{346918} = \frac{876}{531294}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{459173} = \frac{572}{918346} = \frac{584}{937612}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{139564} = \frac{791}{384652} = \frac{896}{435712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{439561} = \frac{427}{653981} = \frac{532}{814796}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{134657} = \frac{459}{213867} = \frac{578}{269314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{145367} = \frac{329}{165487} = \frac{912}{458736}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{371654} = \frac{437}{561982} = \frac{639}{821754}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{365748} = \frac{582}{731496} = \frac{679}{853412}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{138567} = \frac{392}{184756} = \frac{784}{369512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{168357} = \frac{378}{216459} = \frac{756}{432918}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{357168} = \frac{378}{459216} = \frac{756}{918432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{358617} = \frac{392}{478156} = \frac{784}{956312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{548163} = \frac{351}{647829} = \frac{513}{946827}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{479856} = \frac{439}{675182} = \frac{623}{958174}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{316}{458279} = \frac{364}{527891} = \frac{516}{748329}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{319}{264857} = \frac{429}{356187} = \frac{638}{529714}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{319}{648527} = \frac{354}{719682} = \frac{412}{837596}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{189756} = \frac{648}{379512} = \frac{918}{537642}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{416598} = \frac{543}{691782} = \frac{651}{829374}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{341}{278659} = \frac{671}{548329} = \frac{847}{692153}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{341}{598672} = \frac{352}{617984} = \frac{429}{753168}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{342}{178596} = \frac{513}{267894} = \frac{684}{357192}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{342}{179856} = \frac{513}{269784} = \frac{684}{359712}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{342}{185796} = \frac{513}{278694} = \frac{684}{371592}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{342}{185976} = \frac{513}{278964} = \frac{684}{371952}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{342}{195786} = \frac{627}{358941} = \frac{684}{391572}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{342}{197856} = \frac{513}{296784} = \frac{684}{395712}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{342}{198576} = \frac{513}{297864} = \frac{684}{397152}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{342}{597816} = \frac{354}{618792} = \frac{513}{896724}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{348}{125976} = \frac{486}{175932} = \frac{972}{351864}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{349}{671825} = \frac{431}{829675} = \frac{463}{891275}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{351}{482976} = \frac{523}{719648} = \frac{687}{945312}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{352}{184976} = \frac{372}{195486} = \frac{618}{324759}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{352}{194768} = \frac{572}{316498} = \frac{594}{328671}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{352}{197648} = \frac{516}{289734} = \frac{584}{327916}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{356}{147829} = \frac{452}{187693} = \frac{576}{239184}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{357}{168294} = \frac{459}{216378} = \frac{918}{432756}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{357}{169428} = \frac{459}{217836} = \frac{918}{435672}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{357}{281469} = \frac{714}{562938} = \frac{819}{645723}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{357}{281694} = \frac{459}{362178} = \frac{918}{724356}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{357}{286194} = \frac{476}{381592} = \frac{952}{763184}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{357}{429618} = \frac{527}{634198} = \frac{714}{859236}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{359}{148267} = \frac{426}{175938} = \frac{718}{296534}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{362}{179458} = \frac{543}{269187} = \frac{724}{358916}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{362}{194578} = \frac{543}{291867} = \frac{724}{389156}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{364}{195728} = \frac{483}{259716} = \frac{728}{391456}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{364}{298571} = \frac{572}{469183} = \frac{724}{593861}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{369}{187452} = \frac{531}{269748} = \frac{837}{425196}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{374}{162598} = \frac{561}{243897} = \frac{748}{325196}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{374}{182596} = \frac{561}{273894} = \frac{748}{365192}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{374}{196258} = \frac{561}{294387} = \frac{748}{392516}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{374}{198256} = \frac{561}{297384} = \frac{748}{396512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{374}{256198} = \frac{561}{384297} = \frac{748}{512396}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{374}{258196} = \frac{561}{387294} = \frac{748}{516392}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{374}{259618} = \frac{561}{389427} = \frac{748}{519236}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{374}{259816} = \frac{561}{389724} = \frac{748}{519632}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{374}{598162} = \frac{561}{897243} = \frac{572}{914836}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{158249} = \frac{472}{198653} = \frac{752}{316498}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{387}{129645} = \frac{789}{264315} = \frac{819}{274365}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{194582} = \frac{564}{291873} = \frac{752}{389164}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{387}{496521} = \frac{657}{842931} = \frac{726}{931458}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{219458} = \frac{564}{329187} = \frac{752}{438916}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{392}{471856} = \frac{427}{513986} = \frac{742}{893156}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{125496} = \frac{524}{173968} = \frac{954}{316728}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{396}{145782} = \frac{528}{194376} = \frac{594}{218673}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{156492} = \frac{468}{193752} = \frac{756}{312984}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{396}{174258} = \frac{594}{261387} = \frac{792}{348516}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{165942} = \frac{423}{185697} = \frac{567}{248913}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{396}{175824} = \frac{792}{351648} = \frac{972}{431568}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{192564} = \frac{497}{253186} = \frac{749}{381562}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{396}{182574} = \frac{594}{273861} = \frac{792}{365148}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{194562} = \frac{567}{291843} = \frac{756}{389124}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{396}{241758} = \frac{792}{483516} = \frac{936}{571428}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{196452} = \frac{574}{298316} = \frac{658}{341972}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{396}{257418} = \frac{594}{386127} = \frac{792}{514836}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{215964} = \frac{621}{354798} = \frac{756}{431928}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{396}{258174} = \frac{594}{387261} = \frac{792}{516348}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{216594} = \frac{567}{324891} = \frac{792}{453816}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{396}{275814} = \frac{768}{534912} = \frac{824}{573916}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{465912} = \frac{693}{854172} = \frac{756}{931824}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{162574} = \frac{597}{243861} = \frac{796}{325148}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{256794} = \frac{781}{526394} = \frac{813}{547962}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{174256} = \frac{597}{261384} = \frac{796}{348512}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{264795} = \frac{681}{473295} = \frac{897}{623415}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{256174} = \frac{597}{384261} = \frac{796}{512348}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{279654} = \frac{738}{541692} = \frac{813}{596742}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{257416} = \frac{597}{386124} = \frac{796}{514832}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{382}{179456} = \frac{573}{269184} = \frac{764}{358912}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{412}{379658} = \frac{648}{597132} = \frac{824}{759316}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{382}{194576} = \frac{573}{291864} = \frac{764}{389152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{417}{328596} = \frac{819}{645372} = \frac{834}{657192}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{157296} = \frac{432}{176958} = \frac{768}{314592}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{426}{315879} = \frac{512}{379648} = \frac{612}{453798}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{197256} = \frac{672}{345198} = \frac{768}{394512}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{531687} = \frac{473}{586219} = \frac{594}{736182}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{567138} = \frac{431}{569782} = \frac{713}{942586}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{451}{782936} = \frac{491}{852376} = \frac{567}{984312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{459}{182763} = \frac{476}{189532} = \frac{867}{345219}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{459}{187623} = \frac{782}{319654} = \frac{918}{375246}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{462}{157839} = \frac{854}{291763} = \frac{924}{315678}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{462}{379158} = \frac{847}{695123} = \frac{924}{758316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{215397} = \frac{516}{237489} = \frac{792}{364518}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{125673} = \frac{762}{195834} = \frac{978}{251346}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{135768} = \frac{861}{237594} = \frac{984}{271536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{496}{517328} = \frac{589}{614327} = \frac{598}{623714}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{514}{297863} = \frac{758}{439261} = \frac{782}{453169}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{531}{486927} = \frac{637}{584129} = \frac{823}{754691}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{541}{637298} = \frac{694}{817532} = \frac{723}{851694}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{543}{186792} = \frac{924}{317856} = \frac{954}{328176}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{546}{291837} = \frac{672}{359184} = \frac{798}{426531}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{548}{326197} = \frac{876}{521439} = \frac{964}{573821}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{549}{378261} = \frac{789}{543621} = \frac{948}{653172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{329184} = \frac{612}{349758} = \frac{918}{524637}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{491328} = \frac{738}{629514} = \frac{954}{813762}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{583}{429671} = \frac{587}{432619} = \frac{849}{625713}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{183276} = \frac{627}{193458} = \frac{759}{234186}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{327618} = \frac{627}{345819} = \frac{759}{418623}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{596}{427183} = \frac{748}{536129} = \frac{784}{561932}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{597}{142683} = \frac{627}{149853} = \frac{984}{235176}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{615}{293847} = \frac{865}{413297} = \frac{895}{427631}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{631}{572948} = \frac{819}{743652} = \frac{964}{875312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{642}{375891} = \frac{654}{382917} = \frac{984}{576132}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{645}{182793} = \frac{945}{267813} = \frac{965}{273481}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{193752} = \frac{861}{257439} = \frac{957}{286143}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{678}{453921} = \frac{798}{534261} = \frac{842}{563719}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{684}{159372} = \frac{723}{168459} = \frac{792}{184536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{693}{142758} = \frac{697}{143582} = \frac{789}{162534}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{742}{315986} = \frac{756}{321948} = \frac{812}{345796}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{746}{381952} = \frac{893}{457216} = \frac{928}{475136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{746}{851932} = \frac{836}{954712} = \frac{853}{974126}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{753}{819264} = \frac{847}{921536} = \frac{857}{932416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{769}{345281} = \frac{786}{352914} = \frac{789}{354261}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{794}{213586} = \frac{879}{236451} = \frac{936}{251784}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{3568794} = \frac{16}{4758392} = \frac{32}{9516784}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{3587694} = \frac{16}{4783592} = \frac{32}{9567184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{3697584} = \frac{24}{7395168} = \frac{27}{8319564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{3759648} = \frac{18}{5639472} = \frac{21}{6579384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{3975648} = \frac{18}{5963472} = \frac{21}{6957384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{4593768} = \frac{13}{4976582} = \frac{24}{9187536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{4837596} = \frac{18}{7256394} = \frac{21}{8465793}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{4839756} = \frac{18}{7259634} = \frac{21}{8469573}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{4935768} = \frac{21}{8637594} = \frac{24}{9871536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2457869} = \frac{26}{4915738} = \frac{52}{9831476}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2458679} = \frac{26}{4917358} = \frac{52}{9834716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2467859} = \frac{26}{4935718} = \frac{52}{9871436}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2468579} = \frac{26}{4937158} = \frac{52}{9874316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2574689} = \frac{26}{5149378} = \frac{43}{8516279}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{2859467} = \frac{26}{5718934} = \frac{36}{7918524}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{4298567} = \frac{24}{7935816} = \frac{26}{8597134}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2357968} = \frac{28}{4715936} = \frac{56}{9431872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2359678} = \frac{28}{4719356} = \frac{56}{9438712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2365798} = \frac{21}{3548697} = \frac{28}{4731596}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2365978} = \frac{21}{3548967} = \frac{28}{4731956}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2367958} = \frac{28}{4735916} = \frac{56}{9471832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2369578} = \frac{28}{4739156} = \frac{56}{9478312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2376598} = \frac{21}{3564897} = \frac{28}{4753196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2379658} = \frac{21}{3569487} = \frac{28}{4759316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2379856} = \frac{21}{3569784} = \frac{42}{7139568}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2396578} = \frac{21}{3594867} = \frac{28}{4793156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2397658} = \frac{21}{3596487} = \frac{28}{4795316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2397856} = \frac{21}{3596784} = \frac{42}{7193568}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{2658397} = \frac{28}{5316794} = \frac{38}{7215649}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{3657982} = \frac{21}{5486973} = \frac{28}{7315964}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{3659782} = \frac{21}{5489673} = \frac{28}{7319564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{3765982} = \frac{21}{5648973} = \frac{28}{7531964}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{3796582} = \frac{21}{5694873} = \frac{28}{7593164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{3965782} = \frac{21}{5948673} = \frac{28}{7931564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{3976582} = \frac{21}{5964873} = \frac{28}{7953164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2379854} = \frac{24}{3569781} = \frac{48}{7139562}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2397854} = \frac{24}{3596781} = \frac{48}{7193562}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2437958} = \frac{32}{4875916} = \frac{64}{9751832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2439578} = \frac{32}{4879156} = \frac{64}{9758312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2457893} = \frac{32}{4915786} = \frac{64}{9831572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2457938} = \frac{32}{4915876} = \frac{64}{9831752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2458793} = \frac{32}{4917586} = \frac{64}{9835172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2459378} = \frac{32}{4918756} = \frac{64}{9837512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2573984} = \frac{32}{5147968} = \frac{43}{6917582}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2574398} = \frac{24}{3861597} = \frac{32}{5148796}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2583974} = \frac{24}{3875961} = \frac{32}{5167948}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2597438} = \frac{24}{3896157} = \frac{32}{5194876}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{2598374} = \frac{24}{3897561} = \frac{32}{5196748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3742598} = \frac{24}{5613897} = \frac{32}{7485196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3759824} = \frac{31}{7284659} = \frac{32}{7519648}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3794582} = \frac{24}{5691873} = \frac{32}{7589164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3825974} = \frac{24}{5738961} = \frac{32}{7651948}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3895472} = \frac{19}{4625873} = \frac{38}{9251746}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3945728} = \frac{23}{5671984} = \frac{32}{7891456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3945782} = \frac{24}{5918673} = \frac{32}{7891564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3957824} = \frac{32}{7915648} = \frac{37}{9152468}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3974258} = \frac{24}{5961387} = \frac{32}{7948516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{3982574} = \frac{24}{5973861} = \frac{32}{7965148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{2456398} = \frac{19}{2745386} = \frac{48}{6935712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2357964} = \frac{36}{4715928} = \frac{72}{9431856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2359764} = \frac{36}{4719528} = \frac{63}{8259174}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2364579} = \frac{36}{4729158} = \frac{72}{9458316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2379456} = \frac{27}{3569184} = \frac{36}{4758912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2379564} = \frac{36}{4759128} = \frac{54}{7138692}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2379654} = \frac{27}{3569481} = \frac{54}{7138962}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2394576} = \frac{27}{3591864} = \frac{36}{4789152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2397456} = \frac{27}{3596184} = \frac{54}{7192368}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2435976} = \frac{36}{4871952} = \frac{43}{5819276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2439756} = \frac{36}{4879512} = \frac{54}{7319268}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2463579} = \frac{36}{4927158} = \frac{72}{9854316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2543976} = \frac{27}{3815964} = \frac{54}{7631928}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2563794} = \frac{27}{3845691} = \frac{54}{7691382}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2563974} = \frac{27}{3845961} = \frac{36}{5127948}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2574396} = \frac{27}{3861594} = \frac{36}{5148792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2596374} = \frac{27}{3894561} = \frac{36}{5192748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2597436} = \frac{27}{3896154} = \frac{36}{5194872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2739564} = \frac{26}{3957148} = \frac{36}{5479128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{2945736} = \frac{36}{5891472} = \frac{57}{9328164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3625974} = \frac{27}{5438961} = \frac{36}{7251948}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3742596} = \frac{27}{5613894} = \frac{36}{7485192}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3794562} = \frac{27}{5691843} = \frac{36}{7589124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3945762} = \frac{27}{5918643} = \frac{36}{7891524}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3956427} = \frac{26}{5714839} = \frac{36}{7912854}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3962574} = \frac{27}{5943861} = \frac{36}{7925148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{3974256} = \frac{27}{5961384} = \frac{36}{7948512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{5943276} = \frac{19}{6273458} = \frac{23}{7594186}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{2364578} = \frac{38}{4729156} = \frac{76}{9458312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{2378456} = \frac{38}{4756912} = \frac{76}{9513824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{2435876} = \frac{48}{6153792} = \frac{53}{6794812}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{2457863} = \frac{38}{4915726} = \frac{76}{9831452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{2463578} = \frac{38}{4927156} = \frac{76}{9854312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{2745638} = \frac{38}{5491276} = \frac{57}{8236914}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21}{3645789} = \frac{38}{6597142} = \frac{47}{8159623}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1457869} = \frac{46}{2915738} = \frac{92}{5831476}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1458679} = \frac{46}{2917358} = \frac{92}{5834716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1467859} = \frac{46}{2935718} = \frac{92}{5871436}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1468579} = \frac{46}{2937158} = \frac{92}{5874316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1578946} = \frac{46}{3157892} = \frac{92}{6315784}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1587946} = \frac{46}{3175892} = \frac{92}{6351784}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1675849} = \frac{39}{2841657} = \frac{74}{5391862}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1785964} = \frac{46}{3571928} = \frac{92}{7143856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1786459} = \frac{46}{3572918} = \frac{92}{7145836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1795864} = \frac{46}{3591728} = \frac{92}{7183456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1857964} = \frac{46}{3715928} = \frac{92}{7431856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1864579} = \frac{46}{3729158} = \frac{92}{7458316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{1957864} = \frac{46}{3915728} = \frac{92}{7831456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1357968} = \frac{48}{2715936} = \frac{96}{5431872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1359678} = \frac{48}{2719356} = \frac{96}{5438712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1367958} = \frac{48}{2735916} = \frac{96}{5471832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1369578} = \frac{48}{2739156} = \frac{96}{5478312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1379568} = \frac{48}{2759136} = \frac{67}{3851294}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1579368} = \frac{78}{5132946} = \frac{82}{5396174}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1597836} = \frac{48}{3195672} = \frac{52}{3461978}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{1763598} = \frac{48}{3527196} = \frac{84}{6172593}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \triangleright \frac{24}{1783956} = \frac{48}{3567912} = \frac{96}{7135824} & \triangleright \frac{24}{3987516} = \frac{36}{5981274} = \frac{42}{6978153} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{1785963} = \frac{48}{3571926} = \frac{96}{7143852} & \triangleright \frac{26}{1549873} = \frac{36}{2145978} = \frac{54}{3218967} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{1795638} = \frac{48}{3591276} = \frac{72}{5386914} & \triangleright \frac{26}{1895374} = \frac{62}{4519738} = \frac{68}{4957132} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{1795863} = \frac{48}{3591726} = \frac{96}{7183452} & \triangleright \frac{27}{1345869} = \frac{54}{2691738} = \frac{96}{4785312} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{1796358} = \frac{48}{3592716} = \frac{96}{7185432} & \triangleright \frac{27}{1348569} = \frac{54}{2697138} = \frac{72}{3596184} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{1837956} = \frac{48}{3675912} = \frac{96}{7351824} & \triangleright \frac{27}{1385694} = \frac{36}{1847592} = \frac{72}{3695184} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{1857963} = \frac{48}{3715926} = \frac{96}{7431852} & \triangleright \frac{27}{1483569} = \frac{54}{2967138} = \frac{72}{3956184} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{1956378} = \frac{48}{3912756} = \frac{72}{5869134} & \triangleright \frac{27}{1856493} = \frac{54}{3712986} = \frac{86}{5913274} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{1957863} = \frac{48}{3915726} = \frac{96}{7831452} & \triangleright \frac{27}{3586194} = \frac{36}{4781592} = \frac{72}{9563184} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{1963578} = \frac{48}{3927156} = \frac{96}{7854312} & \triangleright \frac{27}{3956418} = \frac{39}{5714826} = \frac{54}{7912836} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{1976358} = \frac{48}{3952716} = \frac{84}{6917253} & \triangleright \frac{27}{5861943} = \frac{36}{7815924} = \frac{39}{8467251} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{3158976} = \frac{48}{6317952} = \frac{58}{7634192} & \triangleright \frac{28}{1349576} = \frac{49}{2361758} = \frac{98}{4723516} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{3518796} = \frac{36}{5278194} = \frac{42}{6157893} & \triangleright \frac{28}{1357496} = \frac{49}{2375618} = \frac{98}{4751236} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{3519876} = \frac{36}{5279814} = \frac{42}{6159783} & \triangleright \frac{28}{1573649} = \frac{32}{1798456} = \frac{56}{3147298} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{3615978} = \frac{48}{7231956} = \frac{52}{7834619} & \triangleright \frac{28}{1574936} = \frac{49}{2756138} = \frac{56}{3149872} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{3875196} = \frac{36}{5812794} = \frac{42}{6781593} & \triangleright \frac{28}{1694357} = \frac{36}{2178459} = \frac{72}{4356918} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{3879516} = \frac{36}{5819274} = \frac{42}{6789153} & \triangleright \frac{28}{1745639} = \frac{56}{3491278} = \frac{84}{5236917} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{3951876} = \frac{36}{5927814} = \frac{42}{6915783} & \triangleright \frac{28}{3571694} = \frac{36}{4592178} = \frac{72}{9184356} \\ & \triangleright \frac{24}{3985716} = \frac{26}{4317859} = \frac{58}{9632147} & \triangleright \frac{28}{3591746} = \frac{42}{5387619} = \frac{56}{7183492} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{3714956} = \frac{47}{6235819} = \frac{73}{9685421}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{3915746} = \frac{42}{5873619} = \frac{56}{7831492}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{4915736} = \frac{32}{5617984} = \frac{56}{9831472}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29}{1365784} = \frac{91}{4285736} = \frac{97}{4568312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29}{1483756} = \frac{57}{2916348} = \frac{68}{3479152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29}{1745638} = \frac{58}{3491276} = \frac{87}{5236914}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29}{3164857} = \frac{39}{4256187} = \frac{58}{6329714}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29}{4563817} = \frac{46}{7239158} = \frac{58}{9127634}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31}{2698457} = \frac{41}{3568927} = \frac{67}{5832149}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31}{4285967} = \frac{52}{7189364} = \frac{62}{8571934}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31}{4592867} = \frac{59}{8741263} = \frac{62}{9185734}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1497568} = \frac{51}{2386749} = \frac{61}{2854739}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1567984} = \frac{48}{2351976} = \frac{86}{4213957}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1578496} = \frac{87}{4291536} = \frac{92}{4538176}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1596784} = \frac{48}{2395176} = \frac{86}{4291357}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1769584} = \frac{54}{2986173} = \frac{72}{3981564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32}{1954768} = \frac{52}{3176498} = \frac{54}{3298671}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{1785962} = \frac{51}{2678943} = \frac{68}{3571924}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{1798562} = \frac{51}{2697843} = \frac{68}{3597124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{1857962} = \frac{51}{2786943} = \frac{68}{3715924}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{1859762} = \frac{51}{2789643} = \frac{68}{3719524}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{1978562} = \frac{51}{2967843} = \frac{68}{3957124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{1985762} = \frac{51}{2978643} = \frac{68}{3971524}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2178596} = \frac{51}{3267894} = \frac{68}{4357192}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2179856} = \frac{51}{3269784} = \frac{68}{4359712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2185796} = \frac{51}{3278694} = \frac{68}{4371592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2185976} = \frac{51}{3278964} = \frac{68}{4371952}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2197856} = \frac{51}{3296784} = \frac{68}{4395712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2198576} = \frac{51}{3297864} = \frac{68}{4397152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34}{2587196} = \frac{68}{5174392} = \frac{94}{7152836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1527948} = \frac{46}{1952378} = \frac{87}{3692541}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1572984} = \frac{72}{3145968} = \frac{79}{3451826}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1597824} = \frac{72}{3195648} = \frac{78}{3461952}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1794582} = \frac{54}{2691873} = \frac{72}{3589164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1825974} = \frac{54}{2738961} = \frac{72}{3651948}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1945287} = \frac{48}{2593716} = \frac{96}{5187432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1945782} = \frac{54}{2918673} = \frac{72}{3891564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{1982574} = \frac{54}{2973861} = \frac{72}{3965148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2147598} = \frac{64}{3817952} = \frac{78}{4653129}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2179458} = \frac{54}{3269187} = \frac{72}{4358916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2415978} = \frac{72}{4831956} = \frac{78}{5234619}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2419758} = \frac{72}{4839516} = \frac{94}{6318257}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2574198} = \frac{54}{3861297} = \frac{72}{5148396}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2581974} = \frac{54}{3872961} = \frac{72}{5163948}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2597418} = \frac{54}{3896127} = \frac{72}{5194836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36}{2598174} = \frac{54}{3897261} = \frac{72}{5196348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{1465829} = \frac{63}{2495871} = \frac{74}{2931658}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{2459168} = \frac{56}{3721984} = \frac{98}{6513472}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{2469158} = \frac{68}{4537912} = \frac{86}{5739124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{2945681} = \frac{52}{4139876} = \frac{74}{5891362}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37}{5429861} = \frac{57}{8364921} = \frac{67}{9832451}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{1625974} = \frac{57}{2438961} = \frac{76}{3251948}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{1742596} = \frac{57}{2613894} = \frac{76}{3485192}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{1794562} = \frac{57}{2691843} = \frac{76}{3589124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{1945762} = \frac{57}{2918643} = \frac{76}{3891524}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{1962574} = \frac{57}{2943861} = \frac{76}{3925148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{1974256} = \frac{57}{2961384} = \frac{76}{3948512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{2179456} = \frac{57}{3269184} = \frac{76}{4358912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{2561974} = \frac{57}{3842961} = \frac{76}{5123948}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{2574196} = \frac{57}{3861294} = \frac{76}{5148392}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{2596174} = \frac{57}{3894261} = \frac{76}{5192348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38}{2597416} = \frac{57}{3896124} = \frac{76}{5194832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{1562478} = \frac{78}{3124956} = \frac{91}{3645782}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{1578246} = \frac{78}{3156492} = \frac{91}{3682574}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{1756248} = \frac{78}{3512496} = \frac{81}{3647592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{2164578} = \frac{59}{3274618} = \frac{78}{4329156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{2461578} = \frac{78}{4923156} = \frac{91}{5743682}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{2478156} = \frac{78}{4956312} = \frac{91}{5782364}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{4527861} = \frac{74}{8591326} = \frac{84}{9752316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{2583697} = \frac{78}{4915326} = \frac{82}{5167394}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{2956387} = \frac{61}{4398527} = \frac{89}{6417523}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{3258967} = \frac{82}{6517934} = \frac{83}{6597421}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{3926857} = \frac{61}{5842397} = \frac{62}{5938174}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{3897516} = \frac{51}{4732698} = \frac{92}{8537416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{3957618} = \frac{81}{7632549} = \frac{84}{7915236}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{5197836} = \frac{61}{7549238} = \frac{78}{9653124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{1928573} = \frac{58}{2431679} = \frac{92}{3857146}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{3815792} = \frac{91}{7548632} = \frac{92}{7631584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47}{1562938} = \frac{81}{2693574} = \frac{94}{3125876}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47}{2631859} = \frac{53}{2967841} = \frac{94}{5263718}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{1237596} = \frac{72}{1856394} = \frac{84}{2165793}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{1239756} = \frac{72}{1859634} = \frac{84}{2169573}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{1357692} = \frac{84}{2375961} = \frac{96}{2715384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{1592736} = \frac{96}{3185472} = \frac{97}{3218654}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{1673952} = \frac{94}{3278156} = \frac{98}{3417652}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{1729356} = \frac{52}{1873469} = \frac{96}{3458712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{2175936} = \frac{93}{4215876} = \frac{96}{4351872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{3561792} = \frac{73}{5416892} = \frac{96}{7123584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{3617952} = \frac{57}{4296318} = \frac{58}{4371692}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{3657912} = \frac{74}{5639281} = \frac{96}{7315824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{3759612} = \frac{72}{5639418} = \frac{84}{6579321}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{3769152} = \frac{83}{6517492} = \frac{94}{7381256}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{3975612} = \frac{72}{5963418} = \frac{84}{6957321}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{7521936} = \frac{62}{9715834} = \frac{63}{9872541}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{1573628} = \frac{56}{1798432} = \frac{98}{3147256}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{1725836} = \frac{56}{1972384} = \frac{98}{3451672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{3716258} = \frac{51}{3867942} = \frac{98}{7432516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52}{1893476} = \frac{59}{2148367} = \frac{73}{2658149}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52}{1937468} = \frac{71}{2645389} = \frac{84}{3129756}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52}{4369781} = \frac{64}{5378192} = \frac{68}{5714329}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{4832916} = \frac{73}{6189524} = \frac{89}{7546132}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{3967142} = \frac{71}{4856329} = \frac{76}{5198324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{67}{2584391} = \frac{76}{2931548} = \frac{92}{3548716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{69}{7824531} = \frac{74}{8391526} = \frac{86}{9752314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{23456789} = \frac{2}{46913578} = \frac{4}{93827156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{23456879} = \frac{2}{46913758} = \frac{4}{93827516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{23784569} = \frac{2}{47569138} = \frac{4}{95138276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{23794658} = \frac{2}{47589316} = \frac{4}{95178632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{23795684} = \frac{2}{47591368} = \frac{4}{95182736}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{23845679} = \frac{2}{47691358} = \frac{4}{95382716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{23946578} = \frac{2}{47893156} = \frac{4}{95786312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{23956784} = \frac{2}{47913568} = \frac{4}{95827136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{24379658} = \frac{2}{48759316} = \frac{4}{97518632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{24396578} = \frac{2}{48793156} = \frac{4}{97586312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{24567839} = \frac{2}{49135678} = \frac{4}{98271356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{24568379} = \frac{2}{49136758} = \frac{4}{98273516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{24657893} = \frac{2}{49315786} = \frac{4}{98631572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{24657938} = \frac{2}{49315876} = \frac{4}{98631752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{24658793} = \frac{2}{49317586} = \frac{4}{98635172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{24659378} = \frac{2}{49318756} = \frac{4}{98637512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{13478569} = \frac{4}{26957138} = \frac{8}{53914276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{13485679} = \frac{4}{26971358} = \frac{8}{53942716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{13567849} = \frac{4}{27135698} = \frac{8}{54271396}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{13567984} = \frac{4}{27135968} = \frac{8}{54271936}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{13568479} = \frac{4}{27136958} = \frac{8}{54273916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{13569784} = \frac{4}{27139568} = \frac{8}{54279136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{13657948} = \frac{4}{27315896} = \frac{8}{54631792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{13659478} = \frac{4}{27318956} = \frac{8}{54637912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{13796584} = \frac{4}{27593168} = \frac{6}{41389752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{13965784} = \frac{4}{27931568} = \frac{6}{41897352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14376598} = \frac{3}{21564897} = \frac{4}{28753196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14379658} = \frac{3}{21569487} = \frac{4}{28759316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14385976} = \frac{3}{21578964} = \frac{6}{43157928}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14396578} = \frac{3}{21594867} = \frac{4}{28793156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14397658} = \frac{3}{21596487} = \frac{4}{28795316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14398576} = \frac{3}{21597864} = \frac{6}{43195728}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14583976} = \frac{3}{21875964} = \frac{6}{43751928}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14598376} = \frac{3}{21897564} = \frac{6}{43795128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14756938} = \frac{4}{29513876} = \frac{7}{51649283}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14783569} = \frac{4}{29567138} = \frac{8}{59134276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14786593} = \frac{4}{29573186} = \frac{8}{59146372}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14793658} = \frac{4}{29587316} = \frac{8}{59174632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14835679} = \frac{4}{29671358} = \frac{8}{59342716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14865793} = \frac{4}{29731586} = \frac{8}{59463172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{14936578} = \frac{4}{29873156} = \frac{8}{59746312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15783964} = \frac{4}{31567928} = \frac{6}{47351892}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15786493} = \frac{4}{31572986} = \frac{8}{63145972}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15793648} = \frac{4}{31587296} = \frac{8}{63174592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15794863} = \frac{4}{31589726} = \frac{8}{63179452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15796384} = \frac{4}{31592768} = \frac{6}{47389152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15798643} = \frac{4}{31597286} = \frac{8}{63194572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15837964} = \frac{4}{31675928} = \frac{6}{47513892}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15843976} = \frac{4}{31687952} = \frac{6}{47531928}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15864793} = \frac{4}{31729586} = \frac{8}{63459172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15936478} = \frac{4}{31872956} = \frac{8}{63745912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15947863} = \frac{4}{31895726} = \frac{8}{63791452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15963784} = \frac{4}{31927568} = \frac{6}{47891352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15978643} = \frac{4}{31957286} = \frac{8}{63914572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{15984376} = \frac{4}{31968752} = \frac{6}{47953128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16357948} = \frac{4}{32715896} = \frac{8}{65431792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16359478} = \frac{4}{32718956} = \frac{8}{65437912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16378594} = \frac{3}{24567891} = \frac{6}{49135782}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16379458} = \frac{3}{24569187} = \frac{4}{32758916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16379584} = \frac{4}{32759168} = \frac{6}{49138752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16385794} = \frac{3}{24578691} = \frac{6}{49157382}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16394578} = \frac{3}{24591867} = \frac{4}{32789156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16395784} = \frac{4}{32791568} = \frac{6}{49187352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16435798} = \frac{4}{32871596} = \frac{8}{65743192}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16435978} = \frac{4}{32871956} = \frac{8}{65743912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16478593} = \frac{4}{32957186} = \frac{8}{65914372}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16479358} = \frac{4}{32958716} = \frac{8}{65917432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16485793} = \frac{4}{32971586} = \frac{8}{65943172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16493578} = \frac{4}{32987156} = \frac{8}{65974312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16578394} = \frac{3}{24867591} = \frac{6}{49735182}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{16583794} = \frac{3}{24875691} = \frac{6}{49751382}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17439658} = \frac{3}{26159487} = \frac{6}{52318974}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17459638} = \frac{3}{26189457} = \frac{6}{52378914}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17594638} = \frac{4}{35189276} = \frac{6}{52783914}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17596438} = \frac{4}{35192876} = \frac{6}{52789314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17643958} = \frac{4}{35287916} = \frac{6}{52931874}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17645938} = \frac{4}{35291876} = \frac{6}{52937814}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17659438} = \frac{3}{26489157} = \frac{6}{52978314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17835649} = \frac{4}{35671298} = \frac{8}{71342596}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17839456} = \frac{3}{26759184} = \frac{4}{35678912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17856349} = \frac{4}{35712698} = \frac{8}{71425396}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17859634} = \frac{3}{26789451} = \frac{4}{35719268}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17945638} = \frac{3}{26918457} = \frac{4}{35891276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17945836} = \frac{3}{26918754} = \frac{4}{35891672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{17983564} = \frac{4}{35967128} = \frac{8}{71934256}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{18356479} = \frac{4}{36712958} = \frac{8}{73425916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{18379456} = \frac{3}{27569184} = \frac{4}{36758912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{18394576} = \frac{3}{27591864} = \frac{4}{36789152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{18563479} = \frac{4}{37126958} = \frac{8}{74253916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{18579634} = \frac{3}{27869451} = \frac{4}{37159268}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{18597634} = \frac{3}{27896451} = \frac{4}{37195268}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{19376458} = \frac{4}{38752916} = \frac{6}{58129374}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{19437658} = \frac{3}{29156487} = \frac{6}{58312974}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{19456378} = \frac{3}{29184567} = \frac{4}{38912756}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{19457836} = \frac{3}{29186754} = \frac{4}{38915672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{19458376} = \frac{3}{29187564} = \frac{4}{38916752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{19463758} = \frac{4}{38927516} = \frac{6}{58391274}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{19576438} = \frac{4}{39152876} = \frac{6}{58729314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{19637458} = \frac{3}{29456187} = \frac{6}{58912374}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{19643758} = \frac{4}{39287516} = \frac{6}{58931274}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{19657438} = \frac{3}{29486157} = \frac{6}{58972314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{19783564} = \frac{4}{39567128} = \frac{8}{79134256}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{19857634} = \frac{3}{29786451} = \frac{4}{39715268}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{34178596} = \frac{3}{51267894} = \frac{4}{68357192}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{34179856} = \frac{3}{51269784} = \frac{4}{68359712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{34185796} = \frac{3}{51278694} = \frac{4}{68371592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{34185976} = \frac{3}{51278964} = \frac{4}{68371952}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{34197856} = \frac{3}{51296784} = \frac{4}{68395712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{34198576} = \frac{3}{51297864} = \frac{4}{68397152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{36179458} = \frac{3}{54269187} = \frac{4}{72358916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{36194578} = \frac{3}{54291867} = \frac{4}{72389156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{36579814} = \frac{3}{54869721} = \frac{4}{73159628}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{36597814} = \frac{3}{54896721} = \frac{4}{73195628}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{37619458} = \frac{3}{56429187} = \frac{4}{75238916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{37659814} = \frac{3}{56489721} = \frac{4}{75319628}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{37819456} = \frac{3}{56729184} = \frac{4}{75638912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{37945618} = \frac{3}{56918427} = \frac{4}{75891236}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{37945816} = \frac{3}{56918724} = \frac{4}{75891632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{37965814} = \frac{3}{56948721} = \frac{4}{75931628}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{38179456} = \frac{3}{57269184} = \frac{4}{76358912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{38194576} = \frac{3}{57291864} = \frac{4}{76389152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{39456178} = \frac{3}{59184267} = \frac{4}{78912356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{39457618} = \frac{3}{59186427} = \frac{4}{78915236}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{39457816} = \frac{3}{59186724} = \frac{4}{78915632}$$

$\triangleright \frac{2}{39458176} = \frac{3}{59187264} = \frac{4}{78916352}$ $\triangleright \frac{2}{39657814} = \frac{3}{59486721} = \frac{4}{79315628}$ $\triangleright \frac{2}{39765814} = \frac{3}{59648721} = \frac{4}{79531628}$ $\triangleright \frac{3}{12569874} = \frac{4}{16759832} = \frac{6}{25139748}$ $\triangleright \frac{3}{12596874} = \frac{4}{16795832} = \frac{6}{25193748}$ $\triangleright \frac{3}{19285476} = \frac{4}{25713968} = \frac{8}{51427936}$ $\triangleright \frac{3}{19478526} = \frac{4}{25971368} = \frac{8}{51942736}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{28619457} = \frac{4}{38159276} = \frac{6}{57238914}$ $\triangleright \frac{3}{29458617} = \frac{4}{39278156} = \frac{6}{58917234}$ $\triangleright \frac{4}{19582376} = \frac{7}{34269158} = \frac{8}{39164752}$ $\triangleright \frac{4}{19823576} = \frac{7}{34691258} = \frac{8}{39647152}$
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6.2.11 2 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 32482 examples, each one with 2 expressions for the digits 1 to 9. Since, this number is too high to write here, below are just few examples:

$\triangleright \frac{5128}{37496} = \frac{5769}{42183}$ $\triangleright \frac{5129}{36478} = \frac{5798}{41236}$ $\triangleright \frac{5136}{47829} = \frac{5328}{49617}$ $\triangleright \frac{5146}{32798} = \frac{8964}{57132}$ $\triangleright \frac{5146}{73289} = \frac{5394}{76821}$ $\triangleright \frac{5148}{36729} = \frac{5876}{41923}$ $\triangleright \frac{5168}{29374} = \frac{8296}{47153}$ $\triangleright \frac{5168}{43792} = \frac{7581}{64239}$ $\triangleright \frac{5187}{64239} = \frac{5928}{73416}$ $\triangleright \frac{5192}{37864} = \frac{8437}{61529}$ $\triangleright \frac{5192}{76384} = \frac{5723}{84196}$	$\triangleright \frac{5194}{23786} = \frac{5936}{27184}$ $\triangleright \frac{5194}{28763} = \frac{5724}{31698}$ $\triangleright \frac{5194}{36782} = \frac{7938}{56214}$ $\triangleright \frac{5198}{27346} = \frac{6187}{32549}$ $\triangleright \frac{5217}{83694} = \frac{5687}{91234}$ $\triangleright \frac{5219}{37468} = \frac{9517}{68324}$ $\triangleright \frac{5236}{17948} = \frac{6358}{21794}$ $\triangleright \frac{5246}{89731} = \frac{5418}{92673}$ $\triangleright \frac{5247}{38169} = \frac{8162}{59374}$ $\triangleright \frac{5267}{13984} = \frac{7328}{19456}$ $\triangleright \frac{5278}{46319} = \frac{9512}{83476}$	$\triangleright \frac{5283}{14967} = \frac{6457}{18293}$ $\triangleright \frac{5283}{17964} = \frac{7631}{25948}$ $\triangleright \frac{5287}{19346} = \frac{9641}{35278}$ $\triangleright \frac{5289}{46371} = \frac{9417}{82563}$ $\triangleright \frac{5291}{36478} = \frac{8954}{61732}$ $\triangleright \frac{5291}{37648} = \frac{8954}{63712}$ $\triangleright \frac{5291}{48763} = \frac{8621}{79453}$ $\triangleright \frac{5317}{28964} = \frac{9816}{53472}$ $\triangleright \frac{5327}{49861} = \frac{9132}{85476}$ $\triangleright \frac{5328}{19647} = \frac{5376}{19824}$ $\triangleright \frac{5328}{71946} = \frac{6512}{87934}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{17982} = \frac{6534}{21978}$ $\triangleright \frac{5346}{21978} = \frac{6318}{25974}$ $\triangleright \frac{5346}{71928} = \frac{6534}{87912}$ $\triangleright \frac{5369}{87412} = \frac{5782}{94136}$ $\triangleright \frac{5371}{46289} = \frac{9563}{82417}$ $\triangleright \frac{5382}{17946} = \frac{6578}{21934}$ $\triangleright \frac{5394}{72168} = \frac{6351}{84972}$ $\triangleright \frac{5396}{14782} = \frac{6532}{17894}$ $\triangleright \frac{5412}{89736} = \frac{5863}{97214}$ $\triangleright \frac{5416}{23798} = \frac{8124}{35697}$ $\triangleright \frac{5416}{23978} = \frac{8124}{35967}$
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$\triangleright \frac{5416}{37982} = \frac{8124}{56973}$	$\triangleright \frac{5467}{29183} = \frac{6958}{37142}$	$\triangleright \frac{5634}{21978} = \frac{8451}{32967}$	$\triangleright \frac{5697}{13824} = \frac{7596}{18432}$
$\triangleright \frac{5416}{39782} = \frac{8124}{59673}$	$\triangleright \frac{5472}{13896} = \frac{9576}{24318}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{17942} = \frac{8457}{26913}$	$\triangleright \frac{5697}{24138} = \frac{7596}{32184}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{23796} = \frac{8127}{35694}$	$\triangleright \frac{5472}{19836} = \frac{6984}{25317}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{19742} = \frac{8457}{29613}$	$\triangleright \frac{5736}{41892} = \frac{8126}{59347}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{23976} = \frac{8127}{35964}$	$\triangleright \frac{5472}{39861} = \frac{7296}{53148}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{21794} = \frac{8457}{32691}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{16398} = \frac{8613}{24597}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{37962} = \frac{8127}{56943}$	$\triangleright \frac{5478}{63921} = \frac{6972}{81354}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{21974} = \frac{8457}{32961}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{18396} = \frac{8613}{27594}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{39762} = \frac{8127}{59643}$	$\triangleright \frac{5487}{13629} = \frac{9548}{23716}$	$\triangleright \frac{5643}{27189} = \frac{6138}{29574}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{19638} = \frac{8613}{29457}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{69237} = \frac{7482}{95613}$	$\triangleright \frac{5491}{38726} = \frac{8417}{59362}$	$\triangleright \frac{5648}{39712} = \frac{9178}{64532}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{19836} = \frac{8613}{29754}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{73692} = \frac{6321}{85974}$	$\triangleright \frac{5493}{71862} = \frac{7324}{95816}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{12738} = \frac{7532}{16984}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{31968} = \frac{8613}{47952}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{76932} = \frac{6321}{89754}$	$\triangleright \frac{5612}{78934} = \frac{6532}{91874}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{13872} = \frac{7532}{18496}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{36198} = \frac{8613}{54297}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{79632} = \frac{5934}{87216}$	$\triangleright \frac{5614}{23798} = \frac{8421}{35697}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{32718} = \frac{5918}{34276}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{38196} = \frac{8613}{57294}$
$\triangleright \frac{5423}{71896} = \frac{5916}{78432}$	$\triangleright \frac{5614}{23978} = \frac{8421}{35967}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{72138} = \frac{7532}{96184}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{39618} = \frac{8613}{59427}$
$\triangleright \frac{5428}{17936} = \frac{7843}{25916}$	$\triangleright \frac{5614}{37982} = \frac{8421}{56973}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{73812} = \frac{7532}{98416}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{39816} = \frac{8613}{59724}$
$\triangleright \frac{5436}{17982} = \frac{8154}{26973}$	$\triangleright \frac{5614}{39782} = \frac{8421}{59673}$	$\triangleright \frac{5671}{32489} = \frac{7918}{45362}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{14398} = \frac{8643}{21597}$
$\triangleright \frac{5436}{19782} = \frac{8154}{29673}$	$\triangleright \frac{5618}{23794} = \frac{8427}{35691}$	$\triangleright \frac{5678}{43921} = \frac{9248}{71536}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{18394} = \frac{8643}{27591}$
$\triangleright \frac{5436}{21798} = \frac{8154}{32697}$	$\triangleright \frac{5618}{23974} = \frac{8427}{35961}$	$\triangleright \frac{5681}{37924} = \frac{6578}{43912}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{19438} = \frac{8643}{29157}$
$\triangleright \frac{5436}{21978} = \frac{8154}{32967}$	$\triangleright \frac{5618}{37942} = \frac{8427}{56913}$	$\triangleright \frac{5682}{31794} = \frac{8523}{47691}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{19834} = \frac{8643}{29751}$
$\triangleright \frac{5436}{89172} = \frac{5738}{94126}$	$\triangleright \frac{5618}{39742} = \frac{8427}{59613}$	$\triangleright \frac{5682}{31974} = \frac{8523}{47961}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{34198} = \frac{8643}{51297}$
$\triangleright \frac{5438}{17962} = \frac{8157}{26943}$	$\triangleright \frac{5624}{37981} = \frac{6512}{43978}$	$\triangleright \frac{5684}{27391} = \frac{7192}{34658}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{38194} = \frac{8643}{57291}$
$\triangleright \frac{5438}{19762} = \frac{8157}{29643}$	$\triangleright \frac{5634}{17982} = \frac{8451}{26973}$	$\triangleright \frac{5687}{43219} = \frac{9823}{74651}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{39418} = \frac{8643}{59127}$
$\triangleright \frac{5438}{21796} = \frac{8157}{32694}$	$\triangleright \frac{5634}{19782} = \frac{8451}{29673}$	$\triangleright \frac{5691}{24738} = \frac{7859}{34162}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{39814} = \frac{8643}{59721}$
$\triangleright \frac{5438}{21976} = \frac{8157}{32964}$	$\triangleright \frac{5634}{21798} = \frac{8451}{32697}$	$\triangleright \frac{5694}{13827} = \frac{7592}{18436}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{41839} = \frac{6298}{45731}$

$\triangleright \frac{5768}{23194} = \frac{8652}{34791}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{31682} = \frac{8691}{47523}$	$\triangleright \frac{5798}{14236} = \frac{8697}{21354}$	$\triangleright \frac{5819}{26473} = \frac{9361}{42587}$
$\triangleright \frac{5768}{29314} = \frac{8652}{43971}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{36182} = \frac{8691}{54273}$	$\triangleright \frac{5798}{14362} = \frac{8697}{21543}$	$\triangleright \frac{5823}{17469} = \frac{5832}{17496}$
$\triangleright \frac{5768}{31942} = \frac{8652}{47913}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{36218} = \frac{8691}{54327}$	$\triangleright \frac{5798}{16234} = \frac{8697}{24351}$	$\triangleright \frac{5824}{31976} = \frac{7592}{41683}$
$\triangleright \frac{5768}{32914} = \frac{8652}{49371}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{38162} = \frac{8691}{57243}$	$\triangleright \frac{5798}{16342} = \frac{8697}{24513}$	$\triangleright \frac{5829}{43617} = \frac{6873}{51429}$
$\triangleright \frac{5782}{16394} = \frac{8673}{24591}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{38216} = \frac{8691}{57324}$	$\triangleright \frac{5798}{21436} = \frac{8697}{32154}$	$\triangleright \frac{5832}{41796} = \frac{6318}{45279}$
$\triangleright \frac{5782}{19436} = \frac{8673}{29154}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{12834} = \frac{6972}{15438}$	$\triangleright \frac{5798}{21634} = \frac{8697}{32451}$	$\triangleright \frac{5834}{17962} = \frac{8751}{26943}$
$\triangleright \frac{5782}{19634} = \frac{8673}{29451}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{13248} = \frac{9387}{21456}$	$\triangleright \frac{5798}{23416} = \frac{8697}{35124}$	$\triangleright \frac{5834}{19762} = \frac{8751}{29643}$
$\triangleright \frac{5782}{34196} = \frac{8673}{51294}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{14238} = \frac{8694}{21357}$	$\triangleright \frac{5798}{23614} = \frac{8697}{35421}$	$\triangleright \frac{5834}{21796} = \frac{8751}{32694}$
$\triangleright \frac{5782}{36194} = \frac{8673}{54291}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{14382} = \frac{8694}{21573}$	$\triangleright \frac{5798}{26314} = \frac{5837}{26491}$	$\triangleright \frac{5834}{21976} = \frac{8751}{32964}$
$\triangleright \frac{5782}{39416} = \frac{8673}{59124}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{18234} = \frac{8694}{27351}$	$\triangleright \frac{5798}{34162} = \frac{8697}{51243}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{17942} = \frac{8754}{26913}$
$\triangleright \frac{5782}{39614} = \frac{8673}{59421}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{18342} = \frac{8694}{27513}$	$\triangleright \frac{5798}{34216} = \frac{8697}{51324}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{19742} = \frac{8754}{29613}$
$\triangleright \frac{5792}{18643} = \frac{9856}{31724}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{21438} = \frac{8694}{32157}$	$\triangleright \frac{5798}{36142} = \frac{8697}{54213}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{21794} = \frac{8754}{32691}$
$\triangleright \frac{5794}{16238} = \frac{8691}{24357}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{21834} = \frac{8694}{32751}$	$\triangleright \frac{5798}{36214} = \frac{8697}{54321}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{21974} = \frac{8754}{32961}$
$\triangleright \frac{5794}{16382} = \frac{8691}{24573}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{23418} = \frac{8694}{35127}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{23796} = \frac{8721}{35694}$	$\triangleright \frac{5841}{36927} = \frac{8496}{53712}$
$\triangleright \frac{5794}{18236} = \frac{8691}{27354}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{23814} = \frac{8694}{35721}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{23976} = \frac{8721}{35964}$	$\triangleright \frac{5862}{37149} = \frac{7816}{49532}$
$\triangleright \frac{5794}{18362} = \frac{8691}{27543}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{34182} = \frac{8694}{51273}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{37962} = \frac{8721}{56943}$	$\triangleright \frac{5862}{71493} = \frac{7816}{95324}$
$\triangleright \frac{5794}{21638} = \frac{8691}{32457}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{34218} = \frac{8694}{51327}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{39762} = \frac{8721}{59643}$	$\triangleright \frac{5864}{73192} = \frac{6597}{82341}$
$\triangleright \frac{5794}{21836} = \frac{8691}{32754}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{38142} = \frac{8694}{57213}$	$\triangleright \frac{5816}{23794} = \frac{8724}{35691}$	$\triangleright \frac{5871}{42693} = \frac{7416}{53928}$
$\triangleright \frac{5794}{23168} = \frac{8691}{34752}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{38214} = \frac{8694}{57321}$	$\triangleright \frac{5816}{23974} = \frac{8724}{35961}$	$\triangleright \frac{5871}{49362} = \frac{8961}{75342}$
$\triangleright \frac{5794}{23618} = \frac{8691}{35427}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{48132} = \frac{6417}{53289}$	$\triangleright \frac{5816}{37942} = \frac{8724}{56913}$	$\triangleright \frac{5874}{63921} = \frac{7654}{83291}$
$\triangleright \frac{5794}{23816} = \frac{8691}{35724}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{48231} = \frac{9436}{78521}$	$\triangleright \frac{5816}{39742} = \frac{8724}{59613}$	$\triangleright \frac{5892}{16734} = \frac{6874}{19523}$

- | | | | |
|---|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{5892}{41736} = \frac{8347}{59126}$ | ▶ $\frac{5962}{37418} = \frac{8943}{56127}$ | ▶ $\frac{5974}{36218} = \frac{8961}{54327}$ | ▶ $\frac{5978}{16342} = \frac{8967}{24513}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5913}{48276} = \frac{8541}{69732}$ | ▶ $\frac{5962}{37814} = \frac{8943}{56721}$ | ▶ $\frac{5974}{38162} = \frac{8961}{57243}$ | ▶ $\frac{5978}{21436} = \frac{8967}{32154}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5936}{41287} = \frac{6832}{47519}$ | ▶ $\frac{5962}{38174} = \frac{8943}{57261}$ | ▶ $\frac{5974}{38216} = \frac{8961}{57324}$ | ▶ $\frac{5978}{21634} = \frac{8967}{32451}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5941}{72683} = \frac{7312}{89456}$ | ▶ $\frac{5964}{13827} = \frac{7952}{18436}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{14238} = \frac{8964}{21357}$ | ▶ $\frac{5978}{23416} = \frac{8967}{35124}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5942}{16378} = \frac{8913}{24567}$ | ▶ $\frac{5964}{27138} = \frac{7952}{36184}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{14382} = \frac{8964}{21573}$ | ▶ $\frac{5978}{23614} = \frac{8967}{35421}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5942}{17638} = \frac{8913}{26457}$ | ▶ $\frac{5967}{13824} = \frac{7956}{18432}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{18234} = \frac{8964}{27351}$ | ▶ $\frac{5978}{34162} = \frac{8967}{51243}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5942}{17836} = \frac{8913}{26754}$ | ▶ $\frac{5967}{24138} = \frac{7956}{32184}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{18342} = \frac{8964}{27513}$ | ▶ $\frac{5978}{34216} = \frac{8967}{51324}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5942}{18376} = \frac{8913}{27564}$ | ▶ $\frac{5968}{23174} = \frac{8952}{34761}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{21438} = \frac{8964}{32157}$ | ▶ $\frac{5978}{36142} = \frac{8967}{54213}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5942}{31768} = \frac{8913}{47652}$ | ▶ $\frac{5968}{31742} = \frac{8952}{47613}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{21834} = \frac{8964}{32751}$ | ▶ $\frac{5978}{36214} = \frac{8967}{54321}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5942}{36178} = \frac{8913}{54267}$ | ▶ $\frac{5973}{28614} = \frac{7964}{38152}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{23418} = \frac{8964}{35127}$ | ▶ $\frac{5982}{14376} = \frac{8973}{21564}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5942}{37618} = \frac{8913}{56427}$ | ▶ $\frac{5974}{13862} = \frac{6283}{14579}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{23814} = \frac{8964}{35721}$ | ▶ $\frac{5982}{16374} = \frac{8973}{24561}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5942}{37816} = \frac{8913}{56724}$ | ▶ $\frac{5974}{16238} = \frac{8961}{24357}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{34182} = \frac{8964}{51273}$ | ▶ $\frac{5982}{17436} = \frac{8973}{26154}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5942}{38176} = \frac{8913}{57264}$ | ▶ $\frac{5974}{16382} = \frac{8961}{24573}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{34218} = \frac{8964}{51327}$ | ▶ $\frac{5982}{17634} = \frac{8973}{26451}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5943}{28617} = \frac{7924}{38156}$ | ▶ $\frac{5974}{18236} = \frac{8961}{27354}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{34281} = \frac{8632}{49517}$ | ▶ $\frac{5982}{34176} = \frac{8973}{51264}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5946}{18732} = \frac{6937}{21854}$ | ▶ $\frac{5974}{18362} = \frac{8961}{27543}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{38142} = \frac{8964}{57213}$ | ▶ $\frac{5982}{36174} = \frac{8973}{54261}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5946}{73218} = \frac{6937}{85421}$ | ▶ $\frac{5974}{21638} = \frac{8961}{32457}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{38214} = \frac{8964}{57321}$ | ▶ $\frac{5982}{37416} = \frac{8973}{56124}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5962}{14378} = \frac{8943}{21567}$ | ▶ $\frac{5974}{23168} = \frac{8961}{34752}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{43128} = \frac{6723}{48519}$ | ▶ $\frac{5982}{37614} = \frac{8973}{56421}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5962}{17438} = \frac{8943}{26157}$ | ▶ $\frac{5974}{23618} = \frac{8961}{35427}$ | ▶ $\frac{5976}{84312} = \frac{6723}{94851}$ | ▶ $\frac{5984}{63712} = \frac{6851}{72943}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5962}{17834} = \frac{8943}{26751}$ | ▶ $\frac{5974}{23816} = \frac{8961}{35724}$ | ▶ $\frac{5978}{14236} = \frac{8967}{21354}$ | ▶ $\frac{5986}{13724} = \frac{7954}{18236}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5962}{18374} = \frac{8943}{27561}$ | ▶ $\frac{5974}{31682} = \frac{8961}{47523}$ | ▶ $\frac{5978}{14362} = \frac{8967}{21543}$ | ▶ $\frac{5986}{47231} = \frac{7134}{56289}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{5962}{34178} = \frac{8943}{51267}$ | ▶ $\frac{5974}{36182} = \frac{8961}{54273}$ | ▶ $\frac{5978}{16234} = \frac{8967}{24351}$ | ▶ $\frac{6123}{75894} = \frac{6594}{81732}$ |

$\triangleright \frac{6129}{45873} = \frac{6583}{49271}$	$\triangleright \frac{6348}{72519} = \frac{8372}{95641}$	$\triangleright \frac{6519}{37842} = \frac{8159}{47362}$	$\triangleright \frac{6754}{38192} = \frac{7982}{45136}$
$\triangleright \frac{6139}{47852} = \frac{7893}{61524}$	$\triangleright \frac{6351}{74298} = \frac{7154}{83692}$	$\triangleright \frac{6527}{38491} = \frac{8132}{47956}$	$\triangleright \frac{6754}{39281} = \frac{9824}{57136}$
$\triangleright \frac{6148}{37259} = \frac{7192}{43586}$	$\triangleright \frac{6357}{12948} = \frac{7824}{15936}$	$\triangleright \frac{6528}{43197} = \frac{6912}{45738}$	$\triangleright \frac{6784}{53192} = \frac{7632}{59841}$
$\triangleright \frac{6149}{72358} = \frac{8127}{95634}$	$\triangleright \frac{6357}{42198} = \frac{7824}{51936}$	$\triangleright \frac{6534}{91278} = \frac{6831}{95427}$	$\triangleright \frac{6785}{13924} = \frac{7935}{16284}$
$\triangleright \frac{6179}{28453} = \frac{6847}{31529}$	$\triangleright \frac{6372}{15984} = \frac{9853}{24716}$	$\triangleright \frac{6572}{14893} = \frac{9548}{21637}$	$\triangleright \frac{6792}{35184} = \frac{7641}{39582}$
$\triangleright \frac{6194}{37582} = \frac{8639}{52417}$	$\triangleright \frac{6372}{85491} = \frac{7128}{95634}$	$\triangleright \frac{6573}{42819} = \frac{7512}{48936}$	$\triangleright \frac{6792}{53184} = \frac{7641}{59832}$
$\triangleright \frac{6198}{73452} = \frac{7231}{85694}$	$\triangleright \frac{6384}{12597} = \frac{7392}{14586}$	$\triangleright \frac{6573}{81942} = \frac{7512}{93648}$	$\triangleright \frac{6794}{13825} = \frac{8342}{16975}$
$\triangleright \frac{6198}{74532} = \frac{7231}{86954}$	$\triangleright \frac{6391}{48752} = \frac{6972}{53184}$	$\triangleright \frac{6579}{42183} = \frac{6851}{43927}$	$\triangleright \frac{6795}{43182} = \frac{9815}{62374}$
$\triangleright \frac{6213}{49875} = \frac{9483}{76125}$	$\triangleright \frac{6413}{58927} = \frac{8321}{76459}$	$\triangleright \frac{6583}{17429} = \frac{9761}{25843}$	$\triangleright \frac{6798}{45312} = \frac{7931}{52864}$
$\triangleright \frac{6237}{48195} = \frac{8217}{63495}$	$\triangleright \frac{6413}{78529} = \frac{7314}{89562}$	$\triangleright \frac{6583}{29174} = \frac{9761}{43258}$	$\triangleright \frac{6817}{94235} = \frac{7123}{98465}$
$\triangleright \frac{6237}{84159} = \frac{6853}{92471}$	$\triangleright \frac{6417}{53928} = \frac{7843}{65912}$	$\triangleright \frac{6593}{71482} = \frac{6821}{73954}$	$\triangleright \frac{6837}{29415} = \frac{8127}{34965}$
$\triangleright \frac{6254}{37819} = \frac{8162}{49357}$	$\triangleright \frac{6435}{21879} = \frac{8145}{27693}$	$\triangleright \frac{6594}{18732} = \frac{7693}{21854}$	$\triangleright \frac{6847}{35219} = \frac{7682}{39514}$
$\triangleright \frac{6258}{43197} = \frac{7152}{49368}$	$\triangleright \frac{6439}{52781} = \frac{7124}{58396}$	$\triangleright \frac{6594}{28731} = \frac{8526}{37149}$	$\triangleright \frac{6847}{52193} = \frac{8517}{64923}$
$\triangleright \frac{6258}{74319} = \frac{7152}{84936}$	$\triangleright \frac{6453}{12987} = \frac{7648}{15392}$	$\triangleright \frac{6594}{73218} = \frac{7693}{85421}$	$\triangleright \frac{6851}{24973} = \frac{8649}{31527}$
$\triangleright \frac{6281}{39754} = \frac{9136}{57824}$	$\triangleright \frac{6453}{79812} = \frac{6931}{85724}$	$\triangleright \frac{6721}{54938} = \frac{7238}{59164}$	$\triangleright \frac{6854}{12397} = \frac{9536}{17248}$
$\triangleright \frac{6293}{15748} = \frac{9541}{23876}$	$\triangleright \frac{6478}{35219} = \frac{7268}{39514}$	$\triangleright \frac{6732}{18594} = \frac{7854}{21693}$	$\triangleright \frac{6859}{27341} = \frac{7942}{31658}$
$\triangleright \frac{6298}{43751} = \frac{7614}{52893}$	$\triangleright \frac{6478}{52931} = \frac{8532}{69714}$	$\triangleright \frac{6732}{59418} = \frac{7854}{69321}$	$\triangleright \frac{6874}{12593} = \frac{7856}{14392}$
$\triangleright \frac{6327}{51948} = \frac{9234}{75816}$	$\triangleright \frac{6489}{27531} = \frac{8549}{36271}$	$\triangleright \frac{6741}{29853} = \frac{7812}{34596}$	$\triangleright \frac{6923}{84157} = \frac{7826}{95134}$
$\triangleright \frac{6345}{18927} = \frac{9635}{28741}$	$\triangleright \frac{6492}{17853} = \frac{7836}{21549}$	$\triangleright \frac{6749}{21835} = \frac{6783}{21945}$	$\triangleright \frac{6931}{27485} = \frac{8729}{34615}$
$\triangleright \frac{6345}{27189} = \frac{9635}{41287}$	$\triangleright \frac{6498}{15732} = \frac{9576}{23184}$	$\triangleright \frac{6751}{42398} = \frac{9263}{58174}$	$\triangleright \frac{6943}{51728} = \frac{9563}{71248}$
$\triangleright \frac{6345}{27918} = \frac{7915}{34826}$	$\triangleright \frac{6517}{32984} = \frac{7546}{38192}$	$\triangleright \frac{6754}{29183} = \frac{8596}{37142}$	$\triangleright \frac{6948}{12573} = \frac{8492}{15367}$

$\triangleright \frac{6948}{17352} = \frac{9457}{23618}$	$\triangleright \frac{7245}{61893} = \frac{9765}{83421}$	$\triangleright \frac{7519}{28634} = \frac{9417}{35862}$	$\triangleright \frac{7942}{36518} = \frac{9823}{45167}$
$\triangleright \frac{6972}{41583} = \frac{7812}{46593}$	$\triangleright \frac{7254}{39861} = \frac{9672}{53148}$	$\triangleright \frac{7543}{18962} = \frac{8734}{21956}$	$\triangleright \frac{7942}{61358} = \frac{9386}{72514}$
$\triangleright \frac{6972}{83415} = \frac{7812}{93465}$	$\triangleright \frac{7294}{16835} = \frac{9378}{21645}$	$\triangleright \frac{7562}{18943} = \frac{8756}{21934}$	$\triangleright \frac{7953}{64812} = \frac{9158}{74632}$
$\triangleright \frac{6973}{52481} = \frac{9614}{72358}$	$\triangleright \frac{7294}{35168} = \frac{9378}{45216}$	$\triangleright \frac{7564}{13298} = \frac{8742}{15369}$	$\triangleright \frac{7964}{21358} = \frac{9614}{25783}$
$\triangleright \frac{6984}{23571} = \frac{8136}{27459}$	$\triangleright \frac{7316}{42598} = \frac{9176}{53428}$	$\triangleright \frac{7564}{38192} = \frac{8357}{42196}$	$\triangleright \frac{7986}{45312} = \frac{9317}{52864}$
$\triangleright \frac{6987}{23154} = \frac{7398}{24516}$	$\triangleright \frac{7326}{18594} = \frac{8547}{21693}$	$\triangleright \frac{7581}{62349} = \frac{7942}{65318}$	$\triangleright \frac{8154}{67392} = \frac{9513}{78624}$
$\triangleright \frac{7123}{48569} = \frac{7961}{54283}$	$\triangleright \frac{7326}{59418} = \frac{8547}{69321}$	$\triangleright \frac{7584}{69312} = \frac{9164}{83752}$	$\triangleright \frac{8154}{73926} = \frac{9513}{86247}$
$\triangleright \frac{7128}{53946} = \frac{8712}{65934}$	$\triangleright \frac{7329}{68145} = \frac{9423}{87615}$	$\triangleright \frac{7632}{58194} = \frac{9864}{75213}$	$\triangleright \frac{8174}{69235} = \frac{9246}{78315}$
$\triangleright \frac{7146}{53928} = \frac{8734}{65912}$	$\triangleright \frac{7359}{42816} = \frac{9834}{57216}$	$\triangleright \frac{7659}{48231} = \frac{9324}{58716}$	$\triangleright \frac{8192}{47536} = \frac{9216}{53478}$
$\triangleright \frac{7149}{35862} = \frac{9532}{47816}$	$\triangleright \frac{7364}{18592} = \frac{9731}{24568}$	$\triangleright \frac{7695}{24381} = \frac{8645}{27391}$	$\triangleright \frac{8214}{35796} = \frac{9583}{41762}$
$\triangleright \frac{7149}{58623} = \frac{9532}{78164}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{18564} = \frac{9768}{24531}$	$\triangleright \frac{7695}{81243} = \frac{8645}{91273}$	$\triangleright \frac{8214}{39576} = \frac{9583}{46172}$
$\triangleright \frac{7152}{34968} = \frac{9238}{45167}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{41856} = \frac{9471}{53628}$	$\triangleright \frac{7826}{31954} = \frac{8729}{35641}$	$\triangleright \frac{8235}{69174} = \frac{9315}{78246}$
$\triangleright \frac{7168}{29435} = \frac{9216}{37845}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{68154} = \frac{8624}{79513}$	$\triangleright \frac{7831}{69524} = \frac{8159}{72436}$	$\triangleright \frac{8316}{74952} = \frac{9471}{85362}$
$\triangleright \frac{7168}{35294} = \frac{9216}{45378}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{81546} = \frac{8624}{95137}$	$\triangleright \frac{7839}{52461} = \frac{9243}{61857}$	$\triangleright \frac{8371}{69542} = \frac{9132}{75864}$
$\triangleright \frac{7192}{65348} = \frac{8294}{75361}$	$\triangleright \frac{7436}{29185} = \frac{9724}{38165}$	$\triangleright \frac{7843}{25691} = \frac{9548}{31276}$	$\triangleright \frac{8374}{95612} = \frac{8532}{97416}$
$\triangleright \frac{7215}{84693} = \frac{7345}{86219}$	$\triangleright \frac{7439}{26815} = \frac{8729}{31465}$	$\triangleright \frac{7854}{12936} = \frac{9367}{15428}$	$\triangleright \frac{8379}{12654} = \frac{8967}{13542}$
$\triangleright \frac{7216}{35948} = \frac{9512}{47386}$	$\triangleright \frac{7452}{69138} = \frac{9234}{85671}$	$\triangleright \frac{7869}{51342} = \frac{8723}{56914}$	$\triangleright \frac{8476}{13529} = \frac{9672}{15438}$
$\triangleright \frac{7216}{35984} = \frac{8569}{42731}$	$\triangleright \frac{7456}{28193} = \frac{9472}{35816}$	$\triangleright \frac{7869}{51423} = \frac{9374}{61258}$	$\triangleright \frac{8493}{61275} = \frac{8791}{63425}$
$\triangleright \frac{7238}{65941} = \frac{8162}{74359}$	$\triangleright \frac{7482}{13659} = \frac{9632}{17584}$	$\triangleright \frac{7923}{68514} = \frac{9452}{81736}$	$\triangleright \frac{8493}{72561} = \frac{9536}{81472}$
$\triangleright \frac{7239}{54861} = \frac{9652}{73148}$	$\triangleright \frac{7514}{28639} = \frac{9826}{37451}$	$\triangleright \frac{7935}{68241} = \frac{8415}{72369}$	$\triangleright \frac{8512}{37496} = \frac{9576}{42183}$
$\triangleright \frac{7241}{59683} = \frac{8912}{73456}$	$\triangleright \frac{7518}{64239} = \frac{8592}{73416}$	$\triangleright \frac{7936}{48512} = \frac{9238}{56471}$	$\triangleright \frac{8512}{46739} = \frac{9728}{53416}$

$\triangleright \frac{8512}{47369} = \frac{9728}{54136}$	$\triangleright \frac{512}{367984} = \frac{576}{413982}$	$\triangleright \frac{528}{413976} = \frac{682}{534719}$	$\triangleright \frac{539}{182476} = \frac{572}{193648}$
$\triangleright \frac{8514}{93267} = \frac{8712}{95436}$	$\triangleright \frac{512}{374968} = \frac{576}{421839}$	$\triangleright \frac{528}{419376} = \frac{946}{751382}$	$\triangleright \frac{539}{216748} = \frac{924}{371568}$
$\triangleright \frac{8519}{47362} = \frac{9736}{54128}$	$\triangleright \frac{512}{837496} = \frac{576}{942183}$	$\triangleright \frac{529}{476813} = \frac{759}{684123}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{163798} = \frac{813}{245697}$
$\triangleright \frac{8532}{79164} = \frac{9243}{85761}$	$\triangleright \frac{513}{724869} = \frac{657}{928341}$	$\triangleright \frac{529}{681743} = \frac{736}{948512}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{163978} = \frac{813}{245967}$
$\triangleright \frac{8561}{27349} = \frac{9784}{31256}$	$\triangleright \frac{513}{728649} = \frac{684}{971532}$	$\triangleright \frac{531}{426987} = \frac{649}{521873}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{176398} = \frac{813}{264597}$
$\triangleright \frac{8561}{49273} = \frac{9784}{56312}$	$\triangleright \frac{513}{729864} = \frac{684}{973152}$	$\triangleright \frac{531}{842697} = \frac{549}{871263}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{178396} = \frac{813}{267594}$
$\triangleright \frac{8619}{25347} = \frac{8957}{26341}$	$\triangleright \frac{516}{247938} = \frac{758}{364219}$	$\triangleright \frac{531}{872964} = \frac{567}{932148}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{179638} = \frac{813}{269457}$
$\triangleright \frac{8631}{74529} = \frac{9453}{81627}$	$\triangleright \frac{516}{427893} = \frac{692}{573841}$	$\triangleright \frac{532}{168974} = \frac{798}{253461}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{179836} = \frac{813}{269754}$
$\triangleright \frac{8653}{21794} = \frac{9671}{24358}$	$\triangleright \frac{516}{438729} = \frac{924}{785631}$	$\triangleright \frac{532}{176894} = \frac{798}{265341}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{183796} = \frac{813}{275694}$
$\triangleright \frac{8673}{94521} = \frac{8732}{95164}$	$\triangleright \frac{517}{238964} = \frac{893}{412756}$	$\triangleright \frac{532}{179648} = \frac{874}{295136}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{183976} = \frac{813}{275964}$
$\triangleright \frac{8732}{15694} = \frac{9324}{16758}$	$\triangleright \frac{517}{246938} = \frac{594}{283716}$	$\triangleright \frac{532}{418796} = \frac{627}{493581}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{196378} = \frac{813}{294567}$
$\triangleright \frac{8791}{54236} = \frac{9263}{57148}$	$\triangleright \frac{517}{846329} = \frac{531}{869247}$	$\triangleright \frac{532}{468179} = \frac{672}{591384}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{197638} = \frac{813}{296457}$
$\triangleright \frac{8946}{51723} = \frac{9372}{54186}$	$\triangleright \frac{518}{276493} = \frac{962}{513487}$	$\triangleright \frac{532}{497861} = \frac{912}{853476}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{197836} = \frac{813}{296754}$
$\triangleright \frac{9163}{54782} = \frac{9724}{58136}$	$\triangleright \frac{518}{294637} = \frac{962}{547183}$	$\triangleright \frac{532}{687914} = \frac{728}{941356}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{198376} = \frac{813}{297564}$
$\triangleright \frac{9184}{32576} = \frac{9758}{34612}$	$\triangleright \frac{518}{327964} = \frac{592}{374816}$	$\triangleright \frac{532}{716984} = \frac{539}{726418}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{317968} = \frac{813}{476952}$
$\triangleright \frac{9184}{57632} = \frac{9758}{61234}$	$\triangleright \frac{518}{642397} = \frac{592}{734168}$	$\triangleright \frac{532}{948176} = \frac{546}{973128}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{319768} = \frac{813}{479652}$
$\triangleright \frac{9384}{56712} = \frac{9637}{58241}$	$\triangleright \frac{518}{764239} = \frac{592}{873416}$	$\triangleright \frac{534}{167892} = \frac{623}{195874}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{361798} = \frac{813}{542697}$
$\triangleright \frac{9456}{71328} = \frac{9653}{72814}$	$\triangleright \frac{521}{679384} = \frac{754}{983216}$	$\triangleright \frac{536}{428197} = \frac{928}{741356}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{361978} = \frac{813}{542967}$
$\triangleright \frac{9472}{81536} = \frac{9546}{82173}$	$\triangleright \frac{524}{179863} = \frac{956}{328147}$	$\triangleright \frac{536}{492718} = \frac{932}{856741}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{376198} = \frac{813}{564297}$
$\triangleright \frac{9618}{52374} = \frac{9847}{53621}$	$\triangleright \frac{527}{189346} = \frac{961}{345278}$	$\triangleright \frac{537}{249168} = \frac{678}{314592}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{378196} = \frac{813}{567294}$
$\triangleright \frac{9718}{45236} = \frac{9831}{45762}$	$\triangleright \frac{528}{147936} = \frac{957}{268134}$	$\triangleright \frac{538}{674921} = \frac{652}{817934}$	$\triangleright \frac{542}{379618} = \frac{813}{569427}$

$\triangleright \frac{542}{379816} = \frac{813}{569724}$	$\triangleright \frac{549}{718623} = \frac{732}{958164}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{197438} = \frac{843}{296157}$	$\triangleright \frac{564}{792318} = \frac{658}{924371}$
$\triangleright \frac{542}{381796} = \frac{813}{572694}$	$\triangleright \frac{549}{723861} = \frac{732}{965148}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{197834} = \frac{843}{296751}$	$\triangleright \frac{564}{871239} = \frac{612}{945387}$
$\triangleright \frac{542}{381976} = \frac{813}{572964}$	$\triangleright \frac{549}{836127} = \frac{621}{945783}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{198374} = \frac{843}{297561}$	$\triangleright \frac{567}{138294} = \frac{756}{184392}$
$\triangleright \frac{542}{396178} = \frac{813}{594267}$	$\triangleright \frac{561}{274839} = \frac{869}{425731}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{341798} = \frac{843}{512697}$	$\triangleright \frac{567}{149283} = \frac{693}{182457}$
$\triangleright \frac{542}{397618} = \frac{813}{596427}$	$\triangleright \frac{561}{284937} = \frac{627}{318459}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{341978} = \frac{843}{512967}$	$\triangleright \frac{567}{294138} = \frac{756}{392184}$
$\triangleright \frac{542}{397816} = \frac{813}{596724}$	$\triangleright \frac{561}{384972} = \frac{748}{513296}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{374198} = \frac{843}{561297}$	$\triangleright \frac{567}{381429} = \frac{637}{428519}$
$\triangleright \frac{542}{398176} = \frac{813}{597264}$	$\triangleright \frac{561}{398472} = \frac{748}{531296}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{378194} = \frac{843}{567291}$	$\triangleright \frac{567}{489321} = \frac{967}{834521}$
$\triangleright \frac{543}{286197} = \frac{724}{381596}$	$\triangleright \frac{561}{493782} = \frac{649}{571238}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{379418} = \frac{843}{569127}$	$\triangleright \frac{567}{839241} = \frac{637}{942851}$
$\triangleright \frac{543}{298617} = \frac{724}{398156}$	$\triangleright \frac{561}{723849} = \frac{748}{965132}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{379814} = \frac{843}{569721}$	$\triangleright \frac{568}{213497} = \frac{856}{321749}$
$\triangleright \frac{546}{137982} = \frac{567}{143289}$	$\triangleright \frac{561}{723984} = \frac{748}{965312}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{381794} = \frac{843}{572691}$	$\triangleright \frac{568}{231794} = \frac{852}{347691}$
$\triangleright \frac{546}{183729} = \frac{576}{193824}$	$\triangleright \frac{561}{827934} = \frac{638}{941572}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{381974} = \frac{843}{572961}$	$\triangleright \frac{568}{231974} = \frac{852}{347961}$
$\triangleright \frac{546}{192738} = \frac{837}{295461}$	$\triangleright \frac{561}{874293} = \frac{572}{891436}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{394178} = \frac{843}{591267}$	$\triangleright \frac{568}{293174} = \frac{852}{439761}$
$\triangleright \frac{546}{312897} = \frac{896}{513472}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{143798} = \frac{843}{215697}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{397418} = \frac{843}{596127}$	$\triangleright \frac{568}{317942} = \frac{852}{476913}$
$\triangleright \frac{546}{891723} = \frac{572}{934186}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{143978} = \frac{843}{215967}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{397814} = \frac{843}{596721}$	$\triangleright \frac{568}{319742} = \frac{852}{479613}$
$\triangleright \frac{546}{897312} = \frac{567}{931824}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{174398} = \frac{843}{261597}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{398174} = \frac{843}{597261}$	$\triangleright \frac{568}{329174} = \frac{852}{493761}$
$\triangleright \frac{549}{126378} = \frac{793}{182546}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{178394} = \frac{843}{267591}$	$\triangleright \frac{564}{138297} = \frac{752}{184396}$	$\triangleright \frac{568}{497213} = \frac{856}{749321}$
$\triangleright \frac{549}{127836} = \frac{793}{184652}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{179438} = \frac{843}{269157}$	$\triangleright \frac{564}{139872} = \frac{639}{158472}$	$\triangleright \frac{572}{193864} = \frac{637}{215894}$
$\triangleright \frac{549}{361278} = \frac{793}{521846}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{179834} = \frac{843}{269751}$	$\triangleright \frac{564}{297138} = \frac{752}{396184}$	$\triangleright \frac{572}{468391} = \frac{728}{596134}$
$\triangleright \frac{549}{371862} = \frac{732}{495816}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{183794} = \frac{843}{275691}$	$\triangleright \frac{564}{318792} = \frac{658}{371924}$	$\triangleright \frac{572}{483691} = \frac{748}{632519}$
$\triangleright \frac{549}{378126} = \frac{793}{546182}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{183974} = \frac{843}{275961}$	$\triangleright \frac{564}{319278} = \frac{658}{372491}$	$\triangleright \frac{573}{286194} = \frac{764}{381592}$
$\triangleright \frac{549}{386172} = \frac{732}{514896}$	$\triangleright \frac{562}{194378} = \frac{843}{291567}$	$\triangleright \frac{564}{783192} = \frac{658}{913724}$	$\triangleright \frac{573}{298614} = \frac{764}{398152}$

$\triangleright \frac{573}{692184} = \frac{756}{913248}$	$\triangleright \frac{574}{329168} = \frac{861}{493752}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{234198} = \frac{864}{351297}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{194362} = \frac{867}{291543}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{162398} = \frac{861}{243597}$	$\triangleright \frac{574}{361982} = \frac{861}{542973}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{238194} = \frac{864}{357291}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{196234} = \frac{867}{294351}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{163982} = \frac{861}{245973}$	$\triangleright \frac{574}{362198} = \frac{861}{543297}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{239418} = \frac{864}{359127}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{196342} = \frac{867}{294513}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{182396} = \frac{861}{273594}$	$\triangleright \frac{574}{381962} = \frac{861}{572943}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{239814} = \frac{864}{359721}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{214396} = \frac{867}{321594}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{183962} = \frac{861}{275943}$	$\triangleright \frac{574}{382196} = \frac{861}{573294}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{341982} = \frac{864}{512973}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{216394} = \frac{867}{324591}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{192836} = \frac{697}{234158}$	$\triangleright \frac{574}{396182} = \frac{861}{594273}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{342198} = \frac{864}{513297}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{219436} = \frac{867}{329154}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{196238} = \frac{861}{294357}$	$\triangleright \frac{574}{396218} = \frac{861}{594327}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{349182} = \frac{896}{543172}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{219634} = \frac{867}{329451}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{196382} = \frac{861}{294573}$	$\triangleright \frac{574}{398162} = \frac{861}{597243}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{381942} = \frac{864}{572913}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{234196} = \frac{867}{351294}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{198236} = \frac{861}{297354}$	$\triangleright \frac{574}{398216} = \frac{861}{597324}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{382194} = \frac{864}{573291}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{236194} = \frac{867}{354291}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{198362} = \frac{861}{297543}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{142398} = \frac{864}{213597}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{394182} = \frac{864}{591273}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{239416} = \frac{867}{359124}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{218396} = \frac{861}{327594}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{143982} = \frac{864}{215973}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{394218} = \frac{864}{591327}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{239614} = \frac{867}{359421}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{219638} = \frac{861}{329457}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{182394} = \frac{864}{273591}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{398142} = \frac{864}{597213}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{341962} = \frac{867}{512943}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{219836} = \frac{861}{329754}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{183942} = \frac{864}{275913}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{398214} = \frac{864}{597321}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{342196} = \frac{867}{513294}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{231968} = \frac{861}{347952}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{194238} = \frac{864}{291357}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{482913} = \frac{832}{697541}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{361942} = \frac{867}{542913}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{236198} = \frac{861}{354297}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{194382} = \frac{864}{291573}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{489312} = \frac{758}{643921}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{362194} = \frac{867}{543291}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{238196} = \frac{861}{357294}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{198234} = \frac{864}{297351}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{918432} = \frac{612}{975834}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{394162} = \frac{867}{591243}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{239618} = \frac{861}{359427}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{198342} = \frac{864}{297513}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{142396} = \frac{867}{213594}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{394216} = \frac{867}{591324}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{239816} = \frac{861}{359724}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{214398} = \frac{864}{321597}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{143962} = \frac{867}{215943}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{396142} = \frac{867}{594213}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{293168} = \frac{861}{439752}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{218394} = \frac{864}{327591}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{162394} = \frac{867}{243591}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{396214} = \frac{867}{594321}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{316928} = \frac{861}{475392}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{219438} = \frac{864}{329157}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{163942} = \frac{867}{245913}$	$\triangleright \frac{581}{297346} = \frac{913}{467258}$
$\triangleright \frac{574}{319682} = \frac{861}{479523}$	$\triangleright \frac{576}{219834} = \frac{864}{329751}$	$\triangleright \frac{578}{194236} = \frac{867}{291354}$	$\triangleright \frac{581}{379642} = \frac{798}{521436}$

$$\triangleright \frac{582}{143796} = \frac{873}{215694}$$

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$$\triangleright \frac{582}{374196} = \frac{873}{561294}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{582}{376194} = \frac{873}{564291}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{582}{379416} = \frac{873}{569124}$$

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$$\triangleright \frac{582}{397614} = \frac{873}{596421}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{582}{436791} = \frac{834}{625917}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{589}{174623} = \frac{893}{264751}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{591}{362874} = \frac{618}{379452}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{138267} = \frac{792}{184356}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{162378} = \frac{891}{243567}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{163782} = \frac{891}{245673}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{176238} = \frac{891}{264357}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{176382} = \frac{891}{264573}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{178236} = \frac{891}{267354}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{178362} = \frac{891}{267543}$$

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$$\triangleright \frac{594}{183762} = \frac{891}{275643}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{186732} = \frac{693}{217854}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{187326} = \frac{693}{218547}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{216378} = \frac{891}{324567}$$

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$$\triangleright \frac{594}{217836} = \frac{891}{326754}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{218376} = \frac{891}{327564}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{231768} = \frac{891}{347652}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{236178} = \frac{891}{354267}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{237618} = \frac{891}{356427}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{237816} = \frac{891}{356724}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{238176} = \frac{891}{357264}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{267138} = \frac{792}{356184}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{286173} = \frac{792}{381564}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{317682} = \frac{891}{476523}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{328617} = \frac{792}{438156}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{361782} = \frac{891}{542673}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{362178} = \frac{891}{543267}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{376182} = \frac{891}{564273}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{376218} = \frac{891}{564327}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{378162} = \frac{891}{567243}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{378216} = \frac{891}{567324}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{381762} = \frac{891}{572643}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{382176} = \frac{891}{573264}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{618732} = \frac{693}{721854}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{673218} = \frac{693}{785421}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{732186} = \frac{693}{854217}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{594}{732618} = \frac{693}{854721}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{142378} = \frac{894}{213567}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{143782} = \frac{894}{215673}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{174238} = \frac{894}{261357}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{174382} = \frac{894}{261573}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{178234} = \frac{894}{267351}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{178342} = \frac{894}{267513}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{182374} = \frac{894}{273561}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{183742} = \frac{894}{275613}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{214378} = \frac{894}{321567}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{217438} = \frac{894}{326157}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{217834} = \frac{894}{326751}$$

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$$\triangleright \frac{596}{234178} = \frac{894}{351267}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{237418} = \frac{894}{356127}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{237814} = \frac{894}{356721}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{238174} = \frac{894}{357261}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{341782} = \frac{894}{512673}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{342178} = \frac{894}{513267}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{374182} = \frac{894}{561273}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{374218} = \frac{894}{561327}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{596}{378142} = \frac{894}{567213}$$

$\triangleright \frac{596}{378214} = \frac{894}{567321}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{217634} = \frac{897}{326451}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{375498} = \frac{918}{563247}$	$\triangleright \frac{628}{357914} = \frac{942}{536871}$
$\triangleright \frac{596}{381742} = \frac{894}{572613}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{234176} = \frac{897}{351264}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{435897} = \frac{948}{675213}$	$\triangleright \frac{628}{359174} = \frac{942}{538761}$
$\triangleright \frac{596}{382174} = \frac{894}{573261}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{236174} = \frac{897}{354261}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{538794} = \frac{714}{628593}$	$\triangleright \frac{628}{375914} = \frac{942}{563871}$
$\triangleright \frac{596}{384271} = \frac{612}{394587}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{237416} = \frac{897}{356124}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{539874} = \frac{714}{629853}$	$\triangleright \frac{628}{379154} = \frac{942}{568731}$
$\triangleright \frac{596}{814732} = \frac{674}{921358}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{237614} = \frac{897}{356421}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{587394} = \frac{714}{685293}$	$\triangleright \frac{628}{391574} = \frac{942}{587361}$
$\triangleright \frac{597}{138264} = \frac{796}{184352}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{341762} = \frac{897}{512643}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{587934} = \frac{714}{685923}$	$\triangleright \frac{628}{391754} = \frac{942}{587631}$
$\triangleright \frac{597}{264138} = \frac{796}{352184}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{342176} = \frac{897}{513264}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{593874} = \frac{714}{692853}$	$\triangleright \frac{629}{534871} = \frac{851}{723649}$
$\triangleright \frac{597}{286143} = \frac{796}{381524}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{361742} = \frac{897}{542613}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{598734} = \frac{714}{698523}$	$\triangleright \frac{632}{745918} = \frac{784}{925316}$
$\triangleright \frac{597}{328614} = \frac{796}{438152}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{362174} = \frac{897}{543261}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{753984} = \frac{748}{921536}$	$\triangleright \frac{634}{287519} = \frac{826}{374591}$
$\triangleright \frac{598}{142376} = \frac{897}{213564}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{367241} = \frac{936}{574812}$	$\triangleright \frac{614}{283975} = \frac{846}{391275}$	$\triangleright \frac{634}{572819} = \frac{754}{681239}$
$\triangleright \frac{598}{143762} = \frac{897}{215643}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{371462} = \frac{621}{385749}$	$\triangleright \frac{615}{238497} = \frac{845}{327691}$	$\triangleright \frac{637}{129584} = \frac{749}{152368}$
$\triangleright \frac{598}{162374} = \frac{897}{243561}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{372416} = \frac{923}{574816}$	$\triangleright \frac{618}{495327} = \frac{648}{519372}$	$\triangleright \frac{638}{125947} = \frac{792}{156348}$
$\triangleright \frac{598}{163742} = \frac{897}{245613}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{374162} = \frac{897}{561243}$	$\triangleright \frac{618}{594732} = \frac{721}{693854}$	$\triangleright \frac{638}{154792} = \frac{754}{182936}$
$\triangleright \frac{598}{174236} = \frac{897}{261354}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{374216} = \frac{897}{561324}$	$\triangleright \frac{618}{732594} = \frac{721}{854693}$	$\triangleright \frac{638}{179452} = \frac{759}{213486}$
$\triangleright \frac{598}{174362} = \frac{897}{261543}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{376214} = \frac{897}{564321}$	$\triangleright \frac{621}{753894} = \frac{761}{923854}$	$\triangleright \frac{638}{452197} = \frac{792}{561348}$
$\triangleright \frac{598}{176234} = \frac{897}{264351}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{436172} = \frac{871}{635294}$	$\triangleright \frac{623}{415897} = \frac{679}{453281}$	$\triangleright \frac{638}{459712} = \frac{783}{564192}$
$\triangleright \frac{598}{176342} = \frac{897}{264513}$	$\triangleright \frac{598}{724316} = \frac{754}{913268}$	$\triangleright \frac{624}{315978} = \frac{896}{453712}$	$\triangleright \frac{638}{547921} = \frac{812}{697354}$
$\triangleright \frac{598}{213647} = \frac{754}{269381}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{349578} = \frac{918}{524367}$	$\triangleright \frac{624}{389571} = \frac{672}{419538}$	$\triangleright \frac{638}{792154} = \frac{754}{936182}$
$\triangleright \frac{598}{214376} = \frac{897}{321564}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{354978} = \frac{918}{532467}$	$\triangleright \frac{627}{134589} = \frac{836}{179452}$	$\triangleright \frac{639}{145782} = \frac{852}{194376}$
$\triangleright \frac{598}{216374} = \frac{897}{324561}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{357498} = \frac{918}{536247}$	$\triangleright \frac{627}{481593} = \frac{968}{743512}$	$\triangleright \frac{639}{182754} = \frac{963}{275418}$
$\triangleright \frac{598}{217436} = \frac{897}{326154}$	$\triangleright \frac{612}{374958} = \frac{918}{562437}$	$\triangleright \frac{627}{853941} = \frac{684}{931572}$	$\triangleright \frac{639}{248571} = \frac{912}{354768}$

$$\triangleright \frac{639}{428175} = \frac{923}{618475}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{639}{512478} = \frac{792}{635184}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{639}{527814} = \frac{693}{572418}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{639}{712485} = \frac{823}{917645}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{642}{597381} = \frac{942}{876531}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{642}{715938} = \frac{749}{835261}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{642}{739158} = \frac{749}{862351}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{645}{712983} = \frac{735}{812469}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{645}{798123} = \frac{745}{921863}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{648}{195372} = \frac{954}{287631}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{648}{357291} = \frac{976}{538142}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{648}{572913} = \frac{936}{827541}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{648}{713529} = \frac{864}{951372}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{648}{739152} = \frac{729}{831546}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{648}{751392} = \frac{729}{845316}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{649}{315827} = \frac{792}{385416}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{649}{328571} = \frac{759}{384261}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{657}{139284} = \frac{846}{179352}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{657}{419823} = \frac{729}{465831}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{658}{147392} = \frac{957}{214368}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{658}{723941} = \frac{742}{816359}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{671}{839542} = \frac{732}{915864}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{672}{195384} = \frac{948}{275631}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{672}{531984} = \frac{938}{742561}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{672}{819534} = \frac{784}{956123}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{675}{428139} = \frac{975}{618423}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{678}{132549} = \frac{792}{154836}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{678}{215943} = \frac{798}{254163}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{679}{358124} = \frac{917}{483652}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{679}{421853} = \frac{861}{534927}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{682}{195734} = \frac{754}{216398}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{684}{193572} = \frac{756}{213948}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{684}{319257} = \frac{972}{453681}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{684}{329517} = \frac{792}{381546}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{684}{357219} = \frac{756}{394821}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{684}{527193} = \frac{732}{564189}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{684}{573192} = \frac{972}{814536}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{684}{713925} = \frac{876}{914325}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{685}{132479} = \frac{945}{182763}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{685}{372914} = \frac{715}{389246}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{689}{125437} = \frac{954}{173682}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{689}{145273} = \frac{728}{153496}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{689}{415732} = \frac{897}{541236}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{693}{125748} = \frac{847}{153692}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{693}{125874} = \frac{792}{143856}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{693}{427581} = \frac{837}{516429}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{693}{481257} = \frac{781}{542369}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{693}{571428} = \frac{819}{675324}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{693}{814275} = \frac{831}{976425}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{693}{845271} = \frac{748}{912356}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{695}{832471} = \frac{745}{892361}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{697}{152438} = \frac{748}{163592}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{697}{382415} = \frac{861}{472395}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{697}{431528} = \frac{738}{456912}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{712}{368549} = \frac{872}{451369}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{712}{459863} = \frac{952}{614873}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{714}{398265} = \frac{782}{436195}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{715}{324896} = \frac{795}{361248}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{715}{628394} = \frac{935}{821746}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{718}{354692} = \frac{748}{369512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{718}{493625} = \frac{914}{628375}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{723}{586149} = \frac{964}{781532}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{726}{418539} = \frac{786}{453129}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{726}{581394} = \frac{781}{625439}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{726}{819534} = \frac{847}{956123}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{728}{169435} = \frac{936}{217845}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{728}{351694} = \frac{936}{452178}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{729}{368145} = \frac{927}{468135}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{729}{461538} = \frac{972}{615384}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{148596} = \frac{864}{175392}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{185946} = \frac{854}{216937}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{186594} = \frac{854}{217693}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{594186} = \frac{854}{693217}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{594618} = \frac{854}{693721}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{618594} = \frac{854}{721693}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{732}{659418} = \frac{854}{769321}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{735}{168294} = \frac{945}{216378}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{735}{169428} = \frac{945}{217836}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{735}{281694} = \frac{945}{362178}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{735}{294168} = \frac{945}{378216}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{735}{681429} = \frac{945}{876123}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{736}{154928} = \frac{852}{179346}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{736}{591284} = \frac{952}{764813}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{738}{125649} = \frac{984}{167532}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{738}{215496} = \frac{873}{254916}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{738}{241695} = \frac{798}{261345}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{738}{461529} = \frac{984}{615372}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{738}{529146} = \frac{873}{625941}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{738}{564912} = \frac{984}{753216}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{738}{629145} = \frac{894}{762135}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{748}{123596} = \frac{867}{143259}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{748}{329516} = \frac{816}{359472}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{748}{359216} = \frac{986}{473512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{748}{532961} = \frac{952}{678314}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{748}{615329} = \frac{952}{783146}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{749}{365218} = \frac{856}{417392}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{752}{139684} = \frac{952}{176834}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{752}{193648} = \frac{987}{254163}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{752}{481936} = \frac{987}{632541}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{752}{813946} = \frac{864}{935172}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{7526}{14893} = \frac{9372}{18546}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{754}{263198} = \frac{841}{293567}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{754}{319826} = \frac{841}{356729}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{754}{391268} = \frac{936}{485712}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{756}{132489} = \frac{768}{134592}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{756}{132894} = \frac{952}{167348}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{756}{398412} = \frac{921}{485367}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{759}{124683} = \frac{869}{142753}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{759}{312846} = \frac{891}{367254}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{759}{368214} = \frac{897}{435162}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{759}{386124} = \frac{891}{453276}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{759}{413862} = \frac{792}{431856}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{759}{436821} = \frac{897}{516243}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{759}{463128} = \frac{891}{543672}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{765}{231948} = \frac{895}{271364}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{768}{493152} = \frac{816}{523974}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{782}{136459} = \frac{856}{149372}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{782}{395416} = \frac{952}{481376}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{782}{593164} = \frac{943}{715286}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{782}{643195} = \frac{934}{768215}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{783}{612549} = \frac{841}{657923}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{783}{694521} = \frac{819}{726453}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{791}{486352} = \frac{917}{563824}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{792}{154638} = \frac{936}{182754}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{792}{318564} = \frac{924}{371658}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{792}{564318} = \frac{924}{658371}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{792}{615384} = \frac{963}{748251}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{792}{638154} = \frac{936}{754182}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{792}{648153} = \frac{912}{746358}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{793}{452681} = \frac{819}{467523}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{793}{865124} = \frac{854}{931672}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{798}{142653} = \frac{874}{156239}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{798}{365142} = \frac{987}{451623}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{798}{431256} = \frac{836}{451792}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{798}{453126} = \frac{931}{528647}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{798}{536124} = \frac{931}{625478}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{798}{541632} = \frac{874}{593216}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{798}{645312} = \frac{931}{752864}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{812}{675439} = \frac{896}{745312}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{816}{497352} = \frac{924}{563178}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{816}{524739} = \frac{912}{586473}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{817}{952364} = \frac{836}{974512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{819}{365274} = \frac{981}{437526}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{819}{426573} = \frac{936}{487512}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{819}{657342} = \frac{936}{751248}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{826}{157943} = \frac{854}{163297}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{826}{453179} = \frac{938}{514627}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{831}{245976} = \frac{941}{278536}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{831}{495276} = \frac{897}{534612}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{834}{156792} = \frac{847}{159236}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{836}{512974} = \frac{874}{536291}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{847}{635129} = \frac{952}{713864}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{849}{567132} = \frac{984}{657312}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{852}{471369} = \frac{936}{517842}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{856}{134927} = \frac{976}{153842}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{861}{439725} = \frac{917}{468325}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{861}{473529} = \frac{943}{518627}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{864}{735912} = \frac{956}{814273}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{864}{739152} = \frac{972}{831546}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{864}{751392} = \frac{972}{845316}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{867}{152439} = \frac{952}{167384}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{869}{451327} = \frac{891}{462753}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{871}{692354} = \frac{938}{745612}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{879}{136245} = \frac{927}{143685}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{891}{753624} = \frac{924}{781536}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{893}{265174} = \frac{931}{276458}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{893}{715246} = \frac{931}{745682}$$

$$\triangleright \frac{893}{754162} = \frac{931}{786254}$$

$\triangleright \frac{938}{142576} = \frac{976}{148352}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{1647893} = \frac{68}{2154937}$	$\triangleright \frac{53}{1782496} = \frac{83}{2791456}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1798236} = \frac{81}{2697354}$
$\triangleright \frac{946}{135278} = \frac{964}{137852}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{1673984} = \frac{79}{2543168}$	$\triangleright \frac{53}{1984267} = \frac{86}{3219754}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1798362} = \frac{81}{2697543}$
$\triangleright \frac{954}{837612} = \frac{972}{853416}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{1976384} = \frac{91}{3458672}$	$\triangleright \frac{53}{6184729} = \frac{68}{7935124}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1823796} = \frac{81}{2735694}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{2378946} = \frac{69}{3218574}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{1984376} = \frac{91}{3472658}$	$\triangleright \frac{53}{6742819} = \frac{67}{8523941}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1823976} = \frac{81}{2735964}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{2674389} = \frac{87}{4562193}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{3186794} = \frac{92}{5638174}$	$\triangleright \frac{53}{6941728} = \frac{73}{9561248}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1837962} = \frac{81}{2756943}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{2936478} = \frac{57}{3281946}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{3679184} = \frac{91}{6438572}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1382697} = \frac{72}{1843596}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1839762} = \frac{81}{2759643}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{2938467} = \frac{57}{3284169}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{3697148} = \frac{84}{5972316}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1382967} = \frac{72}{1843956}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1873692} = \frac{63}{2185974}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{3497682} = \frac{69}{4732158}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{3719846} = \frac{54}{3862917}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1387962} = \frac{76}{1953428}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1876932} = \frac{63}{2189754}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{3728649} = \frac{68}{4971532}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{3761984} = \frac{91}{6583472}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1623798} = \frac{81}{2435697}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1962378} = \frac{81}{2943567}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{3729864} = \frac{68}{4973152}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{3841976} = \frac{91}{6723458}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1623978} = \frac{81}{2435967}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1963782} = \frac{81}{2945673}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{3748296} = \frac{87}{6394152}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{3847961} = \frac{84}{6215937}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1637982} = \frac{81}{2456973}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1976238} = \frac{81}{2964357}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{4283796} = \frac{63}{5291748}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{3894176} = \frac{56}{4193728}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1639782} = \frac{81}{2459673}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1976382} = \frac{81}{2964573}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{4289763} = \frac{91}{7654283}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{3894761} = \frac{84}{6291537}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1673892} = \frac{63}{1952874}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1978236} = \frac{81}{2967354}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{4362897} = \frac{72}{6159384}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{3916784} = \frac{91}{6854372}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1739826} = \frac{98}{3157462}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1978362} = \frac{81}{2967543}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{4379268} = \frac{61}{5237948}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{4681937} = \frac{84}{7563129}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1762398} = \frac{81}{2643597}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1982376} = \frac{81}{2973564}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{4397628} = \frac{83}{7156924}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{4697381} = \frac{64}{5781392}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1763982} = \frac{81}{2645973}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1983762} = \frac{81}{2975643}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{4698273} = \frac{92}{8475316}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{4937816} = \frac{61}{5792438}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1782396} = \frac{81}{2673594}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{2163798} = \frac{81}{3245697}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{7286493} = \frac{68}{9715324}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{4938716} = \frac{91}{8642753}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1783962} = \frac{81}{2675943}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{2163978} = \frac{81}{3245967}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{7294836} = \frac{67}{9583412}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{8417396} = \frac{61}{9874253}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1796238} = \frac{81}{2694357}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{2176398} = \frac{81}{3264597}$
$\triangleright \frac{51}{7298643} = \frac{68}{9731524}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{8741369} = \frac{56}{9413782}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1796283} = \frac{78}{2594631}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{2178396} = \frac{81}{3267594}$
$\triangleright \frac{52}{1483976} = \frac{59}{1683742}$	$\triangleright \frac{52}{8973146} = \frac{54}{9318267}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{1796382} = \frac{81}{2694573}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{2179638} = \frac{81}{3269457}$

$\triangleright \frac{54}{2179836} = \frac{81}{3269754}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{2681937} = \frac{64}{3178592}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3798162} = \frac{81}{5697243}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{7693218} = \frac{63}{8975421}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2183796} = \frac{81}{3275694}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{2861973} = \frac{72}{3815964}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3798216} = \frac{81}{5697324}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{8761392} = \frac{57}{9248136}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2183976} = \frac{81}{3275964}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{2931768} = \frac{81}{4397652}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3817962} = \frac{81}{5726943}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{8917236} = \frac{57}{9412638}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2196378} = \frac{81}{3294567}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3128976} = \frac{78}{4519632}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3819762} = \frac{81}{5729643}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1389472} = \frac{98}{2431576}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2197638} = \frac{81}{3296457}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3176928} = \frac{81}{4765392}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3821796} = \frac{81}{5732694}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1423798} = \frac{84}{2135697}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2197836} = \frac{81}{3296754}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3179682} = \frac{81}{4769523}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3821976} = \frac{81}{5732964}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1423978} = \frac{84}{2135967}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2198376} = \frac{81}{3297564}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3197682} = \frac{81}{4796523}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3871962} = \frac{63}{4517289}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1437928} = \frac{98}{2516374}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2317968} = \frac{81}{3476952}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3286197} = \frac{72}{4381596}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3961782} = \frac{81}{5942673}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1437982} = \frac{84}{2156973}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2319768} = \frac{81}{3479652}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3291768} = \frac{81}{4937652}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3962178} = \frac{81}{5943267}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1439782} = \frac{84}{2159673}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2361798} = \frac{81}{3542697}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3298617} = \frac{72}{4398156}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3972186} = \frac{57}{4192863}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1742398} = \frac{84}{2613597}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2361978} = \frac{81}{3542967}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3617982} = \frac{81}{5426973}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3976182} = \frac{81}{5964273}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1743982} = \frac{84}{2615973}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2376198} = \frac{81}{3564297}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3619782} = \frac{81}{5429673}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3976218} = \frac{81}{5964327}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1749832} = \frac{79}{2468513}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2378196} = \frac{81}{3567294}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3621798} = \frac{81}{5432697}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3978162} = \frac{81}{5967243}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1782394} = \frac{84}{2673591}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2379618} = \frac{81}{3569427}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3621978} = \frac{81}{5432967}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3978216} = \frac{81}{5967324}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1783942} = \frac{84}{2675913}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2379816} = \frac{81}{3569724}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3689172} = \frac{57}{3894126}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3981762} = \frac{81}{5972643}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1793428} = \frac{86}{2754193}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2381796} = \frac{81}{3572694}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3761982} = \frac{81}{5642973}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3982176} = \frac{81}{5973264}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1794238} = \frac{84}{2691357}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2381976} = \frac{81}{3572964}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3762198} = \frac{81}{5643297}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3986172} = \frac{72}{5314896}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1794382} = \frac{84}{2691573}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2396178} = \frac{81}{3594267}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3781962} = \frac{81}{5672943}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{6931278} = \frac{62}{7958134}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1798234} = \frac{84}{2697351}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2397618} = \frac{81}{3596427}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3782196} = \frac{81}{5673294}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{7239861} = \frac{72}{9653148}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1798342} = \frac{84}{2697513}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2397816} = \frac{81}{3596724}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3796182} = \frac{81}{5694273}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{7369218} = \frac{63}{8597421}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1823794} = \frac{84}{2735691}$
$\triangleright \frac{54}{2398176} = \frac{81}{3597264}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{3796218} = \frac{81}{5694327}$	$\triangleright \frac{54}{7628931} = \frac{62}{8759143}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{1823974} = \frac{84}{2735961}$

$\triangleright \frac{56}{1837942} = \frac{84}{2756913}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2183794} = \frac{84}{3275691}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3197824} = \frac{73}{4168592}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3912784} = \frac{91}{6358274}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{1839742} = \frac{84}{2759613}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2183974} = \frac{84}{3275961}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3279184} = \frac{91}{5328674}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3941782} = \frac{84}{5912673}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{1872934} = \frac{76}{2541839}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2194378} = \frac{84}{3291567}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3417982} = \frac{84}{5126973}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3942178} = \frac{84}{5913267}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{1928374} = \frac{68}{2341597}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2197438} = \frac{84}{3296157}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3419782} = \frac{84}{5129673}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3971248} = \frac{91}{6453278}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{1932784} = \frac{81}{2795634}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2197834} = \frac{84}{3296751}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3421798} = \frac{84}{5132697}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3974182} = \frac{84}{5961273}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{1942378} = \frac{84}{2913567}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2198374} = \frac{84}{3297561}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3421978} = \frac{84}{5132967}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3974218} = \frac{84}{5961327}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{1943782} = \frac{84}{2915673}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2341798} = \frac{84}{3512697}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3479812} = \frac{92}{5716834}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3978142} = \frac{84}{5967213}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{1974238} = \frac{84}{2961357}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2341978} = \frac{84}{3512967}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3714928} = \frac{82}{5439716}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3978214} = \frac{84}{5967321}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{1974382} = \frac{84}{2961573}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2374198} = \frac{84}{3561297}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3741982} = \frac{84}{5612973}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3981742} = \frac{84}{5972613}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{1978234} = \frac{84}{2967351}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2378194} = \frac{84}{3567291}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3742198} = \frac{84}{5613297}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3982174} = \frac{84}{5973261}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{1978342} = \frac{84}{2967513}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2379184} = \frac{98}{4163572}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3781942} = \frac{84}{5672913}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{4783219} = \frac{72}{6149853}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{1982374} = \frac{84}{2973561}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2379418} = \frac{84}{3569127}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3782194} = \frac{84}{5673291}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{4783912} = \frac{74}{6321598}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{1983742} = \frac{84}{2975613}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2379814} = \frac{84}{3569721}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3794182} = \frac{84}{5691273}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{4839712} = \frac{91}{7864532}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{1984372} = \frac{98}{3472651}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2381794} = \frac{84}{3572691}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3794218} = \frac{84}{5691327}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{8374912} = \frac{64}{9571328}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{2143798} = \frac{84}{3215697}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2381974} = \frac{84}{3572961}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3798142} = \frac{84}{5697213}$	$\triangleright \frac{57}{1382694} = \frac{76}{1843592}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{2143978} = \frac{84}{3215967}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2394178} = \frac{84}{3591267}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3798214} = \frac{84}{5697321}$	$\triangleright \frac{57}{1382964} = \frac{76}{1843952}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{2173948} = \frac{92}{3571486}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2397418} = \frac{84}{3596127}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3817942} = \frac{84}{5726913}$	$\triangleright \frac{57}{1493286} = \frac{74}{1938652}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{2174398} = \frac{84}{3261597}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2397814} = \frac{84}{3596721}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3819742} = \frac{84}{5729613}$	$\triangleright \frac{57}{1694382} = \frac{93}{2764518}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{2178394} = \frac{84}{3267591}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2398174} = \frac{84}{3597261}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3821794} = \frac{84}{5732691}$	$\triangleright \frac{57}{2386419} = \frac{92}{3851764}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{2179438} = \frac{84}{3269157}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2739184} = \frac{61}{2983754}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3821974} = \frac{84}{5732961}$	$\triangleright \frac{57}{2641893} = \frac{81}{3754269}$
$\triangleright \frac{56}{2179834} = \frac{84}{3269751}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{2789143} = \frac{64}{3187592}$	$\triangleright \frac{56}{3841972} = \frac{98}{6723451}$	$\triangleright \frac{57}{2694138} = \frac{76}{3592184}$

$\triangleright \frac{57}{2861943} = \frac{76}{3815924}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1623974} = \frac{87}{2435961}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2163794} = \frac{87}{3245691}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2397614} = \frac{87}{3596421}$
$\triangleright \frac{57}{2964138} = \frac{76}{3952184}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1637942} = \frac{87}{2456913}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2163974} = \frac{87}{3245961}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3279146} = \frac{83}{4692571}$
$\triangleright \frac{57}{2986143} = \frac{76}{3981524}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1639742} = \frac{87}{2459613}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2174396} = \frac{87}{3261594}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3417962} = \frac{87}{5126943}$
$\triangleright \frac{57}{3192684} = \frac{81}{4536972}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1742396} = \frac{87}{2613594}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2176394} = \frac{87}{3264591}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3419762} = \frac{87}{5129643}$
$\triangleright \frac{57}{3286194} = \frac{76}{4381592}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1743962} = \frac{87}{2615943}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2179436} = \frac{87}{3269154}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3421796} = \frac{87}{5132694}$
$\triangleright \frac{57}{3298614} = \frac{76}{4398152}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1762394} = \frac{87}{2643591}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2179634} = \frac{87}{3269451}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3421976} = \frac{87}{5132964}$
$\triangleright \frac{57}{3486291} = \frac{84}{5137692}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1763942} = \frac{87}{2645913}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2194376} = \frac{87}{3291564}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3617942} = \frac{87}{5426913}$
$\triangleright \frac{57}{3892416} = \frac{84}{5736192}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1794236} = \frac{87}{2691354}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2196374} = \frac{87}{3294561}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3619742} = \frac{87}{5429613}$
$\triangleright \frac{57}{3962184} = \frac{78}{5421936}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1794362} = \frac{87}{2691543}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2197436} = \frac{87}{3296154}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3621794} = \frac{87}{5432691}$
$\triangleright \frac{57}{4139682} = \frac{93}{6754218}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1796234} = \frac{87}{2694351}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2197634} = \frac{87}{3296451}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3621974} = \frac{87}{5432961}$
$\triangleright \frac{57}{4612839} = \frac{64}{5179328}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1796342} = \frac{87}{2694513}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2341796} = \frac{87}{3512694}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3741962} = \frac{87}{5612943}$
$\triangleright \frac{57}{4826931} = \frac{69}{5843127}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1942376} = \frac{87}{2913564}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2341976} = \frac{87}{3512964}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3742196} = \frac{87}{5613294}$
$\triangleright \frac{57}{6319248} = \frac{84}{9312576}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1943762} = \frac{87}{2915643}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2361794} = \frac{87}{3542691}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3761942} = \frac{87}{5642913}$
$\triangleright \frac{57}{6829341} = \frac{63}{7548219}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1962374} = \frac{87}{2943561}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2361974} = \frac{87}{3542961}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3762194} = \frac{87}{5643291}$
$\triangleright \frac{57}{6843192} = \frac{81}{9724536}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1963742} = \frac{87}{2945613}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2374196} = \frac{87}{3561294}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3794162} = \frac{87}{5691243}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{1423796} = \frac{87}{2135694}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1974236} = \frac{87}{2961354}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2376194} = \frac{87}{3564291}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3794216} = \frac{87}{5691324}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{1423976} = \frac{87}{2135964}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1974362} = \frac{87}{2961543}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2379416} = \frac{87}{3569124}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3796142} = \frac{87}{5694213}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{1437962} = \frac{87}{2156943}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1976234} = \frac{87}{2964351}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2379614} = \frac{87}{3569421}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3796214} = \frac{87}{5694321}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{1439762} = \frac{87}{2159643}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{1976342} = \frac{87}{2964513}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2394176} = \frac{87}{3591264}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3941762} = \frac{87}{5912643}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{1469372} = \frac{76}{1925384}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2143796} = \frac{87}{3215694}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2396174} = \frac{87}{3594261}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3942176} = \frac{87}{5913264}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{1623794} = \frac{87}{2435691}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2143976} = \frac{87}{3215964}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{2397416} = \frac{87}{3596124}$	$\triangleright \frac{58}{3961742} = \frac{87}{5942613}$

$\triangleright \frac{58}{3962174} = \frac{87}{5943261}$	$\triangleright \frac{61}{4793258} = \frac{83}{6521974}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{5217849} = \frac{84}{6957132}$	$\triangleright \frac{65}{2478931} = \frac{85}{3241679}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{3974162} = \frac{87}{5961243}$	$\triangleright \frac{61}{8324975} = \frac{67}{9143825}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{5217984} = \frac{84}{6957312}$	$\triangleright \frac{65}{7128394} = \frac{85}{9321746}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{3974216} = \frac{87}{5961324}$	$\triangleright \frac{62}{3517894} = \frac{93}{5276841}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{5297418} = \frac{97}{8156342}$	$\triangleright \frac{67}{2194853} = \frac{81}{2653479}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{3976142} = \frac{87}{5964213}$	$\triangleright \frac{62}{3518974} = \frac{93}{5278461}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{5729148} = \frac{91}{8275436}$	$\triangleright \frac{68}{1953742} = \frac{76}{2183594}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{3976214} = \frac{87}{5964321}$	$\triangleright \frac{62}{3751894} = \frac{93}{5627841}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{5927841} = \frac{91}{8562437}$	$\triangleright \frac{68}{3517249} = \frac{92}{4758631}$
$\triangleright \frac{58}{4127396} = \frac{73}{5194826}$	$\triangleright \frac{62}{3789514} = \frac{93}{5684271}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{7528941} = \frac{78}{9321546}$	$\triangleright \frac{68}{3527194} = \frac{76}{3942158}$
$\triangleright \frac{584}{127936} = \frac{657}{143928}$	$\triangleright \frac{62}{3895174} = \frac{93}{5842761}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{7895412} = \frac{73}{9148652}$	$\triangleright \frac{68}{4315297} = \frac{72}{4569138}$
$\triangleright \frac{586}{149723} = \frac{726}{185493}$	$\triangleright \frac{62}{3897514} = \frac{93}{5846271}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{8579214} = \frac{64}{8715392}$	$\triangleright \frac{68}{7951342} = \frac{74}{8652931}$
$\triangleright \frac{59}{1684273} = \frac{93}{2654871}$	$\triangleright \frac{62}{4581397} = \frac{98}{7241563}$	$\triangleright \frac{64}{1593728} = \frac{78}{1942356}$	$\triangleright \frac{69}{1358472} = \frac{84}{1653792}$
$\triangleright \frac{59}{1784632} = \frac{64}{1935872}$	$\triangleright \frac{62}{7139548} = \frac{74}{8521396}$	$\triangleright \frac{64}{1875392} = \frac{87}{2549361}$	$\triangleright \frac{69}{1854237} = \frac{72}{1934856}$
$\triangleright \frac{59}{2413867} = \frac{89}{3641257}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{1254897} = \frac{93}{1852467}$	$\triangleright \frac{64}{1938752} = \frac{87}{2635491}$	$\triangleright \frac{69}{1872453} = \frac{72}{1953864}$
$\triangleright \frac{59}{2463781} = \frac{86}{3591274}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{1259874} = \frac{72}{1439856}$	$\triangleright \frac{64}{3518792} = \frac{72}{3958641}$	$\triangleright \frac{69}{2384157} = \frac{78}{2695134}$
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$\triangleright \frac{592}{174368} = \frac{814}{239756}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{2418759} = \frac{98}{3762514}$	$\triangleright \frac{64}{7391528} = \frac{72}{8315469}$	$\triangleright \frac{69}{4325817} = \frac{72}{4513896}$
$\triangleright \frac{592}{387416} = \frac{814}{532697}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{4198572} = \frac{68}{4531792}$	$\triangleright \frac{64}{7513928} = \frac{72}{8453169}$	$\triangleright \frac{69}{4351278} = \frac{91}{5738642}$
$\triangleright \frac{61}{2438597} = \frac{69}{2758413}$	$\triangleright \frac{63}{5214798} = \frac{91}{7532486}$	$\triangleright \frac{64}{8739152} = \frac{72}{9831546}$	$\triangleright \frac{69}{5173482} = \frac{72}{5398416}$
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$\triangleright \frac{71}{6543928} = \frac{93}{8571624}$	$\triangleright \frac{72}{5613984} = \frac{96}{7485312}$	$\triangleright \frac{78}{1523964} = \frac{94}{1836572}$	$\triangleright \frac{81}{6472953} = \frac{87}{6952431}$
$\triangleright \frac{71}{8532496} = \frac{81}{9734256}$	$\triangleright \frac{72}{5649138} = \frac{96}{7532184}$	$\triangleright \frac{78}{2631954} = \frac{87}{2935641}$	$\triangleright \frac{81}{7695243} = \frac{91}{8645273}$
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$\triangleright \frac{6}{73259418} = \frac{7}{85469321}$	$\triangleright \frac{7}{32968145} = \frac{9}{42387615}$	$\triangleright \frac{8}{19247536} = \frac{9}{21653478}$	

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References

- [1] DUDENEY, H.E., Amusements in Mathematics, EBD E-Books Directory.com, 1917.
- [2] MADACHY, J.S., Mathematics on Vacations, Charlars Scriber's Son, New York, 1966.
- [3] LUCE, T.T., Pandigital Fraction, <http://intermath.coe.uga.edu/tweb/gwin1-01/luce/tluce15/writeup.htm>.
- [4] SLONE, N. J. A. Sequence A054383 in "The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences, <http://oeis.org/A054383>.
- [5] WEISSTEIN, Eric W., Pandigital Fraction, From MathWorld–A Wolfram Web Resource. <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/PandigitalFraction.html>.
- [6] I.J. TANEJA, Different Digits Equivalent Fractions - I, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Art 148, pp. 1-59, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a148.pdf>.
- [7] I.J. TANEJA, Different Digits Equivalent Fractions - II, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Art 149, pp. 1-56, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a149.pdf>.
- [8] I.J. TANEJA, Different Digits Equivalent Fractions - III, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Art 150, pp. 1-57, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a150.pdf>.
- [9] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Fractions: Addable, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Art 113, pp. 1-72, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a113.pdf>.
- [10] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Fractions: Dottable and Potentiable, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Art 114, pp. 1-25, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a114.pdf>.
- [11] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Fractions: Addable and Dottable Together, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Art 115, pp. 1-80, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a115.pdf>.
- [12] I.J. TANEJA, Equivalent Selfie Fractions: Dottable, Addable and Subtractable, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Art 116, pp. 1-40, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a116.pdf>.
- [13] I.J. TANEJA, Equivalent Selfie Fractions: Addable and Dottable Together, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Art 117, pp. 1-85, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a117.pdf>.
- [14] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Fractions: Addable, Subtractable, Dottable and Potentiable, **Zenodo**, Open Access, March 24, 2019, pp. 1-260, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2604531>.
- [15] I.J. TANEJA, Different Digits Equivalent Fractions - II, **Zenodo**, March 24, 2019. www.zenodo.org.
- [16] I.J. TANEJA, Crazy, Selfie, Fibonacci, Triangular, Amicable Types Representations of Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **21**(2018), Art. 3, pp. 1-140, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a03.pdf>.
- [17] I.J. TANEJA, 2019 In Numbers, **Zenodo**, December 31, 2019, pp. 1-27, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2529103>.